

Proceedings of the 52nd National Conference of
the Italian Society for Agronomy

Galoppatoio reale – Reggia di Portici
University of Naples “Federico II”

25 - 27 September 2023

Edited by

Anna Dalla Marta
Carmelo Maucieri
Domenico Ventrella

Scientific Committee

Michele Perniola
Luca Bechini
Anna Dalla Marta
Michela Farneselli,
Salvatore La Bella,
Giorgio Testa,
Domenico Ventrella
Antonio Pulina
Carmelo Maucieri

Organizing Committee

Albino Maggio
Massimo Fagnano
Mauro Mori
Nunzio Fiorentino
Isabella Sifola
Valerio Cirillo
Stefania De Pascale
Ida Di Mola
Lucia Ottaiano
Emilio Di Stasio
Eugenio Cozzolino
Linda Carrino
Marco Esposito
Antonio Minoliti
Maria Eleonora Pelosi
Claudio Russo
Nausicaa Pollaro
Daniele Todisco
Michela Terrecuso
Francesco Carbone

Società Italiana di Agronomia (SIA)
www.siagr.it

ISBN: 978-88-908499-7-8

The correct citation of article in this book is:

Authors, 2023. Title. Proceedings of the 52nd Conference of the Italian Society of Agronomy (Dalla Marta A., Maucieri C., Ventrella D., Eds.), Naples, Italy, 25th-27th September 2023, pag. x-y

INDEX

Sessione 1 - RECUPERO - Sviluppo delle aree marginali

ORAL PRESENTATIONS

Micro-plastic Effects on Agricultural Soil: A Bibliometric Analysis. *Antonello Calcutta, Ennio D'Emanuele, Sebastiano Infantino, Enrico Naselli, Antonio C. Barbera*

Developing a Planning Process for a Coastal Wetland and Assessing the Role of Agriculture in Ecosystem Services and Biodiversity. *Anna Rita Bernadette Cammerino, Michela Ingaramo, Massimo Monteleone*

Biomass and Seed Yields of Cardoon (*Cynara cardunculus* L.) Fertilized by Biowaste Compost in Two Inland Hilly Areas of Southern Italy. *Luigi Morra, Nino Virzì, Maurizio Bilotto, Tommaso Enotrio, Antonio Merola, Antonio Leonardi, Stefania Licciardello, Ezio Li Puma, Fabiola Sciacca, Massimo Palumbo, Michele Falce, Anna Ciancolini, Gianmaria Baldi*

Influence of Tillage and Nitrogen Fertilization on Durum Wheat Metabolite Profiling and Yield. *Luigi Tedone, Giovanna Marta Fusco, Rosalinda Nicastro, Petronia Carillo*

POSTERS

Productivity and Product Quality of Organically Grown Saffron in the Etna Area. *Umberto Anastasi, Gaetano Pandino, Concetta Scepi, Salvatore Lamacchia*

Field Vegetation Parameters for Pasture Above-ground Biomass Estimation: A Case Study. *Elena Basso, Cristina Pornaro, Francesco Marinello, Stefano Macolino*

Phytomanagement of a Shooting Range Soil with *Ricinus communis* L. *Linda Carrino, Donato Visconti, Nunzio Fiorentino, Massimo Fagnano*

Quantifying Non-photosynthetic Vegetation in a Mixed Grassland Using Hyperspectral Data: A Case Study in Kenya. *Rodolfo Ceriani, Francesco Fava, Giulia Tagliabue, Micol Rossini, Sonja Leitner, Cinzia Panigada, Vincent Odongo, Valentina Vaglia, Paul Mutuo, Kelvin Kinuthia, Ramin Heidarian, Katayoun Fakhelifard, Monica Pepe*

Tolerance of African Fodder Cane to the Cultivation in Heavy Metals Polluted Soils. *Barbara Rachele Ciaramella, Alessandra Piccitto, Alessio Scandurra, Valeria Cafaro, Silvio Calcagno, Salvatore Luciano Cosentino, Giorgio Testa*

Effect of Different Fertilization Strategies on Yield of Cauliflower Grown on Three Different Types of Soil. *Eugenio Cozzolino, Ida Di Mola, Lucia Ottaiano, Maria Eleonora Pelosi, Nunzio Fiorentino, Massimo Fagnano, Mauro Mori*

Seed Yield and Quality of *Medicago intertexta* L. in a Mediterranean Environment. *Giuseppe Di Miceli Giuseppe, Lucia Dinolfo, Nicoletta Lala, Davide Farruggia, Nicolò Iacuzzi, Leto Claudio, Simona Prestigiacomo*

Innovative Products from Apulian Marginal Areas: *Salvia rosmarinus* Schleid. as Source of Bioactive Compounds. *Jihane El Mahdi, Claudia Ruta, Laura Scalvenzi, Giuseppe De Mastro*

Is the Modified Biochar Through the Tannic Acid Suitable in Reclamation of Contaminated Soils by Heavy Metals? A Mesocosm Trial. *Giuseppe Maglione, Carmen Arena, Lucia Santorufò, Ermenegilda Vitale, Gaetano De Tommaso, Fulvio De Paola, Giuseppina Roviello, Elena Chianese, Claudio Ferone, Franca Polimeno, Giulia Maisto, Mauro Iuliano, Luca Vitale*

Monitoring the Development of Meadow Grassland in Agrivoltaic System Through LiDAR Technology. *Michele Moretta, Riccardo Rossi, Marco Moriondo, Gloria Padovan, Enrico Palchetti, Marco Bindi*

Polyannual Cardoon (*Cynara cardunculus* L.) and Compost Amendment Improve Soil Organic Carbon in Two Hilly Areas of Southern Italy. *Luigi Morra, Salvatore Baiano, Antonio Merola, Michele Rinaldi, Nino Virzi, Massimo Palumbo*

Seed Production Of A Valuable Old Variety Of Sulla (*Sulla coronaria* L.) For Sardinian Pastoral Systems. *Teresa Murgia, Maria Nieddu, Maria Sitzia, Giovanni Garau, Pier Paolo Roggero*

Preliminary Results on the Seed Production and Quality of *Tanacetum cinerariifolium* (Trev.) Schultz-Bip. in Southern Italy. *Claudia Ruta, Martina Grdiša, Luigi Tedone, Cataldo Pulvento, Giuseppe De Mastro*

Modelling Camelina (*Camelina sativa* L. Cranz) Yield in Rotation with Barley (*Hordeum vulgare* L.) in Mediterranean Area Using the ARMOSA Crop Model. *Calogero Schillaci, Alessia Perego, Marco Acutis, Marco Botta, Tommaso Tadiello, Mara Gabrielli, Tommaso Barsali, Francesca Tozzi, David Chiaramonti, Arwyn Jones*

Crop Yield Response in the Mediterranean Agroforestry: A Preliminary Metanalysis. *Danilo Scordia, Sebastiano Andrea Corinzia, Jaime Coello, Rosa Vilaplana Ventura, Diana Elisa Jiménez-De-Santiago, Berta Singla Just, Omar Castaño Sanchez, Carme Casas, Marc Tchamitchian, Léa Garreau, Mohamed Emran, Sami Z. Mohamed, Mai Khedr, Mohamed Rashad, Roxanne Suzette Lorilla, Alexandre Parizel, Giuseppe Mancini, Antonella Iurato, Corrado Dimauro, Fabio Gresta, Salvatore Luciano Cosentino, Giorgio Testa*

Impacts of Management Practices on TIMESAT Seasonal Parameters in Mediterranean Grasslands. *Alberto Tanda, Antonio Pulina, Pier Paolo Roggero*

Sessione 2 - CIRCOLARITÀ - Sviluppo di strategie di economia circolare nel settore agro-alimentare

ORAL PRESENTATIONS

Reuse of wastewater in agriculture: risks or benefits? A pilot-scale study on durum wheat (*Triticum durum* Desf.). *Michele Denora, Vincenzo Candido, Francesco De Mastro, Giuseppe Gatta, Cristina De Ceglie, Ruud P. Bartholomeus, Gennaro Brunetti, Michele Perniola*

Effect of Different Fertilization Strategies and Biostimulant Application on Yield and Quality Traits of Eggplant (*Solanum melongena* L.). *Ida Di Mola, Eugenio Cozzolino, Lucia Ottaiano, Roberta Marra, Ferdinando Esposito, Nunzio Fiorentino, Massimo Fagnano, Mauro Mori*

Planning and Managing a Forage System to Constrain Nitrogen Surplus in Dairy Farms. *Francesco Ferrero, Ernesto Tabacco, Gabriele Rolando, Giorgio Borreani*

The Use Of Pelargonic Acid Accelerates Seed-Drying Of Camelina: An Example Of Circularity Of H-EU Project Carina. *Maria Giovanna Sessa, Federica Zanetti, Barbara Alberghini, Andrea Parenti, Sara Berzuini, Angela Vecchi, Anna Ciancolini, Michele Falce, Pieter Ravaglia, Dalila Villano, Gianmaria Baldi, Erika Facciolla, Andrea Monti*

POSTERS

The effect of sludge from citrus peel on the growth of *Lolium multiflorum* Lam. *Silvio Calcagno, Alessandra Piccitto, Carmela Patania, Vivienne Panebianco, Barbara Rachele Ciaramella, Stefania Longo, Giorgio Testa, Salvatore Luciano Cosentino*

Evaluation of Agronomic performance and health-beneficial properties of *Urtica dioica* L. cultivated in Nitrate Vulnerable Zones. *Elettra Frassinetti, Mattia Alpi, Eros D'Amen, Giovanni Dinelli, Ilaria Marotti*

Sustainable Use Of Bioactive Compounds From *Brassicaceae* And *Solanaceae* Wastes For Cereal Crop Protection (SUSinCER). *Chiara Lanzanova, Daniela Pacifico, Roberto Lo Scalzo, Bruno Parisi, Eleonora Pagnotta, Luisa Ugolini, Laura Righetti, Roberto Matteo, Massimo Montanari, Anna Maria Mastrangelo, Daniela Marone, Raffaella Pergamo, Carlotta Balconi*

Growth and Essential Oil Yield of *Salvia officinalis* L. Cultivated under an Agriphotovoltaic System. *Angela Libutti, Laura Frabboni, Antonio Stasi, Marianna Silvestri, Annalisa Tarantino, Grazia Disciglio*

Nano-hydroxyapatite from Wastes: Synthesis and P Release Evaluation Through A Soil Column Compared to Triple Super Phosphate. *Laura Pilotto, Clara Piccirillo, Francesca Scalera, Luca Marchiol, Monica Yorlady Alzate Zuluaga, Youry Pii, Guido Fellet*

Nano-Enabled Agriculture and Circular Economy. Nature-Derived Materials as Smart-Delivery Systems. *Laura Pilotto, Luca Marchiol, Guido Fellet*

Land Occupation Affects Nitrogen Load on Dairy Farms in Northern Italy. *Gabriele Rolando, Francesco Ferrero, Ernesto Tabacco, Giorgio Borreani*

Rooting and Shooting in Single-node Stem cuttings of *Saccharum spontaneum* ssp. *aegyptiacum* as affected by Explant/Transplant Time. *Alessandro Saita, Valeria Cavallaro, Elena Crapio, Alessandra Piccitto, Giorgio Testa, Salvatore Luciano Cosentino, Cristina Patanè*

Sustainable Agronomic Practices for a Top Quality Tobacco. *Maria Isabella Sifola, Daniele Todisco, Luisa del Piano, Eugenio Cozzolino*

Camelina as opportunity for cropping system diversification and bioeconomy development: on-farm multilocation study in Tuscany. *Silvia Tavarini, Alessandro Rossi, Clarissa Clemente, Lara Foschi, Luciana G. Angelini*

Improved digestate for sustainable fertilization: preliminary results of NOMAD project. *Leonardo Verdi, Roberto Vivoli, Marco Mancini, Simone Orlandini, Anna Dalla Marta*

Sessione 3 - BASSO IMPATTO - Riduzione degli sprechi e dell'impatto ambientale

ORAL PRESENTATIONS

A New Sustainable Method Of Soil Solarization For Management Of Soil Pathogens. *Battaglia Valerio, Cermola Michele, Mormile Pasquale, Lahoz Ernesto*

Producing thermoplastics from wheat flour surpluses: mechanical performances of films as related to crop N status, flour baking properties and gluten composition. *Paolo Benincasa, Franco Dominici, Francesca Luzi, Catia Governatori, Laura Gazza, Elena Galassi, Giacomo Tosti, Debora Puglia*

Shade-Avoidance response For Enhanced Tolerance to Weed Competition In a Local Wheat Variety. *Valerio Cirillo, Claudio Russo, Nausicaa Pollaro, Francesco Antonio Carbone, Antonio Di Matteo, Albino Maggio*

Green Mulch For Weed Management In Organic Rice. *Giulia Papandrea, Silvia Fogliatto, Zineb Bennani, Ivan Di Furia, Alessandro Beltramo, Francesco Vidotto*

POSTERS

Carbon Flux As Affected By Different Winter Cover Crops. *Mariam Atait, Roberto Mancinelli, Mohamed Allam, Verdiana Petroselli, Valentina Quintarelli, Emanuele Radicetti*

Environment x genotype influence in the nutritional and antinutritional compounds in camelina seeds. *Sara Berzuini, Federica Zanetti, Barbara Alberghini, Clarissa Clemente, Silvia Tavarini, Luciana Angelini, Incoronata Galasso, Sara Pozzo, Antonella dalle Zotte, Andrea Monti*

Biochar as Soil Amendment to Improve the Sustainability of the Intensive Dairy Cattle Farming. *Lamberto Borrelli, Massimo Valagussa, Alberto Tosca, Daniele Cavalli, Alessandra Lagomarsino, Carla Scotti*

Research Application of Land Parcel Identification System data: a systematic literature review. *Antonio Bruno, Philippe Martin, Elisa Marraccini*

Effect of legume species rotation on durum wheat production in Mediterranean Climate. *Claudio Calia, Luigi Tedone, Claudia Ruta, Cataldo Pulvento, Giuseppe De Mastro*

Environmental evaluation of nitrogen management using self-driving robots. *Davide Cammarano, Vita Antoniuk, Kiril Manevski, Joory Jin, Yeying Zhou, Mathias A. Nemuar*

Reduction of Sorghum Crop Cycle for Water Saving. *Pasquale Campi, Maria Roberta Bruno, Gabriele De Carolis, Anna Francesca Modugno*

Effect of Irrigation Scheduling on Yield-Quality and Water Efficiency Indices in Processing Tomato. *Federica Carucci, Giuseppe Gatta, Anna Gagliardi, Delia Caldarola, Marcella Michela Giuliani*

Agronomical Role Of Different Summer Intercropped Cover Crops On Nutrient Uptake, Weed Control And Yield Performance Of Bread Wheat: A Three-Year Study In The Po Plain. *Paolo Colombatto, Giulia Papandrea, Luca Capo, Raffaele Meloni, Mattia Scapino, Silvia Fogliatto, Amedeo Reyneri, Francesco Vidotto, Massimo Blandino*

Adaptability of Three Ancient Varieties of Durum Wheat Cultivated in Purity and as Mixtures to an Inland Hilly Area of Campania Region. *Eugenio Cozzolino, Ida Di Mola, Lucia Ottaiano, Maria Eleonora Pelosi, Daniele Todisco, Nunzio Fiorentino, Antonio Minoliti, Raffaele Romano, Mauro Mori*

Adaptability of Three Ancient Varieties of Common Wheat Cultivated in Purity and as Mixtures to an Inland Hilly Area of Campania Region. *Ida Di Mola, Lucia Ottaiano, Eugenio Cozzolino, Maria Eleonora Pelosi, Sabrina Nocerino, Nunzio Fiorentino, Antonio Minoliti, Raffaele Romano, Mauro Mori*

Natural-based products as possible sustainable alternatives for cover crops termination. *Giovanni Dinelli, Lorenzo Negri, Antonio Fakaros, Giulia Oliveti, Sara Bosi*

Preliminary Results On The Use Of Dark Green Colour Index (DGCI) To Evaluate The Nutritional Status Of *Camelina Sativa* (L.) Crantz. *Leonardo Ercolini, Andrea Berton, Lisa Caturegli, Nicola Grossi, Nicola Silvestri*

Effects of Arbuscular Mycorrhizal Fungi on Tomato Yield Under deficit irrigation in Greenhouse. *Michela Farneselli, Beatrice Falcinelli, Martina Cerri, Lara Reale, Domizia Donnini, Euro Pannaci, Francesco Tei*

Effects of foliar treatment with various types of biostimulants and different frequency of application on yield and quality of organic oregano. *Davide Farruggia, Salvatore La Bella, Federico Margiotta, Claudio Leto, Mario Licata, Nicolò Iacuzzi*

2D-NANO MAD PLANTS: a PRIN project on the Effects of 2D-nanomaterials on seed plants reproduction. *Guido Fellet, Fabiano Miceli, Mario Baldini, Iris Aloisi, Mauro Tretiach*

Tenebrio molitor Frass as organic fertilizer: results from a germination test on three crops and a pot experiment on sunflower. *Guido Fellet, Alessandro Foscari and Luisa Dalla Costa*

Agronomic Comparison Between Spring And Winter *Camelina Sativa* Cultivation In North Italy. *Martina Ghidoli, Sara Frazzini, Stefano De Benedetti, Stefano Sangiorgio, Michela Landoni, Alessio Scarafoni, Luciana Rossi, Roberto Pihu*

Identifying criteria for harmonizing life cycle assessments of crop-livestock systems and interactions. *Pietro Goglio, Marie Trydeman Knudsen, Klara Van Mierlo, Nina Röhrig, Fossey Maxime, Alberto Maresca, Fatemeh Hashemi, Muhammad Ahmed Waqas, Jenny Yngvesson, Gilles Nassy, Roline Broekema, Simon Moakes, Catherine Pfeifer, Robert Borek, David Yanez-Ruiz, Monica Quevedo Cascante, Alina Sypl, Tomasz Zylowsky, Manuel Romero-Huelva, Laurence G. Smith, Francesco Tei*

Soil amendment application in an olive grove: effects on plant performance. *Rita Leogrande, Liliana Gaeta, Mirko Castellini*

Effects of different agronomic conditions on the production of eight bread wheat varieties. *Roberto Mancinelli, Mohamed Allam, Mariam Atait, Verdiana Petroselli, Emanuele Radicetti*

Understanding the spatiotemporal behaviour and the environmental sustainability of crop yield in an organic farming system. *Stefano Marino, Marco di Cristofaro, Arturo Alvino*

Allelopathic Effect of Buckwheat (*Fagopyrum esculentum L.*) on Germination and Performance of Crops and Weeds: a comprehensive methodology. *Daniel Marusig, Alessandra Virili, Gemini Delle Vedove, Elisa Marraccini*

Reduction of N input using foliar fertilisation and biostimulants: impact on yield and quality of common wheat. *Antonio Minoliti, Ida Di Mola, Lucia Ottaiano, Eugenio Cozzolino, Massimo Fagnano, Mauro Mori, Nunzio Fiorentino*

Camelina, an emerging oilseed crop, intercropped with pulses. *Elena Pagani, Federica Zanetti, Erika Facciolla, Andrea Monti*

Effects Of Deficit Irrigation On Mineral Elements Content Of ‘Early’ Potato. *Gaetano Pandino, Tiziana D’Anna, Giuseppa Scarso, Mariadaniela Mantineo, Davide Arnese, Claudia Formenti, Salvatore Alfio Salicola, Aurelio Scavo, Gaetano Roberto Pesce, Sara Lombardo, Giovanni Mauromicale*

Adaptability of Coloured Potato Cultivars to the Mediterranean Environment. *Alessandra Pellegrino, Salvatore La Rosa, Bruno Parisi, Salvatore Salicola, Giovanni Mauromicale, Anita Ierna*

A Comparative Test Of Rain Gun And Rainger Applied To Grain Maize In The North-eastern Italy. *Gaetano Roberto Pesce, Luca Cestaro, Maurizio Borin, Carmelo Maucieri*

Improving Tomato Production By Inoculation Of Arbuscular Mycorrhizal Fungi. *Valentina Quintarelli, Emanuele Radicetti, Mattia Baretta, Mortadha Ben Hassine, Roberto Mancinelli*

Tomato Plant Growth And Production As Affected By Inoculation With Arbuscular Mycorrhizal Fungi. *Valentina Quintarelli, Emanuele Radicetti, Mattia Baretta, Mortadha Ben Hassine, Roberto Mancinelli*

Use of spectral indices to optimize irrigation management of apricot in Mediterranean environment. *Carmela Riefolo, Laura D’Andrea*

Soil Carbon Content in Long-Term Experiment under Different Soil Tillage Management Systems. *Michele Rinaldi, Salvatore Baiano, Antonio Troccoli, Angelo Pio De Santis, Leonardo Morcone, Luigi Morra*

Foliar application of biostimulants enhances sustainability and agronomic performances of wheat: preliminary results from central Italy. *Angelo Rossini, Roberto Ruggeri, Nada Mzid, Francesco Rossini*

Agronomic, Productive, and Qualitative Response of Sugarcane Accessions for Sicily. *Francesco Salamone, Nicolò Iacuzzi, Noemi Tortorici, Federica Alaimo, Teresa Tuttolomondo, Davide Farruggia*

Agronomic Management Of Hybrid Barley: Effect Of Tillage, Seeding Rate And N Fertilization. *Mattia Scapino, Luca Capo, Raffaele Meloni, Paolo Colombatto, Amedeo Reyneri, Massimo Blandino*

‘Early’ Potato – Pea Intercropping: First Evidence On Productive Traits And Insect Control. *Aurelio Scavo, Sara Lombardo, Antonio Biondi, Gaetano Pandino, Giovanna Tropea Garzia, Salvatore Alfio Salicola, Carmelo Cavallaro, Antonio Gugliuzzo, Claudia Formenti, Fabrizio Lisi, Gaetano Roberto Pesce, Giovanni Mauromicale*

Weed Pressure In An Organic Wheat-Legume Intercropping And Relay Cropping. *Danilo Scordia, Francesca Calderone, Oteri Marianna, Stefania Toscano, Fabio Gresta*

Legume Based Rotation In Low Input Agricultural Systems: Sustainability Aspects, Agronomic Traits And Nutritional Features. *Camilla Tibaldi, Mattia Alpi, Elettra Frassinetti, Giovanni Dinelli, Ilaria Marotti*

Yield, Pests and Weeds in Lentil–Cereal Intercropping. *Giacomo Tosti, Beatrice Falcinelli, Marcello Guiducci*

Weed competition ability of perennial forage legumes and grass growth in mixture and in pure stands under increasing level of simulated shade in rainfed condition. *Lorenzo Gabriele Tramacere, Alberto Mantino, Giorgio Ragaglini, Marcello Mele, Massimo Sbrana, Daniele Antichi*

Oper8 Project, a new European thematic network on non- chemical methods of weed control. *Lorenzo Gabriele Tramacere, Christian Frascioni, Lorenzo Gagliardi, Massimo Sbrana, Daniele Antichi*

A two-step approach for the calibration and simulation of wheat-lentil intercropping systems using MONICA. *Alessandro Triacca, Stefano Carlesi, Federico Leoni, Gilbert Koskey, Anna-Camilla Moonen, Moritz Reckling, Claas Nendel*

Improving Skills on Digital Agriculture in Europe: lessons learnt from the AgriSmart project. *Valentina Vaglia, Francesco Fava, Eugenio Carlon, George Dimitriadis, Martyna Kurek, Erika Nika, Heide Reimer, Peter Vnucko, Ambrogio Zanzi, Stefano Bocchi*

Agronomic And Environmental Effects Of Alternate Wetting And Drying In Italian Rice Cultivation. *Andrea Vitali, Barbara Moretti, Chiara Bertora, Eleonora Miniotti, Silvia Fogliatto, Marco Romani, Luisella Celi, Daniel Said-Pullicino, Francesco Vidotto*

Environmental Sustainability of Durum Wheat Cropping Systems: a Life Cycle Assessment Perspective. *Silvia Zingale, Carlo Ingraio, Giuseppe Indovino, Umberto Anastasi, Antonio Carlo Barbera, Paolo Guarnaccia, Thomas Nemecek*

Sessione 4 - RESILIENZA - Adattamento delle produzioni ai criteri di sostenibilità e ai cambiamenti climatici

ORAL PRESENTATIONS

Adapting Crops For The Green Transition: Smart Protein Project Experiences For Plant Protein Production Across Europe. *Gabriela Alandia, Nisha Sharma, Signe Marie Jensen, Fulai Li, Harm Brinks, Johan Wander, Dragica Grozdanic, Lucia Sanchez, Avichai Amrad, Daniel Marusig, Gemini Delle Vedove*

Application of Multi-Height Beerkan Method and BEST-Procedure to Study the Water Impact Effects on Soil Hydraulic Properties Under Alternative Soil Management. *Mirko Castellini, Antonio Preite, Luisa Giglio, Michele Rinaldi*

A New Approach for Developing Sustainable and Health-Promoting Durum Wheat *Composite Cross Populations*. *Paolo Guarnaccia, Silvia Zingale, Umberto Anastasi, Giuseppe Indovino, Alfio Spina, Giovanni Dinelli, Sara Bosi, Francesca Truzzi, Brunella Trucchi, Stefano Benedettelli*

A Two-Step Evaluation of Permanent Legume Living Mulches for Organic and Conservative Vegetable Systems. *Federico Leoni, Stefano Carlesi, Daniele Antichi, Christian Frascioni, Anna-Camilla Moonen*

POSTERS

Optimizing Camelina Sowing Date and Cultivar Choice to Maximize Vitamin E Content. *Barbara Alberghini, Federica Zanetti, Angela Vecchi, Federico Ferioli, Andrea Monti*

Coupling IoT Technologies, Blockchain and Modelling to Enhance Crop Production and Farmers' Financial Resilience Under Extreme Climatic Events: the RESTORATION Project. *Anna Rita Balingit, Giovanni Argenti, Marco Moriondo, Giacomo Trombi, Roberto Ferrise, Sergi Costafreda-Aumedes, Riccardo Rossi, Gloria Padovan, Niccolò Bartoloni, Sara Landini, Gianluca De Donno, Virginia Fani, Bianca Bindi, Romeo Bandinelli, Camilla Dibari*

Abiotic stress and durum wheat: morpho-physiological aspects in the Mediterranean environment. *Silvia Cantalamessa, Afsaneh Nematpour, Giancarlo Pagnani, Fabio Stagnari, Michele Pisante*

The Detection Of Salt-Tolerant Genotypes To Reduce Yield Losses And Pressure on Fresh-Water Reserves: A Quick, Simple, And Affordable Bioassay. *Linda Carrino, Donato Visconti, Daniele Todisco, Nunzio Fiorentino, Massimo Fagnano*

Temporal Changes in Saturated Hydraulic Conductivity under Minimum- and No-tillage Soil Management. *Mirko Castellini, Simone Di Prima*

Evaluating a World Mini-Collection of Domesticated Cowpea (*Vigna unguiculata* [L.] Walp.) for Intercropping With Cereals. *Daniele Cavalli, Luciano Pecetti, Nicolò Franguelli, Tommaso Notario, Paolo Annicchiarico*

Annual Variability Of N Mineralization From Soil Organic Matter As Affected By Climate. *Octavian P. Chiriac, Marco Pittarello, Barbara Moretti, Carlo Grignani, Laura Zavattaro*

Leaf Gas Exchange of Lignocellulosic Perennial Grasses Under Different Soil Water Availability. *Sebastiano Andrea Corinzia, Danilo Scordia, Giorgio Testa, Elena Crapio, Antonella Iurato, Cristina Patanè, Salvatore Luciano Cosentino*

Yield Of Lignocellulosic Perennial Grasses Under Different Soil Water Availability. *Sebastiano Andrea Corinzia, Elena Crapio, Danilo Scordia, Antonella Iurato, Giorgio Testa, Cristina Patanè, Salvatore Luciano Cosentino*

Climate-Smart Forage Systems for Climate-Smart Soils. *Claudia Dămățircă, Barbara Moretti, Luisella Celi, Maria Vicenza Chiriaco, Giampiero Lombardi, Laura Zavattaro*

Assessment of Grazing Intensity Integrating Google Earth Engine (Sentinel-2) and Livestock GPS locations. *Luca de Guttery, Laura Stendardi, Sergi Costafreda-Aumedes, Edoardo Bellini, Andrea Confessore, Chiara Aquilani, Marco Moriondo, Nicolina Staglianò, Carolina Pugliese, Giovanni Argenti, Camilla Dibari*

Modelling Context-Specific Mitigation Potential of Greenhouse Gas Emissions and Nitrogen Losses in Key European Farming Systems For Dairy Production. *Xabier Díaz de Otálora, Agustín del Prado, Federico Dragoni, Fernando Estelles, Barbara Amon*

Crop Performance of Peanut in a South Italy Environment: Effect of Irrigation and Plant Growth-Promoting Microorganisms on Water Productivity. *Michele Andrea De Santis, Daniela Campaniello, Damiana Tozzi, Luigia Giuzio, Maria Rosaria Corbo, Antonio Bevilacqua, Milena Grazia Rita Sinigaglia, Zina Flagella*

Simulating Soil Heterotrophic Respiration with ARMOSA Model: Calibration with Continuous Field Measures of CO₂ Soil Fluxes from the AGRESTIC Project. *Mara Gabbrielli, Marco Botta, Marco Perfetto, Irìde Volpi, Diego Guidotti, Cristiano Tozzini, Pierluigi Meriggi, Alessia Perego, Marco Acutis, Giorgio Ragolini*

Working On Ancient Wheats And Old Durum Wheat Cultivars At The Dept. Of Agricultural Sciences Of Sassari. *Francesco Giunta, Rosella Motzo, Marina Mefleh, Martina Careddu*

A Network of Farms to Develop and Test Innovations for Climate-Smart Cropping Systems. *Elisa Marraccini, Vittoria Giannini, Gabriela Alandia, Giorgio Borreani, Mirco Corazzin, Gemini Delle Vedove, Francesco Ferrero, Stefano Grigolato, Carmelo Maucieri, Tanja Mimmo, Carlo Nicoletto, Silvia Panozzo, Gaetano R. Pesce, Gabriele Rolando, Luigi Sartori, Paolo Sivilotti, Enrico Sturaro, Ernesto Tabacco, Massimo Tagliavini, Eren Taskin, Damiano Zanotelli, Maurizio Borin*

Greenhouse Gas Emissions and Yield of Durum Wheat Under Organic and Conventional Fertilization in Three Type Soil. *Lucia Ottaiano, Eugenio Cozzolino, Ida Di Mola, Maria Eleonora Pelosi, Luca Vitale, Giuseppe Maglione, Bruno di Matteo, Daniele Todisco, Nunzio Fiorentino, Mauro Mori*

Yield and Quality Comparison of Hard Common Wheat Varieties in NE Italy in the Dry Year 2022. *Anna Panozzo, Simone Piotto, Riccardo Boscaro, Giuseppe Barion, Mirko Volpato, Teofilo Vamerli*

What Happens to Soil Organic Carbon in Venetian Low-lying Plain? Insight from a Long-term Experiment. *Iliaria Piccoli, Riccardo Polese, Nicola Dal Ferro, Francesco Morari, Antonio Berti*

Impact of Alley Poplar Silvoarable Systems with Soybean on Microclimatic Variables. *Simone Piotto, Anna Panozzo, Gaia Pasqualotto, Vinicio Carraro, Giuseppe Barion, Stefano Nale, Lorenzo Furlan, Tommaso Anfodillo, Teofilo Vamerli*

Yield and Yield Components of Alternative Crops in a Climate-Changing Mediterranean Environment. *Cataldo Pulvento, Luigi Tedone, Claudia Ruta, Giuseppe De Mastro*

Adoption of Conservation Agriculture in Winter Wheat (*Triticum Aestivum* L.) with the Aim of Saving Water, Protecting the Environment, Improving Soil Health and Reducing CO₂ Emissions. *Maria Florencia Ribero, Antonio Berti, Michele Pisante*

Leaf Gas Exchange of Sicilian Wheat Landraces Under Contrasting Soil Water Content. *Giorgio Testa, Alessio Scandurra, Paolo Caruso, Valeria Cafaro, Cristina Patanè, Salvatore Luciano Cosentino, Sebastiano Andrea Corinzia*

Can the Adoption of Conservation Agriculture Actually Increase the Soil Carbon Content? *Antonio Troccoli, Salvatore Baiano, Michele Rinaldi, Luigi Morra*

Sessione 5 - TRACCIABILITÀ - Promozione della sicurezza, tracciabilità e tipicità delle filiere

ORAL PRESENTATIONS

Evaluation of different growing systems on the productive and quality features of saffron (*Crocus sativus* L.). *Giovanni Dinelli, Mattia Alpi, Elettra Frassinetti, Ilaria Marotti*

Multi-Mycotoxin Long-Term Monitoring Survey on North-Italian Maize over an 11-Year Period (2011–2021): The Co-Occurrence of Regulated, Masked and Emerging Mycotoxins and Fungal Metabolites. *Sabrina Locatelli, Valentina Scarpino, Chiara Lanzanova, Elio Romano, Amedeo Reyneri*

Multielement profile and chemometrics for traceability of Pomodorino del Piennolo del Vesuvio PDO. *Luigi Ruggiero, Raffaella Ofano, Diana Agrelli, Carmine Amalfitano, Paola Adamo*

Combining a crop model and remote sensing for crop trait retrieval: a methodological framework. *Fosco Mattia Vesely, Anne Schucknecht, Mirco Boschetti, Gabriele Candiani, Monica Pepe, Stefano Bocchi, Francesco Fava*

POSTERS

Hemp Inflorescences Traceability By Low Field NMR Relaxometry And Biometric Evaluation. *Salvatore Baiano, Mariarosaria Sicignano, Francesco Raimo, Luisa del Piano, Tommaso Enotrio, Paolo Lo Meo, Delia Francesca Chillura Martino, Pellegrino Conte*

Plants Toxic to Farm Animals: Assessment of their Chemical Compounds and Distribution in Central Italy. *Elisabetta Bianchi, Giovanni Argenti, Nicolina Staglianò, Federico Selvi, Silvia Lamanna, Claudia Focardi*

Digital Tools for Field Phenotyping of Processing Tomato Genotypes. *Andrea Burato, Federico Landi, Alfonso Pentangelo, Raffaele Cavaliere, Francesco Vitale, Domenico Ronga, Mario Parisi*

FoodOnLine Project: identification of metabolomic profiles for the certification of agri-food products and their traceability through block chain technology. *Cangemi Silvana, Mondelli Attilio, Mouzakioti Georgia, De Martino Antonio, Vinci Giovanni, Mazzei Pierluigi, Ciardella Giorgio, Spaccini Riccardo*

Evaluation of the effects of plant growth promoting microorganisms on wheat growth by spectral phenotyping: preliminary results from Agritech Project. *Michele Andrea De Santis, Antonio Bevilacqua, Annalisa d'Amelio, Damiana Tozzi, Luigia Giuzio, Michele Rinaldi, Nicola Pecchioni, Zina Flagella*

Greenhouse Covered by Photoluminescent Polyethylene Improves the Agronomical Response of Eggplant (*Solanum melongena* L.). *Ida Di Mola, Eugenio Cozzolino, Lucia Ottaiano, Maria Eleonora Pelosi, Sabrina Nocerino, Massimo Rippa, Pasquale Mormile, Luca Beltrame, Mauro Mori*

Mineral Elements Content In Globe Artichoke As Affected By Mulching Treatment. *Gaetano Pandino, Salvatore Susino, Giuseppe Zito, Claudia Formenti, Salvatore Alfio Salicola, Aurelio Scavo, Gaetano Roberto Pesce, Sara Lombardo, Giovanni Mauromicale*

A Multidisciplinary Approach To Detect Stress Symptoms In Vegetable Crops. *Massimo Pugliese, Luca Alfarano, Roberta Bulgari, Gica Stefanescu Miralles, Lorenzo Comba, Riccardo Cecire, Mery Malandrino, Luisella Celi*

Towards the Production of Durum and Common Wheat for a 0-residues Food Supply-Chain. *Amedeo Reyneri, Luca Capo, Aldo Ferrero, Marta Guarise, Giacomo Pedretti, Massimo Blandino*

Sessione 1

RECUPERO - Sviluppo delle aree marginali

ORAL PRESENTATIONS

Micro-plastic Effects on Agricultural Soil: A Bibliometric Analysis

Antonello Calcutta, Ennio D'Emanuele, Sebastiano Infantino, Enrico Naselli, Antonio C. Barbera

Di3A, Univ. Catania, IT, antonio.barbera@unict.it

Introduction

Microplastics (MPs) are a pressing environmental problem in agricultural areas worldwide. While the effects of MPs contamination in the sea have received extensive attention, the contamination of lands has only recently started to be investigated (Sajjad et al., 2022). Here, the Scopus and Web of Science Core Collection (WOS) databases are simultaneously explored by a multi-step approach with the aim of finding trends as well as less explored areas of interest related to MPs in agriculture.

Materials and Methods

SCOPUS and WOS databanks were explored through the combination of VOSviewer (VOS) (Waltman et al., 2010) and statistical analyses. All the entries available in the two databanks till May 2023 were retrieved and exclusively scientific sources were selected for the dataset exports. The “best match” option was preferred while downloading the datasets.

VOS version 1.6.19 was the graphical analysis tool. During the analysis standard parameters were selected, more precisely: clustering resolution: 1; minimum cluster size: 20; and the method applied for normalization was the association strength.

Results

In Figure 1, the co-occurrence maps obtained through VOS by the query “microplastics OR nanoplastics AND agriculture” in WOS (panel A) and in SCOPUS (panel B) are compared.

Figure 1. Co-occurrence maps obtained through VOS by the query “microplastics OR nanoplastics AND agricultur*” retrived from WOS (panel A) and SCOPUS (panel B). The item “agriculture” and “soil” are pointed at by the black lines. 5 clusters are found in WOS and 3 clusters in SCOPUS.

In SCOPUS, 908 records were retrieved resulting in 7518 keywords of which 205 appeared at least 20 times in the exported dataset representing a 2.7% overall. In WOS, 2000 records were retrieved resulting in 25928 keywords, of which 801 occurred more than 20 times representing a 3.1% overall.

The comparison shows that a comprehensive understanding of the “microplastics-agriculture” landscape requires the exploration of more databanks as different clusters are found in the same analysis conditions. Indeed, 5 clusters are found in the WOS databank and 3 clusters in the SCOPUS one. In either of two maps a “agronom*” possible item was not found while “agroecosystem” only appears in the SCOPUS database according to the selected analysis parameters.

In figure 2, the SCOPUS link strengths of the items co-occurring with the item “agriculture” are reported against the score they obtained when normalized.

Figure 2. Distribution of strengths measured between the item “agriculture” and other 204 items. Dataset: SCOPUS. Query “microplastics OR nanoplastics AND agricultur*”. Average value = 20, standard deviation = 18.

Along the distribution the item “China” (link strength = 55) appears on the right half decreasing part of the normal curve highlighting the awareness to the microplastics subject in the Chinese research. “Particle size” (link strength = 64) quite strongly co-occur with “agriculture” because of the many studies dedicated to microplastic particle characterization, effects, interactions and fate (Li et al., 2023).

“Mulch” (link strength =39) is over the average value and “fertilizers” (link strength = 26) lies on the upper part of the curve. Both items are related to environmental problems. The interest towards mulching is related to the organic agriculture as well. The items “heavy metals”, “pesticides” and crops (link strength = 18, 16 and 11 respectively) are found below the average value.

Conclusions

According to the bibliometric analysis, agronomic studies on microplastics and nanoplastics are highly needed especially when referred to crops, pesticides and heavy metals. Keywords belonging to the agronomic field, like organic farming and mycorrhiza, are missing in the co-occurrence map indicating possible emerging areas of investigation.

Literature

Li Z. et al. 2023. A discussion of microplastics in soil and risks for ecosystems and food chains. *Chemosphere*, 313: 137637.
 Sajjad M. et al. 2022. Microplastics in the soil environment: A critical review. *Env. Tech. & Innov.*, 27: 102408.
 Waltman L. et al. 2010. A unified approach to mapping and clustering of bibliometric networks. *J. Inf.*, 4: 629-635.

Developing a Planning Process for a Coastal Wetland and Assessing the Role of Agriculture in Ecosystem Services and Biodiversity

Anna Rita Bernadette Cammerino, Michela Ingaramo, Massimo Monteleone

DAFNE, Univ. Foggia, IT, annarita.cammerino@unifg.it

Introduction

Wetlands can provide a wide spectrum of important ecosystem services that benefit both humans and wildlife (Tang et al., 2018). These services are the result of the full range of ecological functions that take place in this rich and diverse ecosystem. Firstly, wetlands are among the most productive ecosystems in the world and a huge variety of species can be part of a wetland ecosystem. The combination of shallow water, high nutrient levels and high primary productivity are the reasons why a very complex ecosystem can reach its *climax*. These services include supporting, regulating, provisioning, cultural and recreational services. Some wetlands help to provide clean and abundant water supplies, contribute to the water cycle and act as natural water purifiers, filtering sediment and absorbing many pollutants in surface waters, also contributing to flood control, storing floodwater and nutrient retention.

Unfortunately, wetlands have been progressively reduced since 1900 (Davidson, 2014) to make way for agricultural activities, and their drainage was, until a few decades ago, considered a useful reclamation measure to improve living conditions and human health. Today, when wetlands are so limited, their conservation is seen as vital, but it is also a very challenging issue that requires coordinated action across complex and often large watersheds. However, such ecosystems are marginal, fragile, vulnerable and subject to frequent anthropogenic impacts (overexploitation of water resources, infrastructure development, land use conversion and large-scale tourism). As a result, ecological problems such as pollution, eutrophication and biodiversity loss have worsened in recent decades.

In any case, agriculture remains a constant even in wetlands (Heimlich, 2003). Its practice can be a risk factor for the conservation of this ecosystem or, on the contrary, it can be a strengthening element for its stability. This depends entirely on the agricultural model applied. Our aim is to identify management practices that are not only fully compatible with the conservation of the ecosystem, but can even contribute to its regeneration and further diversification. At the same time, we expect that wetland agriculture will be able to benefit from a compensatory effect by achieving greater autonomy from agro-technical inputs and a higher level of stability and resilience.

This contribution should be seen in the frame of the AGRITECH project, Spoke 7 “Integrated models for the development of *marginal areas* to promote multifunctional productive systems enhancing agroecological and socioeconomic sustainability; Task 7.3.3 “Sustainable nature-based solutions for soil and water management and remediation, specific for marginal areas”.

Materials and Methods

Sustainable and regenerative agriculture, biodiversity conservation and recreation/cultural activities are considered the three main pillars of good wetland management. A long-term *strategic plan* is coupled with a short-term *design plan*; the aim is to harmonise these pillars and develop effective actions to progressively achieve the final objectives according to a defined order of priorities. Two different methodological tools have been used to support the development of this wetland planning process, the *Scale of Permanence* (SoP) and the *Driver-Pressure-State-Impact-Response* (DPSIR) model (EEA, 1995).

The SoP (originally proposed by P.A. Yeomans, 1993) is a form of site analysis and designing process according to a sequence of ordered constraints. Design should follow a stepwise or sequential approach, prioritising the landscape components that have the greatest impact but are difficult to change, while leaving the easiest to change and most responsive to our efforts at the end.

The DPSIR is a functional analysis approach for structuring the cause-and-effect relationships associated with management problems. It allows economic, social and environmental information to be integrated into a logical and recursive framework. It helps to identify key relationships, develop an overview, understand responses and decide on management options. The DPSIR framework considers *drivers* (D), e.g. human activities, that exert *pressures* (P) on the environment, leading to changes in some *states* (S), i.e. environmental variables; these changes in turn lead to *impacts* (I) on the ecological system, human health and social conditions, which may trigger a range of *responses* (R). Depending on the type of action taken, responses can be directed at any component of the DPSIR framework by controlling drivers, reducing pressures, improving state and mitigating impacts.

The planning process was applied to a case study represented by the *Laguna del Re* in Siponto (Manfredonia - FG). The *Laguna del Re* ("King's Lagoon") is a coastal wetland of great naturalistic importance, located at the mouth of the Candelaro stream, with an extension of 40 hectares, part of the reclamation system of the Siponto polder. The land reclamation, carried out before World War II, involved a radical transformation of the natural hydrological regime to recover areas for agriculture and human settlement. Today, this area is still one of the cornerstones of Apulian coastal landscape.

Results

According to SoP, the ranking of the design actions should be in the following order: 1. *Climate* > 2. *Landform* > 3. *Waterflows* > 4. *Access, circulation, paths and trails* > 5. *Buildings* > 6. *Vegetation and wildlife* > 7. *Microclimate and zoning* > 8. *Soil fertility management* > 9. *Aesthetics and sense of place*. A relevant environmental project (LIFE 09/NAT/IT/000150) worked out in the *Laguna del Re* has promoted greater biodiversity by restoring the area, which had become silted up, by reopening and redesigning canals, digging 'valleys' (stretches of water) and creating sluices in order to recreate the typical transitional coastal environment, characterised by the alternation of flooded areas and dry land, also for agricultural use. Footpaths, huts, and terraces for birdwatching have been built to promote the use of the oasis. This complex process was achieved by considering the first 5 priority steps of the SoP. The following steps are now being planned and implemented. Through a series of meetings with experts, first, and stakeholders, afterwards, seven main *drivers* were identified: 1) *industrial installations*; 2) *proximity of urban areas*; 3) *road traffic*; 4) *tourist and visitor flows*; 5) *illegal fishing and poaching*; 6) *water management from the irrigation and land reclamation consortium*; 7) *agriculture*. Drivers 1, 2 and 3 can only affect the wetland from the outside (they are external drivers only), while drivers 4, 5, 6 and 7 can affect the wetland from both the inside and the outside. Internal drivers are under the direct control of the wetland management authority and can therefore be guided by a *local design plan*. In contrast, the regulation of external drivers is entrusted to a much broader *territorial strategic plan*, which is more policy oriented. The local design plan can be considered, therefore, as an outline of the territorial strategic plan. Each *driver* (from 1 to 7) was linked to a set of *impacts* and a set of *pressures* from a comprehensive list. Each driver, moreover, was cross-referenced with one or more *states*, i.e. a) *biodiversity*, b) *water conditions*, c) *soil quality*, d) *atmosphere and climate change*, e) *landscape and environmental salubrity*.

Conclusions

The *pressures* and *impacts* most frequently associated with both *drivers* and *states* are considered to be the most critical and those to be prioritised. The corresponding *responses* were then developed to guide decisions on actions to be taken.

Literature

- Davidson N.C. 2014. How much wetland has the world lost? Long-term and recent trends in global wetland area. *Mar. Freshwater. Research.*, 65: 934–941.
- EEA 1995. "Europe's Environment: the Dobris Assessment", European Environment Agency (EEA), Copenhagen.
- Heimlich R. 2003. *Agricultural Resources and Environmental Indicators*. Agriculture Handbook No. 722 (AH722). Economic Research Service, U.S. Department of Agriculture, Washington, DC.
- Tang et al. 2018. Effects of ecological flow release patterns on water quality and ecological restoration of a large shallow lake. *J. Clean Prod.*, 174: 577–590.
- Yeomans P.A. 1993. *Water for every farm: Yeoman Keyline Plan*. Ed. Keyline Design. Pages 272.

Biomass and Seed Yields of Cardoon (*Cynara cardunculus* L.) Fertilized by Biowaste Compost in Two Inland Hilly Areas of Southern Italy

Luigi Morra¹, Nino Virzi², Maurizio Bilotto¹, Tommaso Enotrio¹, Antonio Merola¹, Antonio Leonardi², Stefania Licciardello², Ezio Li Puma², Fabiola Sciacca², Massimo Palumbo², Michele Falce³, Anna Ciancolini³, Gianmaria Baldi³

¹ CREA-CI, sede di Caserta, IT, luigi.morra@crea.gov.it

² CREA-CI, sede di Acireale, IT, nino.virzi@crea.gov.it

³ NOVAMONT SpA, Novara, IT, michele.falce@novamont.com

Introduction

Among the perennial crops, cardoon is a good candidate to be grown in dry lands as a field crop for multi-purposes and non conventional uses. However, these crops can be highly limited by the low soil nutrient and water availability, so it is interesting to evaluate to which extent the use of a low-cost fertilizer as biowaste compost can be a useful tool to improve soil fertility and crop performance (Dominguez et al., 2019). We carried out in two internal hilly locations of Sicily and Campania, two trials in order to assess different fertilization regimes of cardoon. In the present contribution we discuss data about production of biomass and seeds of two years. The research was funded under the Project PON COMETA (2018-2021).

Materials and Methods

In Campania, the experiment was set in a farm located in Calvi (BN), 300 m above sea level (a.s.l.), in a sloping land. Soil had a loam texture with a poor fertility. In Sicily, the trial was set at Aidone (EN), 200 m a.s.l. in a sloping land. Soil had a clay-silt texture with poor fertility. Four fertilization treatments were compared in both the locations according to a CRB design with three replications. Treatments were: 1) Biowaste compost applied once before the seeding, to supply 300 kg ha⁻¹ of total N (COM 300); 2) Biowaste compost applied as above, to supply 600 kg ha⁻¹ of total N (COM 600); 3) pre-sowing mineral fertilization with NPK and, after sprouting in Autumn, 90 kg N ha⁻¹ as Urea (MIN); 4) control not fertilized (CNT). A rainfed crop of cardoon, cv Trinaseed, was seeded on December 18, 2018 at Aidone, and on October 17, 2019 at Calvi, to obtain an initial plant density of 8.3 plants m⁻². Dry weight of aboveground biomass was determined in both the environments in April-May at the maximum leaf mass reaching, and after harvest in August. Yield of seeds were measured by sampling fertile inflorescences from plants inside a collecting area; yield per hectare was estimated on the basis of the yield per plant and of plant density at harvest.

Results

The production of biomass and seeds in the first two years of production of the cardoon at Calvi is shown in Tab. 1. In both years, the plant density at full spring decreased at harvest after the drought of summer months. Plant density decreased from the second to the third year of cycle. Dry biomass produced in spring has always been higher in MIN and COM 600 while COM 300 is equivalent to CNT. Thousand kernel weight showed always values around 40 g. In general the lowest yields were in COM 300 and CNT while COM 600 was comparable to MIN. The dry biomass collected at the end of the cycle was lower than in spring, putting in evidence the high amount of biomass released on soil surface. In Tab. 2 are reported the main results obtained in the trial carried out in Sicily, in the second and third year of cycle (2020 and 2021). In this environment, plant density was much lower but the plants produced a full ground coverage and a wide flowering already in the first year of the cycle. The treatments MIN and COM600 showed in both the years higher values of dry weight biomass while COM300 got the lower values. Number of fertile flower heads per plant and grain yield significantly increased in the third year of cycle (2021), when MIN and CNT reached very high production while COM300 showed yield significantly lower than the other treatments. Thousand kernel weight also increased in 2021 but in this location values resulted lower than in Campania.

Table 1: Plant densities at full vegetative growth phase and at harvest with corresponding dry weight biomass of cardoon; 1000 kernels weight and yields of commercial seeds in the second and third year of cycle (2021 and 2022) at Calvi (BN).

Treatments	Year	Plant density at spring (pp m ⁻²)	Dry weight biomass in spring (t ha ⁻¹)	Plant density at harvest (pp m ⁻²)	Heads per plant (n)	Yield of seeds (kg ha ⁻¹)	1000 kernels weight (g)	Dry weight biomass at harvest (t ha ⁻¹)
MIN	2021	8.4	17.3 a	6.03	2.8	1510 a	41.4	8.0
COM 600		9.8	18.1 a	5.87	2.2	830 ab	38.8	7.8
COM 300		9.5	12.1 ab	5.08	2.1	480 b	43.9	5.3
CNT		9.7	7.7 b	4.92	2.0	450 b	44.1	4.5
Mean		9.3	13.8	5.4	2.2	817.5	42	6.4
Significance		n.s.	***	n.s.	n.s.	*	n.s.	n.s.
MIN	2022	7.7	6.25 a	2.70	3.0	400	42.3	0.4
COM 600		7.3	5.42 a	3.49	3.9	900	40.2	0.7
COM 300		7.6	4.53 ab	1.59	3.0	270	37.5	0.2
CNT		7.4	3.46 b	1.16	4.0	280	40.2	0.2
Mean		7.5	4.9	2.2	3.4	462.5	40	0.37
Significance		n.s.	***	n.s.	n.s.	n.s.	n.s.	n.s.

Different letters indicate means significantly different to Tukey's Test ($\alpha=0.05$); n.s.: not significant differences; * $P \leq 0.05$; *** $P \leq 0.001$

Table 2: Main results concerning the production of biomass and seeds of cardoon in the trial carried out in Sicily, in second and third years of cycle (2020-2021) at Aidone (EN).

Treatments	Year	Plant density in spring (pp m ⁻²)	Dry weight biomass in spring (t ha ⁻¹)	Plant height at max develop. (cm)	Heads per plant (n)	Yield of seeds (kg ha ⁻¹)	1000 kernels weight (g)
MIN	2020	4.2 a	12.9	101	2.4	644.2	28.9
COM 600		3.8 b	13.7	99	2.1	471.9	27.0
COM 300		3.4 c	8.2	96	2.2	447.9	26.6
CNT		4.3 a	9.6	93	2.1	547.7	30.6
Means		3.9	11.11	97.25	2.22	527.92	28.28
Significance		***	n.s.	n.s.	n.s.	n.s.	n.s.
MIN	2021	4.2 a	19.2	142	4.6 a	1197.1 a	32.0
COM 600		3.9 b	14.5	109	3.1 ab	916.5 ab	33.7
COM 300		3.4 c	9.4	118	2.9 b	679.4 b	28.8
CNT		4.2 a	14.0	109	3.6 ab	1099.5 a	29.8
Means		3.93	14.29	119.5	3.56	973.13	31.1
Significance		***	n.s.	n.s.	***	**	n.s.

Different letters, where present, indicates means significantly different to Tukey's Test ($\alpha=0.05$)

n.s.: not significant differences; ***: significant per $p \leq 0.001$; **: significant per $p \leq 0.01$.

Conclusions

In marginal lands, the low input cardoon crop supplied a good amount of biomass and seed; furtherly, the perennial crop tackled weeds development and can contributed to reduce soil erosion. In perspective, combination of compost amendment and reduced doses of N mineral fertilizer appears to be the most promising approach for crop nutrition and soil recovery.

Literature

Dominguez M.T. et al. 2019. Thistle crops in marginal lands after compost addition: plant biomass and effect on soil physical, chemical and biological properties. Land Degrad. Dev., 31(9): 1167-1175.

Influence of Tillage and Nitrogen Fertilization on Durum Wheat Metabolite Profiling and Yield

Luigi Tedone¹, Giovanna Marta Fusco², Rosalinda Nicastrò², Petronia Carillo²

¹ Dep. of Soil, Plant and Food Sciences, Univ. Bari “Aldo Moro”, Bari, IT, luigi.tedone@uniba.it

² Dep. Environmental, Biological and Pharmaceutical Sciences and Technologies, Univ. Campania “L. Vanvitelli”, Caserta, IT

Introduction

Durum wheat represents the most widespread cereal crop in the Mediterranean basin, and Italy is the main country for its cultivation, processing and marketing in the world. Producing high quality durum wheat grain is very challenging since quality parameters are very variable and affected by environmental conditions, crop management, and processing techniques (Flagella, 2006). The use of alternative cropping techniques for durum wheat is strategic for a sustainable intensification of wheat production based on low input soil tillage management, and an increased nutrient use efficiency, in particular nitrogen management (N) (Ali, 2015). However, there is little information in the literature concerning the long-term effects of tillage systems and N application on durum wheat grain quality and metabolic profile in Mediterranean dryland conditions. In this research, the effects of different tillage systems and N application on the metabolic profile of the kernels' components of durum wheat in a long-term fava bean rotation were evaluated.

Materials and Methods

Durum wheat (*Triticum turgidum* L. subsp. *durum* cv. Iride) plants were cultivated in the year 2021-22 as reported in Tedone et al. (2023), in a continuous long-term open field experiment from 2009-2010 in which the following variables were compared:

- rotation: durum wheat vs faba bean (*Vicia faba* var. Minor Persons)
- soil tillage: Conventional tillage (CT), Reduced tillage (RT), Conservation/no tillage (NT)
- nitrogen input: 0, 30, 60, 90 kg N ha⁻¹ applied as urea at the end of tillering phase.

Durum wheat was sown in November 2021, using a seed density of 400 germinable seeds m⁻². The harvest was carried out in June–July using a Wintersteiger Classic plot combine, on a sample area of 15 m². Grain yield and total protein content were measured on the sampled grain. The metabolic profiling on the same samples was performed according to Woodrow et al. (2017) and Dell'Aversana et al. (2021).

Results

Figure 1. Grain yield according to tillage system and nitrogen application.

The NT treatment showed a high and significant ($p \leq 0.05$) increase in grain yield (+53% and +42% compared to RT and CT, respectively), while nitrogen application causes a slight increase (about 10%) compared to non-fertilised treatments. RT and NT farming systems did not differ significantly between them. Protein content was influenced by tillage system, with higher values in RT and CT than in NT system. Considering the metabolic profile of all treatment, the RT x 90 N ha⁻¹ fertilization (RT_90) treatment showed the highest contents of total and soluble proteins, and proline. However, the highest

Figure 2. Cluster heat map analysis summarizing wheat plant responses to a factorial experiment with three farming systems (CT = conventional tillage, RT = reduced tillage, NT = no tillage) and four N fertilization levels (0, 30, 60, and 90 kg N ha⁻¹). The figure was generated using the <https://biit.cs.ut.ee/clustvis/> online program package with Euclidean distance as the similarity measure and hierarchical clustering with complete linkage.

concentrations of proline, soluble sugars (glucose and (asparagine and glutamine) were present in the treatment RT x 30 N ha⁻¹ fertilization (RT_30). In the latter treatment, the content of asparagine and hexoses (glucose + fructose), in particular, were 79% and 20% higher than the average of all other treatments. The previous results are summarized by the heat map in Figure 2.

Conclusions

The data highlight that NT farming after long-term rotation with faba bean increased the N use efficiency in wheat, boosting grain yield while reducing protein content which resulted diluted in the higher production. It must point out that recorded values were always higher

than 13%, the percentage preferred by pasta makers to obtain good tolerance to overcooking, low stickiness, high firmness and low cooking loss (Sissons et al., 2021). On the contrary traditional and reduced tillage showed higher total and soluble protein contents but lower grain yields. This study provides very useful information for scientists and farmers on how to achieve satisfactory grain yields and quality through an eco-sustainable approach in arid regions. However, it is worth to note that the high levels of asparagine and hexoses present in the RED_30 grain could have food safety implication because of their conversion to acrylamide during baking or pasta production (Halford et al., 2012). If some farming treatments are more eco-friendly but compromise food safety, this constitutes a serious issue with negative agronomic consequences of which it is necessary to be aware of. Therefore, further studies are needed to return a comprehensive evaluation of the parameters that can influence the asparagine content in grain in relation to farming system.

Literature

- Ali S. et al. 2015. Optimization of the environmental performance of rainfed durum wheat by adjusting the management practices. *J. Clean. Prod.*, 87: 105-118.
- Dell'Aversana E. et al. 2021. Salinity duration differently modulates physiological parameters and metabolites profile in roots of two contrasting barley genotypes. *Plants*, 10(2): 307.
- Flagella Z. 2006. Nutritional and technological quality of the durum wheat. *Ital. J. Agron.*, 1(s1), 203-239.
- Halford N.G. et al. 2012. The acrylamide problem: a plant and agronomic science issue. *J. Exp. Bot.*, 63(8): 2841-2851.
- Sissons M. et al. 2021. Impact of durum wheat protein content on spaghetti *in vitro* starch digestion and technological properties. *J. Cereal Sci.*, 98: 103156.
- Tedone L. et al. 2023. Effects of different types of soil management on organic carbon and nitrogen contents and the stability index of a durum wheat–faba bean rotation under a Mediterranean climate. *Agronomy*, 13(5): 1298.
- Troccoli A. et al. 2000. Durum wheat quality: a multidisciplinary concept. *J. Cereal Sci.*, 32: 99–113.
- Woodrow P. et al. 2017. Durum wheat seedling responses to simultaneous high light and salinity involve a fine reconfiguration of amino acids and carbohydrate metabolism. *Physiol. Plant.*, 159: 290-312.

POSTERS

Productivity and Product Quality of Organically Grown Saffron in the Etna Area

Umberto Anastasi¹, Gaetano Pandino¹, Concetta Scepi¹, Salvatore Lamacchia²

¹ Di3A, Univ. Catania, IT, umberto.anastasi@unict.it

² Bio Campi – Società Cooperativa Agricola Sociale A.R.L., Linguaglossa, IT, biocampi.bio@gmail.com

Introduction

Saffron (*Crocus sativus* L.) is a plant belonging to *Iridaceae* family widespread in the Mediterranean area whose product are the stigmas of flowers widely used in food, medicinal, cosmetic, perfumes and textile dyes sectors (Gresta et al., 2008). Recently there has been a growing interest for this species, due to the valuable organoleptic and health characteristics of the derived spice, which is particularly appreciated in high-level gastronomy, offering concrete opportunities to smallholder and family farmers to valorise a product on a local scale because of its superior quality, expression of the diversified pedoclimatic conditions, above all those of the marginal areas of the Italian territory such as the high hills and mountains. The project “Nuove prospettive per lo zafferano dell’Etna, dalla tavola alle applicazioni cosmeceutiche e nutraceutiche” (EtnaSaffronInnovation) financed through the “PSR Sicilia 2014-2020 Measure 16.1” fits into this context and aims at assessing the productivity and quality of product of saffron cultivated under organic regime in close relationship with the environmental potential offered by one of the territories with the greatest appeal in Sicily, the Etna area.

Materials and Methods

The open-field experimental activity lasted two-years (2020-2021) and was conducted at the pilot farm “BioCampi” (lead partner of the project “EtnaSaffronInnovation”) on a large plot of 1,000 m² located in the Etna area (Linguaglossa: 37°49’44” 15°08’59”, 550 m a.s.l.). After an adequate preparation of the field area, which included the supply of 20 t ha⁻¹ of organic manure, 20,000 corms/1,000 m² were planted at the end of August at a distance of 0.4 x 0.2 m. The soil of the field has a sandy-loam texture and the following chemical characteristics: pH 7.2, CSC 14.1 meq/100g, organic carbon 31.1 g/Kg, total nitrogen 2.4 g/Kg, assimilable phosphorus 16.0 mg/Kg, exchangeable potassium 243.0 mg/Kg. The crop establishment was optimal and manual weed control was carried out. In both years, during the flowering period, the number of flowers and the dry weight of the stigmas were monitored. At the end of each growing season, the evaluation of the bioactive molecules of the flowers collected was performed according to the ISO 3632-1:2011 standard method. The colouring power expressed in direct reading of crocin absorbance at 440 nm, the bittering power expressed in direct reading of picrocrocin absorbance at 257 nm and the aromatic power expressed in direct reading of safranal absorbance at 330 nm. The antioxidant activity, the total polyphenol and anthocyanin content of the stigmas were also analysed. In the second growing season, the antioxidant activity, the total polyphenol and anthocyanin content were evaluated on the tepals (as by-products of the flowers).

Results

The results shown in figure 1 evidenced that in the harvesting period of the first season, which lasted for the entire month of November, the saffron plants provided a total of 12,299 flowers/1,000 m² and produced 55.96 g of stigmas/1,000 m², concentrating the production (7,841 flowers/1,000 m² and 30.53 g of stigmas/1,000 m²) in the week between 17 and 23 November, with the production peak reached on 19 November (1,774 flowers/1,000 m²), while the maximum weight of the stigmas, equal to 7.19 g/1,000 m², was obtained the previous day (November 18).

In the second year, flowering began about ten days earlier, during the last ten days of October, and ended about a week earlier than the previous year. The production level was lower than in the first year reaching, overall, 7,558 flowers/1,000 m² and 32.60 g of stigmas/1,000 m², with a production mainly concentrated in a span of 15 days, between 31 October and 14 November (7,961 flowers/1,000 m² and 35.50 g of

stigmas/1,000 m²), with the production peak reached on 12 November (757 flowers/1,000 m²), while the highest weight of stigmas was obtained on 8 November (3.34 g/1,000 m²).

Fig. 1 - Number of flowers and dry weight of stigmas collected at the “BioCampi” farm in the two cropping seasons (2020 and 2021)

Overall, the saffron samples analyses evidenced a medium-high picrocrocin and safranal content within the ISO categories I and II, whereas levels not in line with the standards were highlighted for the crocin content (Tab. 1). On the other hand, the residual parts of the flowers have a total polyphenol content 4-5-fold higher, an anthocyanin content 7-fold higher and an antioxidant activity 3-fold higher than the main product.

Tab. 1 - Mean values (\pm S.D.) of the bioactive constituents in the stigmas and tepals collected at the “BioCampi” farm in the two cropping seasons (2020 and 2021)

	Polyphenols (mg/g gallic ac.)	Anthocyanins (mg/g C3G ¹)	Antioxidant activity (%)	Picrocrocin*	Safranal*	Crocin**
First season (2020)						
Stigmas	14.69 \pm 0.34	0.526 \pm 0.01	14.99 \pm 0.22	57.09 \pm 1.48	35.46 \pm 12.50	33.49 \pm 2.80
Second season (2021)						
Stigmas	16.35 \pm 2.06	0.408 \pm 0.04	12.01 \pm 0.06	62.46 \pm 4.52	35.44 \pm 2.10	64.30 \pm 4.23
Tepals	71.90 \pm 4.74	3.560 \pm 0.12	39.80 \pm 3.82	-	-	-

¹C3G: cyanidin -3-*O*-glucoside

*Saffron quality evaluation according to ISO 3632-2

Conclusions

The results provided preliminary information on the prospect of the organically grown saffron in the Etna area. The establishment of the crop was optimal, despite the competition from weeds, which represented the main critical aspect of the agronomic management. The productive performance of the crop was not satisfying as compared to conventional management, especially in the second year, probably due to the effect of the thermal regime, which proved to be overall not optimal. The qualitative features of the stigmas were almost in line with the reference standards, and the analyses of the residual portions of the flower highlight the possibility of exploitation.

Literature

Gresta F. et al. 2008. Saffron, an alternative crop for sustainable agricultural systems. A review. Agron. Sustain. Dev., 28(1): 95-112.

Field Vegetation Parameters for Pasture Above-ground Biomass Estimation: A Case Study

Elena Basso¹, Cristina Pornaro¹, Francesco Marinello², Stefano Macolino¹

¹ DAFNAE, Univ. Padova, IT, stefano.macolino@unipd.it

²TESAF, Univ. Padova, IT

Introduction

The implementation of remote sensing technologies for agricultural applications has undergone continuous growth in the last couple of decades. Accurate measurements of grassland biophysical and biochemical parameters are the basis for monitoring grassland ecosystems. Above-ground biomass estimation is the focus of the grassland study (Wang et al., 2022). It is traditionally estimated through field surveys which are time-consuming and applicable in small areas only (Wang et al., 2022). More advanced and spatially extensive grassland monitoring methods include the use of remotely sensed data acquired from sensors (optical and/or radar) mounted on different platforms (Li et al., 2017), such as aircraft, helicopters, spacecraft or from satellite images (Wang et al., 2022). Based on specific spectral bands of the above optical images acquired, some vegetation indices have been developed. The normalized difference vegetation index (NDVI) is the most widely used (Karimi et al., 2018) due to its high correlation with the biomass (Cunliffe et al., 2020). Direct data deriving from field surveys are necessary to evaluate the reliability of remote sensing in estimating grassland biomass. However, collecting field data of above-ground biomass is time-consuming. Other parameters, easier to collect, such as grass height, NDVI quantified through handheld proximal sensors, and vegetation density, could be used instead of biomass measurement. The present study aimed to find the most suitable parameter to estimate the pasture above-ground biomass.

Materials and Methods

This study was carried out in a pasture located in Schio (VI, North-Eastern Italy; 45.6889 N, 11.3607 E) and characterized by high vegetation heterogeneity. The pasture surface was 4.17 ha, with a mean slope of 10°. The mean annual temperature of the study area is 13.8°C, and the annual rainfalls are 1307 mm (Malo station; 1994-2022). The pasture surface was grazed by 12 beef cattle from March to November, split into 8 sections, with the herd staying in each section for 3 days, and then moving into the following section. The pasture surface was overlapped with a grid of points 20 meters spaced, for a total of 53 positions where 1 m² plots were located. On 3rd to 5th of May, at each position, NDVI was measured (CS-45 RapidScan, Holland Scientific), along with grass height by means of a grass plate meter (Grasshopper), and of a graduated rod. Furthermore, at each position, the above-ground biomass was collected and over-dried at 105°C for 48 hours to determine dry matter yield (DM). Vegetation density was calculated by dividing grass height measured with the plate meter by grass height measured with the rod (the closer the value is to 1, the more similar the two heights are). Pearson coefficients were calculated using R version 4.0.2 (R Core Team, 2022) to assess the correlations between grass height measured with plate meter, grass height measured with rod, vegetation density, NDVI, and DM yield.

Results

The NDVI and DM yield were significantly correlated with grass height measured with both plate meter and rod, while only DM yield was significantly correlated with vegetation density (Fig. 1). The variability on DM yield was lower where the vegetation density was high (close to 1), while large variation in DM yield occurred where the vegetation density was lower. This result suggests that DM yield estimation was more precise with a denser and uniform canopy. The NDVI was not significantly correlated with DM yield (Fig.1). Furthermore, the variability of NDVI values increased with the increase of vegetation density (Fig. 1).

Figure 1. Pearson's correlation coefficients between NDVI, grass height measured with plate meter (PM height), grass height measured with rod (R height), DM yield, and vegetation density (VD). Plots on the diagonal show kernel density distribution.

Conclusions

The NDVI measured by means of a handheld instrument is not a useful tool for estimating DM yield in the study area, while better results were found for vegetation height. The vegetation density plays a key role in the DM estimation. Vegetation density seems to be a better DM yield predictor in high-yielding grasslands than in low-productive grasslands.

Acknowledgement

This study was carried out within the Agritech National Research Center and received funding from the European Union Next-GenerationEU (PIANO NAZIONALE DI RIPRESA E RESILIENZA (PNRR) – MISSIONE 4 COMPONENTE 2, INVESTIMENTO 1.4 – D.D. 1032 17/06/2022, CN00000022). This manuscript reflects only the authors' views and opinions, neither the European Union nor the European Commission can be considered responsible for them.

Literature

- Cunliffe A.M. et al. 2020. Aboveground biomass corresponds strongly with drone-derived canopy height but weakly with greenness (NDVI) in a shrub tundra landscape. *Environ. Res. Letters*, 15(12): 125004.
- Karimi S. et al. 2018. Generalizability of gene expression programming and random forest methodologies in estimating cropland and grassland leaf area index. *Comput. Electron. Agric.*, 144: 232–240.
- Li Y. et al. 2017. The influence of land use on the grassland fire occurrence in the northeastern inner mongolia autonomous region, China. *Sensors*, 17: 437.
- R Core Team (2022). R: A language and environment for statistical computing. R Foundation for Statistical Computing, Vienna, Austria.
- Wang Z. et al. 2022. Review of remote sensing applications in grassland monitoring. *Remote Sens.*, 14(12): 2903.

Phytomanagement of a Shooting Range Soil with *Ricinus communis* L.

Linda Carrino, Donato Visconti, Nunzio Fiorentino, Massimo Fagnano
Department of Agricultural Sciences, Univ. Naples "Federico II", IT, linda.carrino@unina.it

Introduction

Soil pollution is a growing concern. Among the many anthropogenic factors that led to soil quality loss, shooting range activities causes environmental contamination due to bullet deposition in the soil (Dinake et al., 2018). Bullets are mainly composed of lead (Pb; > 90%), while antimony (Sb; 2–5%) and arsenic (As; 0.5–2%) are used as hardening materials (Johnson et al., 2005). The ageing and weathering of bullet fragments lead to their dissolution, and thus to the migration of potentially toxic elements (PTEs) through the soil. To limit their availability, different practices can be adopted (e.g., adjusting the soil pH, controlling the runoff), even physical removal of bullets. However, bullet removal showed a diverse effect depending on the different types of soils, even leading to increased Pb bioavailability (Fayiga and Saha, 2016), due to increased fragmentation. The use of vegetation to reduce the leaching of PTEs has been reported as a good management strategy for shooting range soils (Levonmäki et al., 2006). Besides vegetation cover, a variety of amendments have been proposed to reduce PTEs' mobility and improve plants' growth. Compost application, for instance, resulted effective in reducing Pb availability (Fleming et al., 2013). The combined use of compost and arbuscular mycorrhiza fungi (AMF) can reduce PTEs' bioavailability and increase plant growth, minimizing their dispersion in the environment (Visconti et al., 2020). In the presented study, compost (obtained from the organic fraction of municipal solid wastes) and arbuscular mycorrhiza fungi were used to assess the feasibility of remediating a former shooting range, by using an energy crop.

Materials and Methods

The study site, an area of 5 ha located in the Acerra municipality (Naples, Italy), was used as a shooting range for almost 10 years. The area is characterized by potential contamination of Pb, As and Sb, due to the concentration of bullets and their fragments, exceeding the Italian legal threshold for agricultural sites (Repubblica Italiana, 2006). An uncontaminated agricultural soil was collected nearby to assess background contamination values and as reference soil. Almost 240 kg of each soil was placed on a tarp and mixed carefully to obtain a homogeneous material. Compost was thoughtfully mixed to PTE soil at a dose corresponding to 30 Mg ha⁻¹, and the soil was then transferred to pots to stabilize (Ø = 40 cm; V = 35 L) four weeks before transplant. Agricultural soil was simply transferred to pots without amendment. Seeds of *Ricinus communis* L., originating from North Africa (Tunisia) (from now on, TUNI 1), were sown on a polystyrene plateau with commercial soil and placed in open-air to let them adjust to the field climatic condition. After one month, plants were transplanted into the experimental pots. At transplant, 5 g of mycorrhiza inoculum (a commercial biostimulant used with a mycorrhiza-based formula with *Rhizoglyphus irregulare* and *Funneliformis mosseae*) were applied near the plant roots, with the aid of sprayed water to increase adhesion. Mineral fertilization was carried out with ammonium sulphate. The following factors were tested for PTE soil with TUNI 1:

- i) Fertilization: Compost application (C); Mineral fertilization (M); No fertilization (NoF);
- ii) Biostimulation: with arbuscular mycorrhiza fungi (AMF); without AMF (NoAMF).

Plants were rain-fed during the experiment, with emergency irrigation when required. The experimental units were arranged in a completely randomized block design, with four replications. Plants were analyzed for biomass production, photosynthesis efficiency, and PTEs concentration in the different parts. Soil PTEs modification was studied as well.

Results

Here are reported some of the significant results. The concentration of PTEs in the different plant organs was mainly determined by the application of AMF (Table 1). Pb was found in a greater concentration without AMF application in all the plant organs. The same happened for Sb and As, but only in the roots. Fertilizer application boosted the translocation of Pb in the leaves, with higher concentration in the compost treatment. Conversely, As concentration was higher in the roots of plants with mineral fertilization. No statistical differences were recorded for Sb concentrations as affected by amendment application. The translocation factor (TF) for all the PTEs analyzed and for all the treatments, was < 1 (Figure 1). Biostimulants did not increase TF for any PTE. No statistical differences were recorded in the plant biomass, photosynthesis efficiency, or nutrient uptake.

Figure 1. Translocation factor for the different PTEs

Table 1. Mean PTE concentration (mg/kg) in the different plant organs, for PTE soil. Means that do not share a letter are significantly different according to the LSD test (* p<0.05; ** p< 0.01; *** p<0.001; ns = not significant).

		Pb			Sb			As		
		Leaves	Stem	Roots	Leaves	Stem	Roots	Leaves	Stem	Roots
Fertilization (F)	C	2.31 a	5.25	18.94	0.59	0.12	0.89	0.24	0.12	0.39 b
	M	1.63 b	2.20	23.72	0.55	0.13	0.97	0.19	0.14	0.51 a
	NoF	1.70 b	4.85	23.38	0.53	0.12	1.10	0.19	0.12	0.45 ab
Biostimulation (B)	No AMF (B0)	2.06 a	5.36 a	24.67 a	0.59	0.12	1.13 a	0.23	0.12	0.49 a
	AMF (B1)	1.69 b	4.17 b	19.36 b	0.52	0.12	0.84 b	0.19	0.14	0.41 b
F x B	C - B0	2.62	5.95	19.39	0.68	0.12	1.03	0.28	0.12	0.40
	C - B1	1.99	4.54	18.50	0.50	0.11	0.75	0.21	0.12	0.38
	M - B0	1.69	4.90	26.49	0.55	0.13	1.06	0.19	0.12	0.57
	M - B1	1.57	3.51	20.95	0.55	0.12	0.87	0.19	0.16	0.44
	NoF - B0	1.88	5.22	28.12	0.54	0.12	1.30	0.22	0.12	0.49
	NoF - B1	1.51	4.47	18.63	0.51	0.12	0.90	0.16	0.13	0.41
	Significance	F	***	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns
	B	**	**	*	ns	ns	**	ns	ns	*
	F x B	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns

Conclusions

Ricinus communis L. has been found capable of producing the same biomass and seed yield in both contaminated and uncontaminated soils, regardless of fertilization, thus confirming its high resistance to abiotic stresses. The application of compost increased Pb translocation from the roots to the shoots, while mineral fertilization enhanced As accumulation in roots. The AMF reduced the accumulation of contaminants in the plant. According to the translocation factor, *Ricinus communis* L. accumulated Pb, As, and Sb mainly in the roots, so demonstrating to be a good candidate for phytostabilization programs.

Literature

- Dinake P. et al. 2018. Quantitative assessment of environmental risk from lead pollution of shooting range soils. *Chem. Speciat. Bioavailab.*, 30(1): 76–85.
- Fayiga A. O. & Saha U. 2016. The effect of bullet removal and vegetation on mobility of Pb in shooting range soils. *Chemosphere*, 160: 252–257.
- Fleming M. et al. 2013. Extractability and bioavailability of Pb and As in historically contaminated orchard soil: Effects of compost amendments. *Environ. Pollut.*, 177: 90–97.
- Johnson A. C. et al. 2005. Solubility of Antimony and Other Elements in Samples Taken from Shooting Ranges. *J. Environ. Qual.*, 34: 248–254
- Repubblica Italiana, 2006. Decreto Legislativo 3 aprile 2006, n. 152. *Gazzetta Ufficiale*, 172.
- Visconti D. et al. 2020. Securing of an industrial soil using turfgrass assisted by biostimulants and compost amendment. *Agronomy*, 10(9): 1310.

Quantifying Non-photosynthetic Vegetation in a Mixed Grassland Using Hyperspectral Data: A Case Study in Kenya

Rodolfo Ceriani¹, Francesco Fava², Giulia Tagliabue³, Micol Rossini³, Sonja Leitner⁴, Cinzia Panigada³, Vincent Odongo⁴, Valentina Vaglia², Paul Mutuo⁴, Kelvin Kinuthia⁴, Ramin Heidarian⁵, Katayoun Fakherifard⁵, Monica Pepe⁵

¹ DISAA, Univ. Milano, IT, rodolfo.ceriani@studenti.unimi.it,

² ESP, Univ. Milano, IT, francesco.fava@unimi.it,

³ DISAT, Univ. Milano-Bicocca, IT, giulia.tagliabue@unimib.it,

⁴ Mazingira Centre for Environmental Research and Education, International Livestock Research Institute (ILRI), Nairobi, Kenya s.leitner@cgiar.org,

⁵ IREA, Consiglio Nazionale della Ricerca, Milano, IT, pepe.m@irea.cnr.it

Introduction

Satellite remote sensing is applied to monitor agronomic variables and agricultural practices, including detecting, and measuring non-photosynthetic vegetation (NPV). NPV is important in water, nutrient, and carbon cycling in agroecosystems, making it a key variable to be mapped using satellite data. New generation spaceborne hyperspectral sensors like PRecursoRE IperSpettrale della Missione Applicativa (PRISMA) sense the 0.4-2.5 μm spectral range with narrow bands, thus offering unprecedented opportunities for NPV mapping in crops and grasslands exploiting subtle absorption features, (e.g., cellulose-lignin at 2.1 μm). Since PRISMA proved to be useful for mapping NPV in croplands (Pepe et al., 2020; Berger et al., 2021), our objective is to understand if it offers the same potential for mixed grasslands, which are characterized by high spatial heterogeneity. Mapping and monitoring NPV in mixed grasslands is important to understand ecological dynamics and support land and grazing management decisions. This study is a first attempt to quantify the NPV fraction in a semi-arid grassland site located in Kenya. We have first applied a model already developed and calibrated for crop analysis to predict grassland NPV from field spectral reflectance data. The second step will be to refine the model and apply it to the PRISMA image to obtain a quantitative map. This short communication focuses on the results of the first step.

Materials and Methods

The study site is located in Kenya's Kapiti Research Station and Wildlife Conservancy, a 13,000 hectares farm used for livestock grazing, fodder production and wildlife conservation, supporting diverse rangelands, including semi-natural open grasslands with high plant species diversity. The region has two main vegetation growing seasons interspersed by two dry seasons with low green vegetation cover, with a short vegetation cycle and large interannual variability (Cheng et al., 2021). A PRISMA scene was acquired on January 19th, 2023. PRISMA acquires 234 bands ranging from 0.4 to 2.5 μm with a spectral resolution of 9–15 nm and a spatial one of 30 m. The PRISMA image was pre-processed to obtain a reflectance product accurately geocoded. An intensive field campaign was conducted on the week of January 18-22 2023, with the goals of measuring ground reference spectra for validation of PRISMA reflectance, and of the NPV prediction model. A total of 26 0.25m² plots were established: for each plot, the reflectance was acquired with a full-range (0.35 to 2.5 μm) portable spectrometer (SR-3500, Spectral Evolution) and a nadir digital image of the target was taken. The digital images were processed to estimate the NPV and soil cover fractions. This enabled us to create a dataset containing, for each plot, the NPV and bare soil fractional cover, together with the corresponding reflectance resampled to PRISMA spectral bands. An NPV prediction model, originally developed to quantify NPV of intensive crops, was adapted and tested for this study. The model was trained using a USGS spectral library (Hively et al., 2022), containing nearly 900 in-situ surface reflectance spectra collected, annotated, and spectrally resampled the same way as the Kapiti dataset. The Gaussian Exponential Optimization (EGO) of selected absorption bands (Pepe et al., 2022)

was first applied to the spectra in the USGS spectral library. Then, a machine learning algorithm (i.e., Random Forest - RF) was used to link the absorption bands characteristics (band depth, width, center, and asymmetry) extracted by EGO and the corresponding NPV percentages. The RF model proved to perform well when tested for crop residue cover. Here, we tested the model robustness on mixed grasslands applying the RF model on our field dataset.

Results

Our results show that the RF model applied to the Kapiti dataset performs similarly to the global dataset ($R^2 \sim 0.83$; $RPD \sim 2.0$; $nRMSE \sim 15.3$), indicating that the model could be used to estimate NPV in mixed grasslands in Kenya (Figure 1). Results are promising also considering that data were acquired across a wide gradient of NPV fractions on two different soil types (red and black cotton). Overall, despite the vast differences in vegetation and soil chemistry between the dataset used for model training (USGS is based on wheat, maize and soybean and North American soils) and our dataset on mixed grasslands in Africa, the model proved to be robust enough to be further tested on PRISMA data for NPV mapping over the whole study area.

Conclusions

Overall, our findings demonstrate the potential of hyperspectral remote sensing to assess NPV on mixed grasslands and the robustness of a RF model trained with a large spectral library for crops also for heterogeneous grassland vegetation. The next step will be to apply and validate the model on the whole Kapiti farm using PRISMA data and to test the model also during periods where NPV is not the dominant vegetation fraction (i.e., it is mixed with green vegetation). Overall, this work can open up a new frontier of research on extensive pastoral environments, which have been little studied so far, thanks to the use of models and latest generation hyperspectral sensors.

Figure 1. Performance of the USGS-optimized RF model on Kapiti data

Literature

Berger K. et al. 2021. Assessing Non-Photosynthetic Cropland Biomass from Spaceborne Hyperspectral Imagery. *Remote Sens.*, 13(22): 4711.

Cheng Y. et al. 2021. Phenology of short vegetation cycles in a Kenyan rangeland from PlanetScope and Sentinel-2. *Remote Sens. Environ.*, 248: 112004.

Hively W.D. et al. 2022. Reflectance spectra of agricultural field conditions supporting remote-sensing evaluation of non-photosynthetic vegetation cover (ver. 1.1, November 2022): U.S. Geological Survey data release.

Pepe M. et al. 2022. Mapping spatial distribution of crop residues using PRISMA satellite imaging spectroscopy. *Eur. J. Remote Sens.*, 56(1), 2122872.

Pepe M. et al. 2020. Detection and classification of non-photosynthetic vegetation from PRISMA hyperspectral data in croplands. *Remote Sens.*, 12(23): 3903.

Tolerance of African Fodder Cane to the Cultivation in Heavy Metals Polluted Soils

Barbara Rachele Ciaramella, Alessandra Piccitto, Alessio Scandurra, Valeria Cafaro, Silvio Calcagno, Salvatore Luciano Cosentino, Giorgio Testa

Di3A, Univ. Catania, IT, gtesta@unict.it

Introduction

Biomass is a renewable and sustainable source of energy that contributes to the diversification of energy supply, reduces dependence on fossil fuels and mitigates greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions. Therefore, biomass production on marginal soils is recommended to reduce land use and change ethical issues related to competition with food crops. Furthermore, although the marginal conditions of the soils, such as contaminated soils, may hinder the cultivation of traditional crops, industrial crops manage not only the restoration of the contaminated areas, but the same way allowed to get a benefit from several perspectives, obtaining technological and environmental performance suitable. Among all the available techniques, phytoremediation is a sustainable technique that utilizes plants to remediate the contaminated site (Gomes et al., 2022)

To optimize phytoremediation application in heavy metal contaminated soils, the used crops need to fulfill several conditions: the tolerance to heavy metals, high production of biomass, deep and extensive root systems, well-known agronomic techniques, and low request for agronomic input. In this way, the cultivation of energy crops for phytoremediation is an alternative that improves the production of a renewable and sustainable feedstock for energy while remediating the soil.

In this scenario, *Saccharum spontaneum* L. ssp. *aegyptiacum* is a perennial drought-tolerant grass specie capable of grown in stressful conditions and can accumulate considerable amounts of heavy metal, promoting soil remediation and at the same time is indicated as a possible crop dedicated to the production of biomass for energy (Cosentino et al., 2019)

In this experiment, *Saccharum spontaneum* L. ssp. *aegyptiacum* (Willd.) was tested in contaminated soil with different concentrations of zinc, cadmium, lead, and nickel, seeking the productivity and the phytoremediation tolerance to the heavy metals contaminated soils.

Materials and Methods

The present experiment was carried out during March-November 2021 at the University of Catania. *Saccharum spontaneum* L. ssp. *aegyptiacum* (Willd.) was grown in a contaminated pot of 12 kg, previously contaminated with four heavy metals in two different levels, high and low. In particular, the soil was contaminated using nitrate of cadmium [$\text{Cd}(\text{NO}_3)_2$], nitrate of lead [$\text{Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2$], nitrate of zinc [$\text{Zn}(\text{NO}_3)_2$], and nitrate of nickel [$\text{Ni}(\text{NO}_3)_2$]. The concentration of heavy metal in the soil was applied followed two concentrations for heavy metal. And the concentration of cadmium in the soil was equal to 4 and 8 mg kg^{-1} , for nickel 110 and 220 mg kg^{-1} , while for lead and zinc the concentration were equal to 450 and 900 mg kg^{-1} . The nitric metal salt per pot was calculated by multiplying the molecular weight of the salt by the grams of metal contained per pot and finally dividing by the molar weight of the metal. A nitrate fertilizer control was added to reach the same concentration of the highest level of $\text{Zn}(\text{NO}_3)_2$. Clonal rhizomes of African fodder cane were propagated through rhizome cuttings, with 2-3 main buds each and rhizome weight as homogeneous as possible. African fodder cane rhizomes were collected from the germplasm collection at the Experimental farm of the University of Catania (37°24'N, 15°03'E, 10 m a.s.l.) and transplanted in the pots two months after the soil contamination. The irrigation was kept in optimal conditions for the whole crop cycle. Pots were arranged in a completely randomized design with three replications.

Results

Lead contamination showed to have low or even no effect regarding African fodder cane productivity (Fig.1). Not even the highest concentration of Pb in soil limited plant growth, proving that the tolerance of this crop is high and making its cultivation in heavily Pb contaminated soils a plausible alternative.

African fodder cane growth was affected by Cd contamination in soil, having a decrease in productivity when Cd concentration increased, showing that the concentration of this heavy metal in soil has a direct effect in plants productivity.

The productivity results of African fodder cane cultivated in Ni and Zn contaminated soils indicated that this crop is sensitive to the presence of both these metals regardless of their concentration.

The tolerance index (TI) is used to evaluate plants' susceptibility to the level of contamination present in the pot (Gomes et al., 2022). It was calculated as the ratio between the dry aboveground biomass (g pot^{-1}) of plants grown on contaminated soils and that of control pots. African fodder cane showed great tolerance to the presence of lead in the soil, in the concentration of 900-450 mg kg^{-1} , in cadmium at the concentration of 4 mg kg^{-1} and nickel at the concentration of 110 mg kg^{-1} (Fig.2). The highest susceptibility of this crop was observed for zinc at the concentration of 900 mg kg^{-1} .

Along with the cultivation of African fodder cane in Pb, Cd, Zn and Ni contaminated soils being showed as viable considering that the amount of biomass produced do not suffered critical effects, the utilization of African fodder cane for bioenergy, biofuels, and bioproducts can help us to mitigate the human impact in the environment.

Conclusions

In conclusion, the present study highlighted the ability of a biomass specie, no-food lignocellulosic perennial grasses to tolerate the heavy metals in the soil to increasing stress.

The tolerance index and the raising level of heavy metals in the soil provide and insight of the stress condition of the plant. Furthermore, the presence of lead in the soil did not affect the productivity even at the highest concentration (900 mg kg^{-1}), showing that African fodder cane be able to cope with the stress conditions obtained from the presence of lead in the soil.

Literature

Cosentino S.L. et al. 2018. The Importance of Perennial Grasses as a Feedstock for Bioenergy and Bioproducts. In: Perennial Grasses for Bioenergy and Bioproducts: Production, Uses, Sustainability and Markets for Giant Reed, Miscanthus, Switchgrass, Reed Canary Grass and Bamboo.

Gomes L. A. et al. 2022. Environmental and socio-economic impact assessment of the switchgrass production in heavy metals contaminated soils. Lect. Notes Mech. Eng., 410-419.

Figure 1 - Aboveground biomass (g pot^{-1}) in relation to the different heavy metals in soil.

Figure 2 - Tolerance index (%) in relation to the different heavy metals in soil.

Effect of Different Fertilization Strategies on Yield of Cauliflower Grown on Three Different Types of Soil

Eugenio Cozzolino¹, Ida Di Mola², Lucia Ottaiano², Maria Eleonora Pelosi², Nunzio Fiorentino², Massimo Fagnano², Mauro Mori²

¹ CREA-CI, Caserta, IT, eugenio.cozzolino@crea.gov.it

² DiA, Univ. Napoli, IT, ida.dimola@unina.it

Introduction

Several researches showed that mineral fertilizers increase crop productivity, but could degrade soil quality. Over the past decade, efforts have been made to reduce the dependence on the use of mineral fertilizers by using organic fertilizers based on natural materials, that can help overcome the negative effects of overuse of mineral fertilizers (Golabi et al., 2004; Brown and Cotton, 2011).

The aim of the current study was to evaluate the residual effect of two different organic fertilizers on cauliflower yield, as compared to a standard mineral fertilization.

Materials and Methods

The test was carried out on cauliflower cv. Rafale (HM CLAUSE, Davis, CA -USA) at the experimental site of the Department of Agricultural Sciences of the University of Naples (Portici, Italy). The previous crop was wheat and three different strategies of nitrogen (N) fertilization were tested (compost, digestate, and mineral fertilizer). The experimental design was a factorial combination between three different types of soil (clay, sand, and loam) and four different fertilization strategies (non-fertilized -CTR; residual effect of fertilization with compost -COM; residual effect of fertilization with digestate -DIG; mineral fertilization -MIN). MIN was distributed as ammonium nitrate (26% N) in 3 times (October 21st, November 15th, and December 7th), while the digestate (0.6% organic N) and compost (2% organic N) were distributed in the previous test on wheat (December 20th, 2021): all the fertilizers were applied according to a reference dose of 120 kg ha⁻¹. The cauliflower transplant was made on September 22nd, 2022 and the harvests were made from 10 to 20 January 2023, when the marketable size was reached. At the harvest, the following measurements were made: yield, height, diameter and dry matter (DM) of corymb, and plant biomass. All data were subjected to two-way ANOVA by SPSS (version 22, Chicago, Illinois) and means were separated using Tukey's Test at $p \leq 0.05$.

Results

The cauliflower yield was significantly affected by the interaction between the soil type and N fertilization strategies, ranging from 3.5 t ha⁻¹ of the not fertilized plants to 29.4 t ha⁻¹ of plants fertilized with mineral fertilizer (Fig. 1). Overall, the best productive performance was obtained in the loam and clay soil (14.6 t ha⁻¹, on the average, vs. 11.3 t ha⁻¹ of sandy soil). In all soils, the mineral fertilization elicited the higher yield followed by compost and then by digestate.

Also all other analyzed parameters, except the corymb DM, were significantly affected by the interaction between the soil type and N fertilization strategies. Notably, the cycle duration was lower for MIN plants irrespective of soil type but overall, the plants grown on sandy soil showed a longer cycle (109.4 vs. 107.2 days of the other soils) (Tab.1). The plant biomass was always higher with MIN irrespective

Fig. 1 Marketable yield of cauliflower as affected by soil types and N fertilization strategies

of soil type, and lower in not fertilized plants; overall, on sandy soil, plants growth was lower (Tab.1). As regards the height and diameter of corymbs, the behaviour was similar to that recorded for yield; the higher values were obtained by MIN plants in all soil types, followed in order by COM, DIG, and CTR plants (Tab.1). Finally, the dry matter percentage of corymbs was only affected by N fertilization strategies and the highest values was recorded in the not fertilized plots and the lowest for plants fertilized with compost and mineral digestate (Tab.1).

Table 1. Cycle duration (days after transplant –DAT), plants biomass and dry matter (DM), and height, diameter and DM of corymb as affected by the interaction between soil type and fertilization.

Treatments		Plant		Corymb		
		Cycle	Biomass	Height	Diameter	DM
		DAT	$t\ ha^{-1}$	cm	cm	%
Soil	Fertilization					
Loam	CTR	110.3 ± 0.01 a	19.7 ± 0.9 g	7.3 ± 0.1 g	7.5 ± 0.1 g	7.0 ± 1.4
	DIG	104.0 ± 0.01 c	29.5 ± 1.7 f	9.3 ± 0.1 e	10.5 ± 0.1 d	7.6 ± 0.3
	COM	109.7 ± 0.01 a	46.3 ± 0.2 c	10.7 ± 0.0 c	12.9 ± 0.2 c	6.9 ± 0.5
	MIN	104.0 ± 0.01 c	74.7 ± 0.3 a	11.2 ± 0.1 ab	16.5 ± 0.1 a	7.2 ± 0.1
Sandy	CTR	109.7 ± 0.01 a	10.8 ± 0.8 i	5.8 ± 0.1 i	6.2 ± 0.1 i	9.3 ± 0.4
	DIG	110.0 ± 0.01 a	16.9 ± 0.2 h	7.0 ± 0.1 h	8.3 ± 0.1 f	8.2 ± 0.1
	COM	109.7 ± 0.01 a	34.5 ± 1.2 d	9.2 ± 0.0 e	10.6 ± 0.1 d	7.4 ± 0.7
	MIN	108.0 ± 0.01 b	63.5 ± 1.3 b	11.0 ± 0.1 b	16.0 ± 0.0 b	7.2 ± 0.1
Clay	CTR	109.7 ± 0.01 a	16.9 ± 0.6 h	7.3 ± 0.1 g	7.1 ± 0.1 h	8.5 ± 0.1
	DIG	107.3 ± 0.01 b	31.9 ± 0.6 e	9.0 ± 0.2 f	10.3 ± 0.1 e	7.7 ± 0.3
	COM	108.3 ± 0.01 b	46.6 ± 0.7 c	10.2 ± 0.1 d	13.0 ± 0.1 c	6.7 ± 0.3
	MIN	104.0 ± 0.01 c	74.3 ± 1.0 a	11.3 ± 0.1 a	16.4 ± 0.2 a	6.4 ± 0.9
Significance						
Soil Type (ST)		**	**	**	**	NS
Fertilization (F)		**	**	**	**	*
ST x F		**	**	**	**	NS

NS, *, ** Not-significant or significant at $p < 0.05$ and 0.01 , respectively. Different letters within each column indicate significant differences at $P \leq 0.05$. CTR: not-fertilized; DIG: residual effect of fertilization with digestate; COM: residual effect of fertilization with compost; MIN: fertilized with mineral fertilizers.

Conclusions

Our results highlighted that obviously mineral fertilizers always allowed the best productive performance, but the compost showed a discrete marketable yield (46.5% as compared to mineral fertilization, on the average). Overall, the cauliflower reached the higher yield on loam and clay soils.

Literature

Brown S. and Cotton M. 2011. Changes in soil properties and carbon content following compost application: Result of on-farming sampling. *Compost Sci. Util.*, 19(2): 87-96.

Golabi M.H. et al. 2004. Use of composted organic waste as alternative to synthetic fertilizers for enhancing crop productivity and agricultural sustainability on the tropical island of Guam. *Proceeding of 13th International Soil Conservation Organization Conferences*, Brisbane.

Seed Yield and Quality of *Medicago intertextata* L. in a Mediterranean Environment

Giuseppe Di Miceli, Lucia Dinolfo, Nicoletta Lala, Davide Farruggia, Nicolò Iacuzzi, Leto Claudio, Simona Prestigiacomo

Dep. of Agricultural, Food and Forest Sciences, Univ. Palermo, IT, giuseppe.dimiceli@unipa.it

Introduction

Medicago intertextata L. (Mill.) (Pignatti 2017; Bartolucci et al., 2018) is an annual self-seeding legume species, widely distributed in the Mediterranean basin and well known among local farmers for its palatability, biomass productivity, and nutritive value. It is a stout procumbent or ascending plant with yellow flowers growing to a height of 20-50 cm with distinct pods characterized by long curved sharp flattened to pods (Kernick 1978). *M. intertextata* is recognized for its remarkable tolerance to flooded and salinity conditions, distinguishing it as one of the most resilient annual species within the *Medicago* genus (Francis & Poole, 1973) due to a mechanism developed to cope with salt stress (Laouar et al., 2000; Zahran et al., 2007, El-Shafey and Al-Sherif, 2020). These characteristics are particularly prominent in the Mediterranean basin, an area known for its challenging environmental conditions (Kepner et al., 2005). Furthermore, *M. intertextata*, as self-seeding species, exhibits significant potential as forage crop for pasture improvement (Abdelguerfi and Laouar, 1999). However, certain constraints have been identified, particularly related to its morphological features. One notable feature is the presence of a long and thin peduncle, which causes the pods to drop rapidly upon drying, making the harvesting process challenging for seed production. The lack of knowledge regarding the agronomic aspects of this species, represents a constraint for the introduction and the spread of this crop in forage cropping systems. Consequently, the aim of this work is the evaluation of patterns of change in seed yield with different seeding rates in *M. intertextata* in a semi-arid Mediterranean environment.

Materials and Methods

The trial was carried out during the 2021/22 growing season in a semi-arid, hilly area of Sicily in the experimental farm “Sparacia” (Cammarata, Agrigento, Italy). In the site, both climatic patterns and soil conditions are typical of the Mediterranean dry environments. In the field, with wheat as previous crop, the seedbed was prepared through plowing and complementary operations. The soil was not fertilized. Seeds of a population of *M. intertextata*, were sown in December 2021. Treatments consisted of two seed rates densities: 20 germinable seeds/m² (T1) and 160 germinable seeds/m² (T2). The treatments were arranged in a completely randomized block design with three replications. At maturity, plant height was measured, successively stands were manually cut and shed pods were gathered. Total cut fresh biomass and pods were weighted. A sample of fresh biomass was sampled and pods were weighted, and oven dried at 65°C until the constant weight was reached. The pods were then passed through a laboratory hulling machine to assess seed yield. Furthermore, for each treatment, a germination test was carried out on samples using 400 seeds (100 seeds x 4 replicates) placed on moist filter paper into Petri dishes and put in a germinator for 24 days at 20°C. The analysis of variance was performed according to the experimental design and the least significant difference (LSD) values were calculated at the 0.05 level of probability.

Results

All treatments recorded a moderate productive response, reaching dry matter yields at the end of the season of 4,260 kg ha⁻¹ and 4,967kg ha⁻¹ respectively for T1 and T2. At the first treatment (low seeding density), the seeds of pods had the lowest 1000-seed weight, indicating that reserve accumulation was still in progress. Germination percentage and hard seed percentage of *M. intertextata* seeds were not significantly affected by the sowing rate. All treatments produced seed which had a germination percentage of over 80%. For all plant densities germination tests showed very high incidence of hard seeds (65% and 77%

respectively for T1 and T2), despite the hulling machine used which usually determined an efficient seed abrasion. The high seed yield of T1 is justified by an increased plant development due to a lack of intraspecific competition because of the low seeding density. In fact, the number of Pods/plant and Seed/pod as well as seed/plant are significantly higher than in T2. Nevertheless, the seed yield is higher in T2 due to the increased the number of plants per m² (Table 1).

Table 1. 1000-seed weight (TSW), germination, hard seeds, pods per plant, seeds per pods and seeds per plant

Plant density (n m ²)	TSW (g)	Germination (%)	Hard seeds (%)	Pods/plant (n)	Seeds/pod (n)	Seeds/plant (n)	Seed yield (kg ha ⁻¹)
T1 20	11,0	85	65	37,8	8,7	328	723
T2 160	14,3	92	77	5,3	6,4	34	773
LSD 0,05	2,7	ns	ns	18	2,1	130	35
Mean	12,7	88	71	21,6	7,5	181	748

Conclusions

Although these are preliminary results, this study foresees a second agricultural season which is currently being worked on. These findings provide valuable insights into the relationship between seeding density and seed yield in *M. intertexta*. Furthermore, it should be noted that the high percentage of hard seeds, remaining on the soil surface, could regenerate a pasture stand in the subsequent growing seasons. These first part of outcomes could offer potential guidance for optimizing seed production in this species. However, to maximize commercial seed production, alternative harvesting methods need to be investigated. Further research is warranted to explore additional factors influencing seed quality and yield, such as environmental conditions and agronomic practices.

Literature

- Bartolucci F. et al. 2018. An updated checklist of the vascular flora alien to Italy. *Plant Biosyst.*, 152(3): 556-592.
- El-Shafey, N.M. and Al-Sherif E. 2020. Wild medics from different original habitats can be used as forage legumes in salt affected soil. *J. Clean WAS*, 4(2): 47-55.
- Kernick, M.D. 1978. Ecological Management of Arid and, Semi-Arid Rangelands in Africa and the near Middle East (EMASAR-Phase II) Volume IV: Indigenous Arid and Semi-Arid Forage Plants of North Africa, the Near and Middle East-Technical Data.
- Laouar M. and Abdelguerfi A. 1999. Aspects of the variability of *Medicago intertexta* populations and their relations with factors of the origin environment. In *Lucerne and medics for the XXI century. Proceedings XIII EUCARPIA Medicago spp. Group Meeting, Perugia, Italy, 13-16 September 1999.* (pp. 162-169). Università di Perugia.
- Laouar M. et al. 2000. Etude du complexe d'especes *Medicago ciliaris-M. intertexta*. Variabilité morphologique et phénologique. *Ann. Inst. Nat. Agro.*, 21: 51-70.
- Pignatti S. et al. 2017. *Flora d'italia*. Pp. 556-571, 2° ed, 2, New Business media, Milano.
- Zahran H.H. et al. 2007. Effect of salt stress on the expression of NHX-type ion transporters in *Medicago intertexta* and *Melilotus indicus* plants. *Physiol. Plant.*, 131(1): 122-130.

Innovative Products from Apulian Marginal Areas: *Salvia rosmarinus* Schleid. as Source of Bioactive Compounds

Jihane El Mahdi¹, Claudia Ruta², Laura Scalvenzi², Giuseppe De Mastro²

¹ Wageningen University and Research, Netherlands jihane.elmahdi@wur.nl

² Department of Soil, Plant and Food Science, Univ. Bari "Aldo Moro", IT, claudia.ruta@uniba.it, laura.scalvenzi@uniba.it, giuseppe.demastro@uniba.it

Introduction

Salvia rosmarinus L. is an evergreen shrub native to the Mediterranean basin, where grows wildly in a range of varieties, subspecies and biotypes. Leaves and flowers are rich in essential oils (EOs), that have shown interesting biological activities which make them excellent candidates for crop protection, particularly as bioherbicides but also in cosmetics and pharmaceuticals, thanks to their antimicrobial activities. Wild rosemary populations are characterized by morphological and chemical differences, sometimes even inside the same species. Previous studies indicate that infraspecific differences are likely to occur in terms of chemical composition of EOs, indicating the presence of different chemotypes. In Apulian marginal areas, rosemary wild populations characterized by a high tolerance to unfavourable climate and soil conditions are growing at their best. In fact, the *S. rosmarinus* cultivation and transformation in that southern region can turn into an opportunity to valorize local biodiversity (chemotypes) through the development of value chains in different sectors (agriculture, cosmetic, herbal, etc.). The collected germplasm can have a potential use for weed control as herbicide. The objective of the present study was to characterise the morphological and chemical traits of seven wild rosemary germoplasms grown in Apulian marginal areas, as a potential source of bioactive compounds.

Materials and Methods

Seven clones of wild biotypes of *S. rosmarinus*, selected from different marginal areas in the Apulia region, were investigated for the morphological and chemical traits.

Spring shoots collected for each biotype were analysed in terms of length, diameter, internode number and length. The length, width and surface area of 30 leaves per biotype were determined through an image analysis software (Scion image program).

Entire shoots after drying were used for distillation of essential oils. 10 g of dry matter were dispersed in 400 mL of water in a Clevenger-type assembly distillation apparatus. Hydro-distillation occurred for 3 hours at 90°C. The essential oils analysis was carried out through gas-chromatography coupled with mass spectroscopy (GC-MS). Data were processed for ANOVA and mean separation performed by Duncan's Multiple Range Test. The component concentrations in EOs were used to perform the hierarchical cluster analysis, which allowed to find different chemotypes.

Results

Morphological trait variability within biotypes showed difference in term of spring shoots length values.

The shoot length of biotypes 1, 2, 6 and 3 ranging from 115 to 127 mm, while 7, 5 and 4 reached the highest length values, from 185.3 to 191.7 mm.

A direct proportional relationship between spring shoots length and number of internodes was observed (fig. 1).

With regard to the leaves, the highest number was recorded with biotypes 5 and 7, respectively 334 and 371, while for biotypes 2, 1, 6, 3 and 4 the leaf number ranged from 117.3 to 147.3. Quite interesting has been to evaluate the relationship between the number of leaves and their size. The higher the number of leaves per shoot, the smaller their surface area (fig. 2).

Fig. 1. Shoot length and internode number of *S. rosmarinus* biotypes

Fig. 2. Leaves number and area of *S. rosmarinus* biotypes

The EO chemical characterization allowed to distinguish five *S. rosmarinus* chemotypes. Two of them showed a very similar composition. According to the percentage criterion applied by El Mahdi et al. (2020) were identified the following four chemotypes:

Biotypes	Chemotypes
1-4	α -pinene
5-7	camphor
2-6	α -pinene; 1,8 cineole
3	α -pinene; 1,8 cineole; camphor

The resulting qualitative characteristics of the *S. rosmarinus* EOs have been tested in a previous study on their bio-herbicidal potential (El Mahdi et al., 2020). A visible higher potency phytotoxic of camphor chemotype and α -pinene and 1,8 cineole chemotype was confirmed on *Amarantus retroflexus* and *Lolium perenne*.

The dose was the most determining factor in all the studied effects, dicots were more susceptible than monocots, and the seed stage was more susceptible than young seedlings.

Conclusions

The morphological and chemical characterization of *S. rosmarinus* biotypes in Apulian region underlined some differences, that allowed to distinguish four chemotypes in relation to the EO composition. Based on previous studies carried out by the same research group, interesting results were also obtained on agricultural application of their EOs, in particular for weed control. The results of the present study disclose new scenarios on Apulian marginal areas, since the development of value chains based on wild rosemary cultivation can turn into an opportunity to produce bioactive compounds as innovative products.

Acknowledgment Research funded by NATIONAL RESEARCH CENTRE FOR AGRICULTURAL TECHNOLOGIES (AGRITECH)

Literature

- De Mastro et al. 2004. Bio-morphological and chemical characterization of rosemary (*Rosmarinus officinalis* L.) biotypes. *Acta Hort.*, 629: 471-482.
- El Mahdi et al. 2020. Bio-Herbicidal Potential of The Essential Oils from Different *Rosmarinus officinalis* L. Chemotypes in Laboratory Assays. *Agronomy*, 10: 775.
- Satyaj et al. 2017. Chemotypic characterization and biological activity of *Rosmarinus officinalis*. *Foods*, 6(3): 20.

Is the Modified Biochar Through the Tannic Acid Suitable in Reclamation of Contaminated Soils by Heavy Metals? A Mesocosm Trial

Giuseppe Maglione¹, Carmen Arena², Lucia Santorufo², Ermenegilda Vitale², Gaetano De Tommaso³, Fulvio De Paola³, Giuseppina Roviello⁴, Elena Chianese⁵, Claudio Ferone⁴, Franca Polimeno¹, Giulia Maisto², Mauro Iuliano³, Luca Vitale⁶

¹ CNR-ISPAAM, Portici, IT, giuseppe.maglione@cnr.it

² Dip. Biologia, Univ. Napoli, IT, carmen.arena@unina.it

³ Dip. Scienze Chimiche, Univ. Napoli, IT, gaetano.detommaso@unina.it

⁴ Dip. Ingegneria, Univ. Napoli 'Parthenope', IT, giuseppina.roviello@uniparthenope.it

⁵ Dip. Scienze e Tecnologie, Univ. Napoli 'Parthenope', IT, elena.chianese@uniparthenope.it

⁶ CNR-ISAFoM, Portici, IT, luca.vitale@cnr.it

Introduction

Chemically modified biochar, showing high-affinity adsorption sites, can improve its ability to bind contaminants (Qiu et al., 2022). As it is widely reported that surface oxygen-containing functional groups can enhance the adsorption capacity of biochar, it can be supposed that tannic acid (TA) can improve the chelating affinity of biochar for several contaminants. The increased removal of metals due to TA-modified biochar has been reported for aqueous matrices (Chen et al., 2021) but not for soils. The present research has evaluated: 1) the suitability of TA-modified biochar in improving the removal of Cd and Pb from soils, 2) the impact of TA-modified biochar on soil fertility and 3) the uptake of Pb and Cd from lettuce, a well-known bioaccumulator.

Materials and Methods

A mesocosm trial was set-up using three treatments (each in 4 replicates): control (CTRL), unmodified- (B) and tannic acid-modified (TA-B) biochar. Unmodified and modified biochar were added (2.5% w/w) to soil contaminated by Cd and Pb. Total Cd and Pb were 10.6 mg kg⁻¹ and 85 mg kg⁻¹, respectively. The impact of B and TA-B on soil microbial activity was evaluated as biomass carbon, basal respiration and urease and β -glucosidase activities in unplanted soil. At the harvesting, occurred at 65 days after transplanting (DAT), photosynthetic activity, pigment and polyphenol contents, and antioxidant capacity were measured on mature leaves, whereas heavy metal content was measured in roots and leaves.

Results

Adsorption isotherms of Cd and Pb ions onto solids (B and TA-B) followed Langmuir model, with pseudo-second-order kinetic model (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Adsorption capacity (Q_E , mg/g) of cadmium (Cd, left) and lead ions (Pb, right) onto B (circle) and TA-B (triangle) at equilibrium concentration C_E (mg/L) in 0.1M of NaClO₄, at 25 °C.

The soil biological activity was affected by the application of modified biochar (Table 1).

Table 1. Microbial biomass carbon (MBC), basal microbial respiration (MR), β -glucosidase and urease activities in control (CTRL) soil, and in soils added with unmodified- (B) and tannic acid-modified (TA-B) biochar. Data are means ($n=4$) \pm SE.

Treatment	MBC	MR	β -glucosidase	Urease
CTRL	6.7 \pm 0.9	0.06 \pm 0.01	4.9 \pm 0.4	0.25 \pm 0.02
B	5.6 \pm 0.9	0.07 \pm 0.01	4.7 \pm 0.4	0.22 \pm 0.03
TA-B	9.1 \pm 0.8	0.16 \pm 0.03	4.5 \pm 0.3	0.27 \pm 0.03

Plants growth was negatively affected by the modified biochar (Table 2). In these plants, a decrease in photosynthetic pigments and an increase in anthocyanins, flavonoids, and FRAP occurred, indicating a stress condition.

Table 2. Maximum net photosynthetic rate (P_{Nmax} , $\mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$), chlorophylls (Chl, $\mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$), carotenoids (Car, $\mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$), anthocyanins (Anth, $\mu\text{mol g}^{-1} \text{FW}$), flavonoids (Flav, $\text{mg CAT eq g}^{-1} \text{FW}$), total polyphenols (TP, $\text{mg GA eq g}^{-1} \text{FW}$), and antioxidant capacity (FRAP, $\mu\text{mol Trolox eq g}^{-1} \text{FW}$) in control (CTRL) plants and in plants grown on soil amended with unmodified (B) and modified (TA-B) biochar. Data are means ($n=4$) \pm SE.

Treatment	P_{Nmax}	Chl	Car	Anth	Flav	TP	FRAP
CTRL	16.6 \pm 0.1	49 \pm 2	8.5 \pm 0.4	0.50 \pm 0.04	12.0 \pm 0.1	0.60 \pm 0.01	0.80 \pm 0.04
B	18.8 \pm 0.7	48 \pm 2	8.5 \pm 0.3	0.60 \pm 0.01	10.9 \pm 0.4	0.20 \pm 0.04	0.60 \pm 0.04
TA-B	15.5 \pm 0.7	36 \pm 2	6.7 \pm 0.2	0.90 \pm 0.01	19.3 \pm 0.3	0.30 \pm 0.05	1.20 \pm 0.04

Plants grown on modified biochar accumulated more Pb than plants grown on soil added with unmodified biochar (Table 3). On the contrary, plants grown on soil added with modified biochar accumulated less Cd than plants subjected to the other treatments (Table 3).

Table 3. Content of cadmium (Cd(II), $\text{mg kg}^{-1} \text{DW}$) and lead (Pb(II), $\text{mg kg}^{-1} \text{DW}$) in roots and leaves of lettuce grown on control soils (CTRL) and on soils added with unmodified- (B) and tannic acid-modified (TA-B) biochar. Data are means ($n=4$) \pm SE.

Treatment	Cd		Pb	
	root	leaves	root	leaves
CTRL	14 \pm 1	6.1 \pm 0.4	29 \pm 2	3.4 \pm 0.8
B	12 \pm 1	6.1 \pm 0.5	49 \pm 7	2.0 \pm 0.3
TA-B	6.8 \pm 0.9	6.2 \pm 0.3	41 \pm 7	4.9 \pm 1

Conclusions

The findings highlighted that the addition of tannic acid-modified biochar in soils could not negatively affect the soil microbiological activity but reduced the Cd uptake by lettuces as compared to the unmodified-biochar. On the contrary, the treatment with tannic acid got worse the biochar capacity to absorb Pb, favouring a greatest Pb uptake by lettuce plants, with negative impact on photosynthesis and photosynthetic pigment content.

Literature

- Chen J. et al. 2021. Efficient removal of tetracycline from water by tannic acid-modified rice straw-derived biochar: kinetics and mechanisms. *J. Mol. Liq.* 340: 117237.
- Qui M. et al. 2022. Biochar for the removal of contaminants from soil and water: a review. *Biochar*, 4: 19.

Monitoring the Development of Meadow Grassland in Agrivoltaic System Through LiDAR Technology

Michele Moretta¹, Riccardo Rossi¹, Marco Moriondo², Gloria Padovan¹, Enrico Palchetti¹, Marco Bindi¹

¹ DAGRI, Univ. Florence, IT michele.moretta@unifi.it

² CNR-IBE, IT

Introduction

Italy aims to accelerate the country's sustainable growth path in order to achieve the European goals for 2030 and 2050. To this aim, it will be of particular importance to identify sustainable paths for the construction of energy infrastructures that combine the need to respect the environment and the territory with the need to achieve decarbonization goals (MiTe,2022). One of the emerging solutions are the "Agrivoltaic" (AV) installations, i.e., photovoltaic systems that allow the preservation of the continuity of agricultural and pastoral cultivation activities on the installation site while ensuring green energy production from renewable sources. Despite the prevalence of studies focusing on engineering and energy aspects of AV systems, integrated assessments involving crop performance are often lacking (Dinesh and Pearce, 2016). However, as the opposition between PV and crop performances is a well-known problem, it is necessary to define requirements, aimed at establishing monitoring systems to verify the impact of photovoltaic installation on crop growth and development. Manual measurements of crop traits, especially above-ground biomass and height, prove slow and labor-intensive, particularly in various crop development stages within an AV environment (Jimenez-Berni et al., 2018). To address these challenges, recent attention has shifted towards employing Light Detection and Ranging (LiDAR) technologies in agriculture. LiDAR utilizes lasers to create detailed 3D reconstructions, including color, facilitating the extraction of morphological traits like plant height, crucial for decision-making in precision farming (Rivera et al., 2023). Here we report the preliminary results of a comparison study between LiDAR (integrated in Ipad) performances correlated with height data taken on the above ground biomass of grass and the fraction of absorbed Photosynthetically Active Radiation (fPAR), that is an important index for evaluating potential biomass accumulation and yield (Tan et al., 2018).

Materials and Methods

The study is being conducted at an AV system in Sant'Alberto, Ravenna (Italy, 44°30'36.69" N- 12° 9'18.72" E), where fixed photovoltaic panels are installed on a 70-hectare permanent grassland sown in 2018. The grassland consists of a mixture of *Festuca arundinacea*, *Dactylis glomerata*, *Trifolium repens* and *Medicago Sativa*. The experimental set-up includes three "Full Light" (FL) control areas located just outside the AV system and 9 experimental areas characterized by 4 treatments, representing different gradients of AV shadow. (Fig.1). To study the effect of the AV system on grassland growth, measurements of the grasses are being taken three times for each harvest period for two years. First, a species recognition/identification is made in each treatment and the percentage of Grasses, Leguminous and Other) (GLO) is detected. To study the effect of the AV system on the height of the grasses, measurements are being taken by a manual herbometer during the growing cycle. In addition, LiDAR scanner installed on iPad Pro ® was used for a rapid multi-temporal and non-destructive estimation of the above biomass canopy height for each treatment and processed according to the workflow outlined in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Different sites under the PV panels (G1: the uncovered interspace adjacent to each panel; G2: front edge of each panel; G3: beneath the center of each panel; G4: back edge of each panel)

Figure 3: a) Point Cloud, b) Ground Classification, c) Digital Terrain Model (DTM), d) Digital surface model (DSM)

Also, fPAR is monitored throughout the growing season to assess the crop's adaptation to the AV conditions. fPAR is measured with a PAR/LAI Ceptometer (AccuPAR LP-80, METER group, USA) in each individual treatment.

Results

LiDAR-derived Grassland Height (GH) reveals a gradient from GR1 to GR2, peaking above 20 cm, followed by a decline from GR2 to GR3, reaching a minimum below 10 cm beneath the PV panel. In GR4, where the PV panel is absent, meadow grassland height increases again. (Fig.3).

Figure 4: Vertical Transect Analyzed by LiDAR applications

Height measurements taken with herbometer (EH) and fPAR results showed a positive correlation (Fig. 4). The result also shows that there is a positive correlation between GH, EH and LAI. The most significant correlation is between GH and EH with $R = 0.92$ and $p = 0.082$.

Figure 5: Canopy Height (cm) and

Conclusions

The preliminary results of this study demonstrate the effectiveness of the LIDAR technology in capturing the influence of AV system in the development of meadow grassland. This technology is a valid saved-time alternative monitoring and crops detection tool in AV systems thanks to the ease with which an iPad can be used within the crop. It will be useful to develop a methodology that, starting from fPAR data estimated by LIDAR-acquired traits, allows the use of crop simulation models and radiative models to estimate the growth and production of a meadow grassland or crop in an AV system.

Acknowledgments: The authors would like to acknowledge “Tozzi Green S.p.A.” for supporting the work.

Literature

- Dinesh H. et al. 2016. The potential of agrivoltaic systems. *Renew. Sust. Energ. Rev.*, 54: 299-308.
- Jimenez-Berni et al. 2018. High Throughput Determination of Plant Height, Ground Cover, and Above-Ground Biomass in Wheat with LiDAR. *Front. Plant Sci.*, 9: 237.
- Ministero della transazione ecologica, Linee Guida in materia di Impianti Agrivoltaici, Italy, 2022
- Rivera et al. 2023. LiDAR applications in precision agriculture for cultivating crops: A review of recent advances. *Comput. Electron. Agric.*, 207: 107737.
- Tan et al. 2018. Remotely Assessing Fraction of Photosynthetically Active Radiation (fPAR) for Wheat Canopies Based on Hyperspectral Vegetation Indexes. *Front. Plant Sci.*, 9: 776.

Polyannual Cardoon (*Cynara cardunculus* L.) and Compost Amendment Improve Soil Organic Carbon in Two Hilly Areas of Southern Italy

Luigi Morra¹, Salvatore Baiano¹, Antonio Merola¹, Michele Rinaldi², Nino Virzi³,
Massimo Palumbo³

¹ CREA-CI, sede di Caserta IT, luigi.morra@crea.gov.it

² CREA-CI, sede di Foggia, IT, michele.rinaldi@crea.gov.it

³ CREA-CI, sede di Acireale, IT, nino.virzi@crea.gov.it

Introduction

Perennial crops are getting attention as high yielding lignocellulosic crops for the cultivation in marginal soils of the Mediterranean region (Fernando et al., 2018). We carried out in two internal hilly locations of Sicily and Campania, two trials in order to assess different fertilization regimes of cardoon, based on the supplying of N as urea or as biowaste compost. In the present contribution we discuss data about soil organic carbon (SOC) stock and its variation as well as the SOC distribution along the first 30 cm of soil profile.

Materials and Methods

In Campania, the experiment was set in farm located in Calvi (BN), 300 m a.s.l. with a loamy, low fertile soil (SOC 6.8 g kg⁻¹), while in Sicily, the experiment was set in at Aidone (EN), 200 m a.s.l. on a clayey-silty, low fertile soil (SOC 11 g kg⁻¹). The same four fertilization treatments were compared in both the locations according to a completely randomized block design with three replications. Treatments were: 1) Biowaste compost applied once before the seeding, to supply 300 kg ha⁻¹ of total N and 3.5 or 3 Mg C ha⁻¹ at Calvi and Aidone, respectively (COM 300); 2) Biowaste compost applied as above, to supply 600 kg ha⁻¹ of total N and 7 or 6 Mg C ha⁻¹ at Calvi and Aidone, respectively (COM 600); 3) pre-sowing mineral fertilization with NPK and, after sprouting during vegetative cycle, 90 kg N ha⁻¹ as Urea (MIN); 4) non-fertilized control (CNT). A rainfed crop of cardoon, cv Trinaseed, was seeded on December, 2018 at Aidone, and on October, 2019 at Calvi. In Autumn 2022 at Calvi and Aidone, respectively, soil samples were collected in each plot in the 0-10 cm and 11-30 cm layers. Soil was air dried, sieved at 2 mm, finely ground to < 0.5 mm and analysed for the determination of SOC concentration by the Walkley-Black colorimetric method (FAO, 2020). The SOC stock (Mg C ha⁻¹) for the 0-30 cm depth layer was calculated using the equation: SOC stock = SOC × ρ × d × 0.1 (FAO, 2020), where d is the soil depth of 30 cm, 0.1 is a factor for converting g C cm⁻² to Mg C ha⁻¹ and ρ is the bulk density 1.43 Mg m⁻³ and 1.32 Mg m⁻³ for Calvi and Aidone, respectively.

Results

As shown in Fig.1, focusing on the 0-30 cm soil layers, SOC concentration increased only in COM 600 at Calvi while it was steady at Aidone. However, in the 0-10 cm layer it is evident the effect of OC accumulation due to the deposition of a litter of leaves from cardoon. Both at Calvi and Aidone, OC content reached the highest concentrations with COM 600 even if COM 300 did not separate significantly from MIN and CNT. In the underneath 11-30 cm layer, instead, OC concentration was more closer or lower than the initial average content with the exception of COM 600. The best results, in term of SOC stock and its variation respect to the beginning of trials were always measured in COM 600 in both the locations (Fig. 2). Based on the variation of stocks occurred in 3 or 4 years, the SOC sequestration rate was 1.5 and 2.7 Mg C ha⁻¹ year⁻¹ at Aidone and Calvi, respectively. These values are higher than increments of 0.9 - 1 Mg C ha⁻¹

¹ year⁻¹ estimated by D'Avino et al. (2020) with SOMBIT and RothC models on the basis of data gathered from seven-years cardoon crops in Sardinia.

Figure 1: Evolution of soil carbon content measured in 2022 in the whole layer 0-30 cm and in the two layers 0-10 cm, 11-30 cm in Calvi and Aidone after 3 and 4 years of cardoon cycle, respectively. Bar on each column represent standard deviation (N=3); different letters on the same coloured columns represent means significantly different to Tukey HSD Test (P≤ 0.05).
 Figure 2: Soil C stock in 0-30 cm layer after 3 and 4 years of cardoon cycle in Calvi and Aidone, respectively; C stock

variation with respect to initial content in each soil. Bar on each column represent standard deviation (N=3).

Conclusions

Biowaste compost applied at the highest rate boosted the development of aboveground biomass of cardoon so that also the biomass falling to the ground added an input of C to activate an enriching process of SOC stock. The improvement of soil quality in marginal lands could be a crucial aspect for the introduction of perennial industrial crops able to enhance ecosystem services.

Acknowledgment: Research was funded under the Project PON COMETA (2018-2021).

Literature

- D'Avino L. et al. 2020. Introduction of cardoon (*Cynara cardunculus* L.) in a rainfed rotation to improve soil organic carbon stock in marginal lands. *Agronomy*, 10: 946.
- FAO, 2020. A protocol for measurement, monitoring, reporting and verification of soil organic carbon in agricultural landscapes – GSOC-MRV Protocol. Rome.
- Fernando A.L. et al. 2018. Environmental impact assessment of perennial crops cultivation on marginal soils in the Mediterranean regions. *Biomass Bioenergy*, 111: 174-186.

Seed Production Of A Valuable Old Variety Of Sulla (*Sulla coronaria* L.) For Sardinian Pastoral Systems

Teresa Murgia¹, Maria Nieddu¹, Maria Sitzia², Giovanni Garau¹, Pier Paolo Roggero¹

¹ Department of Agricultural Sciences, Univ. Sassari, IT

² Agris Sardegna, Loc. Bonassai, Olmedo, IT

Introduction

Sulla coronaria L. is a Mediterranean forage legume characterized by a high agronomic and nutritional value, good productivity and favorable seasonal distribution under rainfed conditions, high palatability and adaptability to sheep grazing, and provider of a wide range of ecosystem services (N fixation, pollination, protection from soil erosion and degradation). Currently, the area cultivated with sulla is restricted to alkaline and sub-alkaline soils. Recently, the cultivated area of Sulla in Sardinia significantly increased thanks to the availability of a selected rhizobial inoculant (*R. sullae* WSM1592), which is adapted to a wider range of soil pH than the conventional inoculants. However, the volatility of seed prices and the limited availability of seeds of suitable varieties in the local market constraint the cultivation of sulla, which would be an environmental friendly alternative to short-term grass-based haycrops. The old variety “Grimaldi”, selected by University of Perugia in the 1960ies, is among the threatened valuable germplasm of minor forage species that is not being reproduced by seed companies, that concentrated their breeding efforts on few species and varieties often not suitable for rainfed Mediterranean areas.

The aim of this study was i) to evaluate the effect of seed inoculation on the seed production of *S. coronaria* var. Grimaldi; ii) to assess in a 4-months mesocosm the influence of the inoculum amount on plant growth; iii) to assess the seed production and inter-annual variability of *S. coronaria* cv Grimaldi in relation to plant age.

Materials and Methods

A 4-months mesocosm experiment was run to evaluate the effect of seed inoculation on seed production. The experiment was conducted with different levels of a selected rhizobial inoculant (*R. sullae* WSM1592): 0x, 1x, 5x and 10x to assess the influence of the inoculum amount.

The field experiment was carried out during seasons 2020, 2021 and 2022 in a 4000 m² field. We collected data monthly about the number of plants/m², phenology, and biomass in 6 plots of 0.5m². Finally, at the end of the cycle, yield components were calculated. We considered the number of plants per m², the number of inflorescences per plant, and the number of seeds per plant.

Results

The results of the mesocosm experiment clearly showed a positive effect of the inoculation on seed germinability, which reached 100% already with 1x compared to the uninoculated control (~60%). However, 4-months after emergence, the aboveground plant biomass was not significantly influenced by inoculation. This result was attributed to a relatively abundant N content in the soil at sowing (2 g kg⁻¹).

The field experiment showed a variable seed yield calculated from the seed yield components ranging from 408±119 std err (1st year crop) to 836±151 kg ha⁻¹ (2nd year crop). The number of inflorescences per plant (ranging from 4.2 to 12.2) was the best positively correlated seed yield component with seed yield (R²=0.51; n=20) and seed no. per plant (R²=0.81; n=24). A high rate (>50%) of seed loss at the combine harvester was also observed. The 2nd year seed crop also yielded from 4.6±1.8 to 6.9±0.9 t ha⁻¹ dry forage matter with an average 0.3 leaf/stem ratio, and a max LAI of 3.4 at the end of the winter, showing a high suitability to winter grazing. The overall average SLA was 193 cm² g⁻¹ dry matter.

Conclusions

The results of this study suggest that there is a potential for Sardinian farmers to produce either sulla seeds and forage for their needs, but that seed yield interannual variability is very high and seed inoculation with selected *R. sullae* strains can be an essential requirement. Winter forage yield is a fundamental strength of the cv. Grimaldi under Mediterranean conditions.

Preliminary Results on the Seed Production and Quality of *Tanacetum cinerarifolium* (Trev.) Schultz-Bip. in Southern Italy

Claudia Ruta¹, Martina Grdiša², Luigi Tedone¹, Cataldo Pulvento¹, Giuseppe De Mastro¹

¹ Department of Soil, Plant and Food Science, Univ. Bari “Aldo Moro”, IT, claudia.ruta@uniba.it

² University of Zagreb, Faculty of Agriculture Department for Seed Science and Technology, Zagreb, Croatia.
mgrdisa@agr.hr

Introduction

Pyrethrum (*Tanacetum cinerarifolium* (Trev.) Schultz-Bip.) is a species belonging to the *Asteraceae* family. It is native to Albania and Dalmatia (Heywood, 1976), although currently the main producers in the world market are Kenya and Australia. Its importance is due to pyrethrins, natural insecticide, extracted from flower heads, in increasing demand on the world market. In recent years the interest in the introduction in cultivation of pyrethrum in Salento (southern area of Puglia) is ongoing to support economic and productive sustainable regeneration of this area. Actually, the cultivation of pyrethrum in Salento had already been suggested at the beginning of the 1900s and some experimental activities were carried out in Puglia in the early 2000s with encouraging results, using seed from Dalmatia (Tedone et al., 2000, 2004). Despite these good results, the variability of the seed quality and the low germination rate, underlined by several studies, still limited the production of plants with good productive and qualitative characteristics. Therefore, it is considered particularly interesting to undertake research that could contribute developing a program of seed production and clonal propagation.

With the aim to assess the possibility of obtaining and using quality seed with high germinability, a study was carried out at the Department of Soil, Plant and Food Science, on a commercial seed provided by Sandemetrio Opificio Erboristico Company (Specchia – Italy) and a Croatian accession provided by Faculty of Agriculture, University of Zagreb (Croatia).

Materials and Methods

After the germination test, commercial seed by Sandemetrio and the Croatian accession MAP02965 of *Tanacetum cinerarifolium* (Trev.) Schultz-Bip. were sown in greenhouse to obtain seedlings for the transplant in the field. At the time of sowing, a commercial mix of arbuscular mycorrhizal (AM) fungi (*Glomus intraradices* and *G. mosseae* - Aegis) or AM fungus *Septoglomus viscosum* were used to inoculate the seeds. Non-mycorrhizal seeds were used as control.

The inoculated and not inoculated plantlets were transplanted in the field, three plants per sqm, after three months of growing in greenhouse.

At the ripening of the seeds (6 months after the field transplant), the flower heads were collected and the production parameters (plant height, number of flower heads per plant, weight and diameter of the flower heads, number and weight of the seeds produced) were evaluated.

The data collected were analyzed according to a complete randomized design with four replicates. The Student-Newman-Keuls (SNK) test, at a significance level of $P \leq 0.05$, was used for a comparison of treatment means. Statistical analysis was carried out with CoStat software.

Results

The preliminary germination test showed a higher percentage of germinability in the commercial variety (Sandemetrio) than in the Croatian accession MAP02965 (80% vs 60%). For this first yield, the morphological and productive parameters recorded in the plants and flower heads obtained from the Sandemetrio seed were significantly higher than the values from the Croatian accession MAP02965, showing different phenology between the seed origin (Tab. 1). The Sandemetrio seeds developed higher

plants (72 cm vs 45 cm) and produced a higher number of flower heads (244.5 vs 141.1 n°/plant) with a higher number of seeds per flower head (249.33 vs 156.67 n°/head), and higher weight of the 1000 seeds (1.19 g vs 0.95 g).

Tab. 1. Morphological and productive parameters of plants and flower heads obtained from Sandemetrio seed and Croatian accession MAP02965 of *Tanacetum cinerariifolium* evaluated at the seed yield time

Seed origin	AM treatment	Plant height (cm)	Heads			Seed	
			Number/plant	Diameter (cm)	Weight (g)	Number/head	1000 seed weight (g)
Sandemetrio	Control	74	205.20c	1.87a	0.55a	264.00	1.32
	Commercial Mix	71	281.50a	1.53b	0.39b	218.33	1.10
	<i>S. viscosum</i>	70	246.70b	1.70ab	0.34b	265.67	1.16
Accession MAP 02965	Control	41	138.70	1.57	0.14	171.33a	0.98a
	Commercial Mix	45	127.70	1.47	0.14	136.33b	0.83b
	<i>S. viscosum</i>	50	157.00	1.57	0.16	162.33a	1.06a
<i>Sandemetrio</i>	mean	72a	244.00a	1.70a	0.43a	249.33a	1.19a
<i>Accession MAP 02965</i>	mean	45b	141.10b	1.53b	0.14b	156.67b	0.95b

Different letters within each column indicate significant differences between treatments for each seed source and between the seed source according to SNK' test (P≤0.05)

inoculated with *S. viscosum* were higher than the ones inoculated with the commercial mix, but similar to the control (Table 1). No differences were found between mycorrhizal treatments, regardless of seed origin (data not shown). Concerning the production of seeds per plant (Figure 1), no significant differences were recorded between the control plants and the commercial mix inoculated plants (102.6 g/plant and 92.9 g/plant respectively) for Sandemetrio. A very less production was obtained by the accession MAP02965 which reached the highest performance with the symbiosis with *S. viscosum* (17.3 g/plant vs 12.8 g/plant for Commercial mix and 12.5 g/plant for the control plants).

Conclusions

The preliminary results obtained encourage to keep studying the introduction of the species in Salento with a view to a sustainable and integrated development of rural territories.

Literature

- Grdiša M. et al. 2009. Morphological and Biochemical Diversity of Dalmatian Pyrethrum (*Tanacetum cinerariifolium* (Trevir.) Sch. Bip.) Agric. Conspec. Sci., 74: 2.
- McLaughlin G.A. 1973. History of pyrethrum. Pyrethrum: the natural insecticide, 1-15.
- Tedone L. and Marzi V. 2000. Atti del convegno nazionale di studio: La biodiversità del Pollino come opportunità di sviluppo", 16-17 giugno 2000 (125-139).
- Tedone L. et al. 2004. Coltivazione del piretro (*Chrysanthemum cinerariaefolium* Vis) in Italia meridionale. Ital. Hort., 11: 182-185.

Regarding the different mycorrhizal treatments, for the plants grown from the Sandemetrio seeds it seems that the symbiosis significantly increased the number of heads per plant in comparison with the non-inoculated control, even if the diameter and the weight decreased (Table 1). Regarding the productive parameters of Sandemetrio seeds, they did not show any statistical differences (Table 1). On the contrary, about MAP02965, the number of seeds and the 1000 seed weight of the plants

Fig. 1. Seed production

Modelling Camelina (*Camelina sativa* L. Cranz) Yield in Rotation with Barley (*Hordeum vulgare* L.) in Mediterranean Area Using the ARMOSA Crop Model

Calogero Schillaci¹, Alessia Perego^{2*}, Marco Acutis², Marco Botta², Tommaso Tadiello², Mara Gabrielli², Tommaso Barsali³, Francesca Tozzi³, David Chiaramonti^{3,4}, Arwyn Jones¹

¹ European Commission, Joint research Centre Ispra, calogero.schillaci@ec.europa.eu

² Agricultural and Environmental Sciences – Univ. Milan, IT, alessia.perego@unimi.it

³ RE-CORD – Renewable Energy Consortium for Research and Demonstration, Firenze, Italy, tommaso.barsali@re-cord.org,

⁴ Department of Energy (DENERG), Politecnico di Torino, IT, david.chiaramonti@polito.it

Introduction

The sustainability of the biofuel production is crucial towards the targets of the Renewable Energy Directive (EU) 2018/2001 recast¹ through the Fit-for-55 package^{2,3}, where a new 13% greenhouse gas intensity reduction target has been recently set. In particular, a new sub-target for advanced biofuels (2.2% share in 2030) is encouraging the use of woody biomass, municipal, industrial and food wastes (with the advantage of not competing with food-based lands) as primary feedstock (Leclère et al., 2018). These advantages can be amplified by appropriate process integration for a specific value chain that includes facilities for bioenergy generation at a reasonable distance from the production sites (Guittet et al., 2018). Camelina (*C. sativa* L. Crantz), is a promising biofuel crop with high potential for cultivation on marginal soils (Zanetti et al., 2021), also in rotation with food crop, e.g. barley. In this work, we modelled seed yield for Camelina-Barley rotation (hereafter CAMBAR) were modelled for the years 2000-2020 to estimate quantitatively a number of soil and water parameters. The modelling analysis enabled not only the assessment of the Camelina production but also the evolution of the soil fertility (i.e., soil organic carbon) and Greenhouse Gasses mitigation potential at a large spatial and temporal scale.

Materials and Methods

The suitable areas for the Camelina cultivation were found via a retrospective modelling analysis (2000-2020), which was performed with the ARMOSA (Perego et al., 2013; Valkama et al., 2020) process based model. To do that, input data and parameter were retrieved from published data from experimental field trials, meteorological data from the Monitoring Agricultural ResourceS (MARS) gridded agro-meteorological in Europe, soil properties from Land Use/Cover Area frame statistical Survey LUCAS, topography from the Shuttle Radar Topography Mission at 90m and land cover from CORINE. Areas were defined as marginal (Csikós and Tóth, 2023) using yield as target feature, when the potential Camelina yield simulated in ARMOSA was lower than the average yield in Europe according to a the literature benchmark (Masella et al., 2014; Zanetti et al., 2020). Nine sites with a total of seventeen years of Camelina cultivation have been used for model calibration, whereas six sites were used for validation. The analysis was targeted at regions with a predominantly Mediterranean climate. Simulation by the ARMOSA mechanistic crop model was carried out at on a 25 km grid for soil texture, soil carbon average stock, slope and aspect found in the MARS agricultural area mask. Spatial data and subsequent editing and processing of each simulation was allocated to a 500 m cell via a Geographic Information Systems (GIS). The study area covers around 500,000 km².

Results

¹ <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32018L2001>

² <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:52021DC0550&from=EN>

³ <https://www.consilium.europa.eu/it/policies/green-deal/fit-for-55-the-eu-plan-for-a-green-transition/>

The CAMBAR scenario obtained an average yield of 2,468 kg ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹, with high standard deviation (\pm 641 kg ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹) due to fluctuations for extreme weather patterns. Regarding soil organic carbon stock, the CAMBAR scenario showed an increase of +43 kg ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹, which is in line with other studies carried out in Mediterranean or continental climates under crop rotation with minimum tillage and straw retention. The results of the current scenarios showed a slight increase of SOC stock (0.1-0.15% yr⁻¹). In regions with sufficient precipitation throughout the crop cycle, the increase of SOC stock is lower than the entire study area average, and in some few cases the SOC stock was drastically decreased. However, the model clearly shows that SOC stock can increase when Camelina is introduced in rotation with cereals in areas with high desertification risk. In Spain, in the regions of central Spain accounting for 40% of the total area of investigation in Spain, equivalent to an area of 88,233 km², the SOC increase was in average +200 kg ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹. Scientific innovation and relevance of the study is linked to the proposal of applying process-based model using the daily Temperature and precipitation data at EU scale (MARS AGRI forecast dataset) and produce a number of simulation times the combination of soil textural type (USDA), Slope (0-15%, >15%) and Aspect (North, South, East, West facing slope) improving the model resolution. Process optimization for modelling at 500 m spatial scale after the modelling and mapping. Land cover cropland (code 211) CORINE 2018 was considered as baseline for present day cropland whereas mixed land covers were considered for the alternative scenario (code 241-242-243).

Conclusions

The results of this work constitute a key contribution to policy development at the sub-national, national and EU level, through the investigation of low LUC/ILUC biofuel from marginal areas before these are lost due to land degradation processes and other anthropogenic impacts. Mapping the marginal areas is fundamental to show potential for the production of advanced biofuel crops.

Literature

- Csikós N. and Tóth G. 2023. Concepts of agricultural marginal lands and their utilisation: A review. *Agric. Syst.*, 204: 103560.
- Guittet M. et al. 2018. Assessing the sustainability of biofuel production from camelina in Spain, results of the ITAKA project – analysis of GHG emissions. *Aircr. Eng. Aerosp. Technol.*, 90: 1027–1032.
- Leclère M. et al., 2018. Growing camelina as a second crop in France: A participatory design approach to produce actionable knowledge. *Eur. J. Agron.*, 101: 78–89.
- Masella P. et al. 2014. Agronomic evaluation and phenotypic plasticity of Camelina sativa growing in Lombardia, Italy. *Crop Pasture Sci.*, 65: 453–460.
- Perego A. et al. 2013. The ARMOSA simulation crop model: Overall features, calibration and validation results. *Ital. J. Agrometeorol.*, 3: 23–38.
- Valkama E. et al. 2020. Can conservation agriculture increase soil carbon sequestration? A modelling approach. *Geoderma*, 369: 114298.
- Zanetti F. et al. 2021. Camelina, an ancient oilseed crop actively contributing to the rural renaissance in Europe. A review. *Agron. Sustain. Dev.*, 41: 2.
- Zanetti F. et al., 2020. Winter camelina root characteristics and yield performance under contrasting environmental conditions. *Field Crops Res.*, 252: 107794.

Crop Yield Response in the Mediterranean Agroforestry: A Preliminary Metanalysis

Danilo Scordia¹, Sebastiano Andrea Corinzia², Jaime Coello³, Rosa Vilaplana Ventura⁴, Diana Elisa Jiménez-De-Santiago⁴, Berta Singla Just⁴, Omar Castaño Sanchez⁴, Carme Casas⁴, Marc Tchamitchian⁵, Léa Garreau⁵, Mohamed Emran⁶, Sami Z. Mohamed⁶, Mai Khedr⁶, Mohamed Rashad⁶, Roxanne Suzette Lorilla⁷, Alexandre Parizel⁸, Giuseppe Mancini², Antonella Iurato², Corrado Dimauro⁹, Fabio Gresta¹, Salvatore L. Cosentino², Giorgio Testa²

¹ Dip. Scienze Veterinarie, Univ. Messina, IT, danilo.scordia@unime.it.

² Di3A, Univ. Catania, IT.

³ Forest Science and Technology Centre of Catalonia, Solsona, ES.

⁴ BETA Technological Center, University of Vic-Central University of Catalonia, Vic, ES.

⁵ INRAE, Ecodéveloppement, Avignon, FR.

⁶ Scientific Research and Technological Applications, Alexandria, EG.

⁷ BEYOND Operational Unit, IAASARS, National Observatory of Athens, GR.

⁸ French Agroforestry Association, Auch, FR.

⁹ Dip. Agraria, Univ. Sassari, IT

Introduction

Agroforestry can contribute to the implementation of nine out of the seventeen Sustainable Development Goals, being mentioned explicitly in many strategies of the European Green Deal, such as the Farm to Fork Strategy, the EU Biodiversity Strategy and the Circular Economy Action Plan. The eco-schemes set in the new common agricultural policy list agroforestry among the potential agricultural practices that support the transition towards a sustainable food system and the achievement of the EU's climate objectives. The present study reviewed the research evidence of crop yield in agroforestry systems in the Mediterranean regions of southern Europe and North Africa. The main objective was to quantify the yield response of field crop in agroforestry systems as compared with the sole crop system.

Materials and Methods

A literature search on “Mediterranean” AND “agroforestry” AND “crop yield” terms was carried out in September 2022 in the Web of Science Core Collection (WoS, Clarivate) and SCOPUS (Elsevier B.V.) databases. The search was done within article type, abstract and keywords. After a further refining for language and journals, 627 papers were listed. The final number of studies meeting all the criteria (i.e., replicated field trials, crop yield either in agroforestry and sole crop systems, standard errors/deviation, etc.) and selected for the meta-analysis was 22, covering 36 study sites, located in the Mediterranean temperate environments falling into the Köppen climate classification “Csa, Csb and Bsk”. Crop yield responses in agroforestry *vs* sole crop systems were assessed by the slope of linear regressions and 95% confidence intervals, forcing the regression line through the origin.

Results

The slope of the linear regression, with the intercept forced through the origin, represents an estimation of the magnitude change of the agroforestry crop yield as compared to the crop yield in the sole cropping system (Figure 1). The R^2 was used to assess the prediction of the linear relationships. Good prediction was observed in faba bean, oat and durum wheat ($R^2 > 0.85$), although the slope indicated different crop yield responses. Excluding winter pea, where no relationship was observed between the two system types, alfalfa yield in agroforestry seems the most affected, reducing more than half its yield as compared to the sole cropping system (0.44x). Faba bean, pasture and winter wheat had similar yield responses (0.58, 0.61 and 0.63x) although the prediction was very high for faba bean, intermediate for winter wheat and very low for pasture due probably to the large variability of conditions and management practices reported for pasture in

the reviewed studies (n=48). Durum wheat and forage had similar slopes (0.73 and 0.76x) but not similar goodness of fit (R^2 0.37 and 0.86, respectively). Oat yield response was quite good in agroforestry and with a good prediction, while in barley the prediction was worst than oat, however, the magnitude of change between agroforestry and the sole crop systems (0.93x) was the best among the reviewed crop species.

Figure 1. Yield response of field crops identified from the twenty-two studies. Alfalfa (n=10), barley (n=26), durum wheat (n=22), faba bean (n=6), forage (n=10), pasture (n=48), oat (n=16), pea (n=6), winter wheat (n=18). Black lines represent the linear

regressions below and above the 95% confidence intervals (dashed red lines).

Conclusions

The interaction between trees and associated crops is a complex phenomenon that involves facilitative and competitive relationships. Due to the highly diverse agroforestry systems analyzed in the twenty-two studies, a substantial variability in the crop yield was found. In addition to the site, studies largely differed for the year of study, agroforestry system, tree species, crop species and management practices. However, these explanatory variables were not considered in the present study.

In general, barley and oat seem suitable cereals for agroforestry systems due to their short cycle, drought tolerance and low-input demand. Forage and pasture are extensively used in agroforestry, however, it is essential to manage through sowing forage mixtures and fertilization plan to balance floristic composition, persistence and productivity. Legumes were very susceptible to agroforestry due to shading, while wheat response mostly depended on the cultivar, season and association with tree.

Literature

The literature generated and analyzed during the current study is available from the corresponding author on reasonable request.

Impacts of Management Practices on TIMESAT Seasonal Parameters in Mediterranean Grasslands

Alberto Tanda, Antonio Pulina, Pier Paolo Roggero

Dip. Agraria e Nucleo di Ricerca sulla Desertificazione, Univ. Sassari, IT, anpulina@uniss.it

Introduction

Mediterranean grasslands are characterized by seasonal variations in plant species composition and productivity, which are, in turn, linked to environmental conditions and seasonal weather variability (Porqueddu et al., 2016). The grassland growing season starts in autumn when the first favourable rains occur. After a dormancy period in winter, the combination of increasing temperature and water availability establishes the conditions for increasing pasture productivity in spring. In summer, the lack of precipitation and high temperatures negatively influence the final stages of the vegetative pasture cycle (Seddaiu et al., 2018). However, pasture phenology can vary according to site-specific environmental characteristics, weather, and agronomic and grazing management (Caballero et al., 2009). Mediterranean grassland agroecosystems are threatened by land degradation processes driven by intensification, abandonment trends, and climate change. Remote sensing from satellite images can represent a tool to assess the impact of management and help farmers make sustainable decisions. The analysis of time series of multispectral indices, such as the Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI), can help to understand the environment's effect and management's impact on vegetation and phenology. This study aimed to assess the effect of contrasting management intensities and grazing strategies on seasonal vegetation parameters derived from NDVI time-series analysis in Mediterranean grasslands.

Materials and Methods

The study area was a set of 38 fields (about 250 ha) from Mediterranean grasslands in Sardinia (IT). Grasslands were characterized by different environmental conditions. Grasslands were managed differently, allowing for distinguishing areas with high (e.g., fertilization, sowing, and mowing occurred) and low (managed occasionally or unmanaged) management intensity. Furthermore, within both high- and low-managed fields, two different grazing strategies were adopted: a rotational grazing scheme referred to as Adaptive Multi-Paddock grazing system (AMP) and continuous grazing (CON), both with annual stocking rates ranging from 0.8 to 2.0 LSU ha⁻¹.

Within each field, biomass production was measured from 2017 to 2022. For the same period, remote sensing data from the Sentinel2 satellite were acquired at each available date using Google Earth Engine. The red and NIR bands of each image were used to calculate the NDVI. A correlation analysis between NDVI and biomass was performed. A set of phenological parameters (e.g. start, end, and length of the season, time of the NDVI peak, rate of increase/decrease of NDVI at the beginning and at the end of the season) was obtained by smoothing the NDVI time series using the Savitzky-Golay method implemented in TIMESAT software (version 3.3). A Principal Component Analysis (PCA) was performed by including the average value across the growing seasons of the obtained 14 phenological parameters. The two parameters showing the highest significant correlation with the first two principal components were identified. The effect of the interaction between the land management intensity (High vs Low) and the grazing strategy (AMP vs CON) on the high-correlated parameters was tested by fitting a linear mixed-effect model, through which the field and the season were set as random factors. If the ANOVA test showed significant effects, means were compared through Tukey's test. The statistical analysis was performed using RStudio within the R environment (version 4.3.1).

Results

A good agreement ($r=0.70$, $P<0.0001$) was observed between the NDVI and biomass dynamics over the growing seasons. The first two principal components explained 82.7% of the variability. The phenological parameters discriminated between management intensity (High vs Low). Within high management

intensity, grazing management (AMP vs CON) was also identified (Figure 1). The parameters showing the highest correlation ($>|0.35|$, $P<0.001$) with the first two components were the base value of NDVI (val_base), describing the average value between the starting and ending NDVI values, the length of the season (len), the day of the year when the season starts (doy_SOS), and the value of NDVI at its peak (val_peak). The results of the ANOVA test and the average values of parameters across management intensity and grazing are reported in Table 1.

Figure 6. Biplot of the two first principal components based on TIMESAT phenological parameters explaining 82.7% of the total variability. Dots represent samples (scores) under High and Low management intensities and under Adaptive-Multi Paddock (AMP) and continuous (CON) grazing systems. Red lines represent the loadings, i.e. the contribution of the phenological parameters to the sample pattern.

Table 1. Analysis of variance of the effect of the interaction between management intensity (High vs Low) and grazing (AMP vs CON) on the parameters showing the highest significant correlation with the first two principal components. Different letters indicate different means according to Tukey’s test ($P<0.05$).

TIMESAT parameter	Management	P(F) Grazing	M x G	High		Low	
				AMP	CON	AMP	CON
val_base (NDVI)	<.0001	0.8276	0.0037	0.38 a	0.33 b	0.27 b	0.23 b
len (days)	<.0001	0.0871	0.0673	322 a	290 b	267 b	264 b
doy_SOS (doy)	0.0007	0.0037	0.0130	226.1 b	266.6 a	271.2 a	278.1 a
val_peak (NDVI)	<.0001	0.0019	0.0304	0.90 a	0.90 a	0.86 b	0.82 c

Conclusions

The results confirm the hypothesis that seasonal parameters from the NDVI time series can represent a suitable tool for identifying contrasting grassland management under Mediterranean conditions. Further insights are needed to understand the effect of the interaction between environmental factors and management on forage availability parameters (e.g. autumn production) during the growing season.

Literature

Caballero R. et al. 2009. Grazing systems and biodiversity in Mediterranean areas: Spain, Italy and Greece. *Pastos*, 39: 9-152.
 Porqueddu C. et al. 2016. Grasslands in ‘Old World’ and ‘New World’ Mediterranean-climate zones: past trends, current status and future research priorities. *Grass Forage Sci.*, 71(1): 1-35.
 Seddaiu G. et al. 2018. Mediterranean cork oak wooded grasslands: synergies and trade-offs between plant diversity, pasture production and soil carbon. *Agroforest. Syst.*, 92: 893-908.

Sessione 2

CIRCULARITÀ - Sviluppo di strategie di economia circolare nel settore agro- alimentare

ORAL PRESENTATIONS

Reuse of Wastewater in Agriculture: Risks or Benefits? A Pilot-scale Study on Durum Wheat (*Triticum durum* Desf.)

Michele Denora^{1*}, Vincenzo Candido¹, Francesco De Mastro², Giuseppe Gatta³, Cristina De Ceglie⁴, Ruud P. Bartholomeus^{5,6}, Gennaro Brunetti², Michele Perniola^{1*}

¹*Dip. Culture Europee e del Mediterraneo, Univ. Basilicata, IT, michele.denora@unibas.it, michele.perniola@unibas.it

²Dip. di Scienze del Suolo, della Pianta e degli Alimenti, Univ. di Bari, IT

³Dip. di Scienze Agrarie, Alimentari, Risorse Naturali e Ingegneria, Univ di Foggia, IT

⁴Ist. di Ricerca sulle Acque del Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche, Bari, IT

⁵KWR Water Research Institute, Nieuwegein, NL

⁶Soil Physics and Land Management, Wageningen University, Wageningen, NL

Introduction

Over 70% of freshwater is used for agriculture in most parts of the world, with much higher figures in developing countries. Agriculture is constantly competing for limited availability of water for domestic, industrial and environmental uses. Population growth, rapid urbanisation and climate change contribute to increasing water demand, resource depletion and water pollution (Boretti and Rosa, 2019). This study aimed to investigate the presence and fate of emerging contaminants (antibiotics, anti-inflammatories, plasticisers, personal care products) in soil and durum wheat plants treated with treated municipal wastewater in Southern Italy. An experiment was designed with durum wheat plants grown in lysimeters and subjected to irrigation treatments with fresh water and contaminated wastewater. The study presents useful results on the distribution of contaminants of emerging interest between the various compartments and the degradation pathways.

Materials and Methods

The test was conducted at the experimental site of the Centro Ricerche Agrobiologiche ALSIA Metapontum, in the province of Matera (40.4029 N, 16.7944 E.), Italy. The sowing of the 'Saragolla' variety (*Triticum durum* Def.) took place on 13 January 2022, after the tomato harvest. On the same pots of the previous year, the same test was conducted on the tomato to assess the effect of crop succession. The experimental design involved the comparison of three irrigation treatments: (I) fresh water (FW) irrigation; (II) irrigation with secondary sewage effluent treated and refined with the addition of target contaminants in a dose comparable to the European average concentration (TWWx1); (III) irrigation with secondary sewage effluent treated and refined with emerging contaminants in a triple dose (TWWx3). The lysimeters allowed us to accurately monitor all elements of the water balance and to take drainage water samples to monitor any movement of ECs in the aquifer. In this regard, since the wheat test is carried out in a protected environment, four pre-flowering irrigation interventions were deliberately scheduled. The concentration of ECs in water samples was determined by an on-line solid phase extraction (SPE) method whose analytical conditions (UPLC-QTOF/MS/MS) have been described in detail elsewhere (Montagna et al., 2020). Extraction of ECs from soil was performed following the modified QuEChERS method reported by De Mastro et al. (2022). They were obtained using analytical standards (purity > 99%, provided by Lab Instruments, Italy) of clarithromycin; sulfamethoxazole; trimethoprim; carbamazepine; diclofenac; fluconazole; clibanazole; ketoprofen; metoprolol; naproxen; gemfibrozil and triclosan. Those compounds were specifically selected for their presence in wastewater, which is usually not completely removed during conventional treatment. In general, the concentration of EC in treated wastewater ranges from a few ng/L to a few µg/L (Mordechay et al., 2021). Standards were used to prepare the multi-compound standard solution (1000 ppm). The solution was added to the wastewater used for irrigation to obtain a concentration of 200 and 600 µg/L of each compound to obtain TWWx1 and TWWx3.

Results

The fate of ECs in the soil-plant water system varies depending on the specific contaminant. Naproxen, diclofenac, ketoprofen, metoprolol, trimethoprim, sulfamethoxazole, gemfibrozil, triclosan and clarithromycin introduced into the lysimeters with irrigation water were not found in plant tissue, soil and drainage water. Clarithromycin showed an average presence of 20% only in the soil. This should indicate that 100% of these ECs are rapidly degraded into by-products of different chemical composition. At the end of the growing cycle, climbazole was observed in the soil, 85 % TWWx1 and 75 % in TWWx3, while no accumulation was observed in plant tissues and drainage water. It should be noted that the TWWx3 treatments were carried out to force the concentration of EC relative to the European wastewater average and to stimulate the soil-plant response. The ability of the soil to adsorb these ECs could also explain their absence in drainage water. Carbamazepine and fluconazole were detected in plant tissues, soil and drainage water; they were the least degraded ECs in the by-products. Very interestingly, both products were found to be present close to 45% in the plant compost in the TWWx3 thesis. These results seem to indicate a greater persistence of these two ECs in the soil-water system and longer degradation times than the other ECs analysed. Carbamazepine is one of the most frequently detected ECs in soils irrigated with reclaimed water (Beltrán et al., 2020) and that seems to indicate a high potential for soil and water pollution by this contaminants. However, the presence in our study of carbamazepine and fluconazole in plant tissues (roots, stems, leaves in TWWx1 and also in the grain in TWWx3) indicates a potential uptake and accumulation of those two contaminants also in the edible part of the grain and, consequently, a possible risk to human health. The results from an agronomic point of view showed a significant increase in yield in the theses treated with wastewater (TWWx1; TWWx3), which can be attributed to a higher presence of nutrients in this water.

Conclusions

In the present study, an analysis was conducted on the effects of wastewater reuse in agriculture, particularly for durum wheat production. The behaviour of several emerging contaminants (ECs) in the plant-soil complex was analysed and found to vary. Fluconazole and carbamazepine, in particular, were found to have higher uptake concentrations in the plant, with accumulation observed in the plant and grain especially in the TWWx3 treatment. However, some ECs (such as sulfamethoxazole, trimethoprim, ketoprofen, diclofenac, metoprolol and naproxen) showed high uncertainties in their fate, probably due to degradation in the soil and influential crop parameters. The results of this study contribute to the argument that reuse of treated wastewater for irrigation, if properly monitored, can be a safe approach in agriculture and can support policy makers in developing future legislative frameworks for sustainable water management. However, to obtain a definitive answer on the safety of wastewater reuse for irrigation, further studies are needed to provide more information on ECs, including the formation of metabolites and transformation products, in relation to agricultural systems.

Acknowledgments

This study was carried out within the Agritech National Research Center and received funding from the European Union Next-GenerationEU (PIANO NAZIONALE DI RIPRESA E RESILIENZA (PNRR) – MISSIONE 4 COMPONENTE 2, INVESTIMENTO 1.4 – D.D. 1032 17/06/2022, CN00000022, CUP: C33C22000250001). This manuscript reflects only the authors' views and opinions, neither the European Union nor the European Commission can be considered responsible for them.

Literature

- Boretti A. & Rosa L. 2019. Reassessing the projections of the World Water Development Report. *Npj Clean Water*, 2(1): 15.
- Montagna M.T. et. al. 2020. Microbiological and chemical assessment of wastewater discharged by infiltration trenches in fractured and karstified limestone (SCA.Re.S.Project 2019–2020). *Pathogens*, 9: 1010.
- De Mastro F. et al. 2022. Validation of a modified QuEChERS method for the extraction of multiple classes of pharmaceuticals from soils. *Chem. Biol. Technol. Agric.*, 9(1): 49.

Effect of Different Fertilization Strategies and Biostimulant Application on Yield and Quality Traits of Eggplant (*Solanum melongena* L.)

Ida Di Mola¹, Eugenio Cozzolino², Lucia Ottaiano¹, Roberta Marra¹, Ferdinando Esposito¹, Nunzio Fiorentino¹, Massimo Fagnano¹, Mauro Mori¹

¹ DiA, Univ. Napoli, IT, ida.dimola@unina.it, lucia.ottaiano@unina.it, robmarra@unina.it, ferdynando.esposito@gmail.com, nunzio.fiorentino@unina.it, massimo.fagnano@unina.it, mori@unina.it

² CREA-CI, Caserta, IT, eugenio.cozzolino@crea.gov.it

Introduction

The eggplant is a crop with high nutrient needs but, in order to limit the environmental impact of N fertilization preserving yield and product quality, it should be sustainably managed. In this perspective, the current test aimed to assess the yield and qualitative traits of eggplant fruits subjected to different fertilization strategies (organic compared to mineral) in combination with different biostimulants (vegetal and microbial).

Materials and Methods

The experiment was carried out under a plastic greenhouse located in Portici (NA -Italy). The tested crop was eggplant (*Solanum melongena* L.) ecotype “*Napoletana*” was transplanted with a density of 2.1 plants m⁻² on February 22nd, 2022. The soil was loamy-sand, with 1.69% organic matter, 0.11% total nitrogen (N), 97.29 ppm P₂O₅, and 1584.8 ppm K₂O. The experimental design was a split-plot with 3 typologies of fertilization (digestate –**DIG**; compost –**COM**; mineral –**MIN**), as the main factor, and 3 biostimulant treatments (vegetal biostimulant –**BIO**; microbial biostimulant –**MIC**; not treated with biostimulant –**CTR**), as the secondary factor. All treatments were replicated 3 times per a total of 27 plots. The compost, obtained from the organic fraction of municipal solid residues, had 2% N; the solid digestate, obtained by anaerobic digestion of livestock slurries at the Power Rinasce S.p.A. plant of S. Maria La Fossa (CE), had 0.6% N. The N dose, calculated according to the Fertilization Guidelines of Campania Region, was 390 kg ha⁻¹. Compost and digestate were distributed before the transplant at the dose of 23 and 70 Mg ha⁻¹, respectively; mineral fertilizer was applied by 10 fertirrigations with ammonium nitrate (26% N). The vegetal biostimulant was Auxym[®] (Italpollina S.p.a. - Rivoli Veronese, Italy), obtained by a fermentation process of tropical plants; it was applied as foliar spray 4 times, starting on February 28. The microbial biostimulant was Triatum-P[®], containing the micro-organism *Trichoderma afroharzianum* T-22 at a minimum concentration of 1 x 10⁹ CFU g⁻¹. MIC treatment was applied 5 times, the first one as immersion of seedlings in a solution (at dose of 2.5 kg ha⁻¹) before the transplant, and the other ones as soil applications at the dose of 1.0 kg ha⁻¹. The harvests were made 14 times, starting on May 19th until July 21st, when the fruits reached the marketable size; the sum of first five ones was considered as early yield. At each harvest, yield, number and average weight of fruits were measured, in addition, at the eighth one, a sampling of fruits per each treatment was frozen for the following qualitative analyses: hydrophilic and lipophilic antioxidant activity (HAA and LAA, respectively), ascorbic acid (AA), phenols, and carotenoids. All data were subjected to variance analysis using the SPSS 21 software package, version 22 (Chicago, IL, USA). The means were separated using Tukey’s Test at p ≤ 0.05.

Results

All analyzed parameters were affected only by the main effect of the two experimental factors (Tabs. 1 and 2). The total marketable yield was higher in plants fertilized with MIN (+19.3% compared to the average value of the other two fertilizations), due to a significantly higher number of fruits per square meter and their average weight (Tab.1). Interestingly, the early marketable yield was higher in plants fertilized with digestate: +28.5% and + 78.1% compared to COM and MIN, respectively (Tab.1), and it was mainly due

to the number of fruits, since no differences were recorded between DIG and MIN for their average weight (Tab.1). As regards the effect of biostimulant application on the total marketable yield and its components, both BIO and MIC elicited a statistically higher value than the not treated plants (+29.3%); instead, only MIC elicited higher values of early yield followed, in order, by BIO and CTR (Tab. 1). The fertilization significantly affected only HAA and AA, which reached higher values in plants under organic fertilization, but only DIG was different from MIN (Tab.2). Among biostimulants treatments, the MIC plants showed higher values of LAA, phenols, and carotenoids, while BIO plants had always statically lower values, except for carotenoids, for which they were not different from MIC.

Table 1. Marketable total and early yield and their components of eggplant fruits as affected by fertilization types and biostimulants application

Treatments	Total marketable fruits			Early marketable fruits		
	$n^{\circ} m^{-2}$	$Mg ha^{-1}$	$g fr^{-1}$	$n^{\circ} m^{-2}$	$Mg ha^{-1}$	$g fr^{-1}$
Fertilization						
COM	27.0±1.3 b	50.4±3.2 b	186.2±4.7 b	7.8±0.7 b	15.8±1.8 b	199.5±3.9 b
DIG	26.2±1.2 b	50.7±2.6 b	193.4±2.3 ab	9.5±0.7 a	20.3±1.7 a	213.5±3.8 a
MIN	30.3±1.3 a	60.3±3.2 a	198.7±2.6 a	5.3±0.3 c	11.4±0.8 c	213.5±6.8 a
Biostimulant						
CTR	23.3±0.7 b	44.2±1.9 b	189.3±1.9 b	6.0±0.6 b	12.0±1.3 c	200.3±4.8 b
BIO	29.6±1.0 a	57.3±2.6 a	193.3±2.6 ab	8.1±0.6 a	16.9±1.8 b	208.9±5.9 ab
MIC	30.6±1.0 a	59.9±2.5 a	195.7±2.5 a	8.5±0.9 a	18.6±2.0 a	217.3±4.1 a
Significance						
Fertilization (F)	**	**	**	**	**	*
Biostimulant (B)	**	**	*	**	**	*
F x B	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns

In each column, different letters indicate significant differences; ns, *, and ** refer to not significant or significant at $p < 0.05$, and $p < 0.01$.

Table 2. Qualitative traits of eggplant fruits as affected by fertilization types and biostimulants application

Treatments	HAA	LAA	AA	Phenols	Carotenoids
	$mM AA$ $100g^{-1} dw$	$mM Trolox$ $100g^{-1} dw$	$mg g^{-1} fw$	$mg Gallic Acid$ $g^{-1} dw$	$mg g^{-1} fw$
Fertilization					
COM	5.26±0.35 ab	12.87±0.51	45.42±5.45 a	2.80±0.09	0.017±0.001
DIG	5.71±0.28 a	13.11±0.65	32.82±5.06 ab	2.44±0.16	0.019±0.001
MIN	4.88±0.14 b	12.47±0.80	29.15±3.61 b	2.73±0.17	0.020±0.002
Biostimulant					
CTR	5.38±0.32	12.81±0.69 ab	36.87±4.77	2.62±0.08 ab	0.016±0.001 b
BIO	5.25±0.26	12.11±0.58 b	37.44±5.46	2.46±0.17 b	0.018±0.001 ab
MIC	5.22±0.30	13.53±0.65 a	33.08±5.72	2.89±0.16 a	0.022±0.002 a
Significance					
Fertilization (F)	*	ns	*	ns	ns
Biostimulant (B)	ns	*	ns	*	*
F x B	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns

In each column, different letters indicate significant differences; ns, *, and ** refer to not significant or significant at $p < 0.05$, and $p < 0.01$. dw: dry weight; fw: fresh weight.

Conclusions

Our results highlight that the organic fertilization allowed to reach total marketable yield consistent with the yield of plants fertilized with mineral (only -19.3%). Interestingly, the digestate but also the compost elicited a higher early production compared to MIN fertilization, with consequent economic advantage for farmers since early production usually is payied more than ordinary one. Also for some qualitative traits of eggplant fruits, DIG and COM showed better values. Finally, the biostimulants treatments, especially the application of *Trichoderma*, always increased yield as well as the quality of fruits. Further research will allow to confirm this behaviour also for other crops.

Planning and Managing a Forage System to Constrain Nitrogen Surplus in Dairy Farms

Francesco Ferrero, Ernesto Tabacco, Gabriele Rolando, Giorgio Borreani

DISAFA, Univ. Torino, IT, francesco.ferrero@unito.it, ernesto.tabacco@unito.it, gabriele.rolando@unito.it, giorgio.borreani@unito.it

Introduction

The intensification of dairy farming systems has been accompanied by the development of an intensively fertilized corn-based system to the detriment of forage legume crops and other annual grasses, which are considered to be low producing crops and difficult to conserve as silage (Tabacco et al., 2018). Such a system relies on a high external input, with an increasing demand for nitrogen fertilizers to maintain the high dry matter (DM) yield of mono-cropped corn, and concerns have thus arisen about the environmental impact of such intensive forage systems on dairy farms. Tanaka et al. (2002) and Tabacco et al. (2018) developed the concept of dynamic forage/cropping systems that means growing more crops (both annual and perennial) in the forage system and re-designing crop rotations and intercropping to develop a more self-sufficient, integrated and closed-loop livestock and vegetal production system, using an agro-ecological and ethological approach. The aim of this study was to verify how planning and managing a forage system characterized by high N uptake capacity can maintain high dry matter (DM), crude protein (CP) and metabolizable energy (ME) yields, while reducing potential environmental impacts. We focused on evaluating how such an alternative cropping system, coupled with highly efficient forage conservation practices, can affect the nitrogen balance of a dairy farm operating in the Po plain in Italy.

Materials and Methods

The study was conducted over a 6-year period on a commercial dairy farms located in the Torino Province (Piedmont, Italy). The effects of the transition of the forage system management from a PRE (2017-2019) to a POST (2020-2022) situation were evaluated. Data covering herd composition, livestock production systems, livestock feed management, crop cultivation and management were collected through on-farm questionnaires and registered data available on the farms. All the data concerning farm inputs and farm outputs were obtained through the analysis of all the farm invoices. The nitrogen balance approach involved calculating the difference between the total imported nitrogen and that exported at the farm gate-scale. Results were analysed by means of a paired *t*-test.

Results

The proportion of crops and their utilization is reported in Figure 1a. From PRE to POST period the farm decreased the proportion of UAA for whole crop corn silage and increased that for high moisture ear. Winter cereals for grain were partially substituted by winter cereal for silage. In POST period the farm introduced in the cropping system alfalfa (about 16% of the UAA) and sorghum crops. The farm characteristics, nitrogen output, input and efficiency from PRE to POST situations are reported in Table 1. The farm increased the surface cultivated and milk production, resulting in higher kg milk/ha of UAA from PRE to POST situation. The change in the management of forage system resulted in higher N output and lower N input from PRE to POST situation. N output from milk and meat increased, whereas decreased from sold cereals. N input from mineral fertilizer decreased from PRE to POST situation, whereas increased the N input from biological fixation. The optimized planning and management of the forage system allowed to reduce N surplus per farm (- 36%) and per hectare (-44%), resulting in higher N efficiency from PRE to POST period (+31%). The N input per tonne of milk is reported in Figure 1b. From PRE to POST period the kg of N input per tonne of milk was reduced (31 vs. 21 kg N/t milk). This reduction was mainly due to a reduction of N input from fertilizer, and from purchased feeds.

Figure 1. Proportion of crops and their utilization (a); and N input per t of milk (b) in a 6-year period on a commercial dairy farms located in the Torino Province (Piedmont, Italy).

Table 1. Farm characteristics, N output, input and efficiency from PRE to POST situations of forage system management

	PRE	POST	SE	P-value
Farm characteristic				
UAA (ha)	78	89	2.1	0.051
kg milk/ha UAA	15	17	0.4	0.013
N Output (kg)				
Total	16277	18165	393	0.046
Milk	6402	8075	345	0.002
Meat	667	1068	81	0.015
Crops	3208	1118	327	0.253
Slurry	6000	7904	416	0.135
N Input (kg)				
Total	35926	30671	1318	0.049
Concentrates	16172	16843	271	0.268
Forages	2952	0	600	0.107
Fertilizers	16649	10469	1396	0.004
Biological N fixation	153	3359	664	0.053
N Efficiency				
Surplus kg/ha	252	140	23	0.016
Efficiency (kg N out/kg N in)	0.45	0.59	0.03	0.005
kg N surplus per t milk	17	8	1.7	0.008

Conclusions

Acting on forage system management and introducing forage legumes in the crop rotation could enhance production efficiency and environmental quality in the more intensive forage systems adopted on dairy farms in the Po plain in Italy.

Literature

Tabacco E. et al. 2018. Tabacco, E., Comino, L., & Borreani, G. (2018). Production efficiency, costs and environmental impacts of conventional and dynamic forage systems for dairy farms in Italy. *Eur. J. Agron.*, 99: 1-12.

Tanaka D.L et al. 2002. Dynamic cropping systems: An adaptable approach to crop production in the Great Plains. *Agron. J.*, 94: 957–961.

Acknowledgment

This study was carried out within the Agritech National Research Center and received funding from the European Union Next-GenerationEU (PIANO NAZIONALE DI RIPRESA E RESILIENZA (PNRR) – MISSIONE 4 COMPONENTE 2, INVESTIMENTO 1.4 – D.D. 1032 17/06/2022, CN00000022).

The Use of Pelargonic Acid Accelerates Seed-Drying of Camelina: An Example of Circularity of H-EU Project Carina

Maria Giovanna Sessa¹, Federica Zanetti^{1*}, Barbara Alberghini¹, Andrea Parenti¹, Sara Berzuini¹, Angela Vecchi¹, Anna Ciancolini², Michele Falce², Pieter Ravaglia², Dalila Villano², Gianmaria Baldi², Erika Facciolla¹, Andrea Monti¹

¹ DISTAL, Alma Mater Studiorum, Univ. di Bologna, IT, mariagiovanna.sessa2@unibo.it; federica.zanetti5@unibo.it, barbara.alberghini3@unibo.it, andrea.parenti5@unibo.it, sara.berzuini2@unibo.it, angela.vecchi@unibo.it, erika.facciolla2@unibo.it, a.monti@unibo.it

² Novamont, Novara, IT, Michele.falce@novamont.com, Anna.ciancolini@novamont.com, Pieter.ravaglia@novamont.com, Gianmaria.baldi@novamont.com, Dalila.villano@novamont.com

Introduction

The European bioeconomy sector generates an annual turnover of around 2 trillion euros with more than 17 million of employees. Nevertheless, only part of the current biomass feedstocks used in Europe by the bioeconomy sector is domestically produced, thus technical and sustainable strategies for year-round supply of affordable and low-ILUC (Indirect Land Use Change) feedstocks are urgently needed to support the competitiveness of agricultural and bio-based sectors. Developing sustainable farming solutions for the provision of bio-based feedstocks would also help mitigating the risks of land abandonment, which is occurring at an alarming rate in Europe. Innovative double cropping systems including resilient and emerging intermediate crops would enable farmers to produce domestic and low-ILUC feedstocks replacing fallow periods of the year. The H-EU project CARINA (Carinata and camelina boosting the sustainable diversification in agricultural production systems) has identified two emerging oilseed crops, camelina (*Camelina sativa*) and carinata (*Brassica carinata*), as the most feasible options for integrating them in the current farming systems, as intermediate cash cover crops. CARINA aims at demonstrating the feasible introduction of carinata and camelina in different farming systems across Europe, and the full use of the produced biomass (seeds and crop residues) to source a vast portfolio of biobased products adopting a circular economy approach. Since camelina is characterized by a short growing cycle (Zanetti et al., 2021), it can easily fit as intermediate winter cash cover crop in southern European climates preceding typical spring/summer crops, such as sunflower, sorghum, corn and soybean. Furthermore, with a full circularity approach vegetable oils, derived from CARINA feedstocks, will be converted into pelargonic acid, by Novamont (CARINA's partner), and then used to terminate camelina accelerating its maturity and thus allowing a more anticipate sowing of the succeeding crop, with indisputable benefits on the main crop productivity.

Materials and Methods

With the scope of demonstrating the feasibility of camelina-sorghum/sunflower double cropping system in comparison with the "business as usual system" winter fallow-sorghum/sunflower, a field demo trial, covering the surface of about 1 ha, has been established at the experimental farm of Bologna University in Cadriano (44° 33' N, 11° 23' E). The site is characterized by a silty-clay-loam soil (27% sand, 41% loam, 32% clay, pH: 7.74), and a long-term mean annual temperature of 13.2°C, and cumulative precipitation of 613 mm. Three different camelina commercial varieties were compared in large duplicated strips of about 1500 m², each: CCE 44, a winter type by Camelina Company Spain, CCE117, a spring type by Camelina Company Spain (CARINA's partner), and Lenska, a winter type by Poznan University (CARINA's partner). Sowing took place on October 26, 2022 by means of a mechanical cereal seeder (DAMAX), using an interrow distance of 0.17 m and a seeding rate of 6 kg ha⁻¹. Before sowing 200 kg ha⁻¹ of 18-46 NP fertilizer was applied and then, at stem elongation, additional top-dressing fertilization with 100 kg ha⁻¹ of urea (46% N) has been applied. The trial has been rainfed and the chemical control of weeds and pests has

not been performed. When camelina reached seed residual moisture of about 35% (May 26, 2023), with the scope to accelerate maturity a formulation of pelargonic acid, supplied by Novamont, has been sprayed on half of the surface of the camelina strips (~ 4000 m²). Pelargonic acid (Novamont formulation) has been sprayed at a dose of 14.5 L ha⁻¹ diluted on 200 L ha⁻¹ of water. After 4 d from the application camelina plants resulted completely dried down and the manual harvest on 10 randomized areas of 1 m² has been performed to assess seed yield. The remaining part of the strips will be harvested when physiological maturity will be reached, and seed yield will be assessed on those strips as well. On representative seed samples from each treatments seed quality in terms of seed weight, oil content, and fatty acid composition will be surveyed.

Results

The considered growing season showed a meteorological evolution quite in line the typical one at the study site. The average mean temperature from sowing until May 31 was 9.9°C, and the accumulated Growing Degree Days were 1323. Those values are in line with that of other studies conducted on similar environments on camelina (Righini et al., 2019). The real differences, that severely impacted camelina growth, were the extreme precipitation events characterizing the first 20 days of May in which more than 275 mm of precipitation occurred in several rainy events, leading to extensive soil flooding, which caused an abnormal development of the crop in the last part of its cycle. Fortunately, the application of pelargonic acid permitted to fastly dry down camelina, thus promoting its harvestability (Fig. 1). The effects of Novamont pelargonic acid application were very rapid and impressive, as easily deduced from the photos on Figure 1. The conclusion of the harvesting operations and the full characterization of the harvested seeds, which are still ongoing, will permit to complete evaluation of the effectiveness and effects of pelargonic acid application on camelina.

Fig. 1. Camelina stand before (A) and after (B) pelargonic acid application (Photos taken at Cadriano experimental farm).

Conclusions

Camelina seems a feasible option in intercropping systems in north Italy, preceding the establishment of typical summer crops such as sorghum or sunflower. The application of pelargonic acid permitted to anticipate camelina maturity and thus promoted its harvestability. This represents a good example of circularity since pelargonic acid is derived from vegetable oils such as that of camelina itself.

Acknowledgments

CARINA has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation program under grant agreement No 101081839.

Literature

Righini D. et al. 2019. Shifting sowing of camelina from spring to autumn enhances the oil quality for bio-based applications in response to temperature and seed carbon stock. *Ind. Crop. Prod.*, 137: 66-73.
Zanetti F. et al. 2021. Camelina, an ancient oilseed crop actively contributing to the rural renaissance in Europe. A review. *Agron. Sustain. Dev.*, 41(1): 2.

POSTERS

The Effect of Sludge from Citrus Peel on the Growth of *Lolium multiflorum* Lam.

Silvio Calcagno, Alessandra Piccitto, Carmela Patania, Vivienne Panebianco, Barbara Rachele Ciaramella, Stefania Longo, Giorgio Testa, Salvatore Luciano Cosentino

Di3A, Univ. Catania, IT, cosentin@unict.it

Introduction

The present work studied the agronomic aspects relating to the use of sludge as source of nitrogen as an alternative to mineral nitrogen fertilization. The used sludge is a by-product generated during the process of extracting pectins from citrus peels obtained from Cargill Pectin Italy s.r.l.

Several uses of the residues from the citrus processing industry have been evaluated in recent decades (animal feed, organic fertilizer and as substrate in biorefinery industries) (Satari and Karimi 2018, Dubis et al., 2020).

The sludge is considered as a soil-conditioner able to improve the physical characteristics of the soil (porosity and structure), thanks to its high level of organic matter (Casado-Vela et al., 2006).

The aim of this study was to evaluate the effect of different doses of nitrogen fertilization and sludge, containing an equivalent amount of nitrogen, on growth and productivity of a forage grass species, *Lolium multiflorum* Lam. The experiment was arranged in a randomized block design with three replicates per treatment. Two experimental factors were studied: mineral nitrogen fertilization with three levels (40, 80 and 120 kg N ha⁻¹) and sludge fertilization with an equivalent amount of nitrogen (40, 80, 120 kg N ha⁻¹). Moreover, two additional rates of sludge fertilization (160 and 200 kg N ha⁻¹) were evaluated.

Materials and Methods

The experiment was carried out in 2022 at the University of Catania, Department of Agriculture, Food and Environment (Sicily, Italy). *Lolium multiflorum* Lam. was grown in pots containing 10.5 kg of soil (25 cm in diameter and 30 cm in height), which were filled at the bottom with a layer of 7 kg of clayey soil followed by 3.5 kg of clayey soil mixed with sandy soil (suitably homogenized) and fertilized with 80 kg P₂O₅ ha⁻¹ (as single superphosphate). Two experimental factors were studied: mineral nitrogen fertilization with three levels (40, 80 and 120 kg N ha⁻¹) and sludge fertilization with an equivalent amount of nitrogen (40, 80, 120 kg N ha⁻¹). Moreover, two additional rates of sludge fertilization (160 and 200 kg N ha⁻¹) were evaluated.

Sludge analysis showed a water content of 77.9% and a percentage of 22.1% of dry residue. The nitrogen content was 0.79% of dry residue (analysis by Cargill Pectin Italy s.r.l.).

The amount of nitrogen for each N level was applied as follows: 66% before sowing and 33% as topdressing. Sludge fertilization was applied before sowing, using a water dilution 1:5. Pots containing unfertilized soil were used as a control group. Pots were arranged in a completely randomized experimental design with 3 replications. Manual sowing was carried out on 11 March 2022. During the growing season, the date of seedling emergence and tillering were recorded, samples of the aboveground biomass were harvested to determine fresh and dry weight.

Results

The biomass weight in relation to the treatments at different harvesting time is reported in table 1.

Considering each sampling date, the effect of the nitrogen supply was evident observing an increase on biomass in the treatments fertilized with both mineral nitrogen and sludge as compared to unfertilized treatment. The average production increased from 3.28 to 5.52 g pot⁻¹ in nitrogen fertilized treatments and from 2.81 to 4.18 g pot⁻¹ in sludge fertilization treatments. The biomass production obtained with the maximum sludge dose (200 kg N ha⁻¹) was similar to that achieved with the maximum nitrogen fertilization rate (120 kg N ha⁻¹).

Table 1: Aboveground biomass (g pot⁻¹) in relation to the treatments (nitrogen and sludge fertilization) at different harvesting dates.

Harvesting dates	Nitrogen fertilization			Sludge fertilization					TEST
	N40	N80	N120	N40	N 80	N 120	N 160	N 200	
13/04/2022	1.16	1.52	3.35	1.57	2.12	2.47	2.25	3.72	1.46
26/04/2022	3.98	4.84	6.21	1.74	2.72	3.26	3.06	4.20	1.85
09/05/2022	5.20	4.93	6.38	3.10	3.86	4.56	5.47	4.39	2.50
01/06/2022	2.77	2.90	2.12	4.82	3.48	5.39	5.22	4.41	2.18
Mean	3.28	3.55	4.52	2.81	3.05	3.92	4.00	4.18	2.00

The cumulative biomass production confirmed the positive response of nitrogen and sludge fertilization compared to unfertilized treatment. The highest sludge fertilization levels (N120, N160 and N200 kg N ha⁻¹) allowed to obtain a biomass production higher than intermediate mineral nitrogen fertilization (N80) (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Cumulative biomass (g pot⁻¹) in relation to the treatments (nitrogen and sludge fertilization).

Conclusions

The use of sludge determines a positive effect on biomass production comparable to nitrogen fertilization. Moreover, in a perspective of circular economy and reuse of waste, sludge utilization allows to deal with problems in terms of environmental impacts and energy efficiency.

References

- Satari B. and Karimi K. 2018. Citrus processing wastes: Environmental impacts, recent advances, and future perspectives in total valorization. *Resour. Conserv. Recycl.*, 129: 153–167.
- Dubis B. et al. 2020. The effect of sewage sludge fertilization on the biomass yield of giant miscanthus and the energy balance of the production process. *Energy*, 206: 118189.
- Casado-Vela J. et al. 2006. Evaluation of composted sewage sludge as nutritional source for horticultural soils. *Waste Manag.*, 26 (9): 946-952.

Evaluation of Agronomic Performance and Health-beneficial Properties of *Urtica dioica* L. Cultivated in Nitrate Vulnerable Zones.

Elettra Frassinetti, Mattia Alpi, Eros D'Amen, Giovanni Dinelli, Ilaria Marotti

DISTAL, Univ. Bologna, IT, elettra.frassinetti2@unibo.it, mattia.alpi3@unibo.it, eros.damen2@unibo.it, giovanni.dinelli@unibo.it, ilaria.marotti@unibo.it

Introduction

Nitrate vulnerable zones (NVZs) are areas designated as being at risk from agricultural nitrate pollution. In agricultural areas, the presence and excessive application of pesticides and fertilizers, lead to potentially toxic elements (such as Nitrate) soil contamination. The potentially toxic effect of Nitrate in soil on some crops imposes a strategy of intervention to reduce their concentration. A possible solution might be the cultivation resilient species to restore soil condition. *Urtica dioica* L. is a perennial, low-requirement, and wild edible species, well adapted to iron and nitrogen rich soils. Due to its Nitrate absorption capacity, nettle may be cultivated for NVZs soils restoration, and the plant parts could be used as a source of added value in natural products.

In this work the agronomic and cleaning up performance of *Urtica dioica* L. in different areas of Emilia-Romagna Region sited in NVZs have been evaluated. Total Nitrate content in soil and aerial parts have been evaluated. In addition, the effect of Nitrate on functional quality parameters (Iron and Folic Acid content) production in plants areal tissues had been investigated.

Materials and Methods

Trials have been carried out at Ozzano dell' Emilia (latitude 44°23'16" N, longitude 11°25'54"E, 110 m a.s.l.) and Lizzano in Belvedere (latitude 44° 12'53' N, longitude 10° 51' 50' E, 555 m a.s.l.) since April 2020. The soil composition for Ozzano and Lizzano was sandy loam, and clay loam, respectively. The soil parameters for each location were analyzed by Agriparadigma laboratories (<https://www.agriparadigma.it/>) prior to the stinging nettle experimental trial and at the end of the cycle. During cultivation period in Ozzano (200 L ha⁻¹ under emergency condition) and Lizzano (235 L ha⁻¹ twice a week), irrigation was implemented. Weed management was carried out either manually or by mechanical hoeing. Total rainfalls and mean temperatures data were collected the mean growing degree days (GDD) was calculated. Areal parts were cut three times per years of cultivation at each location and biomass yield was determined by weighing the fresh leaves. Leaf samples representative of each location and cut were evaluated for functional quality parameters as: Folic Acid and Ascorbate, quantified with HPLC Waters e2695 Alliance, and iron (Skoog et al., 2013). In addition, nitrate was extracted and quantified according to Raimondi et al. (2006). One-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) in conjunction with Tukey's honest significant difference was performed for comparing the three growing locations. Significance between means was determined by least significant difference values for $p < 0.05$.

	Ozzano		Lizzano	
	2020	2022	2020	2022
C.E capacity (meq/100g)	27,8	25,2	18,3	25,1
Total N (%)	2,1	1,1	2	1,5
Assimilable P (mg/kg)	20	11	22	20
Exchangeable K	123	329	226	250
Total Organic C (g/kg)	16,5	13	11,7	18
Organic matter (%)	2,9	2,2	2	3,1

Table 1. Results of soil analysis for each location for 2020 and 2022.
C.E capacity = Cation exchange capacity

Results

Stinging nettle is a perennial crop, with yield significant improvements in the second and third year (Radmand et al., 2015). In this research, satisfactory leaf biomass levels were achieved in the second year of cultivation for both locations. A huge yield was obtained in 2022 cuts for both locations. The highest and lowest biomass were consistently obtained at Ozzano in 2022 (4925 kg/ha) and Ozzano in 2020 (232 kg/ha)

respectively (Tab 2). The leaf biomass production recorded in second year of crop age were comparable to the overall above-ground green biomass reported by Jankauskienė (2015). Concerning nitrate content, it was significantly below the threshold level set by the European Food Safety Authority (6000 mg/kg), for all locations and harvest cuts. Nitrate content in plant aerial parts decreases over the years, in parallel with a reduction of nitrates content in soil for both the field. The Nitrate level is related to the facts that aerial parts were cut many times within the cultivation years, avoiding an excessive nitrate accumulation. Iron values are ranged between 1.2 and 3.2 g/kg for Lizzano 2021 and 2022 respectively. Concentrations obtained were comparable to the data reported by Radmand et al. (2015). Increasing Iron content in leaves corresponded to a higher biomass production, and a lower Nitrate level; as reported in literature (Radmand et al., 2015) the Nitrogen fertilization in soil, negatively influence the Iron absorption. Concerning vitamin B9, highest values were reached for Lizzano in 2020 and 2022 and Ozzano 2020; ascorbic acid content is significantly higher in Lizzano field in 2021. Similarly, the highest levels of vitamins content were analogous to that obtained in both commercial and wild stinging nettle (Paulauskiene et al., 2021) respectively.

		NO ₃ ⁻ (mg/kg)	Fe (g/kg)	F.A (mg/100g)	A.A (mg/100g)	Yield (kg/ha)
2020	Lizzano	1113.6 a	1.3 b	50.2 a	55.1 b	648.5 cd
	Ozzano	1684.5 ab	2.8 a	49.0 a	43.9 b	232.4 d
2021	Lizzano	540.1 ab	1.2 b	31.6 bc	72.9 a	2283.2 bc
	Ozzano	351.2 c	1.8 b	24.7 c	31.6 c	3442.5 ab
2022	Lizzano	442.3 bc	3.1 a	55.1 a	17.5 d	4338.8 ab
	Ozzano	352.4 c	1.6 b	37.9 b	17.5 d	4925.7 a
LSD 0.05		1.0	0.6	8.6	9.5	1744.6
<i>p</i>		***	***	***	***	***

Table 2. Different letters within each column for each location represent significant different values ($p \leq 0.05$, Tukey's least significant difference test). The number of stars represent significant differences at the 0.05 (*), 0.01 (**), and 0.001 (***) probability level, respectively. NO₃⁻ = Nitrates content; Fe = Iron content; F.A = Folic acid; A.A = Ascorbic Acid.

Conclusions

The potential for the cultivation of commercial stinging nettle under organic and low input farming practices in Emilia-Romagna Region was evaluated. This study showed that stinging nettle cultivation was feasible, due to the high biomass production and high concentration of nutraceutical compounds (Iron, Ascorbic and Folic Acid). High levels of bioactive compounds combined with a satisfactory yield in both the location in the second and third year of cultivation were observed.

Nitrate leaves levels were always under the threshold set by the European Food Safety Authority, ensuring a good agricultural production, with low level of nitrate. *Urtica dioica* L. showed to be a possible solution for organic cultivation in ZVNs for soil restoration. Due to the efficient use of soil nitrogen and the positive effect on soil composition and structure after 3 years cultivation, for each location were demonstrated.

Literature

- Radman S. et al. 2015. Influence of nitrogen fertilization on chemical composition of cultivated nettle. Emir. J. Food Agric., 27(12): 889-896.
- Shonte T. et al. 2020. Effect of drying methods on chemical composition and antioxidant activity of underutilized stinging nettle leaves. Heliyon, 6: e03938.
- Paulauskiene A. et al. 2021. Influence of harvesting time on the chemical composition of wild stinging nettle (*Urtica dioica* L.). Plants, 10: 686-698.
- Jankauskiene Z. et al. 2015. Changes in the productivity of wild and cultivated stinging nettle as influenced by the planting density and crop age. Zemdirb. Agric., 102(1): 31-40.
- Raimondi G. et al. 2006. Yield and quality of hydroponically grown sweet basil cultivars. Acta Hort., 723: 353-359.
- Skoog D. et al. 2013. Fundamentals of analytical chemistry. Belmont, CA. 9ed.

Sustainable Use of Bioactive Compounds from *Brassicaceae* and *Solanaceae* Wastes for Cereal Crop Protection (SUSinCER)

Chiara Lanzanova¹, Daniela Pacifico², Roberto Lo Scalzo³, Bruno Parisi², Eleonora Pagnotta², Luisa Ugolini², Laura Righetti², Roberto Matteo², Massimo Montanari², Anna Maria Mastrangelo⁴, Daniela Marone⁴, Raffaella Pergamo⁵, Carlotta Balconi¹

¹ CREA-CI, Bergamo, IT, chiara.lanzanova@crea.gov.it

² CREA-CI, Bologna, IT

³ CREA-IT, Milano, IT

⁴ CREA-CI, Foggia, IT

⁵ CREA-PB, Roma, IT

Introduction

Defatted seed meals of oleaginous *Brassicaceae*, such as *Eruca sativa*, and potato (*S. tuberosum* L.) peel are excellent plant matrices to recover potentially useful biomolecules from industrial processes in a circular economy perspective aiming at crop protection. Among several biomolecule classes, glucosinolates and glycoalkaloids, from *Brassicaceae* and potato respectively, have been proven to be effective against plant disease agents (Pacifico et al., 2021). The application of these bioprotectors will deal with new global challenges, such as reducing agri-food waste and increasing sustainability and food safety for the consumer. The SUSinCER project (<http://susincer.crea.gov.it>) aims to investigate the biological activity of secondary metabolites from defatted seed meals of oleaginous *Brassicaceae* and potato peel, against the development of the mycotoxigenic fungal pathogens *Fusarium verticillioides* (*Fv*) and *Fusarium graminearum* (*Fg*) that contaminate cereals, mainly maize and wheat. From many directions, both institutions and international organizations, comes the warning to reduce food industry waste and find new end uses for residues and new nature-based solutions to minimize the exploitation of natural resources and replace hazardous chemicals, such as pesticides and fertilizers. The project is part of this context, with the aim of furthering the search for new opportunities to: i) valorisation of agro-industrial waste from a circular economy perspective; ii) investigation of the availability of solanaceous and brassicaceous wastes in Italy; iii) study of the factors that play for and/or against their valorisation, including the opportunities brought by current and new EU policies.

Materials and Methods

Potato: Three raw potato peel extracts were obtained from two processing cultivars and one advanced hybrid line. All of them were fractionated in duplicate by Solid Phase Extraction (SPE) on a C18 resin in order to obtain extracts containing individual bio-compounds: acidic phenols, steroidal glycoalkaloids and anthocyanins. The HPLC analysis of raw extracts and separated fractions was performed with an Agilent HPLC system series 1200 equipped with autosampler and UV-VIS detector.

Brassicaceae: Two extracts enriched in glucosinolates (GSL) were obtained according to Testai et al. (2022), starting from *B. carinata* and *E. sativa* defatted seed meals (Brassicaceae seed collection, CREA Bologna). The main GSL were furthermore isolated by means of a two-step chromatographic procedure, starting from Brassicaceae ripe seeds. GSL profiles and concentrations were analysed by HPLC-UV in compliance with the EU official ISO 9167-1:2019 method, with minor modifications, after enzymatic desulfation.

Preparation of Fungal Strains

One strain of *Fg* and one strain of *Fv* were used in this work. The fungal strains were transferred in the center of Petri dishes containing Potato Dextrose Agar (PDA) and incubated at 25 °C for 7 day. After the incubation period, the developed fungal colonies were used as the source of inoculum for the *in vitro* assay.

In Vitro Assay

On the surface of a Petri dish 200 µl of different metabolites (extracted from Brassicaceae and potato as detailed below) were spread with a sterile loop. Agar discs were cut from the margin of the mycotoxigenic fungal colony and put at the centre of the Petri dish. Cultures were incubated at 25°C up to complete development of mycelium. Radial growth of the pathogen was measured from 3 to 7 Days After Inoculation (DAI). Fungal toxicity was recorded as percentage of colony diameter inhibition in comparison to control. **Treatments Brassicaceae:** *B.carinata* and *E.sativa* extracts and their main pure GSLs were tested. All treatments (100-50-25-5-1-0,2-mM) were made in the presence or absence of myrosinase enzyme which hydrolyzes GSLs to isothiocyanates. **Treatments Potato:** Total extract from potato peel of five varieties cultivated in conventional or organic conditions and fractions of glycoalkaloids or phenolic compounds were tested.

Results

In vitro antifungal activity

Extracts from Brassicaceae are able to inhibit the growth of *Fg* and *Fv* strains differently (in the range from 100 to 25 mM) and the effect increases with the addition of myrosinase, while pure GSLs significantly inhibited pathogen growth only after myrosinase bioactivation. Raw extracts from Potato peels show inhibitory activity to both fungi, especially on *Fg*. Inherently, all fractions and combination of them show a significantly lower activity on fungi inhibition comparing with the whole peel extract.

Biodegradable pesticides derived from Brassicas extracts is a circular economy strategy which could have a large potential market, provide low environmental impacts solutions to manage waste and to control pest diseases, stimulate new jobs opportunities. The interest on the valorization of Brassicas' extracts is justified by the fact that species belonging to the *Brassicaceae* family are characterized by a very effective and specific chemical defence system based on GSLs. The action of these compounds against biotic stresses suggests that external application of GSLs could promote plant resistance as an alternative to chemical pesticides.

Conclusions

Potato peels, *E.sativa* and *B.carinata* extracts were able to contrast the development of fungal pathogen with different efficacy as evident from their growth inhibitory activities. Potato peels showed a good antifungal activity independent on starting selected variety and agronomic management system adopted. Raw peel extracts inhibited more effectively than solutions of single or combined extracts, even though all of them may decrease fungi radial growth. The isolated GSLs seem to have an enhanced anti-pathogenic effect on selected fungi only after the addition of myrosinase, due to its bioactivation. Some secondary metabolites from defatted seed meals of oleaginous Brassicaceae and potato peel are able to contrast *in vitro* the development of fungal pathogens; results appear to be promising. In the frame of a green strategy, biodegradable bioactive compounds with pesticide activity derived from Potato and Brassicaceae wastes could have a large potential market especially in a view of an integrated, environmentally friendly, and circular agro-economy.

Financial support of by CARIPLO FOUNDATION, in the frame of SUSINCER Project (2020-2024 Bioactive Compounds from Brassicaceae and Solanaceae waste for cereals crop protection; Project code. 2019-2538)

Literature

Pacifico D. et al. 2021. Sustainable Use of Bioactive Compounds From Potato and Brassicaceae Wastes and by-Products for Crop Protection – a Review. *Molecules*, 26: 1-34.

Testai L. et al. 2022. Cardiovascular benefits of *Eruca sativa* Mill. defatted seed meal extract: Potential role of hydrogen sulfide. *Phyther. Res.*, 36: 2616–2627.

Growth and Essential Oil Yield of *Salvia officinalis* L. Cultivated under an Agriphotovoltaic System

Angela Libutti, Laura Frabboni, Antonio Stasi, Marianna Silvestri, Annalisa Tarantino, Grazia Disciglio

Dep. Agriculture, Food, Natural Resources and Engineering, Univ. Foggia, IT, angela.libutti@unifg.it

Introduction

Energy production through renewables aims to meet global energy demand while replacing fossil fuels. In this regard, the solar photovoltaic systems are at the forefront of power generating technologies and are rapidly expanding worldwide. However, they require large surfaces of land, often at the expense of agricultural areas, thus generating a land use conflict between food and energy production. Although in line with most of the 17 Sustainable Development Goals of the United Nations (2030 Agenda), the growth of global renewable energy could be of food security concern. In this context, agriphotovoltaic (AV) systems are receiving growing attention as sustainable solution towards energy-food combination. By allowing plant cultivation under photovoltaic modules, they contribute to solar energy generation without compromising agricultural production on the same area (Valle et al., 2017). In order to promote AV system diffusion on large scale it is important to know how different crop react to varying levels of shade. Because of their tolerance to partial shading conditions (Zubai et al., 2021), officinal plants may be very suitable crops to cultivation through the AV system; however, to date, no information are available in literature on the performance of officinal plants in this cultivation conditions. Therefore, this study aims to assess the growth response and the essential oil yield of sage (*Salvia officinalis* L.) crop growing under a dynamic AV system.

Materials and Methods

The trial was carried out in spring-summer 2022, at the agriphotovoltaic field of M2 Energy S.r.L. Company, located in the agricultural area of San Severo (41° 41' N; 15° 22' E; altitude, 86 m a.s.l.), Foggia district. Sage plants were grown under a monoaxial solar tracker AV system consisting of photovoltaic solar panels installed according to North-South direction and moving by an angle of +/- 45° from East to West, at a high of 2.50 m above soil surface. The panels oriented itself to direct solar radiation and followed sun movement from sunrise to sunset. Soil had a clay-loam texture (USDA classification) with: sand, 38.6%; loam, 22.4%; clay, 39.0%; total N, 2.7 ‰ (Kjeldahl); P₂O₅, 58 ppm (Olsen); exchangeable K₂O, 539 ppm (Scholleberger); EC_e, 0.6 dS cm⁻¹; pH, 8.1; organic matter, 2.5% (Walkley and Black). Sage seedling were transplanted on 5 May 2002, in single rows spaced at 1 m and at a distance of 1 m along the row. The solar panel rotation determined a shaded area (under panels) and an alternately shaded area (between panels) on soil surface. Therefore, the experimental treatments consisted of plants grown on shaded soil (UP) and plants grown on alternately shaded soil (BP). Plants grown under full sun, in the area immediately adjacent to the AV system, were considered as a control (C). The experiment was arranged according to a complete randomized block design with each treatment replicated three times for a total of 9 plots. Each plot was 40 m² (4 m W × 10 m L) with a sampling area of 10 m² (2 m W × 5 m L). Cropping operations, including irrigation, fertilisation, weed and pest control, were carried out according to the standard farming techniques. During the trial, plant growth was weekly monitored by measuring plant height (cm) and the Absolute Growth Rate of height (AGR, cm d⁻¹) was calculated in four periods of the growing cycle (AGR1: 01-14 June; AGR2: 14-28 June; AGR3: 28 June-12 July; AGR4: 12-27 July) by using the plant height measurements carried out at the start and the end of each period. At the balsamic time, two leaf harvests (H₁: 6 July; H₂: 26 July) were performed. Leaves were weighed to obtain the fresh weight, dried in a ventilated oven at 30°C until a steady weight to determine the dry weight. Then, the dry matter content (DM, %) was calculated. Finally, the dry leaves undergone to steam distillation for 2 hours, by using a 70 L steel extractor (Albrigi Luigi EO 131, Verona, Italy) to extract essential oils (EO) and the EO yield (% dw) was obtained. The experimental data were processed by one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) and means compared by Tukey's test at the 5% probability level.

Results

The Absolute Growth Rate of plant height, periodically determined throughout the sage crop cycle for each experimental treatment, is reported in Table 1. Very interestingly, AGR1, AGR2 and AGR3 values didn't

Table 1 – Absolute Growth Rate of height (cm d⁻¹) of sage plants under three different experimental treatments, in four periods of the crop cycle: 01-14 June (AGR1); 14-28 June (AGR2); 29 June-12 July (AGR3); 12-27 July (AGR4).

Treatment	AGR1	AGR2	AGR3	AGR4
C	0.07 ± 0.01 a	0.14 ± 0.01 a	1.76 ± 0.76 a	0.11 ± 0.01 a
UP	0.07 ± 0.03 a	0.21 ± 0.01 a	1.07 ± 0.66 a	0.04 ± 0.01 b
BP	0.06 ± 0.01 a	0.19 ± 0.01 a	1.06 ± 0.23 a	0.04 ± 0.03 b
Significance	ns	ns	ns	**

Values are means (n = 3). In each column, means followed by different letters are significantly different (p ≤ 0.05; Tukey's test). **, F test significant at p ≤ 0.01; ns not significant. C, control; UP, shaded plants; BP, alternately shaded plants.

UP and BP plants compared to C. Similarly, the shading (UP) and alternately shading (BP) growth conditions compared to the full sun condition (C), significantly reduced the dry matter content of leaves (Table 2) both harvested on 6 July (H1) and 26 July (H2), although at a small extent (3 and 7%, respectively). On the contrary, such a growth conditions resulted very favourable for the accumulation of essential oils in

Table 2 – Leaf dry matter content (DM, %) and essential oil yield (EO, % dw) of sage plants under three different experimental treatments, at the two harvests, performed on 6 July 2022 (H1) and 26 July 2022 (H2), respectively.

Treatment	DM (%)		EO (% dw)	
	H1	H2	H1	H2
C	46.9±0.2 a	47.8±0.3 a	1.5±0.1 c	1.2±0.1 b
UP	45.6±0.3 b	44.7±0.2 b	2.2±0.1 a	2.5±0.1 a
BP	45.1±0.3 b	43.9±0.5 b	1.9±0.1 b	2.2±0.1 a
Significance	*	*	**	**

Values are means (n = 3). In each column, means followed by different letters are significantly different (p ≤ 0.05; Tukey's test). **, F test significant at p ≤ 0.01; *, F test significant at p ≤ 0.05. C, control; UP, shaded plants; BP, alternately shaded plants.

still ongoing suggest that it is possible to use the same soil area to simultaneously produce photovoltaic energy and cultivate plant species that demand little light, such as sage. This also allows to increase the biosynthesis of volatile oils, very appreciated to flavouring foods, as antioxidants and preservatives against food spoilage, as well as for applications in aromatherapy and health care.

We thank the M2 Energia S.r.L. Company for putting at disposal the agriphotovoltaic field.

Literature

- Valle B. et al. 2017. Increasing the total productivity of a land by combining mobile photovoltaic panels and food crops. *Appl. Energ.*, 206: 1495-1507.
- Zubay P. et al. 2021. In the shade - Screening of medicinal and aromatic plants for temperate zone agroforestry cultivation. *Ind. Crop. Prod.*, 170: 113764.
- Seker S. et al. 2023. Production of sage, oregano and rosemary under shading conditions and the effects of light on growth and essential oil properties. *Ind. Crop. Prod.*, 170: 116254.

show any significant difference among plants growing in full sun or control (C), on shaded (UP) and alternately shaded (BP) soil, highlighting a similar plant growth performance, irrespective to the growth conditions. However, in the last period of crop cycle, from 12 to 28 July, a significant decrease (63%) of the Absolute Growth rate of height was observed in UP and BP plants compared to C. Similarly, the shading (UP) and alternately shading (BP) growth conditions compared to the full sun condition (C), significantly reduced the dry matter content of leaves (Table 2) both harvested on 6 July (H1) and 26 July (H2), although at a small extent (3 and 7%, respectively). On the contrary, such a growth conditions resulted very favourable for the accumulation of essential oils in sage leaves. Indeed UP and BP plants were characterized by a higher EO yield than C plants, both at H1 and H2, accounting, on average, for 37 and even 96% increases, respectively, and confirming the strong and positive effect of shading and alternately shading growth conditions on EO accumulation in sage leaves, as previously reported (Seker et al., 2023).

Conclusions

The first results of a field experiment started on 2022 and

Nano-hydroxyapatite from Wastes: Synthesis and P Release Evaluation Through a Soil Column Compared to Triple Super Phosphate

Laura Pilotto^{1,2}, Clara Piccirillo³, Francesca Scalera³, Luca Marchiol²,
Monica Yorlady Alzate Zuluaga⁴, Youry Pii⁴, Guido Fellet²

¹ DVS, Univ. Trieste, IT

² DI4A, Univ. Udine, IT

³ Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche, Istituto di Nanotecnologia Monteroni (Lecce)

⁴ Facoltà di Scienze e Tecnologie, Univ. Bolzano, IT

Introduction

Currently, conventional agronomical practices employ large quantities of fertilizers, but at the same time, these nutrients are poorly efficiently used [1]. Recently, nanomaterials were proposed as a tool to improve agrochemicals performance and nutrient use efficiency [2][3]. Nanohydroxyapatite (nHAP, $\text{Ca}_{10}(\text{PO}_4)_6(\text{OH})_2$, Ca/P molar ratio = 1.67) belongs to the calcium phosphate compounds, and it can be used as a source of phosphorus for crops or as a carrier of other nutrients or other molecules functional for plant nutrition and plant protection [3]. nHAP can be extracted from biological sources and wastes such as animal and fish bones, scales, and shell sources. Compared to the stoichiometric nHAP, natural nHAP contains other ions, such as Mg^{2+} , K^+ , and CO_3^{2-} [4]. Furthermore, the composition and the degree of crystallization are also determined by the type of raw material and synthesis conditions. In particular, the temperature is described as one of the principal parameters that influence the nHAP final crystallinity, its solubility and the P-bioavailability in soil. Nonetheless, nHAP results as poorly soluble in soil [6]. *Pseudomonas putida* is a microorganism known in the literature as able to solubilize different forms of P-compounds, including also hydroxyapatite [7]. In this context, this work aims to test nHAPs from chicken bone as a source of phosphorous for plants. In these first steps, nHAP was extracted from chicken bones, and a soil-leaching experiment was set up to test the behaviour of these materials compared to the traditional fertilizer triple super phosphate (TSP) in soil columns with and without *P.putida*.

Materials and Methods

nHAP Synthesis and Characterization

Chicken bones were supplied by a local butcher in Lecce. Firstly, bones were cleaned with hot water. Bones were then heated for 1 hour in a furnace with atmospheric air at two different temperatures, 300°C (nHAP300) and 700°C (nHAP700). In both cases, the thermal ramp was 5°C min⁻¹. The resulting products were ground with an automatic mortar for 3 hours. Nanoparticles were thus characterized by SEM and FTIR spectroscopy. Elemental content was determined by an ICP-OES and a CHN analyzer.

Soil column leaching test

t32 PVC tubes ($\text{Ø} = 4.30$ cm, length = 30 cm) filled with agricultural sterilized soil sieved at 2 mm were used (Fig. 1). The soil (pH = 7.6, CE = 434 ± 11.5 $\mu\text{S} \cdot \text{cm}^{-1}$, sand = 54%, silt = 24%, clay = 22%) was collected from the Experimental Farm of the University of Udine “A. Servadei” (Udine, Italy). The soil was added with 10% of sand to facilitate drainage. A set of observations was also inoculated with *Pseudomonas putida* (MO). The experimental treatments are: (i) Ctrl (Control, unfertilized), (ii) TSP (conventional triple superphosphate), (iii) nHAP 300 °C, (iv) nHAP 700 °C, (v) Ctrl + MO, (vi) TSP + MO, (vii) nHAP 300 °C + MO, and (viii) nHAP 700 °C + MO. Each treatment is replicated four times. The columns were irrigated weekly with

Figure 7- Soil column representation

50 mL of sterile ultrapure water. The leachates were collected and characterized for their P content with an ICP-OES. A total of seven leachings were performed.

Results

nHAP Characterization

Figures 2: SEM images of a) nHAP300 and b) nHAP700.

Figures 2a and 2b report the images obtained from SEM. They show that these nanomaterials have both heterogeneous sizes (nHAP300=50-250 nm and nHAP 700=50-400 nm) but different surface structures. XRD analysis demonstrated that nHAP700 has a crystalline structure more regular than nHAP300, which is amorphous. The two materials also differ in their elemental contents. nHAP300, due to the residual presence of organic matter, has an N%= 5.58, C%=31.3, and a P-content of 88.3 ± 3.25 g/kg, while in nHAP700 has N%= 0.06, C%=0.38, and a P-content = 194 ± 2.89 g/kg.

P leaching

Data regarding P leaching are currently under elaboration. Preliminary results indicate that nanoparticles are less mobile in soil than conventional fertilizer. While the total P leached in TSP treatment is 6.43 ± 0.86 mg, nHAP300's leached P is 0.13 ± 0.01 mg, and in nHAP700 treatment is 0.13 ± 0.01 mg. Furthermore, the presence of *P. putida* does not seem to affect significantly the quantity of P lost (0.21 ± 0.02 mg for nHAP300 and 0.20 ± 0.02 mg for nHAP700).

Conclusions

Nano-hydroxyapatite obtained from animal bone consents to recover P starting from wastes. With its high P-content, both for nHAP300 and nHAP700, and its poor mobility, nHAP has the potential to be utilized as a novel type of fertilizer. This will allow more efficient utilization of resources and the application of a circular economy approach, two key factors of the European Green Deal.

Literature

- Baligar V.C. et al. 2001. Nutrient use efficiency in plants. *Commun. Soil Sci. Plant Anal.*, 32: 921–950.
- Zuverza-Mena N. et al. 2017. Exposure of engineered nanomaterials to plants: Insights into the physiological and biochemical responses—A review. *Plant Physiol. Biochem.*, 110: 236–264.
- Kah M. et al. 2018. A critical evaluation of nanopesticides and nanofertilizers against their conventional analogues. *Nat. Nanotechnol.*, 13: 677–684.
- Maghsoodi M.R. et al. 2020. Dilemma of hydroxyapatite nanoparticles as phosphorus fertilizer: Potentials, challenges, and effects on plants. *Environ. Technol. Innov.*, 19: 100869.
- Fellet G. et al. 2021. Tools for Nano-Enabled Agriculture: Fertilizers Based on Calcium Phosphate, Silicon, and Chitosan Nanostructures. *Agronomy*, 11: 1239.
- Ahmed M. et al. 2021. Valorization of animal bone into phosphorus biofertilizer: effects of animal species, thermal processing method, and production temperature on phosphorus availability. *Soil Sci. and Plant Nutr.*, 67(4): 471-481.
- Srivastava S. et al. 2023. Comparative transcriptome analysis reveals the phosphate starvation alleviation mechanism of phosphate accumulating *Pseudomonas putida* in *Arabidopsis thaliana*. *Sci. Rep.*, 13: 4918.

Nano-Enabled Agriculture and Circular Economy. Nature-Derived Materials as Smart-Delivery Systems

Laura Pilotto^{1,2}, Luca Marchiol², Guido Fellet²

¹ DVS, Univ. Trieste, IT

² DI4A, Univ. Udine, IT

Introduction

The current world population of 8,0 billion is expected to reach 9.7 billion in 2050 and 10.9 billion in 2100 (UN DESA, 2022). As the population grows, so will the demand for food. Most estimates indicate that a 60% increase in agricultural production will be needed to feed humanity by the middle of this century (Giller et al., 2021), meaning in 25 years: an extremely short time, due to the complexity of the challenge. This implies an increased demand for arable land (+67%), irrigation water use (+65%), and N and P fertilizers (+51% and +54%, respectively) (FAO, 2009).

According to the EAT-Lancet Commission on Food, Planet, Health (2019) “the food system is a major driver of climate change, changes in land use, depletion of freshwater resources, and pollution of aquatic and terrestrial ecosystems through excessive nitrogen and phosphorus inputs”. Some policies will have to be implemented to trigger and sustain the transition toward sustainable agriculture. In particular, it is imperative (i) to support research programs leading to ecologically-sound cropping systems and (ii) to define strategies to reduce the excessive use of chemical fertilizers, pesticides, and herbicides in open-field agriculture. (Ehrlich and Harte, 2015).

To answer these burning challenges, the European Commission launched in October 2020 an ambitious plan to achieve a sustainable, fair, and inclusive economy in EU, in line with the UN SDG 2030 (F2F, 2020). Since the excess of nutrients in the environment is a significant source of water, soil and air pollution negatively impacting soil/plant biodiversity and climate, the F2F strategy aims to reduce nutrient losses by at least 50%, while ensuring no deterioration in soil fertility. At the same time, a reduction in fertilizer use by at least 20% is expected by 2030.

These are very important but, simultaneously, very ambitious objectives, considering that they will have to be achieved without forgetting the need to increase food production due to the expected population increase. This apparent paradox can be overcome by introducing technological and process innovations capable of significantly improving the efficiency of food production.

Nanotechnology encompasses science, engineering, and technology at the nanoscale, about 1 to 100 nanometers. (1 nm = 10⁻⁹ m). Nanoscale materials can behave differently than the same bulk material: the chemical reactivity, melting point, optical properties and more properties may change at the nanoscale.

The development of nanotechnologies in the last 25 years has considerably improved, even revolutionized, many technology and industry sectors: information technology, medicine, transportation, energy, environmental science, and everyday products, as well.

With a significant lag compared to other sectors, evidence has been obtained regarding the possible applications of nanotechnologies in the food production chain. According to Yin et al. (2018), nano-enabled agriculture (NEA) describes the application of nanotechnology in agriculture to improve the performance of agrochemicals.

NEA mainly focuses on improving the agrochemical uptake efficiency by crops, enhancing plant growth and food safety, and mitigating the environmental impacts of agriculture. But the real expected innovation will be the significant reduction of the overall applied doses of nanostructured materials compared to conventional fertilizers, herbicides, and pesticides (Zhang et al., 2021). However, nanotechnology applications in the agricultural chain are still marginal and have not yet made it to the market in comparison with other industrial sectors. Compared to other productive sectors, the main reason for the slow development of the NAE is due to the specific peculiarities of agriculture.

Food production has transparent relationships with people's health. The use of nanomaterials in agriculture deals with their use in the field, their dispersion in the environment, and of course, the human and animal

consumption of agricultural products. For this reason, the safety of nanomaterials must be tested for human consumption beyond their effects on plant nutrition against plant pathogens or weeds.

However, this also means that for NEA nature-derived nanostructured materials are more promising than synthetic nanomaterials (Sampathkumar et al., 2020). The use of renewable materials deriving from plant and animal waste biomass to produce nanosized delivery systems in NEA, represents a crucial step towards the fulfillment of circular economy paradigms. Two examples demonstrate how concrete this scenario is.

The first one concerns the valorisation of hydroxyapatite ($\text{Ca}_{10}[\text{PO}_4]_6[\text{OH}_2]$) extracted from biowastes, such as bovine, horse and chicken bones, fish bones and scales (Maschmeyer et al., 2020). The interest in NEA arises from the potential of nano-hydroxyapatite (*n*HAP), which can be used as an alternative P-source for crops or as a smart carrier of other macro/micronutrients or plant protection products (Fellet et al., 2021). The second example concerns lignin. Lignin is the second most abundant organic compound in plants, a biopolymer representing 30% of the non-fossil organic C on earth. Its polyphenolic structure is of high interest towards the design of nanomaterials. Lignin-based nanocarriers can be divided into lignin nanoparticles (LNPs) and lignin nanocapsules (LNCs). Ongoing studies indicate the great potential of lignin nanocarriers as bio- and eco-compatible materials for NEA (Gigli et al., 2022).

Significant efforts are requested to validate using bio- and eco-compatible nanomaterials in NEA. The gap between the laboratory tests and the open field experiments is still wide but also very rich in research opportunities for transitioning toward more sustainable agriculture.

Literature

Ehrlich and Harte 2015. To feed the world in 2050 will require a global revolution. *PNAS*, 112, 48, 14743-14744.

F2F. 2020. Farm to Fork Strategy. https://ec.europa.eu/food/farm2fork_en (21/02/2023).

FAO. 2009. How to Feed the World in 2050. Food and Agriculture Organization.

Fellet et al. 2021. Tools for nano-enabled agriculture: fertilizers based on calcium phosphate, silicon, and chitosan nanostructures. *Agronomy*, 11: 1239.

Gigli et al. 2022. Lignin-based nano-enabled agriculture: A mini-review. *Front. Plant Sci.*, 13: 976410.

Giller et al. 2021. The future of farming: Who will produce our food? *Food Sec.*, 13: 1073-1099.

Lowry et al. 2019. Opportunities and challenges for nanotechnology in the agri-tech revolution. *Nat. Nanotechnol.* 14: 517–522.

Maschmeyer et al., 2020. Upgrading of marine (fish and crustaceans) biowaste for high added-value molecules and bio (nano)-materials. *Chem. Soc. Rev.*, 49: 4527-4563.

NNI. 2023. https://www.nano.gov/sites/default/files/pub_resource/NNI-FY23-Budget-Supplement.pdf.

Sampathkumar et al. 2020. Developing Nano-Delivery Systems for Agriculture and Food Applications with Nature-Derived Polymers. *iScience*, 23(5): 101055.

UN DESA. 2022. World Population Prospects 2022: Summary of Results. UN DESA/POP/2022/TR/NO. 3.

Willett et al. 2019. Food in the Anthropocene: the EAT–Lancet Commission on healthy diets from sustainable food systems. *The Lancet*, 393: 447-492.

Yin et al. 2018. Opportunities to advance sustainable design of nano-enabled agriculture identified through a literature review. *Env. Sci. Nano*, 5: 11-26.

Zhang et al. 2021. Nanotechnology and artificial intelligence to enable sustainable and precision agriculture. *Nat. Plants*, 7: 864-876.

Land Occupation Affects Nitrogen Load on Dairy Farms in Northern Italy

Gabriele Rolando, Francesco Ferrero, Ernesto Tabacco, Giorgio Borreani

DISAFA, Univ. Torino, IT, gabriele.rolando@unito.it, francesco.ferrero@unito.it, ernesto.tabacco@unito.it, giorgio.borreani@unito.it

Introduction

Land occupation is one of the most discussed aspects about livestock competition for agricultural land. The ReCiPe method, one of the most widely used environmental impact calculation methods, calculates a land occupation (LO) value as the impact on biodiversity and does not consider real land occupation of the crops (Huijbregts et al., 2017). The computation of LO to grow purchased feed out of the farm with different levels of self-sufficiency is needed to evaluate meat and milk contribution to food supply and their impacts on environment on global scale (Gerssen-Gondelach et al., 2017). The aims of the study were to evaluate different methods of calculating LO of milk production and to evaluate implications on nitrogen load on farm surfaces of dairy farms.

Materials and Methods

Two years (2019 – 2020) of data collection were used to assess LO in fourteen dairy farms in Northern Italy. Five criteria to calculate LO were evaluated considering the farm utilized agricultural area (UAA) plus the surface used to produce the purchased feeds and bedding materials. The surface occupied by the purchased products was attributed following five criteria. LO1 considered the surface needed to produce soybean and corn obtained converting the animal requirements for purchased feeds (for energy and protein) into corn and soybean grain equivalents. LO2 was calculated as LO1 for purchased concentrates and converting purchased straws and forages into hay equivalent [10.4% Crude protein (CP) and 7.35 MJ kg⁻¹ Dry matter (DM)]. LO3 considered all off-farm products actually purchased including by-products (considering the actual surface needed to be produced). LO4 was calculated as for LO3 except for by-products that were considered as zero land occupation. LO5 was calculated as for LO3 except for by-products that were considered as a fraction determined as a mass allocation of the whole original crop. LO6 was the value obtained from ReCiPe methodology (SimaPro V 9.0 software tool). Agronomic and farm management data were collected from on-farm detailed questionnaires and all data were cross-checked through farm records and other documentary evidences. Nitrogen balance at the farm gate was used to calculate N surplus per hectare.

Results

The farms were characterised by different stocking rates from, 1.6 livestock unit (LU) ha⁻¹ to 8.6 LU ha⁻¹ (Table 1), and different milk production per cow. In addition, a wide range of cropping systems and farm management determined a wide range of self-sufficiency in terms of Metabolizable energy, CP and DM. The milk production intensity expressed as tonne of fat-protein corrected milk (FPCM) ha⁻¹ was calculated with reference to both the UAA and the actual LO (Figure 1a). The milk intensity calculated on the UAA (minimum of 3.7 t FPCM ha⁻¹, maximum of 60.9 t FPCM ha⁻¹ and mean of 25.9 t FPCM ha⁻¹) increases in the highly intensive farms that produce a lot of milk often on few land, with a high animal load. Milk intensity on the actual LO is lower than the one with UUA, ranges from a minimum of 2.8 t FPCM ha⁻¹ to a maximum of 10 t FPCM ha⁻¹ with an average of 7.8 t FPCM ha⁻¹. Farms that are very market-oriented import a large amount of nutrients from outside into their farm area, causing environmental problems (excessive nutrient load). There is high correlation between milk intensity calculated in UAA and N input and N surplus per hectare (Figure 1b); farms with high milk production per hectare of farm UAA are those with high N input and consequently high N surplus per hectare of UAA.

Table 2. Farm characteristics, self-production of ME, CP and DM, and Land Occupation criteria in the studied dairy farms.

Farm characteristics	Farms													
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14
Stocking rate (LU ha ⁻¹)	1.6	1.4	2.1	1.9	3.0	3.0	4.3	3.3	3.7	3.7	5.6	8.6	6.1	8.4
Milk FPCM per cow (kg d ⁻¹)	17.5	26.0	30.7	19.2	29.3	37.8	35.1	35.7	33.3	34.9	37.9	30.8	37.4	38.0
Self-sufficiency ME (%)	0.61	0.57	0.64	0.64	0.61	0.68	0.53	0.57	0.57	0.48	0.28	0.43	0.41	0.41
Self-sufficiency CP (%)	0.77	0.46	0.61	0.75	0.44	0.56	0.40	0.51	0.56	0.48	0.16	0.23	0.26	0.36
Self-sufficiency DM (%)	0.80	0.73	0.62	0.76	0.69	0.71	0.58	0.65	0.59	0.59	0.47	0.51	0.43	0.41
Farm UUA (ha)	38	83	54	180	85	64	121	109	94	177	44	37	37	55
LO1 (ha)	49	125	90	256	182	145	385	280	243	496	220	206	190	325
LO2 (ha)	67	125	127	284	189	166	434	298	261	516	264	209	204	380
LO3 (ha)	96	461	216	319	207	208	502	499	335	1170	508	786	286	530
LO4 (ha)	45	107	74	265	185	125	416	250	252	369	198	136	125	307
LO5 (ha)	54	124	99	271	163	133	383	259	238	432	203	199	178	334
LO6 (ha)	23	93	113	179	155	132	457	283	268	593	243	255	310	425

*LU: Livestock unit; FPCM: Fat Protein Corrected Milk; ME: Metabolizable Energy; CP: Crude Protein; DM: Dry Matter; UUA: Utilized Agricultural Area; LO: Land Occupation.

Figure 8 – Milk intensity reported on UUA and on actual land occupation calculated with LO1 criteria (a); Nitrogen input and nitrogen surplus per hectare of UUA (b).

Conclusion

Reducing dependency on the market by increasing the efficiency of self-production on the farm area represent a strategy for farms to reduce land occupation and nitrogen surplus and ensure sustainable development of milk production by reducing environmental pressure and improving nitrogen efficiency.

Literature

Huijbregts M.A.J. et al. 2017. *Int. J. Life Cycle Assess.*, 22: 138–147.
 Gerssen-Gondelach S.J. et al. 2017. *Agric. Ecosyst. Environ.*, 240: 135–147.

Acknowledgment

This study was carried out within the Agritech National Research Center and received funding from the European Union Next-GenerationEU (PIANO NAZIONALE DI RIPRESA E RESILIENZA (PNRR) – MISSIONE 4 COMPONENTE 2, INVESTIMENTO 1.4 – D.D. 1032 17/06/2022, CN00000022). This manuscript reflects only the authors' views and opinions, neither the European Union nor the European Commission can be considered responsible for them.

Rooting and Shooting in Single-node Stem Cuttings of *Saccharum spontaneum* ssp. *aegyptiacum* as Affected by Explant/Transplant Time

Alessandro Saita¹, Valeria Cavallaro¹, Elena Crapio², Alessandra Piccitto², Giorgio Testa², Salvatore L. Cosentino², Cristina Patanè¹

¹ CNR-IBE, sede di Catania, IT, cristinamaria.patane@cnr.it

² Di3A, Univ. Catania, IT, sl.cosentino@unict.it

Introduction

The lignocellulosic structure of perennial rhizomatous grasses makes these plants good candidates for the energy production in semi-arid areas (Scordia and Cosentino, 2019). Among them, *Saccharum spontaneum* ssp. *aegyptiacum* is considered a drought-resilient bioenergy crop, having high biomass yield and high water use efficiency (Cosentino et al., 2015). Difficult seed production in *Saccharum* imposes the agamic propagation via rhizomes, which implies high economic and energetic costs. The use of stem-cuttings has been proposed as a valid alternative to the expensive agamic propagation via rhizomes, in lignocellulosic plants, such as giant reed (Scordia et al., 2015). In the framework of the PRIN project ‘Technical and biotechnology innovation in perennial lignocellulosic crops for the production of bioenergy, green building and furniture panels’, funded by the Italian Ministry of University, Education and Research (MIUR), a study has been conducted to assess the validity in using the new method of agamic propagation via single-node stem cuttings in *Saccharum*. In particular, the effects of different times of cuttings excision and following transplant, on root and shoot establishment rate were assessed.

Materials and Methods

Single-node stem cuttings of one-year old plants of *Saccharum spontaneum* ssp. *aegyptiacum* were randomly collected from an established open-field experiment at the Experimental Farm of the University of Catania, Italy (10 m a.s.l.). Stem cuttings (~10 cm long) were obtained by cutting the stem excluding the first two and the last three nodes from the bottom. Cuttings, having a single node, were excised from mother plants from November 2021 to October 2022, for total 5 explant times: November 17, 2021 (I); January 18, 2022 (II); March 15, 2022 (III); May 20, 2022 (IV); October 4, 2022 (V). A day after excision, stem cuttings were transplanted in 0.5 L pots (2 cuttings per pot, 3 pots per replicate, 3 replicates per explant/transplant time), keeping the node approximately 2 cm below the soil surface. The pots were filled with a sandy volcanic soil mixed with a commercial substrate (VigorPlant, Vigorplant Italia s.r.l.) (1:1, v/v), and placed under the open air conditions of a typical South Italy Mediterranean area, or in laboratory at room temperature. In both cases, irrigation was applied when needed. No fertilizers were supplied. Daily maximum and minimum air temperature was measured by means of a data logger (ESCORT iLog).

Two months after each transplant time, cuttings were harvested from each pot and roots (when present) were thoroughly washed to remove the soil. After that, they were measured for number of sprouted cuttings, number of rooted cuttings, shoot dry weight (mg), this last at 65°C in ventilated oven. Shooting and rooting percentage on total number of transplanted stem-cuttings were calculated.

Results

The rate of shooting exhibited a different trend in relation to the growth conditions. In open air, it was quite low (< 30%) from transplant I to III, with a minimum percentage (< 9%) measured in November (transplant I) (Fig. 1). Shooting was maximized with the transplant in May (IV), approaching 50%. Afterwards, it

Table 1. Maximum and minimum daily temperatures (°C, average of the period).

	Open air		Room temperature	
	T max	T min	T max	T min
I (Nov '21-Jan '22)	16.3	9.2	19.6	16.8
II (Jan-Mar '22)	16.2	7.0	19.1	15.8
III (Mar-May '22)	19.8	12.0	21.6	19.0
IV (May-Jul '22)	31.3	21.3	29.1	26.8
V (Oct -Dec '22)	24.2	15.0	22.2	20.4

October (V). This pattern may be ascribed to a photosynthates translocation from stems towards the subterranean plant organs, generally occurring in rhizomatous plants in open field, in early autumn, which may have impoverished stem cuttings, making shooting difficult.

In open air, rooting was maximized in May (transplant IV, 41.7%), being null (0%) in November (I) and

Fig. 1. Percentage of shooting and rooting and shoot dry weight in *Saccharum* under open air (on the left) and room temperature (on the right) conditions, in relation to the time of explant/transplant.

preliminary results indicate that, under Mediterranean climate, the best excision time for good stands in open field is May. In nursery, under less fluctuating thermal conditions, an explant/transplant in November is suggested, to allow a following early spring transplant in open field.

Literature

Scordia D. and Cosentino S.L. 2019. Perennial Energy Grasses: Resilient Crops in a Changing European Agriculture. *Agriculture*, 9: 169.

Cosentino S.L. et al. 2015. *Saccharum spontaneum* L. ssp. *aegyptiacum* (Willd.) Hack. a potential perennial grass for biomass production in marginal land in semi-arid Mediterranean environment. *Ind. Crops Prod.*, 75: 93–102.

Scordia D. et al. 2015. New insights into the propagation methods of switchgrass, miscanthus and giant reed. *Bioenergy Res.*, 8: 1480-1491.

dropped again, down to 25% with the last transplant (October). Under room temperature, the rate of shooting did not change, moving transplant from November to May, indicating that milder and less fluctuating temperatures under controlled conditions, than those experienced by stem cuttings in open air conditions, may have stimulated shoot emission (Tab. 1). However, even under more favourable conditions, shooting was reduced to 0% in

November (I) and January (II) and negligible (16.7%) in March (III) and October (V). In this sense, rooting seemed to be more sensitive to low temperature of late autumn-early winter under open air conditions. At room temperature, differently than shooting, rooting rate peaked at 83.3% with the transplant in November (I), but in the following two transplants (January and March), it dropped to less than 10%, to increase again up to 40% with transplant in May (IV). Low rates of rooting with transplants II and III (January and March), even at room temperature, indicate that physiological changes occur in mother plants, which may regulate root emission from stem cuttings. Shoot dry weight was influenced by temperature in open air, being low in fall-winter, and high in late spring. Thermal lowering from November to February, even at room temperature, did not much affect shoot emission but inhibited shoot growth.

Conclusions

This study reveals that stem-cuttings may represent a valuable innovative technique in the propagation of *Saccharum*, to be introduced for an up-scaled propagation of this species. These

Sustainable Agronomic Practices for a Top Quality Tobacco

M. Isabella Sifola^{1*}, Daniele Todisco¹, Luisa del Piano², Eugenio Cozzolino²

¹ DIA, Univ. Napoli "Federico II", IT, sifola@unina.it; daniele.todisco@unina.it

² CREA-CI, luisa.delpiano@crea.gov.it; eugenio.cozzolino@crea.gov.it

Introduction

Green manure and fertilization with organic fraction from municipal solid waste (OFMSW) are two agronomic techniques of great interest for a more sustainable agriculture, considering the numerous beneficial effects on both soils or crops. In particular, if on soils they can determine: i) increases in the content of organic matter; ii) enrichment in nitrogen (N) and other nutrients; iii) increases of water holding capacity, on plants they create favorable conditions for: i) growth (both above- and below-ground plant parts) and development; ii) a more satisfactory areic production; iii) a better resource use efficiency (i.e. N and water). All these beneficial effects are particularly evident in the medium-long term.

There are few studies on effects of green manure, organic fertilizers (Tabaxi et al., 2021) and OFMSW compost (Sifola et al., 2022) on tobacco cultivation. The main aim of the present work was to investigate the effect of both techniques on the growth, yield, and water/N use efficiency of a top quality tobacco crop (dark fire-cured Kentucky) grown in Central Italy.

Materials and Methods

A field experiment was conducted in 2021 at a private farm located in Anghiari (AR, Central Italy), within an important tobacco district of Italy. Green manure (Faba bean minor, cv. Scuro Torre Lama, sowed on 15 October and manured on 20 May; GM) and bare soil (control, NGM) were factorially combined with or without OFMSW compost, as soil conditioner (SC or NSC, respectively). OFMSW compost was applied on May 2021 at a rate of 10,4 Mg ha⁻¹ of dry matter.

Bare soil without OFMSW compost received 160 kg N ha⁻¹ (dose currently applied to Kentucky tobacco in the area) as mineral N while plots treated with OFMSW compost, green manure, or combination of both, received a dose of mineral N ranging from 100 to 50 kg N ha⁻¹, to integrate the amount of N supplied up to 160 kg N ha⁻¹. Amounts of nutrients and organic C applied with compost are the following: 3,0 Mg ha⁻¹ of organic carbon, 33.7 kg ha⁻¹ of nitric N, 31.3 kg ha⁻¹ of P e 109.2 kg of K.

Tobacco seedlings (cv. Foiano) were transplanted on 31 May at 1 x 1 m plant spacing. Plants were regularly irrigated up to the final commercial harvest (seasonal irrigation volume of 2950.6 m³ ha⁻¹). Soil samples were taken in the 0-0.3 m layer at 45, 73, 122 and 142 days after transplanting (DAT) and root weight density (RWD, mg cm⁻³) was measured. At 45, 59, 73, 122 and 144 DAT, plants were collected for growth rate measurements (leaf emergence rate, LER, no. leaves day⁻¹; Phyllochron, days leaf⁻¹; crop growth rate, CGR, kg dry biomass ha⁻¹ day⁻¹). Analytical determinations of total N (% Kjedahl) and nitric N (kg ha⁻¹) were made on leaf biomass at each sampling date.

Commercial leaves were harvested on 27 September and on 7 October 2021. After curing (standard conditions), yield of cured leaves (CLY, Mg ha⁻¹) at 22% standard moisture content was determined. The water use efficiency, as water productivity (WP, kg cured product m⁻³ gross crop evapotranspiration, ET_c) and irrigation water use efficiency (IWUE, kg cured product m⁻³ irrigation water), and the N use efficiency (NUE, kg cured product kg⁻¹ N applied with mineral fertilization) were then calculated.

Results

There was no significant effect of SC on LER, Phyllochron and CGR while GM significantly reduced the leaf emergence and the growth rate in the 45-59 period (data not shown).

Both SC and GM influenced positively the RWD. The relative variations SC vs. NSC and GM vs. NGM were, in fact, always positive, varying from a minimum of +2% (GM at 122 DAT) and a maximum of +52% (SC at 122 DAT). At the end of growing period (144 DAT), the percentage variation GM vs. NGM was

negative (-22%), presumably because most of the roots in that period had moved to the deeper layers (below 0-0.3 m).

There was no significant effect of both soil conditioning and green manuring on nitric N content of leaves except for green manuring at 122 DAT (GM increased nitric N content of leaves; Tab. 1) and soil conditioning at 144 DAT (SC decreased nitric N content of leaves; Tab. 1). Regardless to treatments, leaf nitric N was always rather low, ranging from just 1 to 16% of the leaf total N. This was a positive result because high nitric N in the leaves means, after curing, a potentially high content of tobacco specific nitrosamines (TSNA) in cured products. It is well known that TSNA are potentially carcinogenic compounds.

Both SC and GM significantly improved NUE, with 31 vs. 20 (SC vs. NSC) and 32 vs. 19 (GM vs. NGM) kg cured product kg⁻¹ N applied with mineral fertilization. No effect of both SC and GM was recorded on yield of cured leaves or on both WP and IWUE but C x G interactions were significant (Fig. 1) showing that there were positive effects of GM only in NSC condition (Fig. 1).

Conclusions

The yield obtained by both SC and GM was, on average, comparable with that obtained by the mineral N dose alone. Therefore, there is an advantage to use both SC and GM since they permit to save a lot of mineral N fertilizer (amount of N saved ranged between 35 and 65%) without any reduction of yield. Both SC and GM improved the RWD and NUE.

Tab. 1. Nitric N (kg ha⁻¹) in leaves during growing period.

DAT	45	59	73	122	142
Soil conditioner (C)					
SC	0.93	2.94	6.66	3.96	0.32 a
NSC	0.53	2.42	5.51	7.66	1.08 b
Green manuring (G)					
GM	0.75	1.94	5.96	9.41 b	0.97
NGM	0.71	1.34	6.61	2.21 a	0.42
C	NS	NS	NS	NS	*
G	NS	NS	NS	*	NS
C x G	NS	*	NS	NS	NS

Literature

Sifola M.I. et al. 2022. Yield and Quality of Three Cultivars of Dark Fire-Cured (Kentucky) Tobacco (*Nicotiana tabacum* L.) Subjected to Organic (Compost) and Mineral Nitrogen Fertilization. *Agronomy*, 12: 483.

Tabaxi I et al. 2021. Effect of organic fertilization on quality and yield of oriental tobacco (*Nicotiana tabacum* L.) under Mediterranean conditions. *Asian J. Agric. Biol.* (1).

Fig. 1. The effect of C x G on CLY (yield of cured leaves), WP (water productivity) and IWUE (irrigation water use efficiency)

Camelina as opportunity for cropping system diversification and bioeconomy development: on-farm multilocation study in Tuscany

Silvia Tavarini, Alessandro Rossi, Clarissa Clemente, Lara Foschi, Luciana G. Angelini

DiSAAA-a, Univ. Pisa, IT, silvia.tavarini@unipi.it, alessandro.rossi@phd.unipi.it; clarissa.clemente@phd.unipi.it, lara.foschi@unipi.it, luciana.angelini@unipi.it

Introduction

Cropping system diversification can provide win-win strategies for climate change mitigation and adaptation, as well as can contribute to open new market opportunities and to improve the sustainability of the agri-food sector. In this contest, alternative and multipurpose oilseed crops could respond both to weather challenges and to sustainable development of bioeconomy providing renewable and valuable feedstocks for biorefinery processes. Camelina (*Camelina sativa* (L.) Crantz) is proposed as a valid option for diversification of traditional crop rotations thus cascading on many ecosystem services of high importance for farmers, rural areas and the whole society. Thanks to its high rusticity and environmental adaptability, and low demands of machinery, fertilizers, pesticides, energy and water (Angelini et al., 2020), camelina offers satisfactory production results even in contexts with low agronomic inputs and on marginal lands, as sole crop, cover crop and cash crop. In addition, the relatively short crop cycle and the availability of autumn-winter biotypes is advantageous for diversification of Mediterranean cropping systems. Besides these agronomic advantages, camelina also shows a unique seed chemical composition with a relevant oil content (up to 42% DM), mainly constituted by oleic (C18:1), linoleic (C18:2) and α -linolenic (C18:3) acids, and bioactive compounds like polyphenols (flavonoids and phenolic acids), tocopherols, and glucosinolates with high antioxidant activity. This composition makes camelina oil capable of having beneficial effects on human health and to source various biobased products. The scaling up of a new crop at farm level requires the design of sustainable cultivation systems, combining empirical and scientific knowledge. So, within the COBRAf project (COprodotti per BioRAffinerie), a multilocation trial has been carried out at farm level across different sites of inland areas of Tuscany (central Italy), with the aim to evaluate the productive potential of the crop and its quality and to demonstrate its feasibility at farm level.

Materials and Methods

The camelina variety Calena was tested in spring sowing during 2021 growing season in four commercial farms located in the inland areas of Tuscany, at Fauglia (FA; Pisa Province), Santa Luce (SL; Pisa Province), Fucecchio (FU; Firenze Province), Arezzo (AR; Arezzo Province), under organic (FA, FU and SL) and integrated (AR) management systems. For each farm, crop trials were conducted at field scale (about 1 ha) under rainfed conditions. Crop sequence and management techniques are summarized in Table 1. From sowing to harvest, daily minimum and maximum air temperature and total rainfall, for each cultivation site, were collected from a meteorological station close to each experimental site. Daily reference evapotranspiration was computed through Hargreaves-Samani model. At seed maturity, in each location, samplings were carried out, removing aboveground biomass, in four representative sampling areas of 4.5 m² each, randomly chosen inside each field. Plant density, plant height, above-ground biomass, seed yield and yield components (number of siliques, number of seeds per silique, 1000-seeds weight) have been evaluated. The crop harvest index (HI) was calculated by dividing dry seed weight by dry weight of total above-ground crop biomass at harvest. Thousand seed weight (TSW) was assessed at the Seed Research and Testing Laboratory of DAFE according to the International Rules for Seed Testing (ISTA). The following qualitative traits of seeds were analysed: (i) oil content by Soxhlet extractor apparatus (mod. R 306) (Düsseldorf, Germany); (ii) crude protein content by multiplying the total N percentage (by mini-Kjeldahl method) by 6.25; (iii) fatty acid composition by a GC2010 Shimadzu gas chromatograph

(Columbia, MD, USA) equipped with a flame-ionization detector was used for fatty acid composition. At the same time, the main bioactive compounds such as flavonoids and phenolic acids, tocopherols, and glucosinolates have been evaluated in camelina seeds by using an HPLC system (1200 Series, Agilent Technologies, Madrid, Spain) equipped with a photodiode-array detector (DAD) and a mass spectrometer detector (Agilent Technologies, Madrid, Spain). Results were subjected to one-way ANOVA to evaluate the effect of the environment (location = FA, SL, FU, and AR). Means were compared using Tukey's HSD test when ANOVA F-test was significant at $p \leq 0.05$.

Table 1. Crop management in the four farms.

	Sowing and Harvest date	Soil texture	Preceding crop	Farm conduction	Tillage*	Fertilization**
FA	SD: 04/03/2021 HD: 28/06/2021	Sandy loam	Safflower	Organic	Pl + RH	0.5 t ha ⁻¹ OF (7-13)
SL	SD: 09/03/2021 HD: 28/06/2021	Sandy clay loam	Linseed	Organic	Pl + DH (x3)	None
FU	SD: 26/03/2021 HD: 29/06/2021	Sandy loam	Hemp	Organic	Ri + DH + RH	1.4 t ha ⁻¹ OF (2.8)
AR	SD: 07/04/2021 HD: 20/07/2021	Loam	Linseed	Integrated	Ri + SH	25 kg ha ⁻¹ GF (10-44)

*Pl: ploughing; DH: disk harrow; RH: rotary harrow; SH: spring harrow; Ri: ripper.

**OF: organic fertilizer; GF: granular mineral fertilizer

Results

The on-farm trials highlighted the high environmental adaptability and plasticity of camelina to the inland areas of Tuscany, characterised by sub-optimal soil chemical characteristics, terrain slope, lack of adequate infrastructure for agricultural products processing and few crops included into the traditional crop rotations. Significant differences among locations have been observed in relation to cumulative rainfall, evapotranspiration, crop cycle, and crop productivity. Regarding seed yield, camelina grown at FA showed the highest value (1.00 Mg ha⁻¹), followed by FU (0.73 Mg ha⁻¹), SL (0.42 Mg ha⁻¹) and AR (0.25 Mg ha⁻¹). Crop production efficiency, estimated by HI, was also different with higher HI obtained at DMS (31.6%) compared to the other farms (25.5-21.2%). TSW varied among locations with the following trend: FA (0.97 g) ≥ FU (0.89) ≥ SL (0.86 g) > AR (0.72 g). Similarly, qualitative traits, such as seed oil and crude protein content, fatty acids profile, n-3/n-6 ratio and the phytochemical properties as phenols, flavonoids, and tocopherols were significantly affected by location. These findings indicated that growing conditions and climate variables strongly influence camelina seed quality, thus affecting the suitability for various end-uses.

Conclusions

Although a remarkable variability has been observed depending on cultivation site and on-farm agronomic management, this preliminary multilocation study underlined the suitability of camelina to be introduced in the tested environment, also in in agronomically disadvantaged areas, contributing to the diversification of traditional cropping systems. This is particularly relevant if we consider that the on-farm trials were carried out by farmers who were approaching this crop for the first time. Finally, the seed quality traits confirmed camelina being a good source of oil, protein and bioactive compounds with several human health benefits.

Acknowledgments

This study is part of the project COBRAf – Coprodotti per BioRAffinerie which received funding by PSR 2014-2020 Regione Toscana.

Literature

Angelini L.G. et al. 2020. Performance and Potentiality of Camelina (*Camelina sativa* L. Crantz) Genotypes in Response to Sowing Date under Mediterranean Environment. *Agronomy*, 10: 1929.

Improved digestate for sustainable fertilization: preliminary results of NOMAD project

Leonardo Verdi, Roberto Vivoli, Marco Mancini, Simone Orlandini, Anna Dalla Marta

DAGRI, Univ. Firenze, IT, leonardo.verdi@unifi.it

Introduction

The application of organic fertilizers that are self-produced inside the farm, is an interesting opportunity to reduce the environmental impact of agriculture. Among organic fertilizers, digestate is one of the most interesting options to support crop productions and recycle on-farm resources (Lee et al., 2021). Based on the input feedstocks, the digestate takes on different characteristics with variable fertilisation potentials. Due to the high water content (>90%), its management and use is challenging requiring a considerable amount of energy and costs (Verdi et al., 2019). For this reason, removing water while maintaining nutritional potentials is a strategy to improve the digestate fertilization potentials and support crop production. The H2020 NOMAD project aims to define an innovative approach for digestate valorisation through nutrient concentration and water content reduction (<https://www.projectnomad.eu/>). In the present study, we tested 5 different solid-separated digestates on lettuce in a controlled environment, and greenhouse gas emissions and global warming potential (GWP) were assessed.

Materials and Methods

The experiment was carried out in a greenhouse at the Department of Agriculture, Food, Environment and Forestry (DAGRI) of the University of Florence. Lettuce (var. “Curly”) was cultivated in pots of 20 cm diameter filled by a sandy-loam soil (55% sand, 15.4% clay and 29.6% silt) with 0.68% of total N and 2.16% of organic matter. Lettuce was fertilized using 5 solid fractions of digestate obtained from the NOMAD project, with 3 replicates per treatment: (i) crop wastes from the AgriPower biogas plant (Latina, Italy) (IT); (ii) food wastes from Malaby biogas plant (Warminster, United Kingdom) (UK); (iii) municipal wastewaters from Ta’ Barkat Sewage Treatment Plan (Xghajra, Malta) (MT); (iv) livestock-crop wastes from Afoi Mpisiritsas (Kozani, Western Macedonia - Greece) (GR); (v) digestate from Afoi Mpisiritsas enriched in phosphorus (P) following ultrafiltration concentrate addition; (vi) commercial organic fertilizer (Actiplus, Fertileva) (COM); (vii) control without fertilization (CON). Fertilization rate was 60 kg N ha⁻¹ corresponding to different fertilizers rate (Tab.1).

Table 1. Elemental characterization of each treatment and corresponding amount per pot

Parameter	IT	UK	MT	GR	GREN	COM	CON
N content %	6,78	8,83	12,48	5,51	5,72	2,00	-
NH ₄ ⁺ -N (mg L ⁻¹)	1342	5404	2271	489	225	-	-
NO ₃ ⁻ -N (mg L ⁻¹)	<200	<100	<100	33,1	<100	-	-
Tot org C (%)	14,24	9,62	10,17	15,76	17,15	27,00	-
Tot P (g kg ⁻¹)	0,95	7,98	6,32	1,78	2,26	15,00	-
Tot K (%)	0,49	0,14	0,06	0,17	0,55	2,1	-
Amount (gr pot ⁻¹)	100,00	76,78	54,33	123,05	118,50	30,80	-

Lettuce was transplanted 28 days after fertilizers mixing into the soil to ensuring mineralization. Morphological parameters of plant diameter, plant height and number of leaves were monitored throughout the growing season, while fresh and dry (48 hours at 80°C) weight were measured at harvest. GHG emissions were monitored using a portable gas analyser (Innova 1512, Lumasense, DK) by through photoacoustic spectroscopy technology and the static chamber methodology (Clough et al, 2020). GHG emission measurements were carried out three times per week immediately after chamber closing (C0) and after 1 hour of gas accumulation (C60). Measurements lasted from lettuce transplanting to harvest. GHG fluxes were calculated using the internal gas concentration (C60– C0), chamber area (314 cm²) and volume (9420 cm³), temperature and molar weight of each gas. GWP for each treatment were calculated using the

IPCC reference coefficient of IPCC AR6 (Forster et al., 2021). Yield-scaled emissions (GWP/yields) were expressed as the net contributes of 1 kg of lettuce.

Results

The highest yields were observed from UK, MT and IT (12458,33, 10382,67 and 7375,33 kg ha⁻¹, respectively) due to the higher content of NH₄⁺-N that was more efficiently available to the plants. This is confirmed by our observation on GR, GREN and COM yields that were similar to those of CON (4632,33, 4966,00, 4706,00, 3809,00 kg ha⁻¹, respectively). In all of these treatments the amount of NH₄⁺-N was significantly lower (or 0 in CON) than the other treatments. The number of leaves (*data not shown*) was not significantly different among plants, but plant diameter and height (*data not shown*), similarly to yields, were higher in UK, MT and IT suggesting a more efficient N uptake under these treatments.

Carbon dioxide (CO₂) emissions were similar in all treatments (average 930 kg C ha⁻¹) except for CON, suggesting an increase in microbial community activity due to fertilization. Regarding methane (CH₄) emissions, MT treatment resulted in a small CH₄ consumption (-0.1 kg C ha⁻¹). This is probably due to the source of the fertilizer, municipal wastewaters, with a presumably lower presence of methanogenic bacteria. Nitrous oxide (N₂O) emissions from MT were significantly higher than the others (4,14 kg N ha⁻¹) and this probably due to the high total N and NH₄⁺-N contents. Regarding cumulative impacts, MT and UK provided the higher GWP, while IT provided lower values with comparable emissions to CON (Fig. 1). The analysis of yield-scaled emissions showed that UK and IT ensure the best yields and the lower environmental impacts.

Figure 1. Yields performances (left) and yield-scaled emissions (right) of different treatments

Conclusions

Enhancing digestate fertilization potential is pivotal to achieve environmental targets in agriculture. Reducing the water content of digestate would cut down the management costs and the related environmental impacts linked to management, transport and spreading in field. Crucial aspect is linked to digestate composition as N and NH₄⁺ content on which the success or the failure of production depends.

Literature

- Clough T.J. et al. 2020. Global Research Alliance N₂O chamber methodology guidelines: Design considerations. *J. Environ. Qual.*, 49(5): 1081-1091.
- Forster P.T. et al. 2021. The Earth's Energy Budget, Climate Feedbacks, and Climate Sensitivity. In: *Climate Change 2021: The Physical Science Basis. Contribution of Working Group I to the Sixth Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change* [Masson-Delmotte, V., P. Zhai, A. Pirani, S. L. Connors, C. Péan, S. Berger, N. Caud, Y. Chen, L. Goldfarb, M. I. Gomis, M. Huang, K. Leitzell, E. Lonnoy, J.B.R. Matthews, T. K. Maycock, T. Waterfield, O. Yelekçi, R. Yu and B. Zhou (eds.)]. Cambridge University Press. In Press.
- Lee M.E. et al. 2021. Biogas digestate as a renewable fertilizer: effects of digestate application on crop growth and nutrient composition. *Renew. Agric. Food Syst.*, 36(2): 173-181.
- Verdi L. et al. 2019. Does the use of digestate to replace mineral fertilizers have less emissions of N₂O and NH₃? *Agric. Forest Meteorol.*, 269: 112-118.

Sessione 3

BASSO IMPATTO - Riduzione degli sprechi e dell'impatto ambientale

ORAL PRESENTATIONS

A New Sustainable Method of Soil Solarization for Management of Soil Pathogens

Battaglia Valerio¹, Cermola Michele¹, Mormile Pasquale², Lahoz Ernesto¹

¹ CREA-CI, Caserta, IT

² Green App srl, Contrada Olivola, Benevento, IT

Introduction

The reduction of agrochemicals is one of the major current challenges in agriculture, including soil-borne pathogens control. Soil solarization, is a non-chemical approach that represents one of the most important alternatives in terms of environmental sustainability for weeds, pests, and soil-borne pathogens management in agricultural soils. Solarization has important technical limitations, an improvement of the technique with respect to the impact on soil ecosystem, duration of soil covering and efficiency in heat accumulation in the soil is needed. Solarization requires usually long times of application (40–60 days) in order to reach high temperature up to 30 cm depth in the soil for a time sufficient to sanitize it. The use of soil solarization has caused a concern about the side effects of solarization on soil microbial populations, soil functionality, nutrients availability and soil organic carbon mineralization. Agronomic investigations about solarization evidenced an increase in crop yield and significant changes in composition and richness of soil microbial communities. In Campania Region (Province of Salerno, and Province of Caserta), the increase of crop areas devoted to vegetables crops (fresh cut or head harvested, tomato, muskmelon, lettuce, pepper, etc.) under tunnel-greenhouses has reached a considerable extent in the last few years. Effective, efficient and cost-effective alternative to soil chemical fumigants is still an unsolved problem in order to reduce the environmental impacts of these crops. We tested disinfection effectiveness and efficiency of a new solarization method which is based on the reproduction of a thermal solar panel at agronomical level by two concurrent experiments carried out in 2014–2016 and 2022–2023. The experiments were carried out in order to evaluate: a) the thermal efficacy of the new solarization method, compared to the traditional one; b) the effect of the new solarization procedure on the survival of pathogen and beneficial microorganisms.

Materials and Methods

The experiments were carried out in multichapel plastic tunnels, with a sandy-clay soil. The first farm is sited in Sele River valley, south of Salerno (Campania Region) and was devoted to the production of fresh-cut leafy vegetables (rocket and basil). The second farm is sited in Mondragone, south of Caserta (Campania Region) and was devoted to the production of vegetables (green bean and tomato). The soil solarization (Solin[®]) tested simulates a thermal solar panel basically made up of a black base (heat collector) and a thermal glass as cover, in order to optimize the “greenhouse effect”: the heat is trapped in the box without significant energy loss (Mormile et al., 2013, 2016; Morra et al., 2018). In order to assess the thermal performance of Solin in a 30-days long period, three trials were carried out in five years. Three treatments were compared: standard farm solarization (SFS), Solin (InnS) and unsolarized control (CNT). In a first time temperature was recorded with a thermocouples placed at 10, 20 and 30 cm depth in the soil. In second time, the temperatures recording were made implementing digital tool of bayer (Nematool) for monitoring temperatures at 20 cm depth in the soil. Viability of propagules of fungal pathogens *S. sclerotiorum* (Ss), *F. oxysporum* f. sp. *melonis* (Fom) and *P. cucumerina* (Pc) was determined after solarization in 2014 and 2016 using fungi strains from collection of the CREA of Caserta (Italy). In 2022 and 2023 the viability of beneficial microorganisms of the genus *Trichoderma* spp. (Tr), *Bacillus amyloliquefaciens* (Ba) and *Pseudomonas chlororaphis* (Pc) was verified. The protocol was adapted starting from that described by Vitale et al. (2013).

Results

Solin showed greater thermal efficiency compared to traditional solarization. In fact, minimum as well as maximum temperatures in InnS were higher than SFS at 10, 20 and 30 cm soil depths (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1 - Trend of temperatures in soil at 10, 20 and 30 cm depth with Solin (InnS) and Standard (SFS) Solarization.

Concerning the viability of microorganisms, SFS and InnS significantly lowered percentage viability of propagules of the three fungi compared to CNT (Fig. 2). In particular, InnS showed a significantly higher effectiveness than SFS in reducing viability of both microorganisms pathogenic and beneficial respectively.

Fig. 2 - Effects of soil treatments on the survival of the three fungi *S. sclerotiorum* (ss), *F. oxysporum* f. sp. *melonis* (fom) and *P. cucumerina* (pc). Different letters indicate means significantly different according to the HSD Tukey Test ($P \leq 0.05$). CNT=control not treated; SFS=standard solarization; InnS=innovative solarization.

The results obtained in the experiments conducted in Mondragone (2022-2023) show that SFS simplify soil microbial communities to the *Penicillium* spp. genus only, while Solin showed a greater variety of fungal genera.

Conclusions

Solin enabled to reduce the duration of soil coverage, thus making the treatment more convenient to the crop planning. Heat (temperature) is not selective with respect to the viability of beneficial or pathogenic microorganisms. Solin allows shorter application times with greater efficacy and less impact on soil microbial communities.

Literature

Mormile P. et al. 2013. A combined system for a more efficient soil solarization. *Plasticulture*, 10: 44–55.
 Mormile P. et al. 2016. Improvement of Soil Solarization through a Hybrid System Simulating a Solar Hot Water Panel. *J. Adv. Agric. Technol.*, 3(3): 226–230.
 Morra L. et al. 2018. Solarization working like a “solar hot panel” after compost addition sanitizes soil in thirty days and preserves soil fertility. *Appl. Soil Ecol.*, 126: 65–74.
 Vitale A. et al. 2013. Short-term effects of soil solarization in suppressing *Calonectria microsclerotia*. *Plant Soil*, 368: 603–617.

Producing Thermoplastics from Wheat Flour Surpluses: Mechanical Performances of Films as Related to Crop N Status, Flour Baking Properties and Gluten Composition

Paolo Benincasa¹, Franco Dominici², Francesca Luzi³, Catia Governatori⁴, Laura Gazza⁵, Elena Galassi⁵, Giacomo Tosti¹, Debora Puglia²

¹DSA3, Univ. di Perugia, IT, paolo.benincasa@unipg.it, giacomo.tosti@unipg.it

²DICA Univ. di Perugia, IT, debora.puglia@unipg.it, franco.dominici@unipg.it

³SIMAU, Univ. Politecnica delle Marche, IT, f.luzi@staff.univpm.it

⁴ASSAM Marche, IT, governatori_catia@assam.marche.it

⁵CREA-IT Roma, IT, laura.gazza@crea.gov.it, elena.galassi@crea.gov.it

Introduction

Although wheat is thought to be used for human or animal feeding, there might be circumstances involving alternative non-food uses, e.g. due to unsatisfactory technological quality, unsold stocks, presence of toxins or pesticides etc., so that the grains or flours would ultimately represent a material to dispose of. Recent research has investigated on the plasticization of wheat flour as a non-food alternative (Puglia et al., 2015; Benincasa et al., 2017). These authors demonstrated that the tensile performances of thermoplastics derived from wheat refined flours depend on the kind of proteins and their structural organization in the grain, as revealed by the grain hardness and the Chopin's alveograph parameters (P, L, P/L, W), commonly used to describe the flour baking properties. These are known to depend on the genotype, the soil and climate, and the cultivation practices. For a given genotype in a given environment and season, the nitrogen (N) fertilization schedule is probably the most important factor affecting the content and kind of proteins in the grain. The aim of this work was to evaluate the effect of N fertilization schedule on the protein content, gluten subunits composition and alveographic parameters of wheat flours and on the mechanical properties of derived thermoplastic films.

Materials and Methods

The wheat (*Triticum aestivum* L.) grains source of the flours used for plasticization were harvested in June 2018 from a field experiment carried out at the University of Perugia. A detailed description of the field trial and crop management are reported in Benincasa et al. (2022). Briefly, two cultivars (Bora, BR; Bologna, BL), were subjected to different nitrogen fertilization schedules, according to a split-plot design with four replicates: 1) continuously well N fed (N300), i.e., fertilized with 300 kg N ha⁻¹, split into five applications of 60 kg N ha⁻¹ each; 2) N fed only very early (N60-0), i.e., with one application of 60 kg N ha⁻¹ one month after sowing; 3) N fed only extremely late (N0-120), i.e., with one application of 120 kg N ha⁻¹ at pollination; 4) unfertilized control (N0). The four fertilization treatments were effective, and differences in growth and yield were very marked (Benincasa et al., 2022).

Grains from each of the eight treatments (2 cultivars x 4 crop N schedules) were separately milled, and Chopin's alveograph parameters (P, L, P/L, W) were recorded on 5 doughs per treatment. Gluten content was determined with the Glutomatic 2200 (Perten Instruments). Storage proteins were extracted on 2 replicates per treatments and then fractionated by SDS-PAGE and by A-PAGE gel to obtain different bands of high molecular weight glutenin subunits (HMW-GS), low molecular weight glutenin subunits (LMW-GS) and gliadins (α/β , γ and ω). All fractions were quantitatively compared on the basis of their pixel volumes (UVIpro 12.5 software). Flours were plasticized and filmed according to Puglia et al. (2015). The films, having an average thickness of 300 ± 50 μm , were tested for tensile properties (elastic modulus, E; tensile strength at break, σ_b ; elongation at break, ϵ_b) as in Puglia et al. (2015). The morphology of grains, flours and films was studied by FESEM images.

Results

Differences in alveographic parameters between N treatments were much greater than expected from literature for a same cultivar in the same environment and year (Table 1). These differences appear in agreement with the differences observed in the gluten content (Table 1) and in the absolute and relative abundances of the different gluten subunits and gel bands (data not shown). In particular, in both cultivars, N0 and N60-0, as compared to N0-120 and N300, showed a lower ratio between HMW-GS and LMW-GS, a higher ratio between upper bands and lower bands of HMW-GS, a lower ratio between the upper bands and the lower bands of LMW-GS, a higher ratio between HMW-GS and upper bands of LMW-GS, and a lower abundance of ω -gliadines (data not shown). FESEM images of grains (not shown) revealed greater amount of proteins around starch granules in N300 and N0-120, but no appreciable dimensional differences among treatments in shape and size of starch granules.

As far as tensile properties of films are concerned (Table 1), BL showed higher σ_b , lower ϵ_b , and higher E values than BR. Within each cultivar, the highest ϵ_b values were obtained in N0, followed by N60-0, then N0-120, and, finally, N300. Thus, the ϵ_b would appear to be inversely correlated with crop N availability and total gluten content of the flour. The σ_b was less variable among N treatments, however in both cultivars it was high in N0 and N300 and appreciably lower in N0-120. Tensile properties were consistent with the FESEM images of the fracture surfaces of plasticized films (not shown).

Table. 1 Gluten content, Chopin's alveograph parameters of flours and tensile properties of derived thermoplastic films for the two bread wheat cultivars (Bora and Bologna) grown under four nitrogen fertilization schedules (N0, N60-0, N0-120, N300). Standard errors in brackets. Alveograph parameters are mean outputs of five replicated alveograms as provided by the Alveograph, without SD values

CV	N treat.	Gluten (% d.m.)	P	L	W	P/L	σ_b (MPa)	ϵ_b (%)	E (MPa)
BL	0	6.02 (0.03)	72	78	215	0.92	2.31 (0.22) ^c	40.4 (6.9) ^b	48.2 (2.4) ^b
	60-0	4.54 (0.04)	88	43	166	2.05	1.94 (0.05) ^{ab}	36.7 (1.5) ^b	41.3 (5.0) ^{ab}
	0-120	12.75 (0.01)	74	202	539	0.37	1.73 (0.15) ^a	33.6 (4.0) ^{ab}	33.3 (8.0) ^a
	300	10.00 (0.11)	96	95	380	1.01	2.20 (0.14) ^{bc}	27.8 (2.3) ^a	69.6 (9.4) ^c
BR	0	6.31 (0.01)	83	59	200	1.41	1.29 (0.17) ^a	51.7 (6.7) ^c	19.8 (3.5) ^a
	60-0	5.30 (0.04)	105	32	145	3.28	1.27 (0.17) ^a	45.0 (3.9) ^{bc}	22.7 (7.3) ^a
	0-120	13.14 (0.9)	84	140	361	0.6	1.16 (0.04) ^a	35.4 (3.1) ^{ab}	20.4 (1.8) ^a
	300	9.93 (0.06)	79	114	277	0.69	1.32 (0.14) ^a	31.6 (6.0) ^a	23.0 (3.0) ^a

Conclusions

Results indicate that tensile properties of films were strongly affected by the gluten composition of flours and Chopin's alveograph parameters as affected by the N fertilization schedule. This points out that bioplastic engineering needs to take into greater consideration the variability of biological source material, since even a same cultivar in a same environment can give grains with different gluten composition, due to differences in season climate and N availability. This will help devising agronomic and processing practices to obtain flours or blends for producing films with tailored tensile properties.

Literature

- Benincasa P. et al. 2017. Relationships between wheat flour baking properties and tensile characteristics of derived thermoplastic films. *Ind. Crops Prod.*, 100: 138–145.
- Benincasa P. et al. 2022. Nitrogen fertilization levels and timing affect the plasticity of yield components in bread wheat (*Triticum aestivum* L.). *Field Crops Res.*, 289: 108734.
- Puglia D. et al. 2015. Tensile behavior of thermo-plastic films from wheat flours as function of raw material baking properties. *J. Polym. Environ.*, 24: 37-47.

Shade-Avoidance Response for Enhanced Tolerance to Weed Competition in a Local Wheat Variety

Valerio Cirillo, Claudio Russo, Nausicaa Pollaro, Francesco Antonio Carbone, Antonio Di Matteo, Albino Maggio

Dip. Agraria, Univ. Napoli “Federico II”, IT, valerio.cirillo@unina.it

Introduction

Weeds are among the main constraints for wheat production worldwide, with estimated yield losses around 23% caused by their presence in agricultural fields (Oerke, 2006). Climate change and weed resistance to herbicides will exacerbate weed competitive pressure on crops due to their higher adaptability to different environmental conditions compared to crop species (Cirillo *et al.*, 2018) and a reduced ability of farmers to control them efficiently (Heap, 2023). It is therefore pivotal to find new strategies that can enhance crop competitiveness toward weeds in order to: i) reduce weed-induced yield losses, and ii) reduce herbicide use, which represents the most used class of pesticides in agriculture. A promising strategy for this purpose is to identify specific traits in less domesticated varieties (i.e., local accessions) that can enhance crop competitiveness toward weeds (Ramesh *et al.*, 2017) and eventually consider them for specific breeding programs. This approach may also shed light on the mechanisms allowing crops to better compete with weeds for resources, such as light, water, and nutrients. The aim of this study was to compare the effects of weeds on a modern variety vs. a local one to identify morphological, physiological, and agronomic traits linked with higher tolerance to weed competition.

Materials and Methods

The experiment was performed in the open field at the Department of Agricultural Sciences of the University of Naples Federico II in Portici, (Italy). The modern variety of wheat (*Triticum aestivum* L.) was Rebelde (*Hy*), while the local accession was a Frassineto (*Loc*). We imposed two treatments: weed-free vs. weedy (eight plots per treatment). Weed-free plots were obtained spraying a post-emergence herbicide. At the jointing stage we evaluated plant height, leaf mass per area (LMA), leaf chlorophyll content, and the photosynthetic efficiency (Fv/Fm). At the heading stage, we measured the total biomass accumulation and the spike weight to assess weed impact on growth and productivity. Further analyses on yield and other productive and genetic components are ongoing.

Results

Our results show that *Hy* did not respond to weed-induced shade in terms of height, LMA, chlorophyll content, and Fv/Fm, while *Loc* showed significant variation in all the parameters (+37.5%, -13.7%, +12.5%, and +16.6%, respectively) in response to weed competition (Figure 1-2).

Figure 9. Plant height and leaf mass per area (LMA) of hybrid (HY) and local (LOC) varieties under weedy and weed free conditions measured at the wheat jointing stage. n = 8, ns = not significant; * = p<0.05 according to one-way ANOVA.

Figure 2. Chlorophyll content (Chl) and photosynthetic efficiency (Fv/Fm) of hybrid (*Hy*) and local (*Loc*) varieties under weedy and weed free conditions measured at the wheat jointing stage. n = 8, ns = not significant; * = p<0.05 according to one-way ANOVA.

At the heading stage, wheat fresh biomass and spike weight were significantly affected by weed competition in *Hy* (-49% and -61%, respectively), while in *Loc* the differences were not significant (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Plant height and leaf mass per area (LMA) of hybrid (*Hy*) and local (*Loc*) varieties under weedy and weed free conditions measured at the wheat jointing stage. n = 8, ns = not significant; * = p<0.05 according to one-way ANOVA.

Conclusions

In conclusion, our results show that the hybrid variety (*Hy*) was impaired in its response to weed-induced shade, as indicated by the results on height, LMA, chlorophyll and Fv/Fm (Figure 1-2), which induced growth penalty in terms of total biomass and spike production (Figure 3). On the contrary, the local variety Frassineto (*Loc*) did not show weed induced growth penalty probably because of its responsiveness to shade. It is possible that the selection for short and highly productive wheat plants (i.e., hybrid varieties) induced a trade-off between productivity and adaptation to environmental constraints, including weed competition (Horvath *et al.*, 2023). On the base of these results, the local varieties can represent an important source of tolerance traits to increase wheat competitiveness toward weeds, an aspect that can be taken into account to reduce the use of herbicides in agriculture.

Literature

- Cirillo V. et al. 2018. Crop-weed interaction in saline environments. *Eur. J. Agron.*, 99: 51-61.
- Heap I. 2023. The International Herbicide-Resistant Weed Database. Online.
- Horvath D.P. et al. 2023. Weed-induced crop yield loss: a new paradigm and new challenges. *Trends in Plant Sci.*, 28(5): 567-582.
- Oerke E.C. 2006. Crop losses to pests. *J. Agric. Sci.*, 144: 31.
- Ramesh K. et al. 2017. Role of crop competition in managing weeds in rice, wheat, and maize in India: A review, *Crop Prot.*, 95(14): 21.

Green Mulch for Weed Management in Organic Rice

Giulia Papandrea, Silvia Fogliatto, Zineb Bennani, Ivan Di Furia, Alessandro Beltramo, Francesco Vidotto

DISAFA, Univ. Torino, IT, giulia.papandrea@unito.it

Introduction

Italy is the first rice producer in Europe, both in terms of harvested area and production quantity (FAOSTAT, 2021). Rice production is challenged by weed competition and the repetitive use of herbicides, along with the monocropping system, has led to the selection of herbicide resistant weeds and to water pollution. Organic rice farming has begun to spread in some areas, such as the Vercelli province, and one of the strategies developed by farmers to control weeds without pesticides implies the use of cover crops as a green mulch. This technique consists in sowing a winter cover crop and terminate it in the springtime right after rice seeding, either by shredding or crimping (Fogliatto et al., 2021). Thus, the soil coverage provided by the resulting dead mulch layer can help reducing weed emergence especially in the first stages of rice growing. After the cover crop termination, fields are flooded and the cover crop biomass starts to degrade through fermentation processes. Therefore, in addition to the physical effect provided by the mulch, the compounds released during the fermentation may play a key role in the inhibition of weeds development (Orlando et al., 2020).

The objective of the study is to evaluate the effect of the green mulching on weed development and on rice performances and to make an attempt in identifying the compounds released during the flooding.

Materials and Methods

The study was carried out in 2022 and 2023 and it included both a field (2022) and a mesocosm (2023) trial. The field trial was carried out in two locations (Crescentino and Rovasenda) in Vercelli province (Piedmont region). In Crescentino, the field was seeded in autumn with a mixture of *Lolium multiflorum* (60%) and *Vicia sativa* (40%) at a rate of 60 kg/ha and terminated on April 20 with a disk cultivator, after that rice (cultivar “Selenio”) was broadcast seeded on the standing cover crop. In Rovasenda, the field was seeded in autumn with *L. multiflorum* only (60 kg/ha) and terminated on May 10 with a roller crimper after rice seeding (cultivar “Rosa Marchetti”). Before cover crop termination, the height of the cover crop and the number of weeds were assessed randomly in ten 0.25 m² quadrats; the aboveground biomass of the cover crops was also sampled. Flooding water was sampled four times during the cropping season. Weed density was also assessed in both fields in 0.25 m² quadrats, randomly placed 15 times in the field. On September 15, three replicates of 1 m² of rice were harvested in each field by cutting the whole plant. The overall biomass of the plants was weighted, then the rice grains were separated and weighted. After two days at 70 °C the samples were weighted to assess the humidity and the harvest index.

In order to perform the mesocosm trial in the Department of Agricultural, Forest and Food Sciences in Grugliasco eighteen bins of 1.20 m × 0.8 m × 0.6 m were filled with a 5 cm layer of expanded clay and 43 cm of soil coming from Crescentino paddy fields; cover crops were seeded at a rate of 60 kg/ha on October 4. Six bins were seeded with *V. sativa* to compare two termination techniques, crimping and shredding, with three replicates each. The same approach was also used for *L. multiflorum*, but three extra bins were seeded with this species and terminated as a green manure. Three bins were left with bare soil as a control. The cover crop termination took place on April 20, 2023, after sampling 0.0625 m² of aboveground biomass in each bin and seeding rice variety “Selenio” at a rate of 180 kg/ha. Shredding was performed by cutting the cover crop at the base and then in small pieces of about 5-10 cm, while crimping was performed by flattening the cover crop with a 25 kg weight with a basal area of 0.16 m². For the green manure, *L. multiflorum* was cut in small pieces and buried under a 20 cm layer of soil. After termination, all bins were flooded with a layer of water of about 10 cm and one chamber for gaseous emission measurements was placed in each bin. For the first 10 days, water and gas samplings were performed three times per week. After rice rooting, germination and emergence rates were assessed and the number of rice plants in each bin was counted. All

water samples collected during the growing season in all trials will be analysed to qualify and quantify organic acids and volatile compounds.

Results

In Crescentino field, at cover crop termination *L. multiflorum* was largely prevalent over *V. sativa* (91.5% vs 8.5% plant density). Plant height averaged 27.6 and 40.9 cm for *L. multiflorum* and *V. sativa*, respectively and the cover crop soil coverage was about 60%. The average biomass was 410 g/m² of dry matter, with 48.4% average moisture. Weed density during rice rooting in the field was on average 6.9 plants/m². At the second survey a high presence of *Heteranthera reniformis* was recorded. For this species, due to its growing habit, the abundance was estimated in terms of soil coverage only, which was on average 43%; at the same survey, weed density excluding *H. reniformis* was 5.9 plants/m². In the third survey, *H. reniformis* soil coverage was on average 23% and density of all the other weeds was 7.5 plants/m². Rice yield was 5.9 t/ha (at 13% moisture) and harvest index was 0.58.

In Rovasenda, the cover crop was only composed by *L. multiflorum*; at termination, the height was on average 90.7 cm with a soil coverage of 64%. The cover crop biomass was 415 g/m² of dry matter, with 72.3% average moisture. The first weed survey carried out during rice rooting showed 3.2 weeds/m². The second and the third survey showed a weed density of 19.7 plants/m² and 10 plants/m² respectively. Rice yield was 5.9 t/ha (at 13% moisture) and harvest index was 0.42.

Data on the cover crop development in the mesocosm study in Grugliasco is reported in Table 1. In the bins with the cover crop, weeds were only found in those seeded with *V. villosa*. In the control bins, the biomass was only represented by weeds.

Table 3. Height, dry biomass and moisture of cover crops and weeds in the mesocosm trial

Cover crops	Height (cm)	Dry biomass (g/m ²)	Moisture (%)
<i>Lolium multiflorum</i>	87.1	1886	76
<i>Vicia villosa</i>	90.9	1098 (182 ¹)	84 (82 ¹)
Control (weeds)	67.4	807	83

¹: dry biomass and moisture of weeds grown in bins seeded with *V. villosa*. No weeds were found in bins seeded with *L. multiflorum*.

The number of rice plants per bin was significantly lower in the crimped *L. multiflorum* (12.3 plants) compared to the control (104.7 plants). The other treatments were not different from the control. The number of plants in shredded *L. multiflorum* was on average 45, while in *V. villosa* 67.3 plants were counted in the crimped and 85 in the shredded treatment. This variability was due to the fact that not all emerged plants were able to develop through the dead mulch.

Conclusions

The competitive presence of a cover crop in the intercropping period and its dead mulch during the growing season allowed to maintain weed density within a reasonable range without the use of herbicides. The efficacy is proportional to biomass produced by cover crop, but higher amounts can affect also rice emergence. The compounds released during the biomass fermentation are not well known and further analyses on the organic acids produced are needed to allow a more complete understanding of the mechanisms leading to the inhibition of weed development.

Literature

FAO 2021. FAO Statistical Databases. Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO) of the United Nations, Rome. (Accessed 06-05-2023)

Fogliatto et al. 2021. Cover crop as green mulching for weed management in rice. *Ital. J. Agron.*, 16: 1850.

Orlando et al. 2020. Participatory approach for developing knowledge on organic rice farming: management strategies and productive performance. *Agric. Syst.*, 178: 102739.

POSTERS

Environment x Genotype Influence in the Nutritional and Antinutritional Compounds in Camelina Seeds

Sara Berzuini¹, Federica Zanetti¹, Barbara Alberghini¹, Clarissa Clemente², Silvia Tavarini², Luciana Angelini², Incoronata Galasso³, Sara Pozzo³, Antonella dalle Zotte⁴, Andrea Monti¹

¹ DISTAL, Alma Mater Studiorium, Univ. Bologna, IT, sara.berzuini2@unibo.it, federica.zanetti5@unibo.it, barbara.alberghini2@unibo.it, a.monti@unibo.it

² DiSAAA-a, Univ. Pisa, IT, clarissa.clemente@phd.unipi.it, silvia.tavarini@unipi.it, luciana.angelini@unipi.it

³ CNR- Istituto di Biologia e Biotecnologia Agraria, Milano, IT, galasso@ibba.cnr.it, sara.pozzo@ibba.cnr.it

⁴ MAPS, Univ. Padova, IT, antonella.dallezotte@unipd.it

Introduction

In the last years the interest in camelina [*Camelina sativa* (L.) Crantz] has been growing thanks to its low agronomic input requirement, relatively short growing cycle and the possibility to use the end-products with a multipurpose approach, in fact camelina seed oil has a peculiar fatty acid composition, reporting high values of polyunsaturated fatty acids such as linoleic acid and α -linolenic acid, with high ratio of omega-3/omega-6 (Berti et al., 2016). Moreover, the defatted meal obtained by seed cold pressing can be used for feed applications, replacing the use of soybean meal (Zanetti et al., 2021). In addition to the peculiar oil composition, other parameters might be considered in order to integrate camelina meal as an innovative ingredient for animal feed (Pozzo et al., 2022), for example antinutritional profile should be investigated in order to understand more in depth how genotypes and environmental conditions can influence these parameters and eventually, adjust the agronomical practices to reduce their presence in the final product. In this scenario, three different camelina varieties were evaluated in a three-year trial at two locations in North and Centre of Italy, in the framework of the national project ARGENTO (PRIN 2017).

Materials and Methods

A three-year trial (2019-2022) was established at two different locations in Italy: Cadriano (BO, 44°33'N, 11°23'E) and San Pietro in Grado (PI, 43°33'N, 11°23'E). Three different camelina genotypes were tested: Alan, (supplied by CNR-IBBA, Italy) characterized by a low glucosinolate content, Pearl (supplied by Smart Earth Camelina, Canada) whose fatty acid profile is characterized by low linoleic acid content and improved n-3/n-6 ratio, and Calena (supplied by Saatbau, Austria), a commercial variety used as reference. The experimental design was a split-plot with 4 replicates, sowing date as the main factor and cultivar as

Table 1. Sowing and harvest dates, main meteorological data and GDD in the three growing seasons at both locations.

Location	Year	Sowing time	Sowing date	Harvest date	GDD*	T. min (°C)	T. max (°C)	Precipitation (mm)
Cadriano (Bologna, Italy)	2019	ST1	18/10/2019	30/05/2020	1311	6.3	17.6	446
		ST2	05/03/2020	20/06/2020	1104	8.5	22.0	157
	2020	ST1	22/10/2019	14/06/2021	1444	4.6	15.1	296
		ST2	02/03/2021	21/06/2021	1144	7.4	21.0	98
	2021	ST1	21/10/2021	06/06/2022	1336	4.4	19.0	323
		ST2	02/03/2022	20/06/2022	1246	8.5	21.8	172
San Pietro in Grado (Pisa, Italy)	2019	ST1	10/01/2020	04/06/2020	1277	8.7	16.8	217.6
		ST2	02/04/2020	07/07/2020	1324	13.8	21.7	194
	2020	ST1	09/11/2020	25/05/2021	1277	5.4	15.6	928.6
		ST2	04/03/2021	21/06/2021	1137	8.4	20.9	118.2
	2021	ST1	13/10/2021	27/05/2022	1632	5.7	16.8	484.8
		ST2	07/03/2022	20/06/2022	1213	9.6	21.8	140.8

*t. base 4°C

sub-factor. The trials were sown at both locations in autumn (ST1) and spring (ST2), seeding rate was 500 seeds m⁻² and interrow distance was 13 cm. Nitrogen was applied with the rate of 50 kg N ha⁻¹ at the rosette stage. The main meteorological data from the three growing seasons are summarized in Table 1. At full maturity a central portion of the plot was cut at soil level and threshed with plot combine. Total above-ground biomass, seed yield, seed antinutritional content (glucosinolate, sinapine, phytic acid, etc.), fatty acid (FA) profile, nutritional profile and antioxidant capacity were determined. In particular, antinutritional profile has been analysed in CNR-IBBA (Milan) laboratories while oil FA profile and nutritional content have been surveyed by UNIBO (Bologna), MAPS (Padova), and DISAAA-a (PISA), respectively.

Results

Agronomic parameters and antinutritional compounds were deeply influenced by sowing date, location and genotype whereas nutritional compounds such as flavonoids (total flavonoids content) and antioxidant capacity (expressed as FRAP) were mainly influenced by ST rather than location and genotype (Table 2), corroborating results by Kurasiak-Popowska (2022), where genotype resulted the main factor influencing nutritional compounds. Regarding seed yield, Pearl reported the best performances, with 1.78 Mg ha⁻¹, Alan showed intermediate values (1.74 Mg ha⁻¹), while Calena the lowest yield (1.45 Mg ha⁻¹). Oleic (C18:1) and linoleic acid (C18:2) were influenced by the interaction location x ST, in particular in spring sowing in Pisa both oleic and linoleic acid reported higher values while in autumn sowing a 13% and 12% reductions were observed in oleic and linoleic acid, respectively. Linolenic (C18:3) acid was influenced by sowing time, with higher amounts when autumn sowing was performed (36% vs. 33%, ST1 and ST2, respectively). Total flavonoids content (TFC) showed higher concentrations when camelina was sown in spring (3.94 mg CAE g⁻¹DW) rather than in autumn (3.55 mg CAE g⁻¹DW), probably due to the higher temperatures occurring during seed filling. Antioxidant capacity was slightly influenced by the sowing time, reflecting the TFC, with mean values of 27.64 μmol TEg⁻¹ DW in ST2 and 25.40 μmol TE g⁻¹ DW in ST1. Glucosinolates were mainly influenced by the variety: Pearl reported significantly higher values (32.39 μmol kg⁻¹) while Calena and Alan did not significantly differ (29.66 μmol kg⁻¹ and 28.98 μmol kg⁻¹, respectively). Finally, the phytic acid accumulation showed a significant interaction between location and sowing date: the highest concentrations were recorded in Bologna in ST1 while the lowest values in Pisa in ST2 (28.87 μgPA mg⁻¹ and 21.67 μgPA mg⁻¹, respectively). In general, regarding fatty acid composition and antinutritional compounds, when a significant interaction between location and sowing date was observed, camelina sown in Pisa in spring showed the highest values in oleic (C18:1) and linoleic (C18:2) acids and the lowest contents in antinutritional compounds (Table 2).

Conclusions

Source of variation	DF	Seed Yield	C18:1	C18:2	C18:3	TFC	FRAP	SI	GLS	PA
<i>Main factor</i>										
Location	1	7.60 **	ns	4.20*	37.75***	ns	ns	2.92 .	ns	26.62***
Sowing date	1	29.9***	22.78***	36.57***	ns	4.55*	2.76 .	29.32***	ns	19.28 ***
Variety	2	3.99*	132.46***	91.20 ***	ns	ns	ns	3.31*	25.24***	ns
<i>Interaction</i>										
LocxST	1	15.38***	3.60.	4.92*	ns	ns	ns	9.95**	3.27 .	11.78 ***
LocxVar	2	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns
STxVar	2	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns	7.49 ***	ns

Table 2. Analysis of variance. F values and significance are shown. Signif. codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1. LocxST- location x sowing time, LocxVar- Location x Variety, STxVar- Sowing time x Variety, DF- degrees of freedom, Seed Yield- Seed Yield (Mg ha⁻¹), C18:1- oleic acid, C18:2- linoleic acid (LA), C18:3- α-linolenic acid (ALA), TFC- total flavonoids content, FRAP- ferric reducing antioxidant power, SI- sinapine, GLS- glucosinolates, PA- phytic acid.

This three-year study confirmed the feasibility of camelina cultivation in different environments in Italy both when autumn and spring sowing was performed. Regarding seed yields Pearl was the best performer, while FA profile and antinutritional content were influenced by the environment and the agronomic technique (in particular sowing time).

Acknowledgments

This study is part of the project ARGENTO – Agronomic and genetic improvement of Camelina (*Camelina sativa* (L.) Crantz) for sustainable poultry feeding and healthy food products, which received funding by PRIN2017 (2017LZ3CHF_001).

Literature

- Berti M et al. 2016. Camelina uses, genetics, genomics, production, and management. *Ind. Crop. Prod.*, 94: 690–697.
- Kurasiak-Popowska D. 2022. An Analysis of Variability in the Content of Phenolic Acids and Flavonoids in Camelina Seeds Depending on Weather Conditions, Functional Form, and Genotypes. *Molecules*, 27(11): 3364.
- Pozzo S. et al. 2022. Evaluation of nutritional and antinutritional compounds in a collection of Camelina sativa varieties, *J. Crop Improv.*, 37(6): 934-952.
- Zanetti F. et al. 2021. Camelina, an ancient oilseed crop actively contributing to the rural renaissance in Europe. A review. *Agron. Sustain. Dev.*, 41: 2.

Biochar as Soil Amendment to Improve the Sustainability of the Intensive Dairy Cattle Farming

Lamberto Borrelli¹, Massimo Valagussa², Alberto Tosca³, Daniele Cavalli¹, Alessandra Lagomarsino⁴, Carla Scotti¹

¹ CREA-ZA, Lodi, IT, lamberto.borrelli@crea.gov.it, daniele.cavalli@crea.gov.it, carla.scotti@crea.gov.it

² MAC SRL, Vertemate, IT, info@maclab.it

³ Fondazione Minoprio, Vertemate, IT, a.tosca@fondazioneminoprio.it

⁴ CREA-AA, Firenze, IT, alessandra.lagomarsino@crea.gov.it

Introduction

The intensive dairy cattle farming systems, e.g., those of the Italian Po Valley, produce N surpluses that the Nitrates Directive (91/676/EEC) regulates; however, a more thorough exploitation of the nutrients present in animal effluents is a key point to improve the sustainability of intensive livestock production. Anaerobic digestion of animal effluents and, more recently, biomass pyrolysis are two practices able to simultaneously produce renewable energy and by-products of agronomic value: the digestate (soil fertilizer) and the biochar (soil amendment). The objective of the present research is to investigate the actual impact of biochar application, alone and in association with organic (digestate and bovine slurry) and mineral fertilization, in the intensive rotation system silage maize-Italian ryegrass and in the sandy loam soil of the western Po Valley. In particular, the results of a 5-cycle trial (from 2018-19 to 2022-23) on DMY and soil parameters (C_{org}) will be presented here.

Materials and Methods

Two types of biochar (BG, BP) at the application rates of 10 (D1), 20 (D2) and 40 (D3) t ha⁻¹ DM were incorporated into the soil. The biochar was used alone (B treatment) and associated with digestate, bovine slurry and mineral fertilization (BDig, BSlu and BMin treatments, respectively). The same fertilization treatments without biochar (Dig, Slu, Min) and the unfertilized control (CTR) were also included. Silage maize fertilization was calculated to provide 170 kg ha⁻¹ N available for plant (100% of NH₄-N and 50% of organic N fraction of the organic fertilizers); P₂O₅ (80 Kg ha⁻¹) and K₂O (180 Kg ha⁻¹) were added to urea (BMin). No fertilization was applied to the Italian ryegrass. All other cultural practices are described in Scotti et al. (2022) and Lagomarsino et al. (2022). The experiment design was a split-split-plot arrangement, with treatments as main plots (162 m²), biochar types as subplots (81 m²) and biochar rates as sub-subplot (27 m²). Plots were arranged in two blocks. Soil sampling was performed in spring 2018 before biochar application (cycle 0) and in spring 2023 (cycle 5) at sub-subplot basis. Soil samples were taken from the 0-30 cm layer; at cycle 5, a further sampling from the layer 30-50 cm was taken in the treatments B, BDig treated with BP at the rates D2 and D3 and in the corresponding treatments without biochar CTR and Dig. The parameters C_{org} , total N, C/N, exchangeable K, assimilable P₂O₅ were analysed; only C_{org} data are presented here.

Results

The different treatments did not significantly affect silage maize DMY (averages of cycles 1-4); however, the biochar incorporation decreased the silage yield (-9%) when associated with mineral fertilization (BMin) while did not affect yield in association with organic fertilizers (BDig, BSlu) or when unfertilized (B) (Fig. 1). The effect of biochar on Italian ryegrass yield was significant and positive when associated with organic fertilization (BDig and BSlu, +24%) and in the unfertilized control (B, +28%) while not significant (BMin, +16%) in the case of mineral fertilization (Fig. 1). Then, the biochar incorporation mainly acted as a stock of C_{org} available for the unfertilized ryegrass crop following the fertilized maize silage. In fact, in the 5 cycles of rotation the soil C_{org} content significantly increased in all the treatments with biochar (BDig +30%,

Fig. 1. Silage maize and I. ryegrass DMY (averages of cycles 1-4).

* $P \leq 0.05$; ns= not significant with linear contrasts.

(Dig and CTR) was present in both the layers 0-30 and 30-50 cm (Fig. 3). This indicates that a significant migration of C_{org} in the layer 30-50 cm not interested by tilling has occurred.

Fig.2. Soil C_{org} content (0-30 cm layer) prior to biochar incorporation (cycle 0) and in cycle 5.

Fig.3. Soil C_{org} content in cycle 5 at the soil layers 0-30

and 30-50 cm depth. * $P \leq 0.05$ with linear contrasts.

‡ $P_{0.05} < P < 0.06$; * $P \leq 0.05$; ** $P \leq 0.01$; ns= not significant with linear contrasts.

BSlu +10%, BMin +19%, B +21%) while significantly decreased in Min (-7%) and CTR (-8%) and remained stable in Slu (Fig.2). Bovine slurry was found to simply maintain soil C_{org} content compared with the increase determined by manure incorporation in a previous 12-yr trial (Tomasoni et al., 2009).

After 5 cycles of rotation and at higher rates (20 and 40 t ha⁻¹ DM) of biochar incorporation, a significant difference in C_{org} content between the treatments with (BDig and B) and without biochar

Conclusions

The biochar incorporation had the main effect of creating a significant C_{org} stock into the soil involving also deep soil layers not interested by tilling.

The enhanced soil C_{org} content involved an increase of CEC (Scotti et al., 2022) that is of particular interest in the intensive dairy cattle farming and sandy loam soils of western Po Valley for enhancing nutrient sorption.

Literature

Tomasoni et al. 2009. Effetti di Avvicendamenti Foraggeri e Gestione dei Reflui Zootecnici sulla Sostenibilità delle Produzioni. Atti XXXVIII Convegno SIA (M.Bindi Ed.), Firenze (IT), 21-23.

Lagomarsino et al. 2022. Mitigation of GHG emission from soils fertilized with livestock residues. *Agronomy*, 12: 1593.

Scotti et al. 2022. Agroenvironmental performances of biochar application in the mineral and organic fertilization strategies of maize-ryegrass forage system. *Agriculture*, 12: 925.

Research Application of Land Parcel Identification System Data: a Systematic Literature Review

Antonio Bruno¹, Philippe Martin², Elisa Marraccini¹

¹ DI4A, Univ. Udine, IT, bruno.antonio@spes.uniud.it, elisa.marraccini@uniud.it

² UMR SADAPT, Université Paris-Saclay, INRAE, AgroParisTech, UMR SAD-APT, 91120, Palaiseau, FR, philippe.martin@agroparistech.fr

Introduction

To address the different issues related to agricultural management, it is required to dispose of reliable and spatially explicit source of data to describe and map cropping systems. This is of particular importance in the agricultural regions characterized by a high diversity of cropping systems or a high land fragmentation as such the Mediterranean areas (Debolini et al., 2018). Among the existing different data sources, Land Parcel Identification System (LPIS) has already been used for several and wide purposes: from modelling drivers of farming system trajectories in per-urban areas (Ruiz-Martinez et al., 2022), to mapping crop types by combining temporal statistical metrics of satellite images time series with LPIS data (Asam et al., 2022). In this context, our research aimed to understand which, where and how LPIS data are used, to assess their research potential and issues encountered using LPIS as data source.

Materials and Methods

We conducted a systematic literature review, using the PRISMA protocol (Page et al., 2021). We choose the query string TITLE-ABS-KEY ("LPIS" OR "Land Parcel Identification System") AND (agr* OR farm* OR crop*) which was performed on Scopus database the 8th of April 2023. We decide to consider records from the first paper published to the end of 2022 for the replicability of the research. Then, we included LPIS in extended form too, to avoid possible loss of scientific papers due to the presence of national LPIS acronyms instead of “LPIS”. The second part of the string concern three terms that characterise an application in agronomic research. After a quick reading of abstracts and full text, when available, we set up a scheme to fulfil with main information collected from the papers. The data analysis used was based on a grid including the temporal and spatial levels of the application, the topics, the case study and the ancillary database used with LPIS. Were also included the case study country, the publication year, the source of the paper and the thematic areas considered.

Results and discussion

The first output was of 183 papers, from this we excluded 55 papers because “LPIS” in the short form, did not mean “land parcel identification system”. We read remaining 128 papers, in order to collect information to fill standardized form with the main information already mentioned. Performing full text readings, we removed other 8 records for language and 17 because of the unavailability of the full text.

Analysing temporal scale, we distinguished studies that used more than 1 year of LPIS data (33%), those that used only 1 year of LPIS data (45%) and those ones that did not use any LPIS year (22%). For spatial level we structured the categories according to the extension of areas studied: national (24%), regional/local (57%) and no spatial scale (19%). While topics were divided in agricultural related topics (22%), environmental-related topics (36%) and remote sensing-related topics (42%). To assess the compatibility of LPIS with different ancillary data sources we divided them in the following way: cadastre/census (9%), Copernicus (6%), thematic database (24%), Remote Sensing - Sentinel (18%), Remote Sensing - other (17%) and no ancillary data (26%). Records with no temporal scale and no spatial level (22% of total number of records considered) match each other in 83% of cases. Moreover, it came out that, inside this group, ancillary data were not used in 74% of cases. The majority of pluriannual records dealt with agricultural related topics, mainly farmland dynamics. Instead, one-year LPIS use records concerned remote sensing applications (41% of the papers). Then, national records seemed to be involved in environmental-related topics, usually the authors recur to thematic databases (e.g., soil type maps). When the studies

concerned spatial scales lower than national, we found that remote sensing-related topics were prevailing on the other topic areas, that are essentially equally distributed.

Finally, in table 1 are shown the number of records per study country. It is remarkable that more than 50% of records are concentrated in only 9 countries on 28. Table 2 shows the numbers of publications in the last 10 years. Even if the oldest publication in this literature review dates to 2002 there was an increase in the rate of publication in the last 10 years with 85% of all records concerning LPIS.

Table 4- Principal case study areas (9 countries on 28).

Case study	France	Czech Republic	Slovakia	Spain	Germany	Turkey	Hungary	Ireland	Poland
n° of records	18	11	9	8	7	7	5	5	5
%	15%	9%	8%	7%	6%	6%	4%	4%	4%

Table 5- Number of publications using LPIS in last 10 years, percentage of the total number of identified publications, cumulative percentage starting from last year.

Year	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022
n° of pub.	8	4	7	12	6	1	12	11	12	10	17
Percentage of the total n° of identified pub.	7%	3%	6%	10%	5%	1%	10%	9%	10%	9%	15%
Cumulative percentage starting from last year (2022)	85%	78%	75%	69%	59%	54%	53%	43%	34%	24%	15%

Conclusions

By this review it comes out that LPIS data are used in different ways in agricultural research. Moreover, it is also notable that LPIS data can require some adjustments, due to the specific aim, before the use. In addition, combining LPIS and artificial intelligence for land use/cover changes detection could be an interesting combination to investigate on farm-dynamics and on environmental services. One of the issues highlighted in LPIS data use is related to the legal availability of data, this could be a limitation in some countries. In conclusion, LPIS database appears to be an enticing source of data for agronomic studies, environmental studies and more but, its limitations related to the privacy of the data and the fixing process sometimes required discourages its use.

Literature

Asam et al. 2022. Mapping Crop Types of Germany by Combining Temporal Statistical Metrics of Sentinel-1 and Sentinel-2 Time Series with LPIS Data. *Remote Sens.*, 14: 2981

Debolini et al. 2018. Land and farming system dynamics and their drivers in the Mediterranean Basin. *Land use policy*, 75: 702-710.

Page et al., 2021. The PRISMA 2020 statement: an updated guideline for reporting systematic reviews. *Int. J. Surg.*, 88: 105906.

Ruiz-Martinez et al. 2022. Modeling drivers of farming system trajectories in Mediterranean peri-urban regions: Two case studies in Avignon (France) and Pisa (Italy). *Agricultural Systems*, 202: 103490.

Effect of Legume Species Rotation on Durum Wheat Production in Mediterranean Climate

Claudio Calia, Luigi Tedone, Claudia Ruta, Cataldo Pulvento, Giuseppe De Mastro

Dep. Soil, Plant and Food Science, Univ. Bari "Aldo Moro", IT, luigi.tedone@uniba.it, claudia.ruta@uniba.it, cataldo.pulvento@uniba.it, giuseppe.demastro@uniba.it

Introduction

Cereal crops show a better yield response when placed in rotations with legume crops (Tedone et al., 2022; Preissel et al., 2015; Yusuf et al., 2009). Beneficial influence of legumes appears to be linked to various positive effects, specifically residual soil nitrogen availability, which improves the productivity and quality on subsequent cereal; increasing of soil organic matter, partly deriving from the decomposition of residues from legume crops; improved availability of phosphorous for crops grown in rotation; improvement of the physical properties of the soil, due to the positive effect of the root exudates of legumes (Siddique et al., 2005).

The beneficial effect of legumes are linked also to the soil and climatic conditions and the leguminous crop cycle, whose cycle duration influences the time of nitrogen availability and the time of mineralization of the organic matter in the soil.

Precisely the aspect linked to the quantification of the positive effect that the legume species exerts on the cereal in rotation represents an extremely interesting aspect, in order to identify a more suitable combination between legume and cereal which guarantees sustainability on the following crop.

The described experiment aims to provide information on the best combination between winter legume species (chickpea, faba bean, lentil, pea) and durum wheat in Mediterranean climate.

Materials and Methods

The study refers to the seasons 2020/21 and 2021/22, and was carried out in Gravina in Puglia, southern Italy (40°53'N, 16°17'E, 456 m asl). The site is typical of a semi-arid Mediterranean climate, with an average annual rainfall of 450 mm concentrated mainly during October-May, and with an average annual temperature of 13.5°C.

Soil is silty loam, with good fertility. The previous crop was durum wheat. In 2020/21 season 10 different landraces and varieties of broad beans, chickpeas, peas and lentils were compared according to the split plot design with species as main factor and varieties/landraces as secondary factor. wheat cultivation (cv Antalis) was used as control. Wheat, Faba beans and peas were sown in December 2020 while chickpeas and lentils were sown in February 2021. In 2021/22 season, in all the plot was sowed durum wheat, cv Iride, with sowing effected on 16 of November 2021 and harvest the 7th of July 2022.

For each plot ecophysiological and productive measures were realised for single plot, using a combined plot machine Wintersteiger. On grain samples, productive and quality parameters were measured.

Results

The meteorological trend of the two-year period showed temperatures above the normal, especially during the filling period of the seeds and kernels. In addition, rainfall for the period, in particular 2021/2022, was lower than the poliannual average. These conditions resulted in productions lower than the average of the area, and values of quality of the productions obtained unsatisfactory.

Considering the first season, the 4 compared legumes, peas and faba bean presented an cycle of about 180 days, while chickpea presented a cycle of 160 days. The shorter cycle was measured in lentil, about 140 days.

In terms of grain legume yield of legumes species grown in 2020/21 season, field pea showed the greatest potential in the environmental condition of southern Italy. Field pea produced the greatest seed yield (2.9

Fig. 1 – Legumes yield performace in 2020/21 season.

Fig. 2 – Grain yield of durum wheat according to the legume rotation in 2021/22 season

Fig. 3 – Protein content of durum wheat according to the legume rotation in 2021/22 season

tha⁻¹). The chickpea and faba bean crops presented similar seed yield, respectively 2.2 and 2.1 tha⁻¹, showing a good potential, with variability due to the varieties. Among the grain legume species studied, lentil produced the lowest seed yield (1.0 tha⁻¹), mainly due to the shorter cycle and the need to improved cultivars for this environment.

The result revealed that yield response of subsequent wheat crop was significantly different among the different legume-wheat rotations. In all the case, the performance of wheat after legumes was in all the combinations higher (3.3 tha⁻¹) than the wheat after wheat (3.0 tha⁻¹). The highest wheat grain yield (3.6 tha⁻¹) was recorded in the faba bean-wheat rotation whereas the lowest wheat grain yields (3.1 tha⁻¹) was recorded in the chickpea-wheat and lentil-wheat rotation (fig. 2). The wheat grain yield advantages of the faba bean-wheat and field pea-wheat rotations were 0.6 and 0.4 tha⁻¹ over the wheat-wheat rotation (3.0 tha⁻¹), respectively (fig. 2).

Beneficial effect of legumes was confirmed also by the protein content, one of the main qualitative parameters of wheat, that was higher in all the samples of wheat cultivated after legumes, and presented value of more of 18% in wheat after lentil, chickpea and peas (fig.3).

Conclusions

The preliminary results reported confirm the positive effect that grain legumes present on grown and production of annual cereal crops in rotation and can contribute to the total pool of nitrogen in the soil and improve the yields of cereals.

In our environment, the combination of durum wheat with faba bean and pea appears to be the better rotation in terms of productivity, although the commercial value of chickpea and lentil has to be considered in terms of economic income for farmers.

Literature

Ali S.A. et al. 2019. Wheat response to no-tillage and nitrogen fertilization in a long-term faba bean-based rotation. *Agronomy*, 9(2): 50.

Preissel S. et al. 2015. Magnitude and farm-economic value of grain legume pre-crop benefits in Europe: A review. *Field Crops Res.*, 175: 64-79.

Siddique et al. 2005. Legumes in sustainable cropping systems. *Proceedings of the Fourth International Food Legumes Research Conference, (IFLRC-IV), October 18-22, 2005.* 787-819.

Tedone L. et al. 2023. Long-Term Experiment In Durum Wheat: Effect Of Residues Management And Nitrogen Nutrition Under Different Rotation Systems. *Proceedings of the 51st National conference of the Italian Society for Agronomy.*

Yusuf A.A. et al. 2009. Rotation effects of grain legumes and fallow on maize yield, microbial biomass and chemical properties of an Alfisol in the Nigerian savanna. *Agric. Ecosyst. Environ.*, 129(1-3): 325-331.

Environmental Evaluation of Nitrogen Management Using Self-Driving Robots

Davide Cammarano, Vita Antoniuk, Kiril Manevski, Joory Jin, Yeying Zhou, Mathias A. Nemuar

Dep. Agroecology, iClimate, CBIO, Aarhus University

Introduction

Precision agriculture has been applied for the site-specific nitrogen (N) management by utilizing in-season sensors to detect crop spatio-temporal variability and adjust in-season N input (Mulla, 2013). Several algorithms have been developed for this scope with some being able to predict N uptake within 10-20 kg N/ha (Bean et al., 2018). Although Bean et al. (2018) also pointed out how including weather and soil into machine learning algorithms does not improve the N prediction. In Denmark there is a need to optimize N fertilization but at the same time reduce the leaching and emissions in order to achieve lower environmental impacts and a zero-emission agriculture by 2050. In this sense, crops like potato can benefit from the use of better application of fertilizer. Foliar spray might be able to help keep productivity while decreasing environmental impacts. The proximal and remotely sensed data can be used to map the spatio-temporal variability of crop growth and derive functional relations between N dilution in crops, as well as other soil variables. Self-driving robots for precise leaf surface N application are gaining popularity and offer benefits over soil-applied methods. Therefore, the objective of the proposed project which is part of an ongoing funded effort are to: i) investigate the use of a self-driving robot for precise leaf surface N application and compare it to the performance of the conventional farming techniques; ii) explore the potential of machine learning and AI techniques for N input recommendations in precision agriculture using multispectral data obtained from unmanned aerial systems; iii) evaluate the possibility to use proximal and remote sensors in N leaching predictions.

Given that the project is a newly funded, preliminary results will be presented.

Materials and Methods

An 8 ha field experiment (Figure 1) is used to compare conventional and precise N application methods (using the unmanned ROBOTTI, Agrobot, Denmark) on potato crops in central Denmark in 2023, and for the subsequent 3 years on different crops. Prior to planting, 110 soil samples (at 90 cm depth, 30 cm intervals) were conducted, including texture, organic matter, soil water content. In addition, 110 points at 10 cm were sampled for nitrification potential, denitrifying enzyme activity. Proximal soil sensors, such as gamma ray, electromagnetic conductivity and ground penetration radar were also taken on the same day as the soil sample. 24 suction cups were installed in the field and N will be sampled every 2 weeks (red dots in Fig. 1). On the same points manual chambers for N₂O emissions are also installed. N₂O will be sampled 1, 3, 5 days after N fertilization, then every week. At the same time, soil mineral N, soil water content will be also sampled. Data processing algorithms will be developed for emissions-based farm regulation and to estimate the effect of precision fertilization on N leaching.

Figure 10. Layout of the field. The light blue represent the fertilization made as “business as usual”. The dark blue the robot-based foliar fertilization. The red dots represent the suction cups.

For the in-season fertilization using ROBOTTI, the approach of Peng et al. (2021a) will be used to accurately detect plant N requirement.

Step 1: Determine crop biomass based on f_{Ipar} : Fraction of Intercepted Photosynthetically Active Radiation (Peng et al., 2021b)

Step 2: Random forest regression (RFR) analysis in order to assess crop N status.

Step 3: Critical nitrogen (N_c) dilution curve construction.

N_c : critical nitrogen concentration, minimum nitrogen for maximum dry matter

Results

Given the growing season is ongoing preliminary results include some interesting information from the proximal soil sensors. For example, Figure 2 shows the Ground Penetration Radar results for one transect in the field. And the same day the radar data were taken a detailed soil water content sampling was taken. Overall, it is noticeable that at about 40 cm, for that particular transect there is some change in the radar signal indicating a change in soil structure. And in the same transect the soil water content shows also lower values than other areas. This will be confirmed by the detailed soil sampling done for which results might be available in the coming months. At the same time, crop N uptake, N_2O emissions, soil mineral N and N leaching will be available through this growing season.

Figure 11. Ground penetration radar and spatial soil water content taken in March 2023

Conclusions

This preliminary result indicate a given spatial variability in soil properties in the field that might affect the fate of fertilizer if applied uniformly. In the coming months and year the use of unmanned robot ROBOTTI for foliar fertilization might help reduce N losses (leaching and emissions) and optimize the efficient use of N.

Literature

Bean G.M. et al. 2018. Active-Optical Reflectance Sensing Corn Algorithms Evaluated over the United States Midwest Corn Belt. *Agron. J.*, 110: 2552–2565.

Mulla D.J. 2013. Twenty Five Years of Remote Sensing in Precision Agriculture: Key Advances and Remaining Knowledge Gaps. *Biosyst. Eng.*, 114: 358–37.

Peng J. et al. 2021a. Random Forest Regression Results in Accurate Assessment of Potato Nitrogen Status Based on Multispectral Data from Different Platforms and the Critical Concentration Approach. *Field Crop. Res.*, 268: 108158.

Peng J. et al. 2021b. Environmental Constraints to Net Primary Productivity at Northern Latitudes: A Study across Scales of Radiation Interception and Biomass Production of Potato. *Int. J. Appl. Earth Obs. Geoinf.*, 94: 102232.

Reduction of Sorghum Crop Cycle for Water Saving

Pasquale Campi, Maria Roberta Bruno, Gabriele De Carolis, Anna Francesca Modugno

CREA-AA, IT, pasquale.campi@crea.gov.it

Introduction

Energy crops are currently of great interest and the focus of agronomic research is to identify sustainable strategies to produce high levels of biomass by limiting external inputs. Increasing demand for fresh water resources in the world and the increasing severity of drought by global warming raise great concerns in irrigated agricultural production (FAO, 2020).

This scenario requires the study of agronomic solutions to save irrigation water. In semi-arid environments water is the main agronomic factor to be properly dosed to obtain sustainable production of biomass for the energy supply chain (Campi et al., 2016). One possible scenario is the reduction of the crop cycle through the late sowing of sorghum to make better use of the precipitation of early autumn. The objective of this work is to increase water productivity through deficit irrigation strategies accompanied combined with a shortened crop cycle for biomass sorghum cultivation in semi-arid environments.

Materials and Methods

The experimental field was carried out during the 2018 and 2019 seasons at the experimental farm of the Agriculture and Economic Research Council - Agriculture and Environment Center (CREA - AA), in Rutigliano (Ba, Lat: 40 ° 59 ', long: 17 ° 59', alt: 147 m a.s.l). The soil is clayey and 60 cm deep and the site has a Mediterranean climate characterised by warm and dry summers. Two irrigation treatments (Full irrigation: FI – deficit irrigation: DI) were imposed using a complete randomized experimental design and three repetitions (each block 600 m²). FI treatment restored 100% of the water lost through evapotranspiration (ET) calculated according to the FAO56 approach (Allen et al., 1998). DI treatment by supplying 100% of the ET until the stem elongation stage (46 days after sowing), subsequently sorghum was grown under rainfed conditions. The KWS Bulldozer hybrid was used for the field experiment. In both years the crop sowing was carried out at the end of July with a plant density of 18 plants m⁻². During two seasons, yield, and soil water content (measured by capacitive probes - 10HS, Decagon - installed at 20 and 50 cm depth) were monitored. The seasonal irrigation volumes (I) and sorghum yield data were used to determine the water productivity (WP) for the different treatments.

Results

The evolution in time of the soil water content (mm) into the whole profile showed a similar trend in the two years (Fig. 1) for both treatments (FI and DI). In the FI treatment the soil water content varied between the field capacity and the readily water available threshold. In the DI treatment, from interruption of irrigation until the end crop cycle, the values of soil water content were distributed between readily water

available threshold and wilting point. Only in 2018 there was a temporary increase in the SWC due to rains that occurred at the beginning of October.

Figure 1 – Soil water content (SWC) during two cropping seasons (2018 and 2019) for two water treatments (FI: full irrigation; DI: deficit irrigation). The values of the wilting point (dotted red line), readily water available (dotted green line) and of the field capacity (dotted blue line) are also shown. DAS is the acronym for ‘Days After Sowing’.

Table 1 shows the performance (average of two years 2018 and 2019) obtained from the crop sorghum sown late. The most interesting aspect concerns the increase in irrigation water productivity (WP). The deficit irrigation applied to late sorghum sowing allowed a reduction in the seasonal irrigation volume of 39% and an increase of 22% in the WP value. Biomass with DI treatment has been reduced by 20%, resulting in an irrigation consumption of only 146 mm. Considering that the yield of sown sorghum in May is 20 t ha⁻¹ with an irrigation water consumption of 32 mm (Campi et al., 2016), late sowing allows for an increase water savings to 44% but it is accompanied by a decrease in the yield of 36%.

Table 1: Average performance of the sorghum crop over two years (2018-2019).

Performances of sorghum	FI	DI
Biomass (t ha ⁻¹)	17.4	14.1
WP (kg m ⁻³)	7.5	9.7
Seasonal irrigation volume (mm)	233	146

Conclusions

Late sowing offers a new agronomic solution for biomass sorghum production with limited seasonal irrigation volumes. Indeed, this agronomic strategy enables the reduction or cessation of irrigation from late summer and autumn taking advantage of potential rainfall events, which are typically more frequent during the autumn months. Within the cultivation systems employed in semi-arid environments, biomass sorghum could serve as an intercropping crop.

Literature

- Allen R.G. et al. 1998. Crop evapotranspiration: guidelines for computing crop water requirements. Irrigation and Drainage paper No. 56. FAO, Rome, pp. 300.
- Campi P. et al. 2016. Energy of biomass sorghum irrigated with reclaimed wastewaters. *Eur. J. Agron.*, 76: 176–185.
- FAO. 2020. The State of Food and Agriculture 2020. Overcoming water challenges in agriculture. Rome. <https://doi.org/10.4060/cb1447en>

Effect of Irrigation Scheduling on Yield-Quality and Water Efficiency Indices in Processing Tomato

Federica Carucci¹, Giuseppe Gatta², Anna Gagliardi², Delia Caldarola², Marcella Michela Giuliani²

¹ DAFNE, Univ. Tuscia, IT, federica.carucci@unitus.it

² DAFNE, Univ. Foggia, IT, marcella.giuliani@unifg.it, giuseppe.gatta@unifg.it, anna.gagliardi@unifg.it

Introduction

Processing tomato (*Solanum Lycopersicum* L.) is one of the most representative industrial crops and accounts for the global production of 39 million tonnes. Marketable yield and quality parameters are taking on significant strategic importance in the processing tomato chain (Nemeskéri et al., 2019). Indeed, in some countries such as Italy, the sale price is also determined by the total soluble solids in the fruits, with a premium price for high-quality tomatoes. Tomato has a highly intensive growing system, particularly for its high water-demanding: 400–600 mm of irrigation water, rising due to the ongoing climate change (Giuliani et al., 2019). However, in recent years, we have witnessed a gradual reduction of water reserves for irrigation in quantity and quality. A strong effect of irrigation regime on yield and quality of processing tomatoes has been extensively reported. Therefore, improving irrigation efficiency could help achieve sustainability in water use and contributes to increasing agricultural production's competitiveness. As part of the ongoing project Rewatering (*Looking back to go forward: reassessing crop water requirements in the face of global warming*, financed under the PRIN 2020 funds), the present study focused on the effect of different irrigation scheduling on the yield-quality and irrigation efficiency indices of processing tomato.

Materials and Methods

A field experiment was conducted in 2022 in the Capitanata area, Southern Italy (altitude: 217 m a.s.l., latitude: 41°23'47"N, and longitude: 15°20'04"E), on clay soil (USDA, 1999). The processing tomato, hybrid 'Tayson' (Nunhems Italia Srl), was transplanted on May 19th in paired rows with a plant density of 2.7 plants m⁻². The amount of water to supply at each irrigation event was determined by three different irrigation regimes. The first consisted of a farmer's management (*Farmer*) based on the farming routine and the farmer's intuition. Then, irrigation scheduling based on the soil water content was evaluated with two regimes: *Full* and *RDI*. The water soil content was monitored by Frequency Domain Reflectometry (FDR) sensors placed at three soil depths (0.2, 0.4, and 0.60 m) to better monitor water requirements during the root growth of the tomato crop. The soil hydrological values of field capacity and wilting point were measured, and the irrigation moment was set at 30% of plant-available water consumed. The irrigation water volume was calculated using the water balance method. As for *Full* regime at each irrigation the 100% of irrigation water volume was applied. As for *RDI*, we applied 70%, 100%, and 70% of the irrigation water volume through the following three phenological stages of the crop cycle: from plant establishment to flowering of the first truss; from the flowering of the first truss to fruit breaking colours of the first truss; and from fruit breaking colours of the first truss to harvest. A drip-irrigation system was used, with a single plastic pipe arranged in the middle of each paired row. The amount of water supplied in each irrigation event was measured by flow meters placed on the main irrigation lines of the experimental field. Standard agricultural practices commonly used in the area were performed during the crop season. The crop was hand-harvested when the ripe fruit rate reached about 95% (August 26th, 2022). The marketable fruit yield (t ha⁻¹) and the total soluble solids content (° Brix) were measured on six and ten fruits plot⁻¹, respectively. Then, their combination was used to calculate a synthetic yield quality indicator of tomato production (Yield Quality Index, t ha⁻¹), proposed by Giuliani et al. (2019). Water productivity was then computed considering the ratio between the Yield Quality Index and total water applied to the crop. Furthermore, the Blue Water Footprint was calculated as the ratio between the volume of water supplied with irrigation and the yield (m³ t⁻¹) (Platis et al., 2021). Finally, the ratio between marketable yield and the total water received by the crop (irrigation plus rainfall) was used to define the water use efficiency (WUEy; kg m⁻³). Daily meteorological

conditions were recorded by a weather station placed close to the experimental field. After ANOVA, Tukey's tests detected statistically significant differences among means at the 5% probability level.

Results

Under the *Full* irrigation regime, based on the effective evaluation of the soil water content, has been observed higher significant WUEy value with respect to the *Farmer* regime (figure 1A). The lowest WUEy value observed for the *Farmer* regime confirms that this irrigation management results in excessive water

Figure 1. Effect of irrigation regime on A) water use efficiency (WUEy), B) blue water footprint, C) yield quality index, and D) water productivity index.

water during the plant's less vulnerable phenological phases can lead to a favourable balance between yield and quality (figure 1C). This approach also increases the Water Productivity Index, indicating that the regulated deficit irrigation regime can optimize water use and produce higher-quality products (figure 1D). The Yield Quality Index is proving to be a valuable tool for evaluating industrial tomato production, and it is especially of interest to the processing industry.

Conclusions

Based on initial data from the Rewatering research project, the irrigation method used by farmers must be revised since it showed lower water use efficiency and higher blue water footprint values. However, the RDI regime has produced better quality results, including higher Yield Quality and Water Productivity indices. These findings are significant for the Mediterranean region, where water resources are increasingly scarce, and sustainable usage is crucial.

Literature

- Nemeskéri et al. 2019. Physiological factors and their relationship with the productivity of processing tomato under different water supplies. *Water*, 11(3): 586.
- Giuliani et al. 2019. Identifying the most promising agronomic adaptation strategies for the tomato growing systems in Southern Italy via simulation modeling. *Eur. J. Agron.*, 111: 125937.
- Platis et al. 2021. Analysis of energy and carbon and blue water footprints in agriculture: A case study of tomato cultivation systems. *Euro-Mediterr. J. Environ. Integ.*, 6: 1-10.

Acknowledgments: This research was part of project Rewatering (Looking back to go forward: reassessing crop water requirements in the face of global warming) financed under the PRIN 2020 funds (CUP D73C22000110006).

Agronomical Role of Different Summer Intercropped Cover Crops on Nutrient Uptake, Weed Control and Yield Performance of Bread Wheat: a Three-Year Study in the Po Plain

Paolo Colombatto, Giulia Papandrea, Luca Capo, Raffaele Meloni, Mattia Scapino, Silvia Fogliatto, Amedeo Reyneri, Francesco Vidotto, Massimo Blandino

DISAFA, Univ. Torino, IT, paolo.colombatto@unito.it, giulia.papandrea@unito.it, luca.capo@unito.it, raffaele.meloni@unito.it, mattia.scapino@unito.it, silvia.fogliatto@unito.it, amedeo.reyneri@unito.it, francesco.vidotto@unito.it, massimo.blandino@unito.it.

Introduction

The Farm to Fork Strategy (EU, 2020) outlines new goals to reduce and strengthen the environmental and climate footprint of the agri-food system and its resilience. These goals include reducing the use of pesticides and of mineral fertilizers. In this context, cover crops (CC) could play an important role in soil conservation and improve the sustainability of agricultural systems. CC have been shown to increase soil organic matter, improve soil structure and overall fertility, interrupt pest cycles, and increase plant diversity (Courtland *et al.*, 2021). Furthermore, few studies were carried out in temperate growing areas considering the wheat as cash crop, and the role of CC as solution to reduce mineral fertilization, considering also qualitative traits, and their role in controlling the weed development during the intercropping period.

Materials and Methods

A 3-year field experiment (2020-2023) was carried out on sandy-loam soil in Villafranca P.te (TO), by comparing different summer CC as intercrop of bread wheat. The compared CC were S, Sudan grass (*Sorghum x drummondii*); SV, mixture of Sudan grass and cowpea (*Vigna unguiculata*); VN, mixture of cowpea and niger (*Guizotia abyssinica*). In each year a naturally infested control (NT), without the sowing of CC, and a bare soil treatment (T) with the application of glyphosate to control the development of weed in the intercropping period were also included. The CC were planted a few days after the wheat harvest and straw removal. In the beginning of October, CC were terminated by shredding the biomass and incorporated into the soil by plowing. At the time of termination, the weed occurrence for surface unit was assessed in all treatments. The whole epigeal biomass was weighted, and representative samples were collected and analysed for macronutrient content to quantify their uptake. In the wheat sown in the following growing seasons, a factorial experimental design, with 4 replicates, was set up by comparing the 5 previously reported CC treatments and 3 N rates (0, 90, 150 kg N/ha), applied as ammonium nitrate. A high protein cultivar (Bologna) was used. The NDVI index was detected on both CC and wheat canopy every approximately 7-10 days and used to calculate the AUCDC (Area Under Canopy Development Curve) index, considering the sum of NDVI values during whole crop cycle. Wheat was harvested in July through a plot combine, and grain yield, test weight (TW), thousand kernel weight (TKW) and grain protein content (GPC) were measured for each plot.

Results

Table 1 reports the vegetative index, final biomass and macronutrients uptake for the compared CC. The AUCDC data shows that the CC reported a higher AUCDC index in the intercropping period, compared to the naturally infested soil (NT), mainly characterized by the presence of the weeds *Sorghum halepense* and *Amaranthus retroflexus*. The planting of sorghum (S and SV) reported significantly higher biomass and organic carbon incorporated into the soil, in comparison to VN or NT, but also a significant higher C/N ratio, which suggested a lower mineralization rate for sorghum biomass. N and P uptake were both higher in S, while K uptake resulted higher with the use of VN. The weed occurrence did not differ significantly

among different CC, although all these treatments reported a reduction from 74% to 93% of weed occurrence compared to NT.

Table 6: Comparison of the development, biomass, macronutrient uptake and weed occurrence of different cover crops (CC) planted as intercrop of bread wheat, in comparison to a naturally infested control (NT).

CC	AUCDC	Biomass (t DM/ha)	C/N	N uptake (kg/ha)	P uptake (kg/ha)	K uptake (kg/ha)	Weeds (n°/m ²)
NT	30.8 b	6.8 b	26.0 b	117.0 b	18.3 b	190.4 c	113.2 a
S	38.6 a	12.7 a	40.8 a	156.0 a	33.8 a	266.5 b	12.6 b
SV	38.3 a	12.9 a	43.0 a	137.5 ab	33.4 a	270.0 b	7.5 b
VN	38.3 a	7.2 b	23.1 b	131.4 ab	31.9 a	326.8 a	29.3 b
<i>p-value</i>	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	0.002	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001

Means followed by different letters are significantly different (the level of significance of the p-value is reported in the table)

AUCDC of wheat was significantly and directly influenced by N fertilization rate, but also by the CC factor, which influenced vegetative index inversely proportional to the amount of biomass accumulated into the soil. A similar trend was reported for productive and qualitative parameters: grain yield was highest in the T treatment, where the development of weed in the intercropping period was controlled chemically, while it was lowest in the NT. TW and TKW were found to be unaffected by the N factor, while TW was lower in the NT treatment. GPC and gluten content increased significantly according to the N rate, while all CC treatments, also those with cowpea in mixture (SV and VN), showed lower grain quality values compared to NT or T.

Table 2: Effect of intercrop cover crops and N fertilization on agronomic, yield and qualitative traits of wheat.

Factor	Source of variation	AUCDC	yield (t/ha)	TW (kg/hl)	TKW (g)	GPC (%)	Gluten (%)
Cover Crop (CC)	T	107.9 a	7.6 a	79.5 a	31.9 a	13.7 a	12.5 a
	NT	95.2 b	5.7 c	78.4 b	31.9 a	13.3 a	12.0 a
	S	90.3 c	6.2 bc	79.4 a	32.3 a	12.6 b	11.2 b
	SV	88.6 c	6.0 bc	79.8 a	32.3 a	12.4 b	10.9 b
	VN	91.8 c	6.5 b	79.8 a	32.8 a	12.5 b	11.0 b
	<i>p-value</i>	<0.001	<0.001	0.001	0.553	<0.001	<0.001
Fertilization (N, kg/ha)	0	87.1 c	5.1 c	79.7 a	32.6 a	11.9 c	10.4 c
	90	95.5 b	6.5 b	79.3 a	32.1 a	12.7 b	11.4 b
	150	99.3 a	7.1 a	79.3 a	32.1 a	13.6 a	12.3 a
	<i>p-value</i>	<0.001	<0.001	0.341	0.422	<0.001	<0.001
CC x N	<i>p-value</i>	0.026	0.072	0.022	0.636	0.540	0.643

Means followed by different letters are significantly different (the level of significance of the p-value is reported in the table)

Conclusions

In a temperate growing area, CC intercropped during summer to wheat reported a high biomass yield and good nutrient holding capacity and exert an indirect action in control weed development. All these functions were generally higher when sorghum was included as CC. Furthermore, this experience, carried out after 3-year period, showed controversial effects on the following cash crop, with a probable sequestration of nutrient during the vegetative development of wheat, which clearly affect both grain yield and quality. The experiment will continue, to correctly address the management of the cropping system, with the inclusion of CC, to maximize their ecological and agronomical services, but maintaining a significant contribute to the profitability of the cash crop.

Literature

European Commission (2020). Farm to Fork Strategy: https://food.ec.europa.eu/system/files/2020-05/f2f_action-plan_2020_strategy-info_en.pdf

Courtland K. et al. 2021. Dryland cover crop soil health benefits are maintained with grazing in the US High and Central Plains. *Agric. Ecosyst. Environ.*, 313: 107358.

Adaptability of Three Ancient Varieties of Durum Wheat Cultivated in Purity and as Mixtures to an Inland Hilly Area of Campania Region

Eugenio Cozzolino¹, Ida Di Mola², Lucia Ottaiano², Maria Eleonora Pelosi², Daniele Todisco², Nunzio Fiorentino², Antonio Minoliti², Raffaele Romano³, Mauro Mori²

¹ CREA-CI, Caserta, IT, eugenio.cozzolino@crea.gov.it

² DiA, Univ. Napoli, IT, ida.dimola@unina.it, lucia.ottaiano@unina.it, mariaeleonora.pelosi@unina.it, daniele.todisco@unina.it, nunzio.fiorentino@unina.it, antonio.minoliti@unina.it, mori@unina.it

³ Terramadre Società Cooperativa Agricola, San Giorgio La Molara (BN) IT, raff.romano@libero.it

Introduction

In a previous research, we tested the adaptability of some ancient varieties of durum wheat to cultivation in marginal lands (inland areas) considered their greater suitability for limiting conditions (Di Mola et al., 2021). In the current research, we wanted to evaluate the adaptability of three ancient varieties of durum wheat to an inland hilly area of Campania Region but, in addition to their cultivation in purity, these varieties were also cultivated as mixtures in different percentage and were compared to two modern varieties.

Materials and Methods

The test was carried out at the private organic farm “Paolucci” located in Colle Sannita (BN –South Italy). The experimental design provided for the comparison between 3 ancient varieties of durum wheat (Senatore Cappelli –SC; Marzellina MZ; Saragolla Lucana –SL) cultivated in purity and as mixture at different percentage composition (33% SC + 33% MZ + 33% SL; 50% SC + 25% MZ + 25% SL; 25% SC + 50% MZ + 25% SL; 25% SC + 25% MZ + 50% SL; hereinafter referred to **Mix1**, **Mix2**, **Mix3** and **Mix4**) and 2 modern varieties (Svevo –SV; Pigreco PG). The design was arranged in randomized blocks with 3 replicates per a total of 27 plots; each plot was 20 m². The sowing was made on December 22 2021, with a density of 450 seeds per square meter, and the harvest on July 11, 2022. According to organic cultivation, no fertilizers were added but the wheat was preceded by a legume crop. At the harvest, the following measurements were made: yield and its components, some quality parameters of kernels. All data were subjected to one-way ANOVA by SPSS (version 22, Chicago, Illinois) and means were separated using Tukey’s Test at $p \leq 0.05$.

Results

The varieties Svevo e Pigreco showed the highest yield with 3.5 and 2.4 t ha⁻¹, respectively. Among the ancient varieties and their mixtures, only SC, SL and Mix2 reached 2.0 t ha⁻¹, but only SC was not different from SV and PG (Fig. 1). In terms of culms and spikes per square meter, the differences between the varieties were not marked, only Mix3 had the lowest number of spikes m⁻² and it was different from all other mixtures (Tab.1). As expected, the ancient varieties, cultivated alone or in mixture, were significantly higher than PG and SV, which however had the highest HI, statistically different from the all other treatments (except MZ and Mix4) (Tab.1). As regards the quality parameters of kernels, no statistical differences were recorded for vitreousness and humidity; the shrinking percentage was below 3.5% for all varieties with the lowest value for SV; Mix3 showed the highest 1000 seeds weight and it was different from all other varieties except SC and SL (Tab.2). Finally, all varieties had a high protein percentage, but the best performances were recorded for the four mix and SC (Tab. 2).

Fig. 1. Yield of durum wheat as affected by varieties

Table 1. Yield components (culms and spikes m⁻², plant height and HI) as affected by varieties.

Treatments	Culms n° m ⁻²	Spikes n° m ⁻²	Height cm	HI %
Senatore C.	301.7 ± 15.30 ab	272.7 ± 7.88 ab	106.7 ± 6.01 a	26.0 ± 2.13 c
Marzellina	322.0 ± 32.14 ab	295.7 ± 24.13 ab	73.3 ± 3.33 bc	28.0 ± 1.16 bc
Saragolla L.	258.3 ± 24.88 ab	231.0 ± 10.58 ab	96.7 ± 1.67 a	25.3 ± 1.50 c
Mix1	355.0 ± 16.50 ab	327.3 ± 10.68 a	85.0 ± 2.89 ab	23.8 ± 0.74 c
Mix2	388.3 ± 39.25 a	340.3 ± 39.98 a	90.0 ± 0.21 ab	24.4 ± 2.53 c
Mix3	244.7 ± 30.39 b	198.7 ± 53.94 b	95.0 ± 5.00 ab	22.2 ± 2.69 c
Mix4	324.0 ± 40.29 ab	313.7 ± 32.64 a	85.0 ± 2.89 ab	27.6 ± 1.58 bc
Pigreco	221.0 ± 29.55 b	215.3 ± 31.06 ab	56.7 ± 7.26 c	43.1 ± 0.66 ab
Svevo	271.7 ± 10.09 ab	263.7 ± 3.33 ab	55.0 ± 5.00 c	47.1 ± 1.76 a
<i>Significance</i>	*	*	**	**

In each column, different letter indicate significant differences; *, and ** refer to significant at p < 0.05, and p < 0.01.

Table 2. Quality parameters (1000 seeds weight, and percentage of shrinking, vitreousness, protein and humidity) of durum wheat kernels as affected by varieties

Treatments	Weight g 1000 seeds ⁻¹	Shrinking %	Vitreousness %	Protein %	Humidity %
Senatore C.	53.5 ± 0.17 ab	1.3 ± 0.33 ab	0.7 ± 0.33	18.0 ± 0.33 a	9.0 ± 0.14
Marzellina	32.8 ± 0.07 f	1.0 ± 0.05 ab	1.3 ± 0.33	16.1 ± 0.45 cd	9.3 ± 0.61
Saragolla L.	53.5 ± 0.98 ab	1.7 ± 0.33 ab	1.7 ± 0.33	16.2 ± 0.20 bd	8.7 ± 0.41
Mix1	40.6 ± 1.77 de	1.0 ± 0.58 ab	1.0 ± 0.05	16.9 ± 0.28 ac	8.8 ± 0.45
Mix2	44.1 ± 1.08 cd	2.3 ± 0.33 ab	1.0 ± 0.58	17.3 ± 0.25 ac	9.2 ± 0.33
Mix3	54.1 ± 2.41 a	1.7 ± 0.88 ab	1.0 ± 0.05	17.4 ± 0.18 ac	8.1 ± 0.05
Mix4	36.2 ± 0.66 ef	3.3 ± 0.67 a	1.3 ± 0.88	17.6 ± 0.28 ab	8.7 ± 0.12
Pigreco	47.5 ± 0.68 bc	1.0 ± 0.05 ab	1.0 ± 0.58	14.9 ± 0.03 d	9.3 ± 0.45
Svevo	45.8 ± 0.55 cd	0.7 ± 0.33 b	1.7 ± 0.33	15.3 ± 0.26 d	9.3 ± 0.29
<i>Significance</i>	**	*	ns	**	ns

In each column, different letters indicate significant differences; ns, *, and ** refer to not significant or significant at p < 0.05, and p < 0.01.

Conclusions

Our results highlight that the modern varieties (Svevo and Pigreco) produce more than ancient varieties also in a marginal area (inland hilly) but Senatore Cappelli (ancient variety) reached a similar yield value and a higher protein content of kernels. Further research will can evaluate the agronomic response of these varieties also in different conditions.

Literature

Di Mola et al. 2021. Adaptability of old varieties of durum wheat to a hilly internal area of Campania Region. SIA, 15-17/9/2021

This research was funded by Campania Region PSR 2014-2020 GAL Titerno-Alto Tammaro- Action 16.1.1.2 – Project “Bio&Bio”.

Natural-based Products as Possible Sustainable Alternatives for Cover Crops Termination

Giovanni Dinelli, Lorenzo Negri, Antonio Fakaros, Giulia Oliveti, Sara Bosi

Dip. di Scienze e Tecnologie Agro-alimentari, Univ. Bologna, IT, giovanni.dinelli@unibo.it

Introduction

Pesticides' sales are still on the rise, even where explicit reduction targets have been put forward by governments. In particular, more than 40% of the pesticide annual turnover is occupied by herbicides, constituting the first plant protection market. Among the concrete targets to transform the EU food system, the objective in reducing the use and risk of pesticides and fertilizers by 50% and 20%, respectively, is one of the most ambitious measures that will require the development of alternative and effective solutions ('European Green Deal', 2019).

Over the last decade, about 6.1 billion kilograms of the herbicide glyphosate [N-(phosphonomethyl) glycine] have been applied worldwide. This herbicide has a pivotal role in both the so-called "blue" agriculture and in several schemes of integrated pest management (IPM). Despite being the most heavily applied herbicide in the world, in 2015 glyphosate was classified as 'probably carcinogenic to humans' by the International Agency for Research on Cancer and the renewal of glyphosate's license is still controversial (Mayers et al., 2016). There is an urgent need to move towards sustainable weed management strategies that are much less reliant on herbicide use.

The aim of the present work was to identify some possible alternative treatments for cover crop termination by using less harmful compounds for the human being and the environment than glyphosate based herbicides. In particular, preliminary trials were carried out for testing the herbicidal effects of acetic acid, in combination with mechanical treatment and/or essential oils, in cover crop termination practices.

Materials and Methods

The field experiment to evaluate different cover crop termination methods were carried out in two farms of the Bologna University in 2022: one conventional farm, located in Cadriano (44°33'17.2"N; 11°24'56.7"E) and one organic farm, located in Ozzano dell'Emilia (44°26'03.0"N; 11°28'43.8"E). The experiment was designed as a complete randomized block design, with 3 replicate blocks. Cover crops (mix of *Avena sativa*, *Vicia sativa* and *Vicia villosa*) were planted on October 19, 2021. By mid-April, when the oat was at the middle of the heading stage and the vetch at the elongation stem stage, cover crops were terminated, applying different treatments in the two farms (Table 1).

Table 1. List of cover crop termination methods and applied distribution volumes in the conventional and organic farm (treatment abbreviations are shown in parentheses)

Type of termination	Conventional farm	Organic farm
Vinegar concentrate (acetic acid 20%)	250 L/ha (250_NO_NR)	200 and 300 L/ha (200_NR and 300_NR)
Vinegar concentrate (acetic acid 20%) plus 1% v/v clove-geranium essential oil	250 L/ha (250_O_NR)	not applied
Vinegar concentrate (acetic acid 20%) plus pre-rolling of cover crop	250 L/ha (250_NO_R)	200 and 300 L/ha (200_R and 300_R)
Vinegar concentrate (acetic acid 20%) plus 1% v/v clove-geranium essential oil plus pre-rolling of cover crop	250 L/ha (250_O_R)	not applied
Mechanical termination with chopper	Applied (TRINC)	Applied (TRINC)

The different treatments based on acetic acid were compared with the mechanical termination (chopping) of the cover crop, as "negative control". At 7 DAT, the efficacy of cover crop termination methods was visually assessed through digital image analysis. After 3 weeks, cover crops were incorporated into the soil

with a disc harrow to a 20 cm depth, with two passes. Sunflower was sowed as main crop after cover crop termination and yield was measured at the end of the season, for each different termination treatment.

Results

Efficacy of cover crop termination methods is reported in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Efficacy of cover crop termination methods (abbreviation meanings in Table 1) as percentage of dead vegetation on the total green cover at 7 DAT

Results were different in the two farms, especially in relationship with the different cover crop development. In particular, in the organic farming the cover crop biomass was almost double than in the conventional farm. This condition enhanced the efficacy of mechanical termination in the organic farm (88.6%). In both trials, the higher volumes application of the solutions registered an higher efficacy, especially when it followed a mechanical pre-rolling of the cover crop.

Sunflower yield of the different treatment plots is reported in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Sunflower yield of the different plots (abbreviation meanings in Table 1)

The final yield of the crop wasn't influenced by the different treatments, highlighting that there appear to be no detrimental effects on the crop, compared with mechanical control.

Conclusions

The results confirmed a potential of acetic acid at a concentration of 20% in combination with EOs in cover crop termination. However, the efficacy of the tested treatments was not sufficient to completely dry the green biomass. Additional research activity is required to improve the desiccation of cover crops with tested natural compounds. Probably, the tested solutions would be more efficient as pre-emergence herbicide application, instead of cover crop termination method.

Literature

Mayers et al. 2016. Concerns over use of glyphosate-based herbicides and risks associated with exposures: a consensus statement. *Environ. Health*, 15: 19.

Preliminary Results on the Use of Dark Green Colour Index (DGCI) to Evaluate the Nutritional Status of *Camelina Sativa* (L.) Crantz

Leonardo Ercolini¹, Andrea Berton², Lisa Caturegli³, Nicola Grossi³, Nicola Silvestri³

¹ Centro di Ricerche Agro-Ambientali (CiRAA) “Enrico Avanzi”, Univ. Pisa, IT, leonardo.ercolini@avanzi.unipi.it

² Istituto di Geoscienze e Georisorse (IGG), C–R - Pisa, IT, andrea.berton@cnr.it

³ Dip. di Scienze Agrarie, Alimentari e Agro-Ambientali, Univ. Pisa, IT, lisa.caturegli@unipi.it, nicola.grossi@unipi.it, nicola.silvestri@unipi.it

Introduction

Nowadays, the use of digital radiometric sensors in agriculture is a booming sector. Their ability to acquire quantitative and qualitative data on crops, combined with their ever-increasing versatility, which has made it possible to upload them onto UAV (Unmanned Aerial Vehicle), has made these technologies increasingly used within the most innovative agricultural realities.

The most widely used sensors in the field of Precision Agriculture (PA) are certainly the multi- and hyper-spectral, which, being able to acquire data even outside the visible spectrum, allow the algebraic combination of characteristic spectral bands for the definition of the Vegetation Indices (VIs), useful for highlighting some specific properties of the vegetation (biomass of the canopy, absorbed radiation, chlorophyll content, etc.). The Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI), in this sense, appears to be one of the most used VIs for monitoring the nutritional status of the crop, as it has proven to be very reliable and acquirable in a quickly way.

On the other hand, to calculate this index, it is necessary to use a multispectral camera, which, in addition to its high cost, requires a certain specific know-how both in the acquisition and processing phases, which often make these instruments not very accessible to small and medium-sized farms.

Some recent studies, however, have identified a possible low-cost alternative (1, 2) which involves the use of Red Green and Blue (RGB) images, that can be acquired by any normal camera. This technique is based on the conversion of the RGB values of each pixel into the Hue, Saturation and Brightness (HSB) values, in order to improve the quantification of the green of the image (2), to then calculate a new VIs, the Dark Green Colour Index (DGCI). Nevertheless, if this index is widely used on the turfgrass, its application on field crops is being explored on a limited number of crops. For this reason, this work aims to evaluate the correlation of this index with the NDVI on a crop of *Camelina Sativa* (L.) Crantz. Specifically, the values of the two indices acquired via UAV will be compared to be able to evaluate the two techniques already at an operational level.

Materials and Methods

The study was carried out in May 2023 at the Experimental Centre of the Department of Agriculture, Food and Environment (DAFE) of the University of Pisa (43°40' N; 10°19'E). The RGB and multispectral images were acquired on May 15, 2023 on an experimental field of *Camelina Sativa* (L.) Crantz sown on March 17, 2023. The flight has been carried out using the DJI P4 Multispectral drone (DJI, Shenzhen, China) equipped with six 1/2.9 CMOS sensors, including an RGB sensor for visible light images and five monochrome sensors for the acquisition of multispectral images. The two types of images obtained, were processed and orthorectified through the creation of an orthophoto mosaic using DJI Terra software (DJI, Shenzhen, China). The multispectral orthophoto were then converted into an NDVI map, while the RGB values of the visible images were first converted into Hue, Saturation and Brightness (HSB) values, using GIMP software 2.10.34, and then the DGCI map has been calculated, according to Karcher and Richardson (2003) (2), as:

$$DGCI = [((Hue) - 60)/60 + (1 - (Saturation)) + (1 - (Brightness))]/3$$

The NDVI map was used as an indicator of the nutritional status of the crop, since it had proved to be a reliable tool in a previous work on *Camelina Sativa (L.) Crantz* (3), and the correlation between NDVI and DGCI was studied using Microsoft Excel, considering the values of these indices on 100 pixels.

Results

The DGCI showed a significant correlation with NDVI (Fig.1) ($r = 0.55$). Although, dividing the NDVI into 6 intervals (Tab.1) it emerged that this correlation is mainly due to the relationship present in the intervals 0.4-0.5 ($r = 0.63$) and 0.8-0.9 ($r = 0.66$), while in the others the values of the two indices do not correlate significantly ($r < 0.52$).

Figure 12. graphical representation of the relationship between the DGCI index and NDVI for 100 pixels

Table 7. Pearson correlation coefficients (r) between the Dark Green Colour Index (DGCI) and specific ranges of Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI).

	NDVI (0.4-0.5)	NDVI (0.5-0.6)	NDVI (0.6-0.7)	NDVI (0.7-0.8)	NDVI (0.8-0.9)	NDVI (0.9-1.0)
DGCI	0.63	-0.35	0.12	0.09	0.66	-0.43
p-value	0.01	ns	ns	ns	0.01	ns

Conclusions

This promising index, which has shown excellent results on turfgrass, has however proved to be unreliable for an application in the open field, in this case *Camelina Sativa*. This limit is probably due to the greater radiometric variability present in the images of a crop sown in rows, compared to a turf, due to the greater number of elements present in the image (shaded areas, terrain, etc.). Therefore, while acknowledging the undeniable economic and applicative advantages that this index presents, considering the criticality that have emerged, it does not seem in fact capable of being able to replace the NDVI information on *Camelina Sativa (L.) Crantz*.

Literature

Caturegli L. et al. 2020. Normalized difference vegetation index versus dark green colour index to estimate nitrogen status on bermudagrass hybrid and tall fescue. *Int. J. Remote Sens.*, 41(2): 455-470.
 Karcher D.E. and Richardson M.D. 2003. Quantifying turfgrass color using digital image analysis. *Crop Sci.*, 43: 943-951.
 Clemente C. et al. 2023. Spectral response of camelina (*Camelina sativa (L.) Crantz*) to different nitrogen fertilization regimes under mediterranean conditions. *Agronomy*, 13(6): 1539.

Effects of Arbuscular Mycorrhizal Fungi on Tomato Yield Under deficit irrigation in Greenhouse

Michela Farneselli, Beatrice Falcinelli, Martina Cerri, Lara Reale, Domizia Donnini, Euro Pannaci, Francesco Tei

Dip. di Scienze Agrarie, Alimentari ed Ambientali, Univ. Perugia, IT,

Introduction

Climate change will increase the intensity and the frequency of water stress with adverse effects on crop production. Plant strategies to face future droughts may be enhanced by the application of obligate plant mutualists, known as arbuscular-mycorrhizal (AM) fungi (Mohan et al., 2014). AM fungi have well-documented positive effects on plant growth, nutrient uptake and feeding deterrent compounds (Smith, 2008). The effects of AM fungi on tomato performance and chemical composition of the fruit have been studied in both optimal (Hart et al., 2015) and stressing (Bowls et al., 2016; Silami et al., 2019; Leventis et al., 2021) water condition. These studies found that AM fungi significantly affect the nutrient content of tomato fruits and play an essential role in plant responses to water stress (being potentially associated to greater root water uptake) in agro-ecosystem conditions (Bowls et al., 2016; Hart et al., 2015). On the other hand, the growth of AM fungi and their effect on tomato plants might be affected by soil disturbance, fallow periods, and unpredictable and uncontrolled weather conditions (Mohan et al., 2014). Thus, the aim of this work was to evaluate the effects of AM fungi inoculation in plants grown under controlled greenhouse conditions. Preliminary results of the first tomato crop cycle are hereby reported.

Materials and methods

Cherry tomato plants (*Solanum lycopersicum* L.) were grown in plastic pots in a greenhouse at controlled temperature and humidity. Four experimental treatments (two levels of water regime and two inoculation treatments) were applied according to a randomized block design with three replicates (five pots per block per treatment): Control full irrigated (C, 100% of field capacity and no AM inoculation), limited irrigation (Li, 70% of field capacity and no AM inoculation), Control full irrigated inoculated (C_AM+, 100% of field capacity and AM inoculation) and limited irrigation inoculated (LI_AM+, 70% of field capacity and AM inoculation). The inoculation was administered to the soil one time a week at the recommended dose of Vici Rhyzoteam WG (Koppert) containing 4% of *Glomus spp.*, 0,5% of *Pseudomonas spp.*, 1×10^7 CFU/g *Trichoderma spp.*, 3 % of other vegetable matrices. All treatments were fertilized according to the optimal nutritional requirements. Some physiological and morphological traits were evaluated at the flowering of the third cluster: number and size of stomata (through leaves epidermal peeling), chlorophyll and carotenoids contents and pollen viability (by fluorescein diacetate through epifluorescence microscopy, Pinillos and Cuevas, 2008). The chlorophyll content on leaves assessed by SPAD readings was detected three times during the crop cycle. Upon the proper ripening time, each cluster of fruit was harvested and the fruits were counted and weighed. On the third cluster of fruits, the yield component (fruit yield, number of fruit and mean fruit weight) and the fruit quality parameters (°Brix and pH) were measured on sampled plants. The total yield per plant was also calculated as the sum of the yield from each fruit cluster up to the fourth one. Statistical analysis was performed by a two-way ANOVA.

Results

The application of AM fungi increased the leaves' stomatal number ($28.35 \mu\text{m} \pm 3.52$ in C_AM+ vs $26.96 \mu\text{m} \pm 2.89$ of C) and flower pollen viability (79.2 ± 8.56 in C_AM+ vs 75.71 ± 11.34 of C) under full irrigated conditions. However, none or negative effects were observed under limited irrigation conditions (27 ± 4.35 of LI vs 26.97 ± 3.06 of LI_AM+ for leaves stomatal number; 75.74 ± 7.84 of LI vs $64.06\% \pm 14.83$

LI_AM+, for flower pollen viability). The chlorophyll and carotenoid content (data not shown) and SPAD

Figure 1. SPAD values measured at 15, 30 and 75 days after transplanting (DAT).

readings (Figure 1) were not affected by AM inoculation at any water regime level.

Considering the yield parameters measured at the harvest of the third cluster, a significant yield reduction was caused by the limited irrigation regime (-40% on average among AM treatments), as expected (Table 1). However, the AM inoculation increased the yield by 24% (as an average over the two irrigation regimes) and it was able to mitigate the negative effect of water stress, indeed the fruit yield in Li_AM+ was 21% higher than in Li. A similar trend was observed also for the total yield measured up to the fourth cluster (+18% in Li_AM+ compared to Li, data not shown). The AM inoculation did not affect the number of fruit per bunch and the mean fruit weight (Table 1). The quality traits of fruits (both °brix and pH) were generally affected by

irrigation regime and AM inoculation. In particular, the highest values of total soluble solid contents and pH were observed in treatments subjected to limited irrigation regimes (Li and Li_AM+).

Table 1. Yield (fresh weight, FW), number of fruits, mean fruit weight, and total soluble solid contents (°Brix) and pH measured on fruits at the third fruit cluster.

Treatments	Yield_3° cluster (g FW)	n° fruits	Mean fruit weight (g FW)	°Brix	pH
Control	116	39	3	10.4	4.4
C_AM+	148	47	3	11.6	4.5
Li	71	32	2	14.2	4.6
Li_AM+	86	39	2	12.0	4.6
<i>F test</i>					
<i>Water Stress (WS)</i>	**	<i>n.s.</i>	*	**	**
<i>AM</i>	*	<i>n.s.</i>	<i>n.s.</i>	**	**
<i>WS X AM</i>	<i>n.s.</i>	<i>n.s.</i>	<i>n.s.</i>	**	**
<i>SED (WSxAM)</i>	13.2	6.8	0.34	0.06	0.01

Conclusions

Based on these preliminary results collected by only one crop cycle, AM fungi application significantly affected plant morphology and physiology traits in fully irrigated conditions, while pigments did not change with treatments. The AM inoculation was able to mitigate the negative effect of water stress on yield, while the quality of fruit was mostly affected by the water regime. Further investigations through additional experimental crop cycles, are needed to improve knowledge on the effect of these rhizobacteria on tomato crop grown at different

climatic conditions both in greenhouse and open field environments.

Literature

- Bowles et al. 2016. Effects of arbuscular mycorrhizae on tomato yield.... *Sci. Total Environ.*, 566, 1223-1234.
 Hart, et al. 2015. Inoculation with arbuscular mycorrhizal fungi improves the... *Mycorrhiza*, 25(5), 359-376.
 Leventis, et al., 2021. Arbuscular mycorrhizal fungi enhance growth of tomato under... *Rhizosphere*, 19, 100394.
 Mohan, et al. 2014. Mycorrhizal fungi mediation of terrestrial ecosystem responses to... *Fungal Ecol.* 10, 3-19.
 Pinillos and Cuevas, 2008. Standardization of the fluorochromatic reaction test... *Biotech. Histochem.* 83(1):15-21.
 Smith et al., 2008. Mycorrhizal symbiosis, 3rd edn. Academic, New York
 Slimani, et al., 2022. Impact of a selected mycorrhizal complex and a... *Indian J. Agric. Res.*, 56(6), 696-704.

Effects of Foliar Treatment with Various Types of Biostimulants and Different Frequency of Application on Yield and Quality of Organic Oregano

Davide Farruggia*, Salvatore La Bella, Federico Margiotta, Claudio Leto, Mario Licata, Nicolò Iacuzzi

Dip. di Scienze Agrarie, Alimentari e Forestali, Univ. Palermo, IT, *davide.farruggia@unipa.it

Introduction

Oregano is a perennial medicinal and aromatic plant (MAPs) belonging to *Lamiaceae* family. It usually provides various health benefits for humans due to its antifungal, antimicrobial and antioxidant properties. In the Mediterranean area, this crop is often grown using both low-input farming practices and organic farming methods and it is well-documented that its biomass yield and qualitative characteristics are severely affected by abiotic and biotic factors (Licata et al., 2015; Król et al., 2020). Recently, the research activities carried out in this field have focused on innovative agronomic practices for improving the yield response of oregano and other MAPs. Particularly, the use of biostimulants seems to be one of the most interesting practice due to fact they can represent a promising approach for achieving sustainable and organic agriculture. As stated by Du Jardin (2015), biostimulants are a new generation of products that can be applied to crops increasing and improving the absorption efficiency of nutrients and water and the plant tolerance to various stress factors. They are largely used in the agricultural systems, including conventional, integrated and organic crop production systems. The use of these products is typically viewed as safe for both humans and animals and environmentally friendly and might be regarded sustainable solution to the problems of agriculture caused by man-made climate change (Sabatino et al., 2023). In the last years, these products have been applied on various horticulture crops providing excellent results, however the use of biostimulants on MAPs has been poorly investigated. On this basis, the aim of the present study was to assess the effect of foliar treatments with different types of biostimulants and two frequencies of application on productive and qualitative parameters of Sicilian oregano (*Origanum vulgare* L. ssp. *hirtum*) under organic agriculture conditions.

Methods

Tests were carried out in 2022, at a local farm located in Aragona (Italy) (330 m a.s.l., 37°22'32.71" N, 13°38'33.59" E Google Earth). The soil was classified as Regosol (USDA classification: typic xerorthents). In this study, division of bushes was the method of vegetative propagation for oregano. Plantlings were, then, transplanted in the field at the beginning of spring 2019; the plant spacing was 2.0 × 0.5 m. Plants were grown under rainfed conditions. Weed control was conducted by surface tillage at the beginning of spring and before harvesting. Each treatment was carried out by the first week of April with weekly frequency (F1) for a total of six applications and two-weeks frequency (F2) with 3 total applications. Four different commercial formulations were used for the tests and based on *Eklonia maxima* (B1), *Ascophyllum nodosum* (B2), fulvic acids (B3) and peptides (B4). The control treatment (B0) provided water, only. A portable sprayer with an operating pressure of 250 kPa was used. The experimental design was a randomized complete block with three replications. Each block included 5 plots of 20 m². Treatments (B0-B5) were applied to each parcel randomized in the block. The plots were well spaced in the block; plastic panels were used to delimit each plot and avoid drift during foliar applications. In both years, plants were harvested during the second week of June. At harvest, total fresh yield (TFY) was determined. The plant material was dried in a shaded and ventilated conditions approximately for 10 days at temperature of 25–30 °C. Total dry yield (TDY) was calculated. Essential oil (EO) content was obtained by hydro-distillation of 500 g of dried samples. EO extraction was carried out for about 3 h in accordance with international guidelines. EO content percentage and yield per unit area were determined. Total phenolic content, antioxidant activity, and rosmarinic acid content were also assessed, as described by Lamien-Meda et al. (2010).

Results

The analysis of variance revealed that both main factors and interaction factor had significant effect on all parameters in the study (Table 1). F2 allowed to obtain the highest values of TFY, TDY and EO content. F1 permitted to obtain the highest values of total phenolic, antioxidant activity and rosmarinic acid content. The highest TFY value was found in plants which were treated with Protein Hydrolysates with frequency F2. The highest TDY value was found in plants which were treated with all biostimulants following frequency F2 and with the application of fulvic acids following F1. Foliar application of B3 with frequency F2 allowed to obtain the highest EO content (Table 1).

The highest total phenolic were obtained with interaction B0 × F1, B3 × F1, B4 × F1, B0 × F2, B2 × F1. The highest antioxidant activity were found with interaction B0 × F1, B1 × F1, B4 × F1, B0 × F2, B1 × F2. Foliar application of B4 following frequency F1 and the application of B1 following frequency F2 permitted to obtain the highest value of rosmarinic acid (Table 1).

Table 1. Effect of biostimulants, frequency and their interaction on Total Fresh Yield (TFY), Total Dry Yield (TDY), EO Content, Antioxidant Activity, Rosmarinic Acid.

Biostimulants (B)	TFY [t ha ⁻¹]	TDY [t ha ⁻¹]	EO Content [% v/w]	Total Phenolic [mg Catechin g ⁻¹]	Antioxidant Activity [mg Trolox g ⁻¹]	Rosmarinic Acid [%]
B0	3.2 c	1.5 d	2.8 c	128.5 a	157.2 a	3.0 a
B1	4.0 b	2.2 c	2.9 c	115.7 d	155.7 ab	3.1 a
B2	4.2 b	2.3 bc	3.0 c	121.1 bc	153.8 bc	2.9 ab
B3	4.7 a	2.7 a	3.5 a	117.4 c	150.7 d	2.8 b
B4	4.5 a	2.4 b	3.2 b	121.7 b	152.2 cd	3.0 a
Frequency (F)						
F1	3.7 b	2.0 b	3.0 b	123.6 a	155.9 a	3.1 a
F2	4.5 a	2.4 a	3.2 a	118.1 b	151.9 b	2.9 b
Significance						
B	**	**	**	**	**	*
F	**	**	**	**	**	**
B × F	**	**	**	**	**	**

B0: control; B1: *E. maxima*; B2: *A. nodosum*; B3: Fulvic Acids; B4: Protein Hydrolysates. F1: one week, F2: two weeks.

Means followed by the same letter are not significantly different for $p \leq 0.05$ according to Tukey's test.

** = p -value < 0.01; * = p -value < 0.05; n.s. = not significant.

Conclusions

This study demonstrates that the foliar application of different biostimulants permits to obtain an increase in biomass yield and EO content in oregano grown under organic farming conditions. Furthermore, a limited number of foliar applications seems to be sufficient to obtain the highest yield values. The application of biostimulants had significant effect on the quality of obtained extract. The use of biostimulants can improve the yield parameters on oregano when growing under organic farming practices. Further research is, however, required to assess the effect of biostimulants on the qualitative characteristics of EO.

Literature

- Licata M. et al. 2015. Study of quantitative and qualitative variations in essential oils of Sicilian oregano biotypes. J. Essent. Oil Res., 27(4): 293-306.
- Król B. et al. 2020. Biomass production, active substance content, and bioaccessibility of Greek oregano (*Origanum vulgare* ssp. *hirtum* (Link) Ietswaart) following the application of nitrogen. Ind. Crop. Prod., 148: 112271.
- Du Jardin P. 2015. Plant biostimulants: Definition, concept, main categories and regulation. Sci. Hortic., 196: 3-14.
- Sabatino L. et al. 2023. *Ecklonia maxima*-derivate seaweed extract supply as mitigation strategy to alleviate drought stress in chicory plants. Sci. Hortic., 312: 111856.
- Lamien-Meda A. et al. 2010. Investigation of antioxidant and rosmarinic acid variation in the sage collection of the genebank in Gatersleben. J. Agric. Food Chem., 58(6): 3813-3819.

2D-NANO MAD PLANTS: a PRIN project on the Effects of 2D-nanomaterials on seed plants reproduction

Guido Fellet¹, Fabiano Miceli¹, Mario Baldini¹, Iris Aloisi² and Mauro Tretiach³

¹ Dep. Agricultural, Food, Environmental and Animal Sciences, Univ. Udine, IT, guido.fellet@uniud.it; fabiano.miceli@uniud.it; mario.baldini@uniud.it

² Dep. Biological, Geological, and Environmental Sciences, Univ. Bologna, IT, iris.aloisi2@unibo.it

³ Dep. Life Sciences, Univ. Trieste, IT, tretiach@units.it

Introduction

Since the discovery of graphene in 2004, two dimensional nanomaterials (2DNms) have been used for to develop many innovative 2D-Nms-enabled products. This could result in the release of 2D-Nms into the environment throughout their whole life-cycle. 2D-Nms are easily aerodispersed and can eventually land on plants as well as soils. Varying effects of 2D-Nms, especially of graphene-based materials have been observed on plants, but little is known about their effects on plant sexual reproduction. It was recently demonstrated that graphene oxide, as well as high concentrations of the less reactive few-layer graphene or K-muscovite (mica) might affect pollen germination.

The project 2D-NANO MAD PLANTS, conceived by three research units (RUs) from different universities (University of Trieste, the leading RU; Principal Investigator: Prof. Mauro Tretiach; University of Bologna; Associated Investigator: Dr. Iris Aloisi and University of Udine; associated investigator: Prof. Guido Fellet), intends to investigate the impact of 2DNms as potential future environmental pollutants, on the sexual reproduction of seed plants, a key biological process for both terrestrial ecosystems and crops economy.

In particular, the project will test:

1. the capability of female flowers of anemophilous plants to intercept airborne 2D-Nms;
2. the effects of 2D-Nms on pollen performance with focus on vesicle trafficking, cytoskeleton activity, ROS and Ca²⁺ homeostasis during *in vitro* pollen tube growth;
3. the internalisation of 2D-Nms by pollen tube and stigmatic surfaces;
4. the pollen-stigma interaction *in vivo*;
5. the performance and quality of the first filial generation seed progeny derived from plant reproductive structures exposed to 2D-Nms.

Materials and Methods

The project 2D-NANO MAD PLANTS will study the effect of the following 2DNms: graphene oxide, Boron nitride, Molybdenum disulphite, and mica. *Cannabis sativa*, *Corylus avellana*, *Nicotiana tabacum* and *Zea mays* are the selected species. The project is organised in 6 working packages (WP1-6):

- WP1 aims at revealing possible interference mechanisms of 2D-Nms with the processes of pollen tube growth and defining standard protocols concerning the evaluation of pollen performance via *in vitro* studies.
- WP2 will integrate the information with observations on the interception of airborne 2D-Nms particles by the stigmatic surfaces, their internalisation by the stigmatic epidermis and pollen, and the subsequent interference that 2D-Nms might cause to the germination of pollen deposited on the stigmatic surface.
- WP3 is focused on the study of seed setting of the parental generation and characteristics of the following generation, i.e. the seedlings from seeds derived from the fertilisation process in the presence of different levels of the four 2D-Nms. To date, there are neither data concerning the effects of flower exposure to 2D-Nms in terms of fruit and seed production. Field test will be conducted to identify the effects on the seed production due to the exposure to 2D-Nms.
- The aim of WP4 is the definition of the hazard potential for each of the tested 2D-Nms, evaluated on the basis of all collected data;
- WP5 and WP6 are logistical WPs, being devoted to the dissemination of results and the project management, respectively.

The RUs involved in 2D-NANO MAD PLANTS will receive support from two foreign research institutions and two national research centres: the Centre National de la Recherche Scientifique (CNRS, Strasbourg, France) for the provision of up-to-date data on the environmental fate of 2D-Materials; the Council for Research in Agriculture and Analysis of Agricultural Economics (CREA, Bologna) for support in skills and facilities upon request; the Department of Organic Chemistry (University of Castilla - La Mancha, Ciudad Real, Spain) for the chemical-physical characterisation of 2D-Nms; the Regional Agency for Rural Development (ERSA, Pozzuolo del Friuli, UD) for sharing expertise, skills and contribute to the dissemination activities.

Results and Conclusions

The project started on the 8th of May, 2022 and both lab and field trials are ongoing. The results of this innovative and interdisciplinary project will provide the knowledge to predict possible adverse environmental outcomes deriving from a large scale introduction of 2D-Nms-enabled products in the market which can also have negative impacts on the crop production, as well.

Furthermore, results may be used to plan the development of new technologies, applications and objects using a “safe-by-design” approach, which will mitigate the potential environmental hazards from the initial phase of a 2D-Nms enabled product’s life-cycle .

Acknowledgements

The authors acknowledge funding of the Research Projects of National Relevance (PRIN) programme (Prot. 2020KRY7RB)

Tenebrio molitor Frass as Organic Fertilizer: Results from a Germination Test on Three Crops and a Pot Experiment on Sunflower

Guido Fellet, Alessandro Foscari, Luisa Dalla Costa

Dep. Agricultural, Food, Environmental and Animal Sciences, Univ. Udine, IT, guido.fellet@uniud.it;
alessandro.foscari@uniud.it; luisa.dallacosta@uniud.it

Introduction

In the last century, the world population has increased very rapidly reaching 7.0 billion in 2011 while it was less than 2 billions at the beginning of the XX century. Recent estimates foresee a pick of 9.7 billion in 2050. This will increase the demand for resources like water, food, and energy. Hence, the food production will need to drastically increase (70% by 2050 and double or triple by 2100), while trying to decrease the environmental impact of food production activity (Poveda, 2021). Rearing insects for mass consumption has been developing much interest due to their high nutritional value and the chance they offer in converting efficiently organic matter, especially waste, into protein (Houben et al., 2022). Despite insect production has a much smaller ecological footprint in terms of land and water use and greenhouse warming potential compared to the production of chicken, pigs and cattle, the process is associated with high quantities of insect excreta (frass). Finding an efficient valorization of such wastes is of great interest. The aim of this work is to verify the effects of frass from *Tenebrio molitor* on crop species as a potential organic fertilizer from a perspective of circularity. A first germination test was carried out to test the effects of frass on four crops at different concentrations and a second experiment with sunflower has been set up to verify the applicability of frass as organic fertilizer.

Materials and Methods

The germination test was designed following Emino & Warman (2004) to verify the effects of different doses of frass from *T. molitor* (3.90% N; 1.39% P; 1.55% K). Commercial topsoil Brill® 1 (Agrochimica S.p.A.; pH=6±0.5; CE=0.5 dS/m) was mixed with the 5 doses of frass (6.25, 12.5, 25, 50 and 100%_{DW/DW}) and the sole topsoil was used as control treatment. Eight seeds (n=4 replicas) of *Helianthus annuus* (sunflower), *Solanum lycopersicon* (tomato), *Lactuca sativa* (lactuca) and *Lepidium sativum* (cress) were sowed in 0.2L-pots and let germinate for 14 days (12h:12h day:night). At the end of the growing period, the germination % was calculated as germinated seeds on frass: germinated seeds on control ratio and the seedlings biomass was measured, as well. The second experiment, was set up with 7kg of soil in pots (pH=6.8±0.7, CE=927±26 $\mu\text{S cm}^{-1}$, %N=0.33±0.01; C%=3.14±0.12; sand =54%, silt=24%, clay=22%) to verify the effects of the application of Frass to sunflower. The following treatments were considered: (i) full dose of frass (0.7%_{DW/DW}) calculated to provide the 120 kg ha⁻¹ of N, 43 Kg ha⁻¹ P and 47 Kg ha⁻¹ K (treatment name=*Frass*); (ii) the same amounts of N, P and K were provided with mineral fertilizer (Ca(NO₃)₂, Ca₃(PO₄)₂, KNO₃) (treatment name=*NPK*); (iii) 50% of the dose of N, P and K were provided with frass and 50% with mineral fertilizers (treatment name=*Frass/NPK*). No fertilization was administered to the control treatments. During the growth it was measured the height of plants and the growth stages according to BBCH scale.

Results

At the end of the germination test, no seeds germinated on the substrates with the highest doses of frass (50% and 100%). Figure 1 shows the percentage of germinated seeds of the four species on three substrates with germinated seeds (6,25%, 12.5% and 25% frass w/w) compared to the number of germinated seeds on the control (100% topsoil). In general, the higher the frass % in the substrate, the lower the germination. The 4 species responded similarly on all the substrates with the exception of the dose 25% where only tomato and sunflower were able to germinate. Even at the lowest dose of frass, the species showed a reduction in germination. Considering the seedlings biomass in % for the three doses of frass compared to the one of the control seedlings (data not reported), sunflower at the lowest dose (6,25%) did not differ from the control treatment (98%±10%) and for the doses 12.5% and 25% it reached the highest values (67.5±8.57% and 59.3±4.84%, respectively) compared to the other species. Figure 2 reports the duration of the phenological stages of sunflower recorded during the growing period (not yet concluded). The statistical analysis compares the three treatments *NPK*, *Frass/NPK* and *Frass* with the control. The application of frass significantly reduced the leaf development stage and the stem elongation stage for the *NPK* treatment while the *Frass/NPK* treatment significantly underwent a reduction of the stem elongation stage, only. At 45 days after sowing, the mean height of plants growing on treatments *NPK*, *Frass/NPK*, *Frass* were significantly higher than the control (data not reported) but not different from each other.

Conclusions

Despite frass showed inhibition at the germination test, the ongoing experiment on sunflower is giving promising outcomes. The results so far collected show that the application of frass is supporting the plants growth comparable to the mineral fertilization. The next determination in terms of both the biomass production and its nutritional contents will provide a clearer picture on the goodness and potential of frass as organic fertilizer.

Literature

Houben D. et al. 2020. Potential use of mealworm frass as a fertilizer: Impact on crop growth and soil properties. *Sci. Rep.*, 10: 4659.
 Poveda J. 2021. Insect frass in the development of sustainable agriculture. A review. *Agron. Sust. Dev.*, 41: 5.
 Emino E.R. & Warman P.R. 2004. Biological assay for compost quality. *Compost Sci. Util.*, 12(4): 342-348.

Figure 1. Germination % (germinated seeds on frass: germinated seeds on control) of tomato, sunflower, lettuce and watercress in frass substrate at different concentrations w/w (6.25%, 12.5% and 25%). The bars refer to the mean and standard deviation of 4 replicates for each species. Letters above the bars refer to significant differences for each combination of species and Frass extract concentration ($p < 0.05$, Fisher post hoc test performed after two-way Anova in Table 1). All means were compared to 100 by one-sample t-test ($p < 0.05$, marked with an asterisk). The 50% and 100% Frass concentrations did not lead to any germination and are therefore not shown in the graph (for clarity).

Figure 2. Duration of the phenological stages of sunflower for the different treatments (*Frass*, *Frass/NPK*, *NPK* and Control). Significant differences in duration vs control are indicated with an asterisk (independent-samples t-test, $p < 0.05$). Flowering is currently in progress and its total duration is not yet fully defined (dashed outline).

Agronomic Comparison Between Spring and Winter *Camelina sativa* Cultivation in North Italy

Martina Ghidoli¹, Sara Frazzini², Stefano De Benedetti³, Stefano Sangiorgio¹, Michela Landoni⁴,
Alessio Scarafoni³, Luciana Rossi², Roberto Pilu¹

¹ DISAA, Univ. Milano, IT, martina.ghidoli@unimi.it; stefano.sangiorgio@unimi.it, salvatore.pilu@unimi.it

² DIVAS, Univ. Milano, IT, sara.frazzini@unimi.it; luciana.rossi@unimi.it

³ DEFENS, Univ. Milano, IT, stefano.debenedetti@unimi.it; alessio.scarafoni@unimi.it

⁴ DSTA, Univ. Pavia, IT, michelaveronica.landoni@unipv.it

Introduction

In recent years, the interest in increasingly sustainable agriculture has also turned attention towards new crops. In this scenario, *Camelina sativa* is a perfect crop to study. Camelina is interesting for its oil content, (about 40%), with a high level of polyunsaturated fatty acids (30-40% alpha linolenic acid, 15-25 % linoleic acid, 15% oleic acid, 15% eicosenoic acid). It is characterized by rapid growth, short life cycle and a low input cultivation. All these traits make it suitable for use in marginal areas. However, the use in feed and food is bound by the presence of glucosinolates (GLS), sulfur molecules involved in plant defense. In recent years, they have been studied not only as anti-nutritionals, but also for their use in pharmacology and as natural pesticides. Given the interest in camelina, eight pure lines and a synthetic population were compared in two different growing periods. In this work, the genetic materials were characterized for different phenotypic traits, bromatological and GLS content. The results confirmed in North Italy camelina has higher yields if cultivated in the winter period (about 2 t/ha vs 0.6 t/ha), furthermore, a negative correlation was found between spring and winter yields, indicating that varieties that produce more in winter produce less in spring. Moreover, to our knowledge, it is the first work in which a synthetic population of *Camelina sativa* is tested and proved to be a valid solution for use in various environments both for its adaptability and for the low content of GLS (about 17 mmol/ kg).

Materials and Methods

Plant Materials: Eight different spring lines and a synthetic population of *C. sativa*.

Constitution of synthetic population: The synthetic population was developed in 2018 starting from spring lines of *C. sativa*. The constitution followed a bulk method. The synthetic population used in this study is the F6 generation.

Field experimentation: The experimentation was carried out by evaluating the spring-type pure lines and synthetic population of camelina at two different sowing times, in spring (sowing April 2021, harvest July 2021) and in winter (sowing October 2021, harvest May 2022). No irrigation was provided in both cycles of cultivation. The experimentation was laid out in randomized blocks in both fields; each accession was cultivated in three plots for a total of 27 plots. The size of each plot: 6 m² (5 m x 1.2 m). The sowing was carried out using a manual seeder (rows spaced 0.2 m, density 8 kg/ha). At maturity, the harvest was performed manually cutting at ground level.

Agronomic parameters: At maturity, in each parcel, some agronomic traits were measured: plant height, branch height, number of branches, stem diameter, number of siliques per plant, silique size, number of seeds per siliqua, weight of 1000 seeds.

Bromatological analysis and GLS quantification: Analysis was conducted bulking 100 g per plot for each variety. 5 g of the bulked seeds were sampled for both the analysis in triplicate.

Results

This work aims to evaluate the agronomic performances of 8 pure lines and a synthetic population in the North Italy, comparing two different sowing periods. The data regarding yield, do not show statistical differences among the genetic materials when cultivated in spring or winter period. However, some differences were registered regarding plant height, number of branches and weight of 1000 seeds. While

considering the comparison of yields, statistically significant differences ($p < 0.05$) were found among all the materials suggesting that winter cultivation as cover crop should be the best choice in North Italy agroecosystem. As reported in Angelini and co-authors work, in the Mediterranean area, with autumn sowing the crop encounters relatively milder temperatures during seed filling compared to spring sowing, thus favoring the production of a seed with better chemical characteristics (Angelini et al., 2020). With the aim to dissect yield, agronomics parameters useful for future camelina breeding programs were measured. In addition, bromatological analysis on dry matter, ash, crude fibre, crude protein, oil and GLS analysis were carried out. As regards the bromatological analyses, the protein content rate found was about 26% in 5 pure lines and in the synthetic population, while the highest values were found was 30.7%. While the lowest value of the oil content was 23.6% and the highest 31.4%. The protein content found complies with what is reported in the work of Pepera and co-authors, (range of protein content 20-30%), while the oil content reported is between 35-43% (Perera et al., 2022). In our work, the oil content was probably be traced to drought and high temperatures, as explained in the work of Brock and co-authors in 2020 (Brock et al., 2020). For what concern the GLS quantification, the genetic materials in study showed values from 17 to 26.5 mmol/kg, while in the work of Russo et al. (2014) the range reported for *C. sativa* is 23–44 mmol/g. Taking together all the data, a correlation analysis was performed, and the correlation plot showed statistically significant correlations ($p < 0.05$). Three of these correlations are negative: number of branches and number of seeds per siliqua ($r = - 0.81761$; $p = 0.007103$), branch height and number of siliques per plant ($r = - 0.72895$; $p = 0.025873$), and silique length and yield ($r = - 0.8231$; $p = 0.0064183$). Regarding the strongest correlation between the length of the siliqua and the yield, Li and co-authors found 8 QTLs associated with siliqua length (Li et al., 2021). It can be hypothesized among these QTLs there is one or more genes that are linked with the yield. Positive correlations were found between: weight of 1000 seeds and oil content ($r = 0.74559$; $p = 0.021102$), number of plants per m² and oil content ($r = 0.78185$; $p = 0.012803$) and crude protein and GLS content ($r = 0.66743$; $p = 0.049508$). The correlation regarding the percentage of oil with the weight of 1000 seeds confirms one of the most important traits to look for in a breeding program to improve yield which is the size of the seed, especially to increase the oil content. A multivariate analysis were performed and the main determinants describing clustering highlighted are plant height and GLS content.

Conclusions

In conclusion, the results of this work highlighted, firstly, in North Italy the best yield is obtained following a winter cultivation. Secondly, camelina breeding programs should be developed considering the growing season because our results clearly showed the most productive varieties in winter are the least productive in spring. Thirdly, seed size is the most important parameter to consider having a high oil yield. Finally, synthetic populations of *Camelina sativa* may represent the best genetic constitution for both spring and winter sowing. To our knowledge, this is the first work in which a synthetic population of *Camelina sativa* is developed and tested. The results obtained such as the low GLS content, the intermediate yield in both seasons suggest that the use of the synthetic population is functional in the cultivation of this hexaploid species with low genetic variability in different contexts such as marginal and/or mountainous areas where its tolerance to unfavorable conditions can contribute to yield stability and resistance to abiotic and biotic stresses.

Literature

- Angelini L. et al. 2020. Performance and Potentiality of Camelina (*Camelina Sativa* L. Crantz) Genotypes in Response to Sowing Date under Mediterranean Environment. *Agronomy*, 10: 1929.
- Perera S. et al. 2022. Profiling and Characterization of *Camelina Sativa* (L.) Crantz Meal Proteins. *JAOCS*, 99: 873–89.
- Russo R. et al. 2014. Variability in Glucosinolate Content among *Camelina* Species. *Am. J. Plant Sci.*, 05: 294–98.
- Brock J. et al. 2020. Interactions between Genetics and Environment Shape Camelina Seed Oil Composition. *BMC Plant Biol.*, 20: 423.
- Li H. et al. 2021. Genetic Dissection of Natural Variation in Oilseed Traits of Camelina by Whole-Genome Resequencing and QTL Mapping. *The Plant Genome* 14: e20110.

Identifying criteria for harmonizing life cycle assessments of crop-livestock systems and interactions

Pietro Goglio¹, Marie Trydeman Knudsen^{2,3}, Klara Van Mierlo⁴, Nina Röhrig⁵, Fossey Maxime⁶, Alberto Maresca⁷, Fatemeh Hashemi^{2,3}, Muhammad Ahmed Waqas^{2,3}, Jenny Yngvesson⁸, Gilles Nassy⁹, Roline Broekema⁴, Simon Moakes^{10,11}, Catherine Pfeifer¹¹, Robert Borek¹², David Yanez-Ruiz¹³, Monica Quevedo Cascante^{2,3}, Alina Sypl¹², Tomasz Zylowsky¹², Manuel Romero-Huelva¹³, Laurence G. Smith^{5,8}, Francesco Tei¹

¹Dep. Agricultural, Food and Environmental Sciences, Univ. Perugia, IT, pietro.goglio@unipg.it, francesco.tei@unipg.it

²Dep. Agroecology, Aarhus University, Denmark

³Aarhus University Interdisciplinary Centre for climate change (iCLIMATE), Department of Agroecology, Denmark

⁴Wageningen Economic Research, Bronlân, Netherlands

⁵School of Agriculture, Policy and Development, University of Reading, UK

⁶Institut de l'élevage (IDELE), Paris, France

⁷SEGES Innovation P/S, Aarhus, Denmark

⁸Dep. Biosystems and Technology, Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences, Sweden

⁹Institut du Porc (IFIP), Le Rheu, France

¹⁰Dep. Socio-Economics, Research Institute of Organic Agriculture (FiBL), Frick, Switzerland

¹¹IBERS, Aberystwyth University, UK

¹²Institute of Soil Science and Plant Cultivation - State Research Institute, Puławy, Poland

¹³Estación Experimental del Zaidín (CSIC), Granada, Spain

Introduction

Food production is responsible for 26% of all greenhouse gases (GHGs), and for 70% of land-use globally (Poore and Nemecek, 2018; Goglio et al., 2023). Thus, the contribution of livestock to a sustainable circular bioeconomy and agroecology, its interaction and dependence on cropping and grassland systems should therefore be further investigated (Goglio et al., 2023). Participatory approaches have been successful in assessing design and innovation in agriculture (Mullender et al., 2020); while LCA in assessing environmental impacts of agricultural systems and products. However, LCA methodology needs to be improved with regard to C sequestration and GHGs, crop-livestock interactions, feed-food-fuel competition, biodiversity, and circular economy aspects. There has been no robust attempt to develop an evaluation framework for the assessment of methods addressing these issues (Goglio et al., 2023). Here this gap was addressed through a participatory expert consultation approach focussing on the life cycle inventory accounting for crop-livestock systems.

Materials and Methods

A participatory harmonization approach was adopted to identify key topics and evaluation criteria for LCAs of crop-livestock systems (Mullender et al., 2020). These criteria for LCA methods of livestock systems were identified through a literature review and 29 workshops with experts (n=21) on LCA, GHGs, biodiversity, nutrition and animal welfare, across academia and farmer advisory boards from 14 countries. Two anonymous surveys were carried out and results were discussed to identify key topics and general criteria for LCA methodology. Here results on the general criteria and specific criteria for GHG, biodiversity and circular economy issues were discussed.

Results

For the general criteria, the “Credible” (RACER) and the “Transparency and Reproducibility” (JRC ILCD) general criteria received the highest median score (10), followed by “Completeness” (JRC PEFCR), “Fairness and Acceptance” (JRC ILCD), “Accuracy/Robustness/Data Quality” (ACTA), “FAO LEAP

criterion” and “Robust” (RACER) with a median value of 8. These were prioritised through follow-up workshops (n=7): “Transparency and Reproducibility”, “Completeness”, “Fairness and Acceptance”, “Robustness” and “Accuracy”.

In several workshops (n=19) among the LCA experts, accuracy was retained as specific assessment criteria in the LCA of crop-livestock systems for circular economy.

For biodiversity, predictability, inclusion of invasive and vulnerable species, functional biodiversity, accuracy and comprehensiveness in the assessment of species richness and diversity and accuracy in landscape continuity were identified. Finally, for GHGs, these were the identified criteria: adaptability to soil types, land uses, climate and accuracy in soil C and N₂O emissions estimation. For manure emissions and storage, the inclusion of methane leakage in anaerobic digestion; accuracy in GHG estimation for manure storage and treatment, animal housing and enteric fermentation were retained.

Conclusions

This harmonization approach addressed the need for improved methods and indicators in the LCA of crop-livestock systems across GHGs, circular economy, and biodiversity, prominent in the public domain. Through a participatory research, several general criteria were identified providing a robust framework to assess LCA methodologies for crop-livestock systems and products.

Literature

Goglio P. et al. 2023. Defining common criteria for harmonizing life cycle assessments of livestock systems. *Clean. Prod. Let.*, 4: 100035.
 Mullender S.M. et al. 2020. A delphi-style approach for developing an integrated food/non-food system sustainability assessment tool. *Environ. Impact Assess. Rev.*, 84: 106415.
 Poore J. and Nemecek T. 2018. Reducing food’s environmental impacts through producers and consumers. *Science*, 360: 987–992.

Figure 1. Box plot of the LCA expert responses to identify general criteria for the assessment of LCA methods for crop-livestock systems and product from different LCA frameworks (RACER; JRC ILCD; JRC PEFCR; Goglio et al., 2015; FAO LEAP; proposed by ACTA). The boxes indicate the 1st and 3rd quartiles, dark lines indicate the median. Error bars indicate the maximum and minimum values. Outliers responses more than 1.5 times the inter-quartile range away from the box are shown with hollow circles. High value indicates a high level of importance and a low value indicates a low level of importance (Goglio et al., 2023).

Soil Amendment Application in an Olive Grove: Effects on Plant Performance

Rita Leogrande, Liliana Gaeta, Mirko Castellini

CREA-AA, sede di Bari, IT, rita.leogrande@crea.gov.it

Introduction

The fertilization is an agronomic practice to guarantee crop yield. In the long-term, the huge use of fertilizers and their poor management have led to serious environmental problems.

Nowday and in the future, the key role of agriculture is to achieve optimal production by reducing the impact on the environment. Therefore, the primary sector is increasingly engaged in a radical transition towards a circular, solid and resilient system based on sustainable production processes (Nattasha et al., 2020; Velasco-Munoz et al., 2021). The reuse of various biomass residues, as soil amendments, represents an opportunity to improve nutrient efficiency and overall soil quality. Soil amendments, derived by residuals from other processes such as a variety of composted agro-industrial by-products or pyrolyzed wood materials, are used to improve soil quality and its ability to support plant life. The main aim of their application is to create a suitable environment for plant growth.

In this study, the effects of compost and biochar application on crop response were evaluated, in an olive grove, cv Leccino, under Mediterranean conditions.

Materials and Methods

A two-year field experiment (2021-2022) was carried out in an irrigated olive grove in an area of southern Apulia region affected by the phytosanitary emergency in the olive sector, caused by the quarantine bacterium *Xylella fastidiosa*.

A split plot experimental design with three replications was adopted: two irrigation treatments were allocated to the main plot and four fertilizer treatments were arranged in the sub-plot. Single plot size was of 315 m² consisting of nine olive trees. The following irrigation treatments were compared: V₁₀₀, re-establishing 100% of the maximum evapotranspiration during the whole irrigation season (June-September); V_{RDI}, re-establishing 100% of the maximum evapotranspiration in the irrigation season except

Table 1. Soil amendments chemical characteristics

	Measure	Compost	Biochar
	Unit		
†TOC	g kg ⁻¹	200	882
Total N	g kg ⁻¹	8.0	3.0
pH		8.0	9.60
EC	dS m ⁻¹	2.20	0.46

†TOC, Total Organic Carbon; Total N, total nitrogen; EC, electrical conductivity

during the olive drought-tolerant phenological stage (the pit hardening phase, between the end of July and the end of August), when the irrigation was interrupted. Within each irrigation treatment the following fertilizer strategies were compared: compost (C) and biochar (B), applied as soil amendments; organic fertilizer based on dried blood (SS) and organic commercial fertilizer typically used in the private farm (Control), applied at a dose equivalent to the crop nitrogen requirement (100 kg of N per ha). In table 1, the main biochar and compost characteristics are reported.

From April to June, on six shoots per tree, weekly vegetative growth was measured. At maturity stage (early October), fruits of the same trees monitored for shoot growth were harvested per tree and yield as t ha⁻¹ was estimated.

Data were subjected to analysis of variance and means were compared using SNK post hoc test at p = 0.05 level. Data analysis was carried out using the SAS software.

Results

No interaction between irrigation and fertilization was observed. In this work, only the effects of fertilization treatments on plant and olive yield were evaluated at the end of experiment, after two years of application.

The results of this study highlighted that the application of compost and biochar, as soil amendment, could benefit olive trees. In particular, during the olive vegetative stage, the shoot length in trees treated with compost was similar to the control (Fig. 1). The biochar application seems to cause a decrease shoot length probably attributed to the process of adsorption and immobilization by the biochar of the nutrients (González-Pernas et al., 2022) not available for plants. In any case, lesser development of the tree canopy, in an arid environment like the one in the study, could be a positive way to reduce plant transpiration and consequently to increase water use efficiency.

Figure 1. Shoot growth measurement after two years of organica fertilization. B, biochar; C, compost; SS, organic fertilizer based on dried blood; Control, organic fertilizer typically used in the

Figure 2. Olive yield after two years of organic fertilization. B, biochar; C, compost; SS, organic fertilizer based on dried blood; Control, organic fertilizer typically used in the farm.

possibility to achieve good yield of olive trees with biochar and compost amendment. Then, the re-use of treated agro-industrial waste in agriculture could be an opportunity to recover and enhance these by-products, with a view to a circular economy.

Literature

González-Pernas F.M. et al. 2022. Effects of Biochar on Biointensive Horticultural Crops and Its Economic Viability in the Mediterranean Climate. *Energies*, 15: 3407.

Nattasha et al., 2020. Understanding circular economy implementation in the agri-food supply chain: the case of an Indonesian organic fertiliser producer. *Agric. Food Secur.*, 9: 10.

Velasco-Munoz et al. 2021. Circular economy implementation in the agricultural sector: Definition, strategies and indicators. *Resour. Conserv. Recycl.*, 170: 105618.

Acknowledgments

The authors would like to thank the REGIONE PUGLIA - Dipartimento Agricoltura, Sviluppo Rurale ed Ambientale for funding the present research in the frame of Programma di Sviluppo Rurale (PSR) 2014-2020 Puglia Articolo 35 del Regolamento (UE) n. 1305/2013, Misura 16 “Cooperazione” Sottomisura 16.2 “Sostegno a progetti pilota e allo sviluppo di nuovi prodotti, pratiche, processi e tecnologie” – Biosavex Project. Moreover, the work was also supported by the project Water4AgriFood “Miglioramento delle produzioni agroalimentari mediterranee in condizioni di carenza di risorse idriche”, PNR 2015–2020”, funded by MIUR, PON ARS01_00825, Ricerca e Innovazione 2014–2020.

Greater fertilization effects, although not significant, were found for the olive yield (Fig. 2). The fruit yield ranged from 2.4 t ha⁻¹ to 1.3 t ha⁻¹ and the highest yield was obtained from the biochar treatment (B) with an average increase of 45 % compared with Control. Whereas the fertilizer based on dried blood (SS) caused the lowest olive yield. Finally, compost amendment induced average yield increases of about 15 % and 47 % compared with Control and SS treatments, respectively. Probably, biochar and compost contained the essential macro and micronutrients that are maybe more available during the fruit development (from June to September).

Greater fertilization effects, although not significant, were found for the olive yield (Fig. 2). The fruit yield ranged from 2.4 t ha⁻¹ to 1.3 t ha⁻¹ and the highest yield was obtained from the biochar treatment (B) with an average increase of 45 % compared with Control. Whereas the fertilizer based on dried blood (SS) caused the lowest olive yield. Finally, compost amendment induced average yield increases of about 15 % and 47 % compared with Control and SS treatments, respectively. Probably, biochar and compost contained the essential macro and micronutrients that are maybe more available during the fruit development (from June to September).

Conclusions

The results of two-year experiment reveal the

Effects of Different Agronomic Conditions on the Production of Eight Bread Wheat Varieties

Roberto Mancinelli¹, Mohamed Allam¹, Mariam Atait¹, Verdiana Petroselli¹, Emanuele Radicetti²

¹ DAFNE, Univ. Tuscia, IT, mancinel@unitus.it, mohamed.allam@studenti.unitus.it, mariam.atait@unitus.it, verdiana.petroselli@unitus.it,

² DOCPAS, Univ. Ferrara, IT, emanuele.radicetti@unife.it

Introduction

The upcoming challenges for farmers in coming years are related to the drastic changes in temperatures, rainfall patterns, droughts that negatively affect crop yields. To find solution to climate change and global warming the phenomenon of adaptation represent a key aspect for quantitative and qualitative traits of crop yield, especially for bread wheat. The selection of superior wheat varieties suitable for a particular area play a key role in maintaining high crop yield and quality. Therefore, sustainability of food production has become a priority, increasing the interest in new environmentally friendly tools to replace synthetic agrochemicals or, at least, reduce their impact. The selection of best suitable varieties in different agronomic management could be a way forward to overcome the environmental challenges differently affecting the yield of bread wheat crop varieties (Beres et al., 2020). This study aims to assess effects of variables such as abiotic stresses and management practices on bread wheat performance.

Materials and Methods

The study was carried out at University of Tuscia (UNITUS), Viterbo, Italy, during 2021/2022 growing season of which the climate data are reported in Figure 1. Commercial varieties of bread wheat were evaluated in different treatments. The field was organized in a split plot experimental design with three replications, in which treatments were the main plots and the commercial varieties as sub plots. A total of 8 commercial and widely cultivated bread wheat varieties were evaluated. The bread wheat varieties included Altigo, Bologna, Cosmic, Costello, GK Szilard, Nogal, Skagen, and Skyfall, of which the origin were in France, Italy, Italy, UK, Hungary, France, Denmark, UK, respectively.

Five treatments were applied:

- two fungicide applications, (Full) first application of fungicide "Seguris Xtra" plus the growth regulator "Moddus" at stem elongation stage and second application of fungicide "Prosaro" at heading time;
- one fungicide application, (Optimised) by application of "Prosaro" at heading time.
- No fungicide application (No-treatment);
- two fungicide applications as in the Full plus irrigation (Irrigated);
- management without any synthetic inputs (Organic), all agronomic techniques allowed by Regulation (EU) 2018/848 were adopted.

The sowing was in the middle of November using a seed dose equal for each plot of bread wheat (400 seeds m⁻²). On 02/23/2022, ammonium nitrate was manually applied (50 kg N ha⁻¹), then on 04/20/2022 the urea was applied (50 kg N ha⁻¹). Herbicide "Granstar®" was used for weeding, at stem elongation 8/04/2022. For the Organic treatment organic fertilizer just before the sowing and no weed control was applied. Harvesting time has been in the second middle of June. The statistical analysis was carried out using R software, analysis of variance (ANOVA) has been performed and the differences have been evaluated by student t test.

Figure 1 - Decadal minimum [—] and maximum [---] temperatures (°C), precipitations [■] and precipitation historical data [◆] (mm) at the experimental site in the growing season 2021/2022

Results

Because the 2022 season was intensively dry with below-average rainfall (Fig. 1), the climate conditions surely affected the bread wheat crop. In fact, the precipitations were 63% reduced compared to the historical data, in the period January to June 2022.

Concerning the grain yield, the Irrigation treatment showed the best results (4.5 t ha⁻¹ of d.m. grain), followed by the Organic treatment (2.7 t ha⁻¹ of d.m. grain) and then the other treatments (on average 1.8 t ha⁻¹ of d.m. grain). Best levels of grain yields were observed for Nogal, Cosmic, Bologna, Altigo, GK Szilard varieties. The Irrigated treatment and the Altigo variety shown also the best grain dimension (thousand grain weight 34.7 g and 36 g, respectively). Skyfall variety, even if didn't show the best grain yield, resulted to be good for the grains dimension (33.7 g). Among the treatments Full, Optimised and No-treated, the first one positively affected the specific weight, while among varieties, Bologna variety was the best. In the Organic treatment, the plants resulted taller than other treatments (67 cm vs 55 cm on average). The same varieties which showed highest grain yield at the same time resulted to be taller (Nogal, Cosmic, Bologna, Altigo, GK Szilard).

Table 1- The main effect of treatment and variety on grain yield, thousand grain weight, specific weight, plant height, and moisture content. Values belonging to the same parameter and main effect with different letters (in columns) are statistically different according to LSD test ($p < 0.05$).

	Grain yield (kg ha ⁻¹ of dm)	Thousand grain weight (g)	Specific weight (kg hl ⁻¹)	Plant height (cm)	Grain moisture content (%)
Treatment					
Full	1736.5c	27.5b	70.7a	54.1bc	6.1ab
Optimised	1968.6c	29.2b	69.8b	54.9bc	5.3b
No-treated	1835.1c	28.6b	69.9b	53.6c	6.6ab
Irrigated	4526.5a	34.7a	-	56.6b	7.2a
Organic	2659.8b	28.3b	-	67.1a	6.8a
Variety					
Altigo	2726.5a	36.0a	68.6d	61,5a	7.0ab
Bologna	2854.1a	27.3bc	76.6a	60,4a	6.8ab
Cosmic	2879.5a	29.5b	67.2e	59,1a	5.5bc
Costello	2281.0b	29.0b	68.5d	53,4b	8.3a
GK Szilard	2682.5a	29.3b	72.2c	60,6a	4.6c
Nogal	3006.4a	27.9b	73.1b	62,3a	6.6b
Skagen	1806.4c	24.5c	66.3f	51,3bc	6.4b
Skyfall	2126.1bc	33.7a	68.5d	49,3c	6.1bc

Conclusions

There were no significant effects among Full, Optimised and No-treatment, due to the fungicide and growth regulator application for the increasing of grain yield and other parameters for the selected commercial varieties under dry climatic conditions. Perhaps due to the higher soil water retention, the Organic correctly managed could be a potential alternative. The study can help in the identification of promising wheat varieties with high mean performance under unfavourable climatic conditions. In fact, some varieties such as Nogal, Cosmic, Bologna, Altigo, GK Szilard were able to perform better in such dry climate.

Literature

Beres B.L. et al. 2020. Towards a better understanding of Genotype × Environment × Management interactions – a global Wheat Initiative agronomic research strategy. *Front. Plant Sci.*, 11: 828.

Understanding the Spatiotemporal Behaviour and the Environmental Sustainability of Crop Yield in an Organic Farming System

Stefano Marino¹, Marco di Cristofaro², Arturo Alvino¹

¹ Dip. Agricoltura Ambiente Alimenti, Univ. Molise, IT, stefanomarino@unimol.it

² Dip. Bioscienze e Territorio, Univ. Molise, IT

Introduction

Landscapes that are managed to provide a broad set of ecosystem services have the potential to satisfy the needs of multiple stakeholders while sustaining higher levels of biodiversity, preventing environmental degradation and future costs of environmental restoration (Hölting et al., 2020). Organic farming has begun to represent a practical alternative for reducing the environmental impacts of crop production and increasing biodiversity. However, organic farming systems face various drawbacks, with more significant yield variability affecting crop yield (Jensen et al., 2015). Combining remote sensing techniques and a Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) approach, present work aims to monitor the spatial and temporal crop variability and identify areas with different crop production suitability in relation to the environmental performance of the system. In this way, our methodology should support the adoption of farming management strategies that increase both the multifunctional use and sustainability of landscapes at the farm level.

Materials and Methods

The open-field experiment was conducted in Central Italy (492,680.30 E, 4,632,601.7 N; UTM-WGS84 zone 33 N Italy) on 24 ha in 2021 season. The experimental site was located in a hilly area of the Molise region (Larino, CB). Durum wheat cv Saragolla was grown in the whole field with a seed rate of 550 seeds per square meter. A total of 8 cloud-free Sentinel-2 images were downloaded from ESA's Copernicus Open Access Hub. The NDVI time series were computed. On June 26, the whole field was mechanically harvested, and the grain yield was determined; furthermore, 33 georeferenced samples from 1 m² were hand-cut to calculate yield and yield components. The yield-related traits and NDVI data were analyzed by a clustering method, using hierarchical clustering Ward's minimum variance approach according to Marino et al. (2014) and QGIS was used for the processing of maps. Yield data were further processed in LCA analysis, mapping the environmental impacts of cultivation practices. LCA target is to evaluate crop production impacts, raw materials, product transformation, distribution and disposal are not included. Therefore, a "cradle to grave" LCA (SETAC 1993) was implemented, considering all material and energy flows relating to the agricultural processes of durum wheat production. Furthermore, impacts linked to production/maintenance of infrastructures are excluded. We adopt "1 ha crop surface" as a functional unit. Farming system impacts were estimated using the software SimaPro - version 9.4.0.2 and the ReCiPe 2016 evaluation method for the interpretation of results (Huijbregts et al., 2016). Results were calculated at endpoint level through 3 metrics that refer to three areas of protection, which are human health, ecosystem quality and resource scarcity (Huijbregts et al., 2016). Method includes global normalisation factors for the reference year 2010, allowing comparable scores referring to a general unit (i.e., Pt of impact).

Results

The whole field of 24 ha was harvested on June 26; the average crop yield was 2.3 t ha⁻¹. Agronomic traits data were collected at harvest, analyzed and clustered with NDVI Sentinel-2 data to detect groups with significant differences (Fig. 1). An area identified as cluster 1 with a surface of 7.3 ha showed the highest yield at harvest (3.34 t ha⁻¹). Cluster 2, with an area of about 7.7 ha, showed yield and yield components values much lower than cluster 1, with about 35 % less grain yield, biomass, and spike weight, about 22 % fewer spike numbers per square meter. Cluster 3, with lower yield and yield components data, identified with an area of about 9 ha, showed a yield of 0.72 t ha⁻¹, an average value 70% lower than the mean yield at harvest and 78 % lower than the most productive cluster area. The yield components also recorded

shallow values, mainly due to the negative effect of the high presence of weeds (particularly oats), which reached average values of 250 g m⁻², three times higher than those in the most productive area and soil with a higher silty component.

Figure 1. Yield (t ha⁻¹) and LCA cultivation technique total damage (pt) values

The damage impacts showed that an area equal to 30% of the whole crop surface involves impacts that are 31% lower than the average, and 32% of the whole crop surface involves impacts that align with the average damages (Tab. 1). Finally, on 38% of the entire crop area, impacts are more than three times the average (i.e., +219%). The total damage of 1 ha surface in a conventional farming system in the same cultivation areas it is about is equal to 77 Pt of impact.

Damage category	Unit	Yield (mean values) 2.30 ton ha ⁻¹	Yield CLUSTER I: 3.34 ton ha ⁻¹	Yield CLUSTER II: 2.17 ton ha ⁻¹	Yield CLUSTER III: 0.72 ton ha ⁻¹
Human health	Pt	33.70	23.21	35.71	107.67
Ecosystems	Pt	3.20	2.21	3.39	10.24
Resources	Pt	0.41	0.28	0.43	1.30
TOTAL	Pt	37.31	25.70	39.53	119.20

Table 1. LCA damage category of different yield cluster areas.

Conclusions

The study highlights that Agronomic yield data and the NDVI maps derived from the Satellite Sentinel-2 identify the yield spatial variability for the correct adoption of farming management strategies that increase the multifunctional use of landscapes at the farm level. Moreover, integrating remote sensing techniques and the LCA method has proved particularly useful for assessing the environmental suitability of crop productions and suggesting site-specific solutions to sustainable rural landscape development.

Literature

- Hölting L. et al. 2020. Multifunctional Landscapes. Encyclopedia of the World's Biomes, 128-134.
- Jensen E.S. et al. 2015. Enhancing yields in organic crop production by eco-functional intensification. *Sustain. Agric. Res.*, 4(3): 42–50.
- Huijbregts M.A. et al. 2016. ReCiPe 2016: a harmonized life cycle impact assessment method at midpoint and endpoint level. RIVM Report, 104.
- Marino S. et al. 2014. Use of soil and vegetation spectroradiometry to investigate crop water use efficiency of a drip irrigated tomato. *Eur. J. Agron.*, 59: 67–77.
- SETAC 1993. Guidelines for Life-Cycle Assessment: A "Code of Practice". From the SETAC Workshop, Portugal, 31 March - 3 April 1993. Edition 1.

Allelopathic Effect of Buckwheat (*Fagopyrum esculentum* L.) on Germination and Performance of Crops and Weeds: a comprehensive methodology

Daniel Marusig^{1,2*}, Alessandra Virili¹, Gemini Delle Vedove¹, Elisa Marraccini¹

¹ DI4A, Univ. Udine, IT, alessandra.virili@uniud.it, gemini.dellevedove@uniud.it, elisa.marraccini@uniud.it.

² DSV, Univ. Trieste, IT, *daniel.marusig@phd.units.it.

Introduction

The rapid increase of herbicide-resistant weeds is urging the implementation of agroecological practices aimed to increase the resilience of agroecosystems, while being compatible with modern agricultural production standards (Cheriere et al., 2020). For this purpose, novel practises adopt a combination of mechanical, chemical and cultural techniques to control weed populations. This strategy is referred to as Integrated Weed Management and includes the use of intercropping approaches as an effective practise for weed control (Maitra et al., 2021). A growing body of literature is exploring different legume-based intercropping systems, either comparing different spatial layouts or sowing densities of the companion crops. Many studies have investigated a wide selection of companion crops, based on their resource complementarity with the main crop (Koskey et al., 2022) or on their ability to control weed populations through allelopathy (*i.e.* biochemical inhibition). Particular interest has been put on buckwheat (*Fagopyrum esculentum* - BW), a species of rising economical interest, also known for being allelopathic (Falquet et al., 2015). The weed suppression ability of BW has been reported to come mainly from exudates released by plant residues (Farooq et al., 2020). BW has also been proven to produce allelochemicals through roots exudates (Iqbar et al., 2003). Although the allelopathic effect of BW is known, it has not been tested as companion crop until recently.

This study provides a comprehensive methodology to investigate the interactions between BW, legume crops and weeds (*i.e.* competition and allelopathy). We designed three experimental trials: 1) a germination experiment with BW water extracts; 2) a glasshouse pot experiment, 3) a field intercropping trial. These trials are set up to create an increasing scale of complexity and evaluate the mechanisms by which BW interacts with other species and at what stage.

Materials and Methods

Buckwheat water extracts effect on seeds germination

A germination test in petri dishes has been carried out in spring 2023, to test the allelopathic effect of BW extracts on seed germination of various crops and weeds. A total of 12 species are under investigation, six crops: chickpea (*Cicer arietinum* - CH), lentil (*Lens culinaris* -LN), soybean (*Glycine max* - SB), barley (*Hordeum vulgare*), oat (*Avena sativa*) and quinoa (*Chenopodium quinoa*); and six weeds: Velvetleaf (*Abutilon theophrasti* – VL), red pigweed (*Amaranthus retroflexus* - RP), *Cynodon dactylon*, *Echinochloa crus-galli*, *Setaria italica* and *Sorghum halepense*.

BW water extracts were prepared from milled residuals of buckwheat whole plants. The obtained product stirred in pure water for 6h at constant speed rotation of 150 rounds per minute. Two different water extract concentrations were prepared according to the weight/volume ratio of product and pure water: i) 1:5: 100g of product and 1l of pure water; 1:5: 200g of product and 1l of pure water. Obtained extracts were filtered with filter paper and refrigerated at 4°C until used. For each combination of species - water extract, we test 15 seeds per 5 replicates. Petri dishes are placed in a growth chamber for 7 days with 12h of light and 12h of dark, respectively at 25°C and 20°C. Germination percentage and root length are measured and expressed respectively to the control treatment (water only).

Plants-consociation effect in a controlled environment – A glasshouse experiment

We set up a pot experiment aimed to: 1) test whether BW may provide weed-control services by allelopathy or competition for resources; 2) evaluate if possible plant-suppression effects reported by the germination experiment can be observed in soil.

A total of four species are tested, two crops: CH and LN; and two weeds: VL and RP. Each species is tested under 3 experimental treatments: monoculture (MC), intercropped with buckwheat (IC) and in staircase device (SD), an experimental tool specifically designed to separate the effect of allelopathy from competition by watering plants with percolated water from pots containing pure buckwheat stands. Treatments were placed following a randomized block design. Seeds were sown in 13.5L pots, with surface area of 225cm². Pots were filled with clay-loam sifted soil. BW, LN, RP, and VL were sown at a density of 4 plants per pot in pure stands and at 2 plants per plot when intercropped. CH was sown at 2 plants per pot in the pure stands and one plant per pot when intercropped.

Three samplings are conducted based on BW phenology: at fifth full leaf development, at full bloom and at seeding onset. At each measurement we collect plant height and root length, followed by shoot and root dry weight after being oven-dried at 70°C for 72h.

Crops intercropping for weed management – A field experiment

The objective of this trial is to evaluate the weed control efficiency of BW both between and within the rows of the three grain legumes: CH, LN and SB. We chose two intercropping layouts: 1) alternate rows (AR, crops sown in separate rows); 2) within-row intercropping (WR, crops sown in same row). Plots of both pure legume and pure buckwheat are also included as controls. Furthermore, BW in WR layouts was sown at two different densities: 25% and 50% of the BW monoculture sowing density. Crops were sown in a completely randomized design in 8m long plots with a row distance of 17cm in AR and BW monoculture, while 34cm in WR and the legume monocultures. Target plant densities of pure crops are: 200 plants m⁻² for BW, 40 plants m⁻² for SB, 45 plants m⁻² for CH and 120 plants m⁻² for LN. Plant density of BW was halved in AR, while legume sowing density remained the same in all treatments. CH and LN were sown on 29/03/2023, while SB on 01/06/2023. Hoeing is performed in the pure crops stands and in the WR plots. No weeding is performed in the AR plots. In each plot, we randomly placed two sampling areas of 0.35m² (0.70m x 0.50m) in which crop and weed cover are assessed before and one month after each hoeing, together with weed species identification. At legume flowering and harvest, both crop and weed above-ground biomass are collected. At legume harvest we also assess yield, harvest index, grain nitrogen and fibre content.

Conclusions

The use of this comprehensive methodology is expected to provide information on BW strategies in terms of competition and allelopathy, for which literature still lacks. We aim to provide information on the effect of BW allelochemicals in suppressing germination of crop and weed species. Moreover, we aim to obtain further knowledge on BW mechanisms of competition and allelopathy on crops and weeds, to better evaluate its suitability as a companion species for weed management in intercropping strategies.

Literature

- Koskey G. et al. 2022. Exploiting plant functional diversity in durum wheat–lentil relay intercropping to stabilize crop yields under contrasting climatic conditions. *Agronomy*, 12: 210.
- Maitra S. et al. 2021. Intercropping--A low input agricultural strategy for food and environmental security. *Agronomy*, 11: 343.
- Cheriere, T. et al. 2020. Species choice and spatial arrangement in soybean-based intercropping: Levers that drive yield and weed control. *Field Crops Res.*, 256: 107923.
- Iqbal Z. et al. 2003. Allelopathic activity of buckwheat: isolation and characterization of phenolics. *Weed Sci.*, 51: 657-662.
- Falquet B. et al. 2015. Weed suppression by common buckwheat: A review. *Environ. Control. Biol.*, 51: 1-6
- Farooq N. et al. 2020. Allelopathy for weed management. *Co-evolution of secondary metabolites* 505-519.

Reduction of N Input Using Foliar Fertilisation and Biostimulants: Impact on Yield and Quality of Common Wheat

Antonio Minoliti¹, Ida Di Mola¹, Lucia Ottaiano¹, Eugenio Cozzolino²,
Massimo Fagnano¹, Mauro Mori¹, Nunzio Fiorentino¹

¹ DIA, Univ. Napoli “Federico II”, IT, antonio.minoliti@unina.it, ida.dimola@unina.it, lucia.ottaiano@unina.it,
mori@unina.it, fagnano@unina.it, nunzio.fiorentino@unina.it

² CREA-CI, Caserta, IT, eugenio.cozzolino@crea.gov.it

Introduction

In 2021, global wheat production was 750 million tonnes (35% of total grain production) and about 5.5 million tonnes of grain were produced in Italy in the same year. An appropriate N fertilisation of common wheat aimed to limit N overuse, can contribute to minimize N losses and environmental impact while maintaining high yield and quality of grain. It is well recognized that the use of biostimulants can improve the yield and quality of wheat grain (Al Majathoub, 2004) also under low N input conditions. Seadh et al. (2009) proved a positive effect of foliar fertilisation with macro- and micro-nutrients on wheat grain yield and quality also confirmed by other authors (Arif et al., 2006). There is a lack of knowledge regarding the combined use of biostimulants and foliar fertilization on common wheat in Mediterranean cropping systems. This study aims to evaluate these techniques for limiting direct N input.

Materials and Methods

The trial was conducted in Frignano (68 m a.s.l., Campania region, Italy) at the “D’Amore Francesco” private farm. The crop rotation was common wheat-tomato with high yields sustained by the good soil fertility (Sandy clayey loam texture; OM=1.81%, total N= 0.11%). The sowing was made on December 22nd, 2021, with a density of 400 seeds per square meter. Three varieties of common wheat (Don Carmine, Bisanzio and Metropolis) were cultivated under 2 different N management strategies compared to a non-fertilized control (Test): i) Conv = 180 kg N ha⁻¹ and 75%Conv = 135 kg N ha⁻¹ provided as ammonium nitrate on March 14th. Two products by MENFIN Ltd. were also tested: PRO N BIO 8.1% (F) a plant extract-based foliar fertiliser (applied on May 3rd) and an algae-derived biostimulant (B) AUXIMAR^{TNF} (distributed on March 28th and May 3rd) were applied alone or in combination (F-B) to both Conv and 75%Conv thus obtaining a total of 8 treatments with 3 replicates on 10 m² (2 x 5 m) plots. At harvest (June 21st), the following measurements were carried out on grain: yield; moisture; weight of 1000 seeds (TSW); protein content; gluten; hectolitre weight (HW); starch; hardness, and shrivelled seeds. All data were subjected to analysis of variance with SPSS (SPSS version 22, Chicago, Illinois) and the means were separated according to the LSD test at P < 0.05.

Results

Metropolis resulted the best performing variety with the highest yield and TSW, even if protein and gluten contents were lower than Don Carmine. Our findings indicate that the use of biostimulants and foliar fertilisation can compensate a reduced N dose. In fact, as shown in table 1 the significantly lower grain yield associated to the 25% reduction of N inputs, was compensated by the biostimulant application able to raise up yield to the levels of conventional fertilization. In addition, a tendency to higher yields with the B and F-B application was also recorded for Conv treatment. It is interesting to notice that this result was probably due to an increased TSW under Conv fertilization, while the increased yield of 75%Conv-B was probably due to an increased number of kernels per spike being TSW not different by 75%Conv. A similar pattern was also recorded for protein and gluten contents with F and F-B treatments able to increase values of 75%Conv up to the levels recorded for Conv.

The average total N removal (Fig. 1) of the tested common wheat varieties was 150 kg N ha⁻¹ with values a ranging between 91 kg N ha⁻¹ of the Test and 176 kg N ha⁻¹ of the Conv-F-B treatment. The highest total N uptake was recorded by Metropolis due to a higher grain production and N uptake. The 25% reduction of N input did not significantly reduce both total and grain N uptake even if a tendency to lower values was detected (-13%). It is interesting to notice that biostimulation raised up N uptake value in 75%Conv (+29%) treatment to values close to the best Conventional treatments (Conv-FB 176 kg N ha⁻¹). According to this result, we can hypothesize that biostimulation increased N use efficiency of wheat under reduced N input allowing also a grain yield not different from the conventional fertilization. Under ordinary N input management, both foliar fertilization and biostimulation increased N uptake (+7% for F and +15% for B), but this effect was significant only

Table 8 Grain yield and quality parameters.

Treatments	Grain (Mg ha ⁻¹)	TSW (g)	Proteins (% DW)	Gluten (% DW)
Test	4.2 d	37.3 a	11.7 d	9.2 d
Conv	6.7 ac	32.4 bc	13.0 ac	10.2 ab
Conv - F	6.0 c	31.6 c	13.6 a	10.7 a
Conv - B	7.2 ab	34.8 ac	12.6 c	9.9 bc
Conv - FB	7.3 a	31.1 c	13.4 ab	10.5 ab
75% Conv	6.3 c	37.5 a	11.2 d	8.8 e
75% Conv - F	6.1 c	34.9 ac	12.9 ac	10.2 ab
75% Conv - B	6.8 ac	35.6 ac	12.1 bc	9.5 cd
75% Conv - FB	6.3 bc	35.7 ab	13.1 ac	10.4 ab
Don Carmine	5.5 c	30.0 bc	13.6 a	10.7 a
Bisanzio	6.1 b	33.2 b	12.2 b	9.6 b
Metropolis	7.3 a	40.1 a	12.0 b	9.4 b

when F and B treatments were combined (+18% in Conv F-B as compared to Conv).

Conclusions

According to our results, a reduction of N inputs can be an option also for common wheat if coupled with the application of algae-based biostimulants. This can allow a reduction of costs associated to N inputs in wheat cropping systems limiting also N dispersion to the environment preserving yield and quality of grain. The combined application of foliar fertilization and biostimulant significantly improved wheat

performance also under conventional management, but in this case, it should be evaluated if the costs of these additional treatments can be compensated by the higher value of grain.

Acknowledgements

Research co-funded by MENFIN L.t.d.

Literature

- Al Majathoub M. 2004. Effect of biostimulants on the production of wheat (*Triticum aestivum* L.). Mediterranean Rainfed Agriculture: Strategies for Sustainability, CIHEAM, Zaragoza, 147-150.
- Arif M. et al. 2006. Response of wheat to foliar application of nutrients. J. Agric. Biol. Sci, 1(4):30-34.
- Seadh S.E. et al. 2009. Influence of micronutrient foliar application and nitrogen fertilization on wheat yield and quality of grain and seed. J. Biol. Sci., 9(8): 851-858.

Figure 13 Plant N uptake as affected by tested treatments.

Camelina, an Emerging Oilseed Crop, Intercropped with Pulses

Elena Pagani, Federica Zanetti, Erika Facciolla, Andrea Monti

DISTAL, Univ. Bologna, IT, elena.pagani6@unibo.it, federica.zanetti5@unibo.it, erika.facciolla2@unibo.it, a.monti@unibo.it

Introduction

Camelina (*Camelina sativa* L. Crantz) is currently garnering positive attention by biobased and aviation industries in Europe and North America thanks to its agronomic traits, such as high drought tolerance, short growing cycle, low input requirements, and the availability of both autumn and spring genotypes (Zanetti et al., 2021). Intercropping systems with pulses could be an interesting way to avoid land competition with food and benefit from the widely known advantages of the complementary interaction. These include land use maximization, increased crop stability, reduced weed pressure, and improved resource utilization. Furthermore, pulses are often included in intercrops because of their ability to fix nitrogen increasing its bioavailability in the soil and benefiting its companion plant as well. However, pulses suffer from weed competition especially at the early stages of growth. Furthermore, weed control and nutrient supply in organic farming are crucial aspects to consider. Thus, finding sustainable strategies, able to efficiently improve yields and the use of available resources, without the use of chemical inputs, is an important challenge to address. Therefore, camelina-pea and camelina-lentil combination can be a winning dual strategy: on the one side the iluc issue is solved, on the other the legumes benefit from a greater soil coverage and a consequent lower competition from weeds.

Materials and Methods

The study was carried out at the experimental organic farm of the University of Bologna at Ozzano dell'Emilia (44°25'N, 11°28'E). The experiment compared camelina-forage pea (C+P) and camelina-lentil (C+L) intercropping systems with the respective monocultures for two consecutive growing seasons (2021-2023). The experimental design was a randomized complete block design with four replicates. The seeding rates were 200 kg ha⁻¹ for sole-pea, 160 kg ha⁻¹ for sole-lentil, 8 kg ha⁻¹ sole-camelina, and half density was used for intercropping (50:50). Sowing took place at the end of October for camelina-pea (winter) and at the end of February for camelina-lentil (spring). A row drill was used for sowing, except for intercropped camelina which was broadcasted. The trials were unfertilized and the spring intercropping was irrigated to promote emergence. Soil coverage was assessed at 129 DAS (Days after Sowing) in the first year and 135 DAS in the second one by using the Canopeo app and taking three photos at 60 cm from the soil for each plot. The same survey was performed for spring intercropping at 43 DAS in the first year, and at 49 DAS in the second one. Weed density was surveyed for winter intercropping at 98 and 95 DAS in the first and the second year, respectively. Whereas for the spring trial weed density was determined at 35 DAS only in the second year. To determine the weed density, the weed plant number was counted within three individual areas of 0.04 m² in each plot. Seed yield, land equivalent ratio (LER), and competitive ratio (CR) was determined at harvest only on the first year data so far, since the secondo growing season is still ongoing. LER was used as an indicator of land-use efficiency for intercropping systems, as described by (De Wit et al., 1965).

$$LER = \sum_{j=1}^n \frac{Y_{j,i}}{Y_{j,s}}$$

where $Y_{j,i}$ and $Y_{j,s}$ are the grain yields in the intercropping and monoculture systems, respectively. An LER greater than one indicates that intercropping saves land. The competitive ratio (CR) index was obtained using the equation proposed by Willey (1979):

$$CR_{pulses} = \frac{LER_{pulses}}{LER_{came}} \quad CR_{camelina} = \frac{LER_{came}}{LER_{pulses}}$$

where the maximum value of the parameter refers to the larger competitive capacity of the species in the mixture.

Results

Intercropping systems showed greater soil coverage and lower weed density than the sole-legume and sole-camelina systems, except for the first year C+L soil coverage, and the second year C+P weed density, in which no significant differences were reported. Whereas, no significant differences were found for seed yields (Table 1). The total LER was assessed by the seeding ratio, which was equal to 1 in C+P, and greater than 1 in C+L. However, concerning CR camelina resulted more competitive with lentil than with pea (2.97 IC vs 0.70 SC), whereas CR of pea was .143 and that of lentil was 0.33.

Table 9. Soil coverage (%), Weed density (weeds/m²) and Seed yield (Mg DM /ha) in Camelina-Pea intercropping (C+P) compared to Sole-Pea (SP) and Sole-Camelina (SC) and in Camelina-Lentil intercropping (C+L) compared to Sole-Lentil (SL) and Sole-Camelina (SC) for two consecutive growing seasons (2021-2023)

Year	Soil coverage (%)		Weed density (weeds/m ²)		Seed Yield (Mg DM /ha)		Soil coverage (%)		Weed density (weeds/m ²)	Seed Yield (Mg DM /ha)
	21/22	22/23	21/22	22/23	21/22		21/22	22/23	22/23	21/22
SP	10 b	43 a	81 a	82 a	2.15 a	SL	10 a	80 a	58 a	0.38 a
SC	14 a	34 b	46 b	44 a	1.22 a	SC	12 a	50 b	37 ab	0.44 a
C+P	13 a	52 a	35 b	75 a	1.76 a	C+L	7 a	83 a	14 b	0.51 a

Conclusions

Both intercropping systems resulted excellent alternatives for diversifying organic agricultural systems without affecting the total seed production per area. Nevertheless, even though the total seed yield of the system did not increase significantly, a remarkable higher soil coverage was achieved thus reducing nutrient leaching and promoting competition against weeds. Furthermore, the presence of positive effects between crop components was demonstrated in C+L (LER>1), but at the same time the competitive ratio highlighted the limited competitive ability of lentil intercropped with camelina. So, further investigations on new seeding combination ratio are presumably needed to achieve a better balance on final seed yield of both crops.

Acknowledgements

The present research has been carried out in the framework of the SCOOP project, which is part of the CORE Organic Era-Net Programme supported by the European Union.

Literature

- Zanetti F. et al. 2021. Camelina, an ancient oilseed crop actively contributing to the rural renaissance in Europe. A review. *Agron. Sustain. Dev.*, 41: 2.
- De Wit C.T. et al. 1965. Competition between herbage plants. *J. Agric. Sci.*, 13: 212–221.
- Willey, R. 1979. Intercropping-its importance and research needs: Part 1. Competition and yield advantages. *Field Crop Abstracts*, 32: 1–10.

Effects of Deficit Irrigation on Mineral Elements Content of ‘Early’ Potato

Gaetano Pandino¹, Tiziana D’Anna², Giuseppa Scarso², Mariadaniela Mantineo², Davide Arnese¹, Claudia Formenti¹, Salvatore Alfio Salicola¹, Aurelio Scavo¹, Gaetano Roberto Pesce¹, Sara Lombardo^{1*}, Giovanni Mauromicale¹

¹ Di3A, Univ. Catania, IT, sara.lombardo@unict.it

² “I.I.S. Leonardo – sede A.M. Mazzei”, Giarre, IT

Introduction

Water is a pivotal key for crop production, because of its crucial role in nutrient uptake and transport, temperature regulation, and several physiological processes, including photosynthesis. The reduction in freshwater resources is the main problem for agricultural crop production specially, in arid and semi-arid regions, such as Mediterranean Basin. The water shortage lead to agriculture is forced to find new agro-technical approaches to adopt sustainable water use. For example, strategies to improve water use efficiency of irrigated crops are: deficit irrigation, precision irrigation technologies such as drip irrigation, smart irrigation, soil and water conservation practices (Bwambale et al., 2022). In arid and semi-arid regions, the deficit irrigation (DI) practice appears as a valuable and sustainable method for saving water to crop production, increase water use efficiency and optimize the yield of crops (Geerts and Raes, 2009). There are many reports proposing DI as a viable strategy to produce more per unit of water applied in different crops, including potato. This is one of the most important crop in the world, and it has high water requirements. It is typically grown in Mediterranean coastal areas during winter–spring seasons to obtain an early product, highly appreciated for its specific qualitative traits and profitably exported to northern European countries for fresh consumption (Lombardo et al., 2020). It represents a rich source of minerals contributing from 5 to 26% dietary reference intake (White et al., 2009). A recent study on ‘early’ potato conducted in a semi-arid Mediterranean environments validated the DI technique to save irrigation water without significantly compromising yields (Jerna and Mauromicale, 2023). However, the effects on nutritive quality have been little investigated. Therefore, the main aim of this research was to evaluate the effects of DI levels on mineral elements content of some ‘early’ cultivars grown under Mediterranean conditions.

Materials and Methods

A field experiment was conducted in the 2022 growing season at the experimental farm of the “I.I.S. Leonardo – A.M. Mazzei-” located on Giarre (CT), a typical area for ‘early’ potato cultivation in the southern Italy. The design was a split-plot with 3 blocks, considering the deficit irrigation level [irrigation only at plant emergence (I0), irrigation along the whole cycle supplying 50% (I50) and 100% (I100, as control) of the the maximum evapotranspiration (ETm)] as main plots and potato cultivars (‘Arizona’, ‘Levante’, ‘Paradiso’ and ‘Vogue’) as sub-plots. All the plots received an optimal fertilization formulated following the indications from Sicily Department of Agriculture. Tubers were harvested manually at the end of the cycle (about 120 days after planting) when 80% of leaves were bleached and dry. At least 20 marketable tubers (Ø 35–70 mm), of uniform size and disease-free, were washed with tap water, dried with tissue paper, diced and immediately oven-dried at 65 °C (Binder, Milan, Italy), until a constant weight was reached. The obtained dry material was ground and used for the determination of mineral elements (Ca, Mg, K, Fe, Mn and Zn) by AOAC method (1995). The content was expressed as mg kg⁻¹ of dry matter (DM). The data were subjected to two-way (‘deficit irrigation level x cultivar’) analysis of variance and means were separated by LSD test, when the *F*-test was significant.

Results

The content of both micro- and macro-mineral elements appeared to be statistically influenced by the DI level, with the exception of Mn (Figure). In particular, the I100 treatment showed a higher level of Mg, compared to the I50 and I0 treatments (Figure 1). On the other hand, the I0 irrigation treatment revealed the highest content of Ca, while the I50 treatment was characterized by the higher level of Zn (1.9 mg kg⁻¹ of DM) (Figure 1). In relation to the cultivar, ‘Arizona’ recorded both the highest content of Ca and Zn compared to the other cultivars under study (Figure 1). ‘Vogue’, along with ‘Levante’, reported the lowest content of Mn (0.9 mg kg⁻¹ of DM, on average) (Figure 1). As regards the Fe and K content, the cultivars under study did not show statistically significant differences (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Effect of deficit irrigation level and cultivar on the mineral elements content of ‘early’ potato tubers. Different letters within the same variable indicate significant differences for $P \leq 0.05$. I0: irrigation only at plant emergence; I50: irrigation along the whole cycle supplying 50% of the ET_m; I100: irrigation along the whole cycle supplying 100% of the ET_m (as control).

Conclusions

Overall, this study indicated that the irrigation regime based on 50% ET_m may represent a valid compromise in ‘early’ potato cultivation management in the perspective of both economic and environmental sustainability, saving about 1250 m³ ha⁻¹ of water irrigation. In addition, it provided a good content of K, Fe and Zn. However, further research still appears necessary to investigate the effects of DI level on other quality characteristics (*i.e.* carotenoids and starch content) of ‘early’ potato tubers.

Literature

- Bwambale E. et al. 2022. Smart irrigation monitoring and control strategies for improving water use efficiency in precision agriculture: A review. *Agric. Water Manag.*, 260: 107324.
- Geerts S. and Raes D. 2009. Deficit irrigation as an on-farm strategy to maximize crop water productivity in dry areas. *Agric. Water Manag.*, 96: 1275-1284.
- Ierna A. and Mauromicale G. 2023. Eco-physiological and productive response of deficit irrigated potatoes. *Agronomy*, 13: 591.
- Lombardo S. et al. 2020. Optimizing nitrogen fertilization to improve qualitative performances and physiological and yield responses of potato (*Solanum tuberosum* L.). *Agronomy*, 10: 352.
- White P.J. et al. 2009. Relationships between yield and mineral concentrations in potato tubers. *HortSci.*, 44: 6-11.

Adaptability of Coloured Potato Cultivars to the Mediterranean Environment

Alessandra Pellegrino¹, Salvatore La Rosa¹, Bruno Parisi², Salvatore Salicola³, Giovanni Mauromicale³, Anita Ierna¹

¹ IBE-CNR, Catania, IT, alessandra.pellegrino@cnr.it, salvatore.larosa@cnr.it, anita.ierna@cnr.it

² CREA-CI, Bologna, IT, bruno.paris@crea.gov.it

³ Di3A, Univ. Catania, IT, salvosalicola94@hotmail.it, g.mauromicale@unict.it

Introduction

In the Mediterranean Basin, potato (*Solanum tuberosum* L.) with a dedicated surface area of ~3 million hectares and an overall production of 28 Mt of tubers (FAO, 2020) is cultivated not only in the usual cycle (spring–summer), but also in a winter–spring cycle (from November–January to March–early June), especially in several coastal countries such as southern Italy, Tunisia, Egypt, Cyprus, Israel, Lebanon and Turkey for early production. The early potato represents an economically important crop in Sicily, highly appreciated in Italy and abroad for the peculiar qualitative characteristics compared to the common potato (Ierna and Mauromicale 2022). In recent years, however, regional potato growing has been called upon to expand the available germplasm, above all in response to growing foreign competition. Given that consumers appear increasingly oriented towards products with high functional standards, skin and/or pulp coloured potatoes are seeing a growing interest, especially in relation to their high content in anthocyanins and/or carotenoids which are antioxidants in the human diet (Lombardo et al., 2013). This research, fitting in to such context, was carried out within the Project "ALIFUN - Development of functional foods for the innovation of traditional Italian food products" (ARS01-00783), with the aim of evaluating the adaptability of coloured potato cultivars to a highly representative area of Sicilian potato growing.

Materials and methods

Field experiment was conducted during 2021 on the coastal plain south of Siracusa (37° 00' N, 15°31' E, 20 m a.s.l.), Sicily, a typical area for early potato cultivation, on a clay-loam soil. Three yellow skin and intense yellow flesh cultivars (Hermes, Monique, Regina), three deep purple skin and purple flesh cultivars (Salad Blue, Violet Queen, Bleu st. Galler) and yellow light skin and flesh cultivar Soprano (as control) were evaluated. The adaptability to the Mediterranean environment was primarily evaluated through a series of production parameters. The experimental design used was a randomized block with three replications; each block consisted of seven cultivars, i.e. six rows each consisting of 90 plants at 5.3 plant m⁻² (0.25 m × 0.75 m). Planting was carried out by hand on 14 January, utilizing whole sprouted seed-tubers. Throughout the crop cycle, 120 kg ha⁻¹ di N, 120 kg ha⁻¹ di P₂O₅, 150 kg ha⁻¹ di K₂O and about 1000 m³ha⁻¹ of irrigation water were supplied. Cultivation management (weeds, animal and vegetable parasites control) was carried out in harmony with the needs of the crop. Leaf SPAD absorbance (correlated to chlorophyll content) was measured in the field using a portable Chl meter (SPAD 502, Minolta Camera, Osaka, Japan) weekly at 93, 100, 107 and 114 days after planting (DAP). All measurements were made from the tip of the youngest fully expanded leaf between 11:00 and 13:00 h (local solar time). Tubers were hand harvested at 125 DAP and were classified in marketable (unitary weight > 20 g) and unmarketable (unitary weight < 20 g, or deformed, green and diseased). Marketable tubers were used to determine marketable yield (MY), the number of marketable tubers per plant (NMTP) and the average marketable tuber weight (AMTW). Based on the measurement of the transverse diameter, marketable tubers were also divided into three dimensional classes: <40 mm, 40-60 mm and > 60 mm) and the percentage incidence of each class on the overall marketable production was calculated. A representative sample of marketable tubers - at least thirty tubers per replicate for each cultivar - was washed and dried at 65 °C up to constant weight to evaluate dry matter (DM) content (AOAC, 2010).

Results

The SPAD values, on the average of the four weekly measurements, in the pigmented cultivars were significantly lower than in the cv. Soprano, ranging between 38.1 SPAD units (Salad Blue) and 46.9 SPAD units (Regina) (Table 1). Yellow flesh cultivars, with the exception of Hermes, yielded similarly to Soprano (39.0 t ha⁻¹), whereas purple flesh cultivars gave significantly lower MY than cv. Soprano, ranging between 16.7 t ha⁻¹ (Bleau St. Galler) and 32.7 t ha⁻¹ (Salad Blue). Yield differences depended more on the AMTW which fluctuated between 23.4 g (Bleau San Galler) and 69.4 g (Hermes), than on the NMTP, ranging from 7.9 (Hermes) to 17.2 (Salad Blue) (Table 1).

Table 1 – Chlorophyll content (SPAD), marketable yield (MY), number of marketable tubers per plant (NMTP), average marketable tuber weight (AMTW) and tubers’ dry matter content (DM) in relation to cultivars. Different letters within each column indicate significance at P≤0.01.

Cultivar	SPAD (units)	MY (t ha ⁻¹)	NMTP (N plant ⁻¹)	AMTW (g)	DM (%)
Hermes	40.8 c	29.5 c	7.9 e	69.6 a	20.8 a
Monique	42.1 c	39.3 a	15.3 b	50.1 c	14.8 c
Regina	46.9 b	36.5 a	15.5 b	44.6 d	16.9 b
Salad blue	38.1 d	32.7 b	17.2 a	35.7 e	18.9 b
Violet Queen	45.0 b	27.9 c	15.0 b	34.9 e	17.4 b
Bleau st. Galler	46.6 b	16.7 d	13.6 c	23.4 f	21.8 a
Soprano (control)	49.2 a	39.0 a	11.7 d	62.7 b	18.0 b

Figure 1 - Percentage of tubers in three dimensional classes (<40 mm, 40-60 mm and > 60 mm) in the studied cultivars

Tuber dry matter content ranged from 14.8% (Monique) to about 21.3% (Hermes and Bleau st. Galler); the remaining cultivars showed values not statistically different from Soprano (18%) (Table1). Monique, Regina, Salad Blue and Soprano showed a high incidence (63%) in the 40-60 mm class, while Violet Queen and Bleau st. Galler showed a high incidence (50% and 77% respectively) in the lower calibre class (<40 mm); on the contrary, Hermes showed almost 50% of the production in the highest calibre class (>60 mm) (Figure 1).

Conclusion

The results of this research, even if preliminary, seem to show a good adaptability of studied coloured potato cultivars to the Mediterranean environment, providing, with the exclusion of only one, yield characteristics similar to cultivar used as control. Together with their high tubers dry matter content, this makes them worthy of attention from both growers and consumers.

Literature

- AOAC, Association of Official Analytical Chemists. Official Methods of Analysis. <http://www.aoac.org/> (accessed 26 January 2018).
- FAO, 2020. FAO statistical database. Production. Crops. Rome, Italy. <http://faostat.fao.org> (accessed 30 October 2021).
- Ierna A. and Mauromicale G., 2022. How irrigation water saving strategy can affect tuber growth and nutritional composition of potato. *Sci. Hortic.*, 299: 111034.
- Lombardo S. et al. 2013. The influence of growing environment on the antioxidant and mineral content of “early” crop potato. *J. Food Compos. Anal.*, 32: 28–35.

A Comparative Test of Rain Gun and Rainger Applied to Grain Maize in the North-eastern Italy

Gaetano Roberto Pesce, Luca Cestaro, Maurizio Borin, Carmelo Maucieri

DAFNAE, Univ. Padova, IT, gaetano.pesce@unipd.it

Introduction

Maize for grain production is the second most cultivated cereal in Italy, with an average of 585,000 ha (mainly concentrated in North Italy) (ISTAT, 2023). Water stress represents main abiotic adversity, for this crop as it reduces yields and negatively affects grain quality. Flowering is the most sensitive phase to water shortages, and occurs when temperatures are high and rainfall is scarce. Irregular distribution of rainfall due to climate changes worsened the drought in the periods of maximum crop water requirement. For these reasons, maize cultivation needs a rational management of irrigation exploiting the potential offered by the up to date available technologies (e.g. remote sensing from satellites) and choosing the most efficient irrigation systems. Hence, an experiment was conducted to compare two irrigation systems (rain gun and Rainger) adopting the Climate FieldView™ platform for irrigation management.

Materials and Methods

The experiment was conducted from 2020 to 2022 in a farm located in North-East Italy (Rovigo province). The soil texture is loamy, while the local climate is temperate with humid summers. The experiment was conducted in four plots of approximately 70 m × 595 m, two irrigated with rain gun and two with Rainger, for a total of ~16.5 ha. Each plot was divided into four replications of ~1 ha (70 m × 150 m). The corn hybrid employed in the three years was DKC 6980 (FAO class 700). The adopted methodology was typical of the On Farm Experimentation approach: real field conditions and interaction between the researcher and the farmer (Toffolini and Jeuffroy, 2022). Pre-sowing fertilization was carried out each year supplying 170 kg N ha⁻¹ and 60 kg P₂O₅ ha⁻¹ as poultry manure. Sowings were done to obtain a density of 9 plants m⁻² with a row spacing of 75 cm. Irrigation management was carried out using the Climate FieldView™ platform, which operates on satellite data (Sentinel-2). ET_c was determined by the platform from the LAI estimation, obtained with the canopy reflectance measurement. The irrigations were provided only in June, July and August (in 2022 also in May) in order to replenish 100% of the ET_c. However, since the information provided by the satellite was on a weekly basis and the platform did not consider the meteorological conditions, some inspections by the field technician and a supplementary meteorological station were still necessary, in order to make prudent decisions about the time of irrigation. The water use efficiency (WUE) was calculated as the dry matter of grain obtained with the unit volume of water resulting from the sum of rainfall and irrigation (kg DM m⁻³). The grain was harvested with a harvester equipped with sensors able to generate grain yield maps. An agrometeorological station next to the experimental field measured and recorded: solar radiation, air temperature, rainfall, dew point, relative humidity, vapor deficit pressure and leaf wetness.

Results

Seasonal rainfall constantly decreased along the three years (Table 1), determining an increase of the seasonal irrigation volumes (Table 1). The ET_c obtained with Climate FieldView was decidedly higher than ET_c obtained using the ET₀ calculated with the Hargreaves formula adapted to the conditions of north-eastern Italy (Berti et al., 2014) and Kc (Allen et al., 1998) (Table 1). Furthermore, the average temperatures recorded during the cultivation cycles increased from 2020 to 2022, as well as the days with maximum temperature above the maximum cardinal temperature (Table 1). These data describe the growing stress to which the crop was subjected over the years. Rainger achieved significantly higher yields than rain gun in two of the three years (Table 2). However, yields constantly decreased over the three years with both

irrigation systems, but at a different rate (Table 2). Similarly to yield, the WUE was significantly higher with Rainger than with rain gun in two years characterized by lower rainfall (Table 2).

Table 1. Comparison between water supplies and losses (mm), mean air temperatures and cultivation cycles length during the three experimental years.

Year	Irrigation system	Cycle duration (d)	Rainfall (mm)	SWC 10-60 (mm)	Irrigation (mm)	ETc Sat (mm)	ETc Har (mm)	Δ Sat (mm)	Δ Har (mm)	Mean air temperature (°C)	DAMCT (d)
2020	Rain gun	162	327	125	200	794	568	-142	84	19.9	51
	Rainger	153			177	773	551	-144	78		46
2021	Rain gun	154	264	125	280	813	580	-144	90	20.7	61
	Rainger	153			180	840	580	-271	-11		61
2022	Rain gun	139	172	110	320	608	574	-6	28	22.1	86
	Rainger	145			251	667	592	-134	-59		87

SWC 10-60 = soil water content at a depth of 10 to 60 cm before sowing. ETc Sat = ETc calculated by the app from satellite measurements. ETc Har = ETc calculated by adding the daily ET0 (according to Hargreaves) calculated with the data collected by the meteorological station. Δ Sat = Difference between water supplies and losses (ETc) calculated by the app starting from satellite measurements. Δ Har = Difference between water supplies and losses (ETc) calculated by adding the daily ET0 (according to Hargreaves) obtained with the data collected by the meteorological station. DAMCT = days with maximum temperature above the maximum cardinal temperature.

Table 2. Grain yields and WUE obtained with the two irrigation systems in the three years of experimentation. *ns* = not significant differences between irrigation systems within each year. Different capital letters indicate yield significant differences between irrigation systems within each year. Different small letters indicate WUE significant differences between irrigation systems within each year.

Source of variation		Yield	WUE
Y	I	(t DM ha ⁻¹)	(kg m ⁻³)
2020	Rain gun	13.0 <i>ns</i>	2.38 <i>ns</i>
	Rainger	13.2 <i>ns</i>	2.52 <i>ns</i>
2021	Rain gun	11.0 B	1.81 b
	Rainger	11.6 A	2.28 a
2022	Rain gun	9.0 <u>B</u>	1.54 <u>b</u>
	Rainger	11.0 <u>A</u>	2.16 <u>a</u>

WUE = water use efficiency. Y = year. I = irrigation system.

Literature

Allen R.G. et al. 1998. Crop evapotranspiration-Guidelines for computing crop water requirements-FAO Irrigation and drainage paper 56. Fao, Rome, 300(9), D05109.

Berti A. et al. 2014. Assessing reference evapotranspiration by the Hargreaves method in north-eastern Italy. Agric. Water Manag., 140: 20-25.

ISTAT 2023. <https://www.istat.it/>, retrieved on May 13th, 2023.

Toffolini Q. and Jeuffroy M.H. 2022. On-farm experimentation practices and associated farmer-researcher relationships: a systematic literature review. Agron. Sustain. Dev., 42(6): 114.

Conclusions

Yields and WUE values obtained with Rainger were significantly higher than those obtained with rain gun. On the other hand, a significant and progressive decrease from 2020 to 2022 for both yields and WUE was observed. These variations could reflect the thermo-pluviometric trend over the three-year period, characterized by decreasing annual rainfall and increasing annual mean temperatures.

Acknowledgment

This study was carried out within the Agritech National Research Center and received funding from the European Union Next-GenerationEU (PIANO NAZIONALE DI RIPRESA E RESILIENZA (PNRR) – MISSIONE 4 COMPONENTE 2, INVESTIMENTO 1.4 – D.D. 1032 17/06/2022, CN00000022). This manuscript reflects only the authors' views and opinions, neither the European Union nor the European Commission can be considered responsible for them.

Improving Tomato Production by Inoculation of Arbuscular Mycorrhizal Fungi

Valentina Quintarelli¹, Emanuele Radicetti^{1*}, Mattia Baretta¹,
Mortadha Ben Hassine¹, Roberto Mancinelli²

¹ DOCPAS, Univ. Ferrara, IT, emanuele.radicetti@unife.it

² DAFNE), Univ. Tuscia, IT

Introduction

The Mediterranean area is expected to be strongly affected by the climate change determining a reduction of the average yearly precipitation, which leads to water scarcity. Tomato (*Lycopersicon esculentum* Mill.) is one of the most important vegetable crops widely cultivated in Mediterranean. Tomato is a water-demanding crop, and, consequently, water deficit can result in severe yield decreases compared with cultivation under fully irrigated conditions. Among others, drought causes nutrition disturbances as roots are unable to take up a range of nutrients from the soil due to reduced root activity and interruption of water continuity in soil pores. In addition, the high costs and excessive fertilizer application in intensive cropping systems also raises economical and environmental concerns, respectively. The symbiotic relationship between arbuscular mycorrhizal fungi (AMF) and higher plant roots helps plants cope with drought stress (Leventis et al., 2021). Nowadays, there is considerable interest in harnessing these fungal bioresources as bioinoculants for improving growth and tolerance to sub-optimal conditions of economically important crops. The aims of this study are to examine the effects of two commercial mycorrhizal products on tomato production.

Materials and Methods

The experiment was carried out during the 2022 tomato growing season at F.lli Baretta farm located in Ferrara, Italy (44°72'70" N, 12°08'12" E, altitude 2 m). Tomato plants of a commercial variety (*Lycopersicon esculentum* Mill.) cv. Heinz 1301 F1 were produced in a private nursery. The experiment consisted in two commercial inoculums: (i) MICOSAT F®, containing a mixture of selected mycorrhizal fungi, bacteria and streptomices derived from rhizosphere (hereafter called AMF_1), and (ii) MYCOUP 360 composed of a mycorrhizae-forming fungus and bacteria (hereafter called AMF_2). Both commercial products were applied at tomato sowing under nursery conditions. In addition, a no inoculated tomato plants were cultivated (hereafter called NoAMF). All treatments were replicated three times in a complete randomized blocks experimental design. One-month old tomato seedlings were transplanted under field condition on April 28, 2022, at the stage of five true leaves and managed under organic farming practices until tomato harvesting on 8 August, 2022. Each plot was of 27 m² (4.5 x 6 m). A Chlorophyll Concentration Meter (MC-100) was used to obtain readings estimating chlorophyll concentration of tomato plants on the 4th fully grown leaf from the top of the plant. The readings were performed every 10 days throughout the growing season. Ten measurements per treatment were taken in each replication and averaged. The tomato yield and yield characteristics were determined by harvesting and weighing the fresh red fruits of 5 consecutive tomato plants picked from the middle paired rows from all plots. Tomato fruits were collected based on: marketable tomato yield (number and weight) considering red

Figure 1. The effects of AMF inoculation on chlorophyll content (SPAD readings) of tomato leaves during the growing cycle of the crop. Data correspond to the 2022 growing seasons. Error bars represent standard error from mean (n = 9).

and disease free fruits, and un-marketable tomato fruits divided into green fruits (number) and rotten fruits (number).

Results

Figure 2. The effect of AMF inoculation on marketable tomato yield and tomato straw. Values belonging to the same character without common letters are statistically different according to LSD (0.05).

The SPAD values generally tended to increase after tomato transplanting reaching the high values at the end of June (flowering stage) which then tended to be constant up to the harvesting. However, several differences were observed among treatments, especially AMF_2 showed the highest values during the whole cultivation period, followed by AMF_1, while the lowest values was observed in NoAMF (Fig. 1). Moreover, inoculated plants (AMF_1 and AMF_2) reach levels of photosynthetic capacity (estimated by the SPAD values) higher to those of NoAMF tomato plants, showing that mycorrhization is capable to improve the photosynthetic activity of

	Marketable tomato fruit (n. m ⁻²)	Longitudinal diameter (cm)	Equatorial diameter (cm)	Firmness (N)	SSC (°Brix)	pH
NoAMF	169.3 c	5.28 b	3.85 b	5.27 b	5.25 a	4.30 a
AMF_1	292.0 a	5.21 b	3.85 b	6.24 a	5.18 a	4.25 a
AMF_2	252.0 b	5.60 a	4.05 a	6.26 a	5.21 a	4.26 a

Table 1. The main effects of tomato plant inoculation on quality parameters of the marketable tomato fruits at tomato harvesting. Mean values belonging to the same factor without common letters are statistically different to LSD ($p < 0.05$). SSC = Soluble Solid Content.

tomato plants as observed by Fracasso et al. (2020). AMF can stimulate plant growth through a range of mechanisms, including exudation of substances acting as plant growth regulators or stimulation of their biosynthesis by plants, improved nutrient acquisition. Similarly, the marketable tomato yield and straw measured at tomato harvesting were higher in AMF_1 and AMF_2 compared with NoAMF (on average 10.8 vs. 7.8 t ha⁻¹ of FM and 2.9 vs. 2.2 t ha⁻¹ of DM, respectively, Fig. 2). Several studies have shown that AMF can increase tomato fruit production, an effect that could be ascribed to enhanced plant nutrition status and protection against plant diseases. The AMF_1 inoculated tomato plants produced the highest number of fruits, followed by AMF_2, while NoAMF showed the lowest number of tomato fruits (292, 252 and 169.3 n m⁻², respectively). Tomato fruit measured AMF_2 leading in greater tomato fruit size. The firmness of tomato fruit was higher in both AMF_1 and AMF_2 than NoAMF (on average 6.25 vs. 5.27 N, respectively), while no differences were observed on SSC and pH.

Conclusions

The improved vegetative growth of plants inoculated with all AMF strains tested in this study, but especially with AMF_2, corroborates previous studies, which showed that application of appropriate AMF strains may improve tomato growth and fruit yield. These results show that AMF represent a promising resource for improving both sustainable food production needs for future demand throughout the world.

Literature

- Leventis G. et al. 2021. Arbuscular mycorrhizal fungi enhance growth of tomato under normal and drought conditions, via different water regulation mechanisms. *Rhizosphere*, 19: 100394
- Fracasso A. et al. 2020. Physiological Beneficial Effect of *Rhizophagus intraradices* Inoculation on Tomato Plant Yield under Water Deficit Conditions. *Agronomy*, 10: 71.

Tomato Plant Growth and Production as Affected by Inoculation with Arbuscular Mycorrhizal Fungi

Valentina Quintarelli¹, Emanuele Radicetti^{1*}, Mattia Baretta¹,
Mortadha Ben Hassine¹, Roberto Mancinelli²

¹DOCPAS, Univ. Ferrara, IT, emanuele.radicetti@unife.it

²DAFNE, Univ. Tuscia, IT

Introduction

Nowadays, the growth and development of cultivated plants, especially tomato, are severely limited by biotic and abiotic stresses. To cope with this constraint, the plant establishes symbiotic relationships with arbuscular mycorrhizal fungi (AMF) in the soil whose extension of the hyphae allows a better and deeper exploration, improving plant health (Balestrini & Lumini, 2018). The need to produce quality tomato seedlings, capable of withstanding adverse abiotic and biotic stresses after transplanting and improve mineral nutrient uptake, inspired producers to consider the inoculation with AMF in the nursery. The main objective of this study was to investigate the interactive effects of nursery inoculation with AMF on growth and yield of tomato seedlings under field conditions.

Materials and Methods

The experiment was carried out during the 2022 growing season at F.lli Baretta farm located in Ferrara, Italy (44°72'70" N, 12°08'12" E, altitude 2 m). Tomato plants (*Lycopersicon esculentum* Mill.) of a commercial variety cv. Heinz 1301 F1 were produced in a private nursery. The experiment consisted in two commercial inoculums: (i) MICOSAT F®, containing a mixture of selected mycorrhizal fungi, bacteria and streptomices derived from rhizosphere (hereafter called AMF_1), and (ii) MYCOUP 360 composed of a mycorrhizae-forming fungus and a bacteria (hereafter called AMF_2). Both commercial products were applied at tomato sowing under nursery conditions. In addition, a no inoculated tomato plants were cultivated (hereafter called NoAMF). One-month old tomato seedlings were transplanted under field condition on April 28, 2022, at the stage of five true leaves and managed under organic farming practices until tomato harvesting on 8 August, 2022. Each plot was of 27 m² (4.5 x 6 m). All treatments were replicated three times in a complete randomized blocks experimental design. At tomato transplanting (T0), 5 tomato seedlings of each experimental treatments were carefully cleaned and subjected to determination of shoot and root characteristics. The same parameters were measured 30 days after tomato transplanting (T1) by collecting 5 tomato plants from the soil. At harvesting, 5 tomato plants were harvested to determine fruit yield and fruit characteristics. Tomato fruits were collected based on: marketable tomato yield (number and weight) considering red and disease free fruits, and un-marketable tomato fruits divided into green fruits (number) and rotten fruits (number).

Results

At transplanting, tomato seedlings subjected to inoculation (AMF_1 and AMF_2) showed higher values of shoot biomass, plant height, number of leaves and root biomass compared to the No_AMF tomato seedling (Table 1). However, the greatest differences were observed 30 days after tomato transplanting, with AMF_2 that showed the greatest shoot biomass (66 g plant⁻¹ of FM) and greater value of root length (35.4 mm). However, both AMF_1 and AMF_2 showed significant higher values of stem diameter (8.5 mm), number of leaves (33.9 n. plants⁻¹

Figure 1. Tomato seedling collected 30 days after transplanting (T1).

¹), leaf length and width (5.13 and 2.82 cm, respectively) and SPAD values (50.5) compared with the No_AMF tomato plants (Table 1).

Treatments	Shoot fresh biomass (g plant ⁻¹)	Shoot dry biomass (g plant ⁻¹)	Plant height (cm)	Stem diameter (mm)	Leaves (n. plant ⁻¹)	Leaf length (cm)	Leaf width (cm)	SPAD	Root biomass (g plant ⁻¹)	Root length (cm)
Nomic	1.88 b	0.20 b	16.6 b	3.3 a	12.8 b	2.35 a	1.25 a	20.4 a	0.49 b	7.9 a
T0 Micosat	2.26 a	0.25 a	17.6 ab	3.8 a	16.5 a	2.51 a	1.30 a	20.0 a	0.73 a	7.7 a
Micoup	2.13 ab	0.24 a	17.8 a	3.5 a	16.3 a	2.27 a	1.21 a	19.4 a	0.65 a	7.3 a
Nomic	35.63 c	5.16 b	40.2 c	7.3 b	28.0 b	4.54 b	2.50 b	46.5 b	5.35 c	21.7 c
T1 Micosat	42.96 b	6.64 b	44.7 a	8.7 a	33.7 a	4.91 a	2.75 a	49.8 a	6.68 b	25.4 b
Micoup	66.45 a	9.43 a	42.8 b	8.3 a	34.0 a	5.35 a	2.89 a	51.1 a	9.22 a	35.4 a

Table 1. The main effects of tomato plant inoculation on plant characteristics at transplanting (T0) and 30 days after transplanting (T1). Mean values belonging to the same factor without common letters are statistically different to LSD ($p < 0.05$).

Figure 2. The effect of AMF inoculation on fruit yield and tomato fruit characteristics. Values belonging to the same character without common letters are statistically different according to LSD ($P < 0.05$).

The capacity to overcome transplant shock and become established in a field environment after transplanting depends on the water and nutrient uptake capacity of the roots, and the capacity of the preexisting root system to rapidly expand. Indeed, AMF constitute a type of association characterized by the formation of intracellular structures called arbuscules, where exchange of nutrients and carbon exchanges between the symbiotic partners takes place. Nzanza and colleagues (2012) demonstrated that pre-inoculation of AMF at nursery condition have a positive impact in improving the growth and development of tomato seedlings determining higher weight of shoot and root than the control. The results also found that inoculation of AMF has a positive effect on the fruit yield of processing tomato (+33%) improving the fruit set of the plant. In facts, fruit yield of inoculated plant showed higher marketable tomato fruit production compared with No_AMF (on average 1.48 vs. 1.11 kg plant⁻¹, respectively). In detailed, inoculated plants showed high number of marketable tomato fruits per plants (+72%), especially in AMF_1 (41.7 n. plant⁻¹). It is also interesting to note that AMF_1 and AMF_2 showed the higher level of green fruit indicating healthy tomato plants, even if this aspect could be not desirable for processing tomato. Conversely, rotten tomato fruits were reduced by 15% under inoculated tomato plants indicating the better status of

the fruits. Therefore, the quantity and quality of tomato fruits produced in the inoculated plants was better than in the no inoculated plants.

Conclusions

The nursery inoculation of tomato plants with AMF determined favourable conditions for the adaptation of tomato seedlings to transplanting stress showing more resilient tomato plants compared to the control. The improved fruit yield and the high value of marketable tomato showed that AMF can maintain and improve the quality and quantity production of tomato crop.

Literature

- Nzanza B. et al. 2012. Yield and nutrient content of tomato (*Solanum lycopersicum* L.) as influenced by *Trichoderma harzianum* and *Glomus mosseae* inoculation. *Sci. Hort.*, 144: 55-59.
- Balestrini R. and Lumini E. 2018. Focus on mycorrhizal symbioses. *Appl. Soil Ecol.*, 123: 299-304

Use of Spectral Indices to Optimize Irrigation Management of Apricot in Mediterranean Environment

Carmela Riefolo, Laura D'Andrea

CREA-AA, Sede di Bari, IT, carmela.riefolo@crea.gov.it, laura.dandrea@crea.gov.it

Introduction

Apricot (*Prunus armeniaca* L.) is represented with more than 75% of the world production in European and Mediterranean countries. Apricot is particularly suitable for low input growing agricultural systems as observed in southern Italy, where apricot productions are spreading widely. This species is characterized by a nonsurplus production by a wide range of possible valorization and by a particular adaptation to different environmental conditions due to a notable richness of local genotypes. It, like all crops in the Mediterranean area, can suffer from low water availability so it is important a correct irrigation management. In this regard, a research was carried out with two varieties and in two years using hyperspectral analysis to determine the physiological response of apricot leaves in the same irrigation management in order to optimize water resources so valuable in the Mediterranean area.

Materials and Methods

Two apricot varieties, Farlis and Farbaly, were studied. They were grown in an experimental field of Putignano (BA) in Apulia Region of Southern Italy. Leaves of 9 trees of each one were analyzed. Each tree was divided in 2 hemispheres, shaded and illuminated. On shaded hemisphere, 2 theses were chosen: east, north. On illuminated hemisphere, 2 theses were chosen: south, west. Along central length of tree 1 thesis was chosen called central. Three scans were carried out with Field Spec 4 on one leaf representing each thesis. Finally, each variety was represented by 162 spectra. The reflectance spectra were collected in two years of activity (2019-2020). In particular, hyperspectral data collected in late July were considered. Leaf spectral measurements were performed in the field with Field Spec IV spectroradiometer (Analytical Spectral Devices Inc., Boulder, Colorado, USA) using artificial light able to detect a spectral signature in a range of 350–2500 nm. Field Spec IV provided spectra with 2151 bands having a resolution of 1 nm. The calibration was repeated for each plant, with a standard white reference 10 × 10 cm² disk (Spectralon panel, Lab-sphere, Inc., North Sutton, NH, USA) increasing the comparability of measurements. Continuum Removal (CR) methodology computed D_{epht} values at minimum reflectance of absorbance peaks as a measure of intensity to a reflectance reference value of 1 (Van Der Meer, 2004). This elaboration was performed by ViewSpecPro Program (Analytical Spectral Devices Inc., Boulder, Colorado, USA).

Results

In order to assess the water content in apricot leaves, CR data of Farlis and Farbaly, were computed for individual theses of the 2 years activities, and compared. The methodology was applied around wavelength ranges showing a minimum of reflectance (Table 1).

Table 1. Wavelength ranges with a minimum of reflectance identified as zones (Z)

Range (nm)	Minimum wavelength.(nm)	Zone
820-1100	1000	Z1
1100-1270	1170	Z2
1270-1660	1460	Z3
1660-1880	1830	Z4
1880-2170	1980	Z5

The reflectance ranges (Z) where there are absorbance peaks are similar to those found by an other research (Gonzalez-Fernandez et al., 2015). Figure 1 shows the D_{epht} values in Farlis and Farbaly, from Z1 to Z4 Farbaly shows D_{epht} higher than Farlis, while in Z5 the trend is inverted. These differences are significative

in Z1, Z2 and Z5 according to t-test of Student at a level of probability <0.01 . The Z1 region was associated to dry matter content and leaf structure (Gaulton et al., 2013), Z2 region to leaf water content (Clevers et al., 2010), and Z5 region to organic compounds characterized by O-H link as Z3 (Shenk et al., 2001). Z4 was associated probably to lignin content but not to water (Goetze et al., 2010). The inversion of trend from Z1 and Z2 respect to Z5 confirms the association with water content that, when is lower, determines an higher organic compounds content.

Figure 1. Representation of Continuum Removal methodology with Depht value computed according to Van Der Meer (2004) applied to Farbaly (red line) and Farlis (blue line) at the wavelengths showing a peak of absorbance.

Conclusions

Farbaly showed an absorbance peak greater significantly than Farlis, in a region associated with water content. This trend was inverted in Z5 region associated with organic compounds content, confirming the higher water content in Farbaly. So the leaf structure and water content determine physiological conditions in Farbaly better than in Farlis in the same irrigation management. This experimental approach provides a simple way to help irrigation management for different apricot varieties in dry environments.

Literature

- Clevers J.G.P.W. et al. 2010. Estimating canopy water content using hyperspectral remote sensing data. *Int. J. Appl. Earth Obs. Geoinf*, 12: 119–125.
- Gaulton R. et al. 2013. The potential of dual wavelength laser scanning for estimating vegetation moisture content. *Remote Sens. Environ*, 132: 32–39.
- Gonzalez-Fernandez A.B. et al. 2015. Spectroscopic estimation of leaf water content in commercial vineyards using continuum removal and partial least squares regression. *Sci. Hortic*, 188: 15–22.
- Götze C. et al. 2010. Spectrometric analyses in comparison to the physiological condition of heavy metal stressed floodplain vegetation in a standardised experiment. *Cent. Eur. J. Geosci*, 2: 132–137.
- Shenk J.S. et al. 2001. Application of NIR spectroscopy to agricultural products. In: Burns, D.A., Ciurczak, E.D. (Eds.), *Handbook of Near Infrared Analysis (Practical Spectroscopy Series)*, second ed. Donald A. Burns, New York, NY, pp. 419–474.
- Van Der Meer F. 2004. Analysis of spectral absorption features in hyperspectral imagery. *Int. J. Appl. Earth Obs. Geoinf*, 5(1): 55–68.

Soil Carbon Content in Long-Term Experiment under Different Soil Tillage Management Systems

Michele Rinaldi¹, Salvatore Baiano², Antonio Troccoli¹, Angelo Pio De Santis¹, Leonardo Morcone¹, Luigi Morra²

¹ CREA-CI, Foggia, IT, michele.rinaldi@crea.gov.it

² CREA-CI, Caserta, IT, luigi.morra@crea.gov.it

Introduction

Soil fertility decline, due to soil erosion and organic matter depletion, is the biggest sustainability challenge for conventional tillage in dryland agriculture of Southern Italy and the adoption of No-Tillage (NT) practices can address these issue (Troccoli et al., 2015). Conservation agriculture (CA) includes three main components: crop rotation, reduced soil disturbance (including NT, and minimum tillage, MT) and crop residue mulching (Rinaldi et al., 2022).

It has been estimated that a soil organic carbon (SOC) sequestration rate of 0.4–0.8 Pg C yr⁻¹ can be achieved through the adoption of CA practices across all cropping systems globally, which may account for 33–100% of total SOC sequestration potential in the world. Furthermore, converting soil tillage from conventional (CT) to NT alone can potentially increase SOC at a rate of 0.1–1 Mg C ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹ (Lal, 2004). In addition, NT can mitigate soil CO₂ emissions and improve soil structural stability, soil nutrient availability, and water holding capacity (Li et al., 2019).

Aim of this work is to assess the response of soil organic carbon content and soil structural stability to two different soil tillage management systems (NT and MT) applied in Southern Italy for 9 years.

Materials and Methods

The experiment was established in the fall 2013 at the CREA-CI (Foggia, Italy; 41° 28'N, 15° 32'E; 75 m a.s.l.) on a clay-loam soil (Typic Chromoxerert). Main soil traits were 30% clay, 25% sand; pH 7.5; 12.5 g kg⁻¹ total C. Mean long-term rainfall of the site is 479 mm and mean air temperatures are 12.2 °C in fall, 8.2 °C in winter, and 17.6 °C in spring.

The experiment was a randomized block design, replicated 5 times with elementary plots of about 1 ha size. Two soil tillage management systems were compared: direct seeding on No-Tillage (NT) and Minimum-Tillage (MT). MT included wheat straw removal before the tillage operation, disk cultivator at 15 cm depth and a vibro-till at 10 cm before sowing; NT included crop residues left on soil surface, use of glyphosate at a rate of 720 g of active ingredient ha⁻¹ for weed control one week before sowing (Gaspardo NO-TILL). Common durum wheat (DW) management was followed: sowing at the beginning of December, cv. Sfinge, fertilization at the end of tillering with 400 kg ha⁻¹ of ENTEC 25:15:0, chemical weed control at boot stage, harvest at the end of June. The sequence of crops in the rotation changed in the experiment duration; 5 years of continuous DW, Bare soil, DW, Faba bean and DW in 2022.

Soil sampling was made withdrawing separately in the 0-10 and 11-30 cm soil depth layers on November 2022. Each plot/replication was divided into four equal quarters, from each of which five soil cores were collected to form a composite sample. An aliquot of each field-moist sample was gently broken to pass an 8-mm sieve, air-dried, and fractionated using a Wet Sieving Apparatus model 08.13 (Royal Eijkelkamp, Giesbeek, NL) for the determination of the mean weight diameter (MWD) of aggregates according to the formula $MWD = \sum_{i=1}^n WiXi$, where Xi is the arithmetic mean diameter of each size fraction (mm) and Wi the proportion of the total water-stable aggregates in the corresponding size fraction. Another aliquot of each sample, instead, was air dried, sieved at 2 mm, finely ground to <0.5 mm and analysed for the determination of soil organic carbon concentration (SOC), expressed as g C kg⁻¹ soil, by the Walkley-Black colorimetric method (FAO, 2020). The SOC pool (Mg C ha⁻¹) for the 0-30 cm depth layer was calculated using the equation: SOC pool= SOC × ρ × d × 0.1 (FAO, 2020), where d is the soil depth of 30 cm, 0.1 is a factor for converting g C cm⁻² to Mg C ha⁻¹ and ρ is the bulk density (kg dm⁻³) calculated according to Aguilera et al. (2013).

All data were subjected to ANOVA using the R software, and the means were separated by the Tukey test.

Results

After 9 years of experiment, SOC pool did not significantly differ between the two tillage treatments (Table 1), with increases of 0.16-0.26 Mg C ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹ compared to the beginning of the trial, in agreement with Lal (2004). SOC concentrations measured at two different layers, however, showed that NT accumulated significantly more organic carbon than MT in the upper layer 0-10 cm, while no significant effect was observed in the layer 11-30 cm. To this SOC increase in the upper layer corresponded also a significant increase of the MWD indicating that, in this soil, SOC contributed significantly to the soil structure improvement with larger aggregates (Table 2).

Table 1. Effect of No Tillage (NT) and Minimum Tillage (MT) on soil organic carbon (SOC) pool after 9 years from the start of the experiment.

Treatment	Layer cm	Initial SOC pool (Mg C ha ⁻¹)	Final SOC pool (Mg C ha ⁻¹)	SOC pool increase (Mg C ha ⁻¹)
NT	0-30	50.8	53.2	2.4
MT	0-30	50.8	52.2	1.4

Conclusions

The results of this field experimental long-term study confirm the positive effects of NT application for 9 years on soil carbon content and on the soil size aggregates, with greater values in NT than in MT for both indicators. The only weakness is that this effect resulted limited to 0-10 soil layer depth only, where the surface residue composition greatly occurred. This represents an important outcome as an action to combat the desertification and in the framework of soil tillage intensity reduction and of CA diffusion.

Table 2. Effect of NT and MT treatments on SOC concentrations and mean weight diameter (MWD) of soil aggregates in the layers 0-10 and 11-30 cm after 9 years from the start of the experiment. Different letters denote significant differences (Tukey test, $p < 0.05$).

Treatment	Layer cm	SOC g C kg ⁻¹ soil	MWD mm
NT	0-10	14,8 a	1.27 a
MT	0-10	13,4 b	1.00 b
NT	11-30	12,4 b	0.89 b
MT	11-30	12,7 b	0.91 b

Acknowledgements

Funded by PRIMA Foundation (GA n. 1912), research project “Research-based participatory approaches for adopting Conservation Agriculture in the Mediterranean Area – CAMA”.

Literature

- Aguilera et al. 2013. Managing soil carbon for climate change mitigation and adaptation in Mediterranean cropping systems: A meta-analysis. *Agric. Ecosyst. Environ.*, 168: 25-36.
- FAO 2020. A protocol for measurement, monitoring, reporting and verification of soil organic carbon in agricultural landscapes – GSOC-MRV Protocol. Rome. <https://doi.org/10.4060/cb0509en>
- Lal 2004. Carbon Sequestration in Dryland Agriculture. Book: <https://doi.org/10.2135/cssaspecpub32.c20>
- Li et al. 2019. Residue retention and minimum tillage improve physical environment of the soil in croplands: A global meta-analysis. *Soil Tillage Res.*, 194: 104292.
- Rinaldi et al. 2022. Open Questions and Research Needs in the Adoption of Conservation Agriculture in the Mediterranean Area. *Agronomy*, 12: 1112.
- Troccoli et al. 2015. Is it appropriate to support the farmers for adopting Conservation Agriculture? Economic and environmental impact assessment. *Ital. J. Agron.*, 10: 169-177.

Foliar Application of Biostimulants Enhances Sustainability and Agronomic Performances of Wheat: Preliminary Results from Central Italy.

Angelo Rossini, Roberto Ruggeri, Nada Mzid, Francesco Rossini

Dip. di Scienze Agrarie e Forestali, Univ. Tuscia, IT, rossini@unitus.it

Introduction

Due to the relevant increase in the global fertilizer prices and the environmental awareness, the use of synthetic fertilizers to boost crop yield and quality has become a more and more questionable practice. As such, exploring alternative and sustainable products and their way and time of application represents a great potential to rethink crop nutrition for years to come. The use of foliar biostimulants (FBS) has been suggested as valid option to increase plant growth, yield, quality, nitrogen use efficiency and tolerance to biotic and abiotic stresses (Calvo et al., 2014). The occurrence of such stresses has become increasingly common especially in the Mediterranean Basin, which was globally recognized as a climate change hot spot. Many studies reported that PGPR (Plant Growth-Promoting Rhizobacteria), seaweed extract and Glycine betaine applied as FBS enhanced the crop performance under stress conditions (Kocira et al., 2018; Singh, 2018; Bakaeva et al., 2022; Diaz-Zorita et al., 2001). Recently, other studies have shown that foliar fertilization can reduce the total amounts of nitrogen fertilizer applied to the soil while improving grain yield and grain protein content in bread wheat under Mediterranean climatic conditions (Mathlouthi et al., 2022). Moreover, since supplementary foliar application of mineral nutrients can alleviate the adverse effects of abiotic stresses (e.g., heat and drought) on crop yield and quality, this fertilization method will probably be the best way forward in the Mediterranean environment. The objective of this study was to assess the agronomic performance of both bread and durum wheat when subjected to an alternative and more sustainable fertilization strategy, as compared to the traditional use of synthetic fertilizers under Mediterranean climatic conditions.

Materials and Methods

The field trial was conducted under rainfed conditions in the middle Tiber valley (Attigliano-TR, Italy), during 2021-2022 season. Experiments were carried out at the same site on two different species: durum wheat (*Triticum turgidum* L. subsp. *durum* (Desf.) Husn) cultivar Egeo and bread wheat (*Triticum aestivum* L.) cultivar Solehio. Experimental area for each species was 10 ha. Individual plot area used to collect the data presented in this study was 0.2 ha. Experimental units were replicated three times. Two fertilization strategies were compared. The first fertilization strategy (Control) was the traditional one, based on: (i) one pre-sowing application of 200 kg ha⁻¹ of commercial Diammonium Phosphate (NP 18–46), and (ii) 200 kg ha⁻¹ of Urea (N 46), split in two times, the first one at the stage of tillering (100 kg ha⁻¹), and the second during the beginning of the stem elongation (100 kg ha⁻¹).

The other fertilization strategy (Treated) was based on: (i) one pre-sowing application of 200 kg ha⁻¹ of commercial Diammonium Phosphate (NP 18–46), and (ii) 16,5 kg ha⁻¹ of a FBS based on 10 kg of vegetable nitrogen fertilizer (N 5%), containing 3% of glycinebetaine, 4 kg of micronized vaterite (Ca 29%) and 2 kg of a product containing a seaweed extract of *Codium fragile* (Suringar) Hariot and an extract of *Opuntia ficus-barbarica* A. Berger, and 0,5 kg of a inoculum of mycorrhizal fungi (*Glomus* spp. 0,001%) and PGPR (*Pseudomonas protegens*, *Azospirillum brasilense*, *Bacillus subtilis*, *Bacillus megaterium*, *Bacillus amyloliquefaciens* 5*10⁹ UFC/g), split in two times, the first one at the stage of tillering (8,25 kg ha⁻¹), and the second during the beginning of the stem elongation (8,25 kg ha⁻¹). For each species, the following traits were recorded: grain yield (t ha⁻¹, 13% moisture content), grain protein content (GPC, %), test weight (kg hL⁻¹) and chlorophyll content (Chl content, spad units). A one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) was performed using R (version 3.5.2).

Results

As shown in Table 1, the “Treated” strategy, based on FBS application, significantly enhanced grain yield, as compared to “Control” treatment in durum wheat. Specifically, the adoption of the alternative fertilization method resulted in almost 60% yield increase (4.6 t ha⁻¹ vs. 2.9 t ha⁻¹). Positive and significant results were also found for GPC and Chl content. Even though test weight was found to be higher under “Treated” condition than “Control” one (+4%), this result was not statistically significant.

Table 1. Grain yield, grain protein content (GPC), test weight and chlorophyll (Chl) content for each fertilization strategy (Treated and Control) in durum wheat.

Treatment	Grain yield (t ha ⁻¹)	GPC (%)	Test weight (kg hL ⁻¹)	Chl content (spad units)
Treated	4.6 a	14.7 a	82.0 ns	45.4 a
Control	2.9 b	13.3 b	78.8 ns	27.4 b

Within each column, means followed by different letter were significantly different at the 0.05 probability level; ns: not significant; GPC: grain protein content; Chl content: chlorophyll content

On the contrary, the application of the alternative fertilization strategy had not significant effect on agronomic performance of bread wheat, with the exception of GPC (Table 2). However, “Treated” method increased grain yield by more than 10%, GPC by 4%, test weight by 2.5%, and Chl content by 24%.

Table 2. Grain yield, grain protein content (GPC), test weight and chlorophyll (Chl) content for each fertilization strategy (Treated and Control) in bread wheat.

Treatment	Grain yield (t ha ⁻¹)	GPC (%)	Test weight (kg hL ⁻¹)	Chl content (spad units)
Treated	5.1 ns	12.2 a	78.0 ns	48.0 ns
Control	4.6 ns	11.7 b	76.1 ns	38.7 ns

Within each column, means followed by different letter were significantly different at the 0.05 probability level; ns: not significant; GPC: grain protein content; Chl content: chlorophyll content

Conclusions

The application of an alternative fertilization protocol, based on the use of foliar biostimulant, significantly increased grain yield in durum wheat and grain protein content in both durum and bread wheat. This study proved that the use of foliar biostimulants can help farmers to reduce the amount of synthetic nitrogen fertilizers, without reducing the yield and quality of wheat under Mediterranean climatic conditions

Literature

- Bakaeva M. et al. 2022. PGP-Bacterium *Pseudomonas protegens* Improves Bread Wheat Growth and Mitigates Herbicide and Drought Stress. *Plants*, 11: 3289.
- Calvo P. et al. 2014. Agricultural uses of plant biostimulants. *Plant Soil*, 383: 3-41.
- Díaz-Zorita M. et al. 2001. Applications of Foliar Fertilizers Containing Glycine betaine Improve Wheat Yields. *J. Agron. Crop Sci.*, 186(3): 209-215.
- Kocira A. et al. 2018. Enhancement of yield, nutritional and nutraceutical properties of two common bean cultivars following the application of seaweed extract (*Ecklonia maxima*). *Saudi J. Biol. Sci.*, 25(3): 563-571.
- Mathlouthi F. et al. 2022. A New Fertilization Approach for Bread Wheat in the Mediterranean Environment: Effects on Yield and Grain Protein Content. *Agronomy*, 12: 2152.
- Singh I. 2018. Plant Growth Promoting Rhizobacteria (PGPR) and their various mechanisms for plant growth enhancement in stressful conditions: a review. *Eur. J. Biol. Res.*, 8: 191-213.

Agronomic, Productive, and Qualitative Response of Sugarcane Accessions for Sicily

Francesco Salamone, Nicolò Iacuzzi*, Noemi Tortorici, Federica Alaimo, Teresa Tuttolomondo, Davide Farruggia

Dip. Scienze Agrarie, Alimentari e Forestali, Univ. Palermo, IT, *nicolo.iacuzzi@unipa.it

Introduction

Sugarcane (*Saccharum officinarum* L.) is widely cultivated in tropical and subtropical environments of the world. This crop was recently reintroduced in Sicily for agro-industrial uses. The possibility of growing sugar cane in non-tropical or subtropical areas is affected by temperature. Sugarcane cannot be grown in regions where the average temperature of the coldest month is below 10 °C. These conditions can be found in the coastal areas of western Sicily. In this area, new sugar cane fields have been planted recently (data being published). Zhang et al. (2015) report that, within the varieties of sugar cane, there are cultivars characterized by tolerance to cold. Xiao et al. (2017) report that genotypic variability is one of the most important endogenous factors that significantly affect the adaptability of the species, the production and the aromatic profile of the juice, in response to the cultivation environment. The aim of this study was to evaluate agronomic and productive response of 7 varieties and 2 accessions of sugarcane cultivated in Mediterranean environment.

Materials and Methods

The study was carried out from 2022 to 2023 at “Campo Carboj” experimental farm, University of Palermo (Italy) (37° 58'86.0" N, 12 ° 89' 55.7" E, 39 m a.s.l.). The soil was classified as sandy, clay loam. According to the Köppen-Geiger climate classification, the study site is characterized by a warm temperate climate with dry summers and mild winters. An experimental randomized block design has been adopted. Before planting, a deep tillage was carried out, followed by an organic fertilization and secondary tillage. Sugarcane genotypes tested in this study are shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Plant material under study

Variety / accession	Origin	Centre
PSR 07-334	Filippine	Philsurin
FR 87-83	Guadeloupe	Visacane
KN 07-0037	Kenana	Sudan
CPCL 02-1295	USA - Florida	USDA
CP 06-2495	USA - Florida	USDA
CP 09-1952	USA - Florida	USDA
Mex 69-290	Messico	Visacane
Ananas	Caribbean	-
Baltasia	Caribbean	-

The planting was carried out in May 2022 using stem cuttings with one bud. Plant distances were 1m x 0.5m. Irrigation was carried out with a microportate system that provided the restitution of ETm. Agronomic, production and quality parameters were determined during harvest in March 2023. All production and quality data were determined according to Chen and Chou (1993). Data were compared using analysis of variance. The difference between means was carried out using the Tukey test. Statistical analysis was performed using the package MINITAB 19 for Windows.

Results

Analysis of variance (Table 2) showed significant differences for all biometric and productive parameters. Plant height ranged from 212.16 cm (FR87-83) and 130.73 (CPCL 02-1295). The highest millable canes length was detected in CP 06-2495 and FR87-83 (about 170 cm), showing a greater precocity for harvesting. Intermediate millable canes length, not statistically different, were observed in Baltasia, PSR 07-334, Mex 69-290. The lowest millable canes length values were observed in Ananas, CP 09-1152, CPCL 02-1295 (Table 2). The highest number of nodes (about 14) was found in PSR 07-334 and CP 06-2495 while the lowest (about 11) in Mex 69-290, CP09-1952 and KN07-0037. Average node diameter ranged from 31.98

cm (Baltasià) and 20.96 (CP 09-1952). The highest number of tillers and number of millable canes were obtained in Mex 69-290 variety. The highest fresh biomass yield were observed in Baltasià, FR 87-83 and PSR 07-334, with values of about 30000 kg ha⁻¹, while the lowest (under 20000 kg ha⁻¹) in CPCL 02-1295 and CP 09-1952 (Table 2).

Table 2. Effects of Variety/Accession on biometric parameters.

Variety/Accession	Plant height (cm)	Millable canes length (cm)	Number of nodes (n)	Average node diameter (mm)	Number of tillers (n ha ⁻¹)	Number of Millable canes (n ha ⁻¹)	Fresh biomass yield (kg ha ⁻¹)
PSR 07-334	190.93 ab	155.04 abc	14.91 a	28.08 ab	247000 ab	189333 b	30425.8 ab
FR 87-83	212.16 a	164.47 ab	12.6 bc	28.31 ab	237500 b	160000 c	32963.8 ab
KN 07-0037	173.25 bc	143.5 bc	10.8 c	28.79 ab	188350 d	180833 b	28351.7 bc
CPCL 02-1295	130.73 d	98.04 d	11.5 c	25.06 ab	118000 f	117333 e	18290 d
CP 06-2495	170.62 bc	167.95 a	13.9 ab	22.7 b	175000 e	157500 c	21365.8 cd
CP 09-1952	177.5 abc	134.57 c	11.45 c	20.96 b	183333 de	152333 cd	18220.3 d
Mex 69-290	196.83 ab	157.0 abc	11.5 c	26.42 ab	253333 a	206667 a	25500 bcd
Ananas	142.0 cd	142.57 bc	12.23 bc	27.9 ab	180000 de	138333 d	27520.3 bc
Baltasià	189.6 ab	156.5 abc	15.5 bc	31.98 a	217000 c	138667 d	37981.3 a
<i>p-value</i>	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.018	0.000	0.000	0.000

Means followed by the same letter are not significantly different for $p \leq 0.05$ according to Tukey's test.

Statistically significant differences were also found in production (Total Juice, CCS and Sugar yield) and quality parameters (°brix, pH and Sucrose) (Table 3).

Table 3. Effects of Variety/accession on production parameters

Variety/Accession	Total juice (t ha ⁻¹)	°Brix of juice (°)	pH of juice	Sucrose (g/cm ³)	CCS (%)	Sugar yield (t ha ⁻¹)
PSR 07-334	11995 abc	22.9 a	5.28 d	19.76 b	13.51 b	4.11 ab
FR 87-83	11292.5 abc	19.82 b	5.24 d	15.35 d	9.02 c	3.04 ab
KN 07-0037	12623.3 ab	14.74 c	5.4 abc	12.33 e	8.3 c	2.31 b
CPCL 02-1295	5850 d	24.1 a	5.42 a	16.73 cd	10.06 c	1.84 b
CP 06-2495	7871.5 d	23.87 a	5.3 bcd	18.98 bc	13 b	2.78 ab
CP 09-1952	5932.5 d	23.82 a	5.44 a	23.11 a	16.66 a	3.03 ab
Mex 69-290	9876.7 bcd	20.69 b	5.29 cd	19.61 bc	14 ab	3.55 ab
Ananas	9586.7 bcd	20.65 b	5.36 abcd	19.54 bc	13.94 ab	3.86 ab
Baltasià	14312.5 a	20.24 b	5.42 ab	19.56 bc	14.08 ab	5.33 a
<i>p-value</i>	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.026

Means followed by the same letter are not significantly different for $p \leq 0.05$ according to Tukey's test. CCS = Commercial Cane Sugar.

Production and quality parameters represent important traits for the choice of varieties to be used in commercial sugar cane fields (Tai and Miller, 2002). The higher juice production and sugar yield were obtained in Baltasià accession; these values were lower than those reported by Islam et al., (2011). Variations in juice yield could be attributed to growing environment, variety, cultivation method, and extraction method (Chauhan et al., 2021). The highest CCS and sucrose values were found in CP 09-1952 variety. In this variety and in the varieties of the same origin (CP 06-2495 and CPCL 02-1295) the highest values of °brix and pH were observed, in line with those obtained by Chauhan et al. (2021).

Conclusions

The results observed in this study, although preliminary, are promising and showing the possibility of cultivation of some sugarcane varieties in Mediterranean environment. Yield obtained is lower than yield recorded in traditional areas of sugarcane cultivation, while the quality characteristics are very similar. Further research are in progress to implement data on agronomic response of other sugarcane accessions suitable for Sicilian environment.

Literature

- Zhang, F. J., et al. (2015). Effect of drought stress on anatomical structure and chloroplast ultrastructure in leaves of sugarcane. *Sugar Tech*, 17, 41-48.
- Xiao, et al., (2017). Analysis of sugarcane juice quality indexes. *Journal of Food Quality*, 2017.
- Chen & Chou (1993). *Cane sugar handbook: a manual for cane sugar manufacturers and their chemists*. John Wiley & Sons.
- Tai & Miller (2002). Germplasm diversity among four sugarcane species for sugar composition. *Crop science*, 42(3), 958-964.
- Islam, et al. (2011). Growth, yield and juice quality of some selected sugarcane clones under water-logging stress condition. *World Journal of Agricultural Sciences*, 7(4), 504-509.
- Chauhan et al. (2021). High pressure, temperature and time-dependent effects on enzymatic and microbial properties of fresh sugarcane juice. *Journal of food science and technology*, 54.12: 4135-4138.

Agronomic Management of Hybrid Barley: Effect of Tillage, Seeding Rate and N Fertilization

Mattia Scapino, Luca Capo, Raffaele Meloni, Paolo Colombatto, Amedeo Reyneri, Massimo Blandino

DISAFA, Univ. Torino, IT, mattia.scapino@unito.it

Introduction

Currently, hybrid barleys (*Hordeum vulgare* L.) are cultivated in more than half of the crop surface of Italy. As a consequence of the heterosis phenomenon, they have a greater vigour compared to conventional pure line cultivars (Longin et al., 2012). Furthermore, to fully exploit their strength traits, while limiting their weakness ones (high seed cost and, consequently, low seeding rate), it is required to develop agronomic programmes specifically adapted for hybrid genotypes in specific production situations (Schmitz et al., 2021). The aim of the present study was to investigate the effect of different agronomic practices, related with the plant density, on the yield and qualitative traits of hybrid barley cultivars, in comparison with conventional ones.

Materials and Methods

The study was carried out in the North-West Italy over three growing seasons (2017-2020). The experimental field was characterized by a superficial loam soil, with a medium content of organic matter and nutrients. The compared treatments were a factorial combination of 2 soil tillages [ploughing (conventional tillage, CT) and minimum tillage (MT)], 4 combinations of cultivar x seeding rate [hybrid barley cv. Tektoo x 70 (H70) and 140 (H140) kg of seed ha⁻¹ and conventional barley cv. Ketos x 140 (C140) and 210 (C210) kg seed ha⁻¹] and 2 nitrogen (N) fertilization timings (60+60 and 30+90 kg N ha⁻¹ at growth stages GS 21 and 31, respectively). The experiment was carried out according to a split-plot design with soil tillage, cultivar and seeding rate as main-plot treatment and N fertilization as sub-plot one. Each treatment was replicated four times and the sub-plot area was 12 m². The biomass development was expressed as the area under canopy greenness curve (AUCDC), using the NDVI values measured weekly during the vegetative (growth stages, GS 21-61) and the ripening (GS 61-91) period. The grain yield was obtained by harvesting the whole sub-plot with a plot-combine and it was adjusted to 13% moisture content. The yield components were measured: ear density and kernels per ear (at dough stage, GS 85) and thousand kernel weight (TKW) after harvest. The grain protein content (GPC) and the deoxynivalenol contamination (DON) were assessed as qualitative parameters. The data were analysed using a mixed effects model, with crop practices as fixed effects and year as random effect. Analysis of variance (ANOVA) was performed and when the effects were significant, the means were compared using the Bonferroni post-hoc test at p -value \leq 0.05.

Results

The CT increased both AUCDC GS 21-61 and AUCDC GS 61-91 values of barley compared to the MT condition (Figure 1). A significant effect was reported for the interaction between cv. and seeding rate: C210 had higher AUCDC GS 21-61 value compared to H70 due to the initial higher plant density, while both H140 and C140 reported an intermediate value. During ripening, the hybrid (H70 and H140) had reported higher NDVI values than the conventional genotype, due to a higher stay green. The N fertilization strategy directly influenced NDVI values according to the growth stage: 60+60 treatment reported the higher AUCDC GS 21-61 value, while in opposite 30+90 reported higher AUCDC GS 61-91. No statistical differences were found between the different soil tillages on grain yield and yield components (Table 1), while GPC and DON were higher for CT and MT, respectively. The hybrid (H70 and H140) had higher grain yield (+7.6%), kernels per ear (+16.3%) and TKW (+13.7%) compared to the conventional cultivar, which resulted in higher ear density at both density (C140 and C210). Qualitatively, C210 had higher GPC, whereas the hybrid showed higher DON values. The 60+60 N fertilization treatment lead to higher grain yield (+2.9%) and lower GPC than 30+90. Interactions between factors were significant for AUCDC GS

21-61, grain yield, kernels per ear and TKW (data not shown): as expected, the higher seeding rates showed more stable AUCDC GS 21-61 values between tillage. Furthermore, the hybrid cv. was less affected by the timing of N fertilization than the conventional one.

Figure 1. Effect of tillage, cultivar with different seeding density and N fertilization on AUCDC GS 21-61 (vegetative growth stages) and AUCDC GS 61-91 values (ripening growth stages).

Within each experimental factor, different letters between treatments indicate significant differences (p -value < 0.05).

Table 1. Effect of tillage, cultivar with different seeding density and fertilization on grain yield and yield components.

Factor	Source of variation	Grain yield (t ha ⁻¹)	Ear density (n. m ⁻²)	Kernels per ear (n. ear ⁻¹)	TKW (g)	GPC (%)	DON (μg kg ⁻¹)
Tillage	CT	6.0 a	351 a	46 a	43.8 a	11.7 a	3406 b
	MT	6.1 a	364 a	45 a	44.4 a	11.3 b	5289 a
	<i>p</i> -value	0.351	0.118	0.073	0.167	< 0.001	< 0.001
Cultivar x Density	H70	6.3 a	325 b	50 a	47.0 a	11.6 ab	6066 a
	H140	6.2 a	325 b	48 a	46.9 a	11.2 b	4459 ab
	C140	5.8 b	377 a	45 b	41.3 b	11.5 ab	3761 b
	C210	5.8 b	402 a	40 c	41.3 b	11.7 a	3216 b
	<i>p</i> -value	< 0.001	< 0.001	< 0.001	< 0.001	0.033	< 0.001
Fertilization (kg N ha ⁻¹)	60+60	6.1 a	363 a	45 b	44.2 a	11.3 b	4233 a
	30+90	5.9 b	353 a	46 a	44.0 a	11.7 a	4545 a
	<i>p</i> -value	0.001	0.148	0.013	0.500	< 0.001	0.200

Means followed by different letters are significantly different. The level of significance (p -value) is shown in the table.

Conclusions

The hybrid cv. presented on average significant grain yield benefits and similar GPC compared to the conventional one, as a consequence of higher stay green, with advantages recorded in different production situations (growing seasons, soil tillages), and an overall better nutrient use efficiency. The lower ear density of the hybrid was compensated by higher kernels per ear and thousand kernel weight. In the considered conditions and for both cultivars, a higher seeding rate did not increase significantly the ear density and, consequently, the yield benefits. Furthermore, the hybrid could take benefits from a N fertilization more equally applied between the tillering and the beginning of the stem elongation. As far as the safety trait is concerned, the hybrid showed a higher susceptibility to mycotoxin contamination, requiring a higher attention in designing cropping systems less prone to Fusarium head blight disease.

Literature

- Longin C.F.H. et al. 2012. Hybrid Breeding in Autogamous Cereals. *Theor. Appl. Genet.*, 125: 1087–1096.
- Schmitz P.K., & Ransom J.K. 2021. Seeding rate effects on hybrid spring wheat yield, yield components, and quality. *Agronomy*, 11(6): 1240.

‘Early’ Potato – Pea Intercropping: First Evidence on Productive Traits and Insect Control

Aurelio Scavo, Sara Lombardo, Antonio Biondi, Gaetano Pandino, Giovanna Tropea Garzia, Salvatore Alfio Salicola, Carmelo Cavallaro, Antonio Gugliuzzo, Claudia Formenti, Fabrizio Lisi, Gaetano Roberto Pesce, Giovanni Mauromicale

Di3A, Univ. Catania, IT, aurelio.scavo@unict.it

Introduction

Potato (*Solanum tuberosum* L.) is one of the most important staple crops worldwide. In some areas of the Mediterranean Basin, thanks to specific pedo-climatic conditions, it has been demonstrated the possibility of cultivating an off-season potato crop (harvested from March to June), namely ‘early’ potato, under organic farming (Lombardo et al., 2012). Although the lower yields achievable in organic than conventional systems, ‘early’ potato has a premium price that offers a sufficient profit margin to growers targeting the export markets. In this context, both farmers and market demand for new sustainable agronomic practices for ‘early’ potato cultivation. Intercropping, *i.e.* the simultaneous cultivation of different plant species on the same soil unit, can be a valid tool by virtue of the numerous ecosystem services provided (Khanal et al., 2021). However, it has been never investigated in ‘early’ potato crop. Therefore, the goals of the present work were to investigate the influence of ‘early’ potato – pea (*Pisum sativum* L.) intercropping on potato productive traits and incidence of damaged tubers by insect pests.

Materials and Methods

A field trial was performed during the 2021/2022 growing season across two organic farms located in Rosolini (Location I) and Ispica (Location II) (South Sicily, Italy), an area devoted to ‘early’ potato cultivation. The local climate is semiarid Mediterranean, characterized by hot summers, mild-wet winters and mean annual rainfall of 500 mm. In both locations, the experiment was arranged in a split-plot design with 3 blocks, considering the cultivation system (*i.e.* intercropping *vs.* pure crop) as main plots and potato cultivars (*i.e.* Arizona and Levante) as sub-plots. Agronomic management followed the standard practices of the zone. The crop harvest was carried out by hand at the end of the biological cycle, about 120 days after planting. Tubers which were greened, misshapen or displayed pathological damage were classed as unmarketable, as well as those with weight lower than 20 g. This allowed the calculation of the marketable yield (MY), mean tuber fresh weight (MTFW) and number of tubers per plant (NTP). These data were statistically analysed for each cultivar by analysis of variance (ANOVA) with the LSD test at $\alpha = 0.05$.

After harvest, all tubers were also visually checked for any evidence of insect attacks. In particular, damage caused by click beetles (Coleoptera: Elateridae), potato tuberworm larvae (*Phthorimaea operculella* Zeller) (Lepidoptera: Gelechiidae), armyworms (Lepidoptera: Noctuidae), and *Gryllotalpa* sp. (Orthoptera: Gryllotalpidae) were identified. Moreover, the mean number of attacked tubers by each pest, as well as their proportion were estimated. Non-parametric Kruskal–Wallis tests followed by Dunn's post hoc test ($p < 0.05$) were carried out for multiple mean comparisons among cultivation system.

Results

About productive traits (Figure 1), intercropping, as compared to the pure crop, caused a significant increase of MY in location I (+87.9% for ‘Arizona’ and +61.7% for ‘Levante’) and location II (+7.3%). The increase of MY for the cv. Arizona was mainly due to the enhancement of AMTW (+67.6%), whereas for the cultivar Levante, it was related to the increase of NMT (+63.3% in location I and +27.0% in location II).

About insect attacks (Figure 1), the results showed that intercropping significantly reduced the percentage of tubers damaged by different insect pests when tested for the cv. Levante. Conversely, more attacks by insect pests were found in control plants when the tested cultivar was ‘Arizona’. The results could be explained by temporal differences between the phenological stages of the two different tested potato

cultivars in relation to the sprouting of tubers (*i.e.*, more attractive for certain pests compared to potato tubers) of the other species used in the intercropping.

Figure 1 – Effect of ‘early’ potato – pea intercropping on potato productive traits, specific and total insect damage. For productive traits, different letters within each cultivar indicate statistically significant differences ($P \leq 0.05$, LSD test). For damaged tubers, asterisks within location and type of damage indicate significant differences for Kruskal–Wallis tests followed by Dunn's post hoc test ($P \leq 0.05$). Bars are standard deviation for productive traits and standard error for tuber damaged ($n=3$). MY: marketable yield; AMTW: average marketable tuber weight; NMT: number of tubers plant⁻¹.

Conclusions

From the present preliminary results, it emerged that intercropping with pea may be a promising agronomic technique for the sustainable enhancement of ‘early’ potato productive performances in organic farming. Nevertheless, intercropping with pea reduced the incidence of tubers damaged by insect pests in ‘Levante’, while an opposite trend was observed in ‘Arizona’. Further efforts are needed to better investigate the effects of ‘early’ potato – pea intercropping on different potato cultivars in the medium-long term period.

Literature

Khanal U. et al. 2021. Intercropping—Evaluating the advantages to broadacre systems. *Agriculture*, 11: 453.
 Lombardo S. et al. 2012. The phenology: yield and tuber composition of ‘early’ crop potatoes: a comparison between organic and conventional cultivation systems. *Renewable Agric. Food Syst.*, 28: 50-58.

Weed Pressure in an Organic Wheat-Legume Intercropping and Relay Cropping

Danilo Scordia, Francesca Calderone, Oteri Marianna, Stefania Toscano, Fabio Gresta

Dip. Scienze Veterinarie, Univ. Messina, IT, danilo.scordia@unime.it

Introduction

The European green transition aims to reach the greenhouse gas emissions neutrality by 2050 (EU Green Deal). In the agricultural sector, the eco-schemes set in the new CAP (2023-2027) target to achieve at least 25% of the EU's agricultural land under organic farming, to reduce nutrient losses by at least 50% and to reduce use of fertilisers by at least 20% by 2030. However, it is well known that crop yield in organic farming are more affected than conventional farming since crops are subjected to a number of biotic and abiotic stress hard to control. Weed pressure and timely crop nutrition, for instance, are big issues in organic farming for many field crops; hence, agro-ecological practices that make better use of natural resources and allow wider soil coverage could represent a possible solution. In this view, intercropping and relay cropping using forage legume species in double-cropping might offer nitrogen to the companion crop, while competing physically with weeds for land. The present study explores the weed control by forage legume species, either in intercropping and in relay cropping, with durum wheat in a semi-arid Mediterranean area with the aim to reduce nitrogen requirement and protect the main crop from weed pressure.

Materials and Methods

The field trial was carried out in an organic farm located in Patti (Messina, 38°11'N, 14°99'E) in a clay soil in 2022-23. The twenty-year average minimum and maximum air temperature is 13.0 and 22.9°C, respectively, and the twenty-year average precipitation and evapotranspiration is 783.5 and 1041.0 mm, respectively. The soil was ploughed in late summer and dish harrowed in autumn at 30 cm and 20 cm, respectively. A light soil milling was performed just after sowing. In a split-plot experimental design, the main plot was assigned to the organic fertilization, distributed at soil milling, calculated as N in three levels: 0, 60 and 120 kg N ha⁻¹. Durum wheat (var. Core) was sown alone (control), and associated with forage legumes (*Trifolium subterraneum*, *Lotus corniculatus*, *Medicago polymorpha*) in the sub-plot, on 3 January 2023 for the intercropping system, and at durum wheat tillering stage (28 February 2023) for the relay cropping system. Both durum wheat and forage legumes were manually broadcasted at the highest range of seed density for each species. A single plot measured 5 m x 8 m (40 m²). On 14 April 2023, weeds were counted in a marked sub-plot of 1 m² in each treatment and replication. Data on weed pressure were statistically analysed according to the experimental layout, with cropping system, nitrogen fertilization and legume species as fixed effect. Means were separated using the Tukey HSD test ($p \leq 0.05$).

Results

The ANOVA showed high significance of N fertilization, cropping system and legume species main effects (Table 1). Significant interactions were also found. The best treatment combination on weed control were (Figure 1): the intercropping of durum wheat and *M. polymorpha* (8 weeds m⁻²), the intercropping of durum wheat and *L. corniculatus* (14 weeds m⁻²) and the intercropping of durum wheat and *T. subterraneum* (16 weeds m⁻²), all in N0. These were not different than the intercropping of durum wheat and *M. polymorpha* in N2 (14 weeds m⁻²), the relay of durum wheat and *M. polymorpha* in N0 and the relay of durum wheat and trifolium in N0 (18 and 20 weeds m⁻², respectively). The worst combination were the control (single crop) in N2 (128 weeds m⁻²) and the relay cropping of durum wheat and *L. corniculatus*, and durum wheat and *T. subterraneum* in N2 (116 and 104 weeds m⁻², respectively).

Table 1. ANOVA for main effects and interaction. Degree of freedom (df) and mean square (MS) and significance: not significant (ns), $p \leq 0.001$ (***), $p \leq 0.01$ (**), and $p \leq 0.05$ (*).

Source	df	MS
Blocks	2	37.5ns
Nitrogen (N)	2	20269.5***
Main-plot error	4	45.5
Cropping system (CS)	1	6844.5***
N x CS	2	3286.5***
Sub-plot error	6	51.5
Legume (L)	3	3849.83***
N x L	6	2910.83***
CS x L	3	129.83*
N x CS x L	6	299.83***
Error	36	36.5

Figure 1. Interaction of experimental factors (nitrogen x cropping systems x species) on weed number per square meter. Nitrogen fertilization (N0, N1, N2), Intercropping (I), Relay cropping (R), *Trifolium subterraneum*, (T), *Lotus corniculatus* (L), *Medicago polymorpha* (M) and control (C). Different letters indicate statistically different means ($p \leq 0.05$).

Conclusions

The present study offers very preliminary indications on the use of agro-ecological practices to control weeds in durum wheat under organic farming systems. Overall, the nitrogen fertilization improved crop growth but supported weed development, and the relay system, sowing legume species at the wheat tillering stage, was not as effective as the intercropping. Among legume species, *M. polymorpha* behaved better than either *T. subterraneum* and *L. corniculatus* in limiting weeds even with the highest nitrogen supply. In addition to follow-up weed control, the present trial will be assessed at the end of the growing season for grain yield and quality, nitrogen and land use efficiency.

Literature

European Commission, Directorate-General for Agriculture and Rural Development (2021). List of potential Agricultural Practices that Eco-schemes could support. January 2021 #EUGreenDeal. https://agriculture.ec.europa.eu/system/files/2021-01/factsheet-agri-practices-under-ecoscheme_en_0.pdf. Accessed on 31 May 2023.

Legume Based Rotation in Low Input Agricultural Systems: Sustainability Aspects, Agronomic Traits and Nutritional Features

Camilla Tibaldi, Mattia Alpi, Elettra Frassinetti, Giovanni Dinelli, Ilaria Marotti

DISTAL, Univ. Bologna, IT, camilla.tibaldi2@unibo.it, mattia.alpi3@unibo.it, elettra.frassinetti2@unibo.it,
giovanni.dinelli@unibo.it, ilaria.marotti@unibo.it

Introduction

Global increasing population and climate change are current issues that drive to a more sustainable food system. Plant-based meat alternatives (PBMA) have generated considerable consumer interest, as they can be considered as a valid and sustainable substitute to meat-based diet (Hu et al., 2019). Indeed, PBMA production generate less greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions and require less energy, water, and land use compared with livestock production (Heller et al., 2019). In this perspective, legumes represent the main source of vegetable proteins and, among them, peas (*Pisum sativum* L.) are rich of high-quality proteins and nutritional compounds which can provide several health benefits.

In this work the agronomic performance of grain legumes (pea grain) will be evaluated in two consecutive years of cultivation (2021 and 2022) in different Italian environments, and the nutritional and health characteristics of peas for human nutrition will be studied.

Materials and Methods

Field trials were conducted in two different environments for each year of cultivation (2021 and 2022): mountainous (Loiano, BO, 44°17'56.632"N 11°21'1.648"E, 800 m a.s.l.) and plain environment (Ozzano dell'Emilia, BO, 44°24'45.61"N 11°28'27.647"E, 82 m a.s.l.). Trials included the cultivation under organic conditions of one 'afila' cultivar of pea and a mixture of three different cultivars of peas. Analyses about soil characteristics are in progress. The seeds were purchased from Arcoiris S.R.L (Modena, Italy) and sown at 200 kg/ha of seed. Winter and Spring sowing were chosen for mountain and plain location, respectively. Trials were all rain fed and weed management was carried out manually. The harvest was performed at two phenological stages: green ripening (BBCH-79) and dry ripening (BBCH-89). The green ripening peas were evaluated for: total polyphenol (TP) and flavonoid (TF) compounds as described by Di Silvestro et al. (2012); anti-oxidant activities according to the DPPH and FRAP assays (Benzie & Strain, 1996; Floegel et al., 2011). The quantification of soluble (SDF) and insoluble (IDF) dietary fibres and total digestible (TDS) and resistant starch (RS) was identified using Megazyme array kits, cat. no. K-TDFR-200A and Megazyme, cat. no. K-DSTRS. Lipid content (LIP) was performed according to Folch method (AOC, 1990) (Folch et al., 1957), while Protein content (PRO) was determined according to Dumas method (VELP, 2020). Two-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) in conjunction with Tukey's honest significant difference was performed to compare the two growing environments and years of cultivation. Significance between means was determined by least significant difference values for $p < 0.05$. Discriminant analysis was applied to the standardized data matrix of TP, TF, DPPH, FRAP, and SDF, IDF, TDS, RS, LIP and PRO recorded in the two growing environments and carried out by using Statistica 6.0 software (2001, StatSoft, Tulsa, OK, USA).

Results

Green ripening biomass yield in 2021 was 3.70 and 3.69 Mg/ha for mountain and plain environment, respectively, indicating no significative difference, as well for 2022 (4.63 and 5.36 Mg/ha). However, the dry ripening grain harvested in plain environment showed a significant higher biomass yield (1.86 and 1.37 Mg/ha, for 2021 and 2022, respectively) compared to mountainous (0.94 and 1.57 Mg/ha, for 2021 and 2022, respectively).

		Heigh	Branches	Flowers	Pods	TP	TF	FRAP	DPPH	IDF	SDF	LIP	PRO	TDS	RS
		(cm)	(#)	(#)	(#)	(mg GAE/100g)	(mg CE/100g)	(mmol Fe ²⁺ /100g)	(µmol TE/g)	(%)	(g/100g)	(g/100g)	(g/100g)	(g/100g)	(g/100g)
Environment	mountain	60,21 <i>a</i>	14,55 <i>a</i>	2,39 <i>a</i>	4,07 <i>a</i>	117,75 <i>a</i>	46,55 <i>a</i>	0,93 <i>a</i>	2,55 <i>a</i>	27,32 <i>a</i>	8,84 <i>a</i>	1,97 <i>a</i>	20,69 <i>b</i>	25,99 <i>a</i>	7,75 <i>a</i>
	plain	27,36 <i>b</i>	11,45 <i>b</i>	0,87 <i>b</i>	1,42 <i>b</i>	104,96 <i>a</i>	43,52 <i>a</i>	0,82 <i>a</i>	3,07 <i>a</i>	28,95 <i>a</i>	9,02 <i>a</i>	2,23 <i>a</i>	23,90 <i>a</i>	23,37 <i>b</i>	6,74 <i>a</i>
Year of cultivation	2021	46,76 <i>a</i>	14,03 <i>a</i>	2,05 <i>a</i>	2,98 <i>a</i>	128,66 <i>a</i>	54,81 <i>a</i>	0,98 <i>a</i>	2,91 <i>a</i>	27,11 <i>a</i>	7,81 <i>b</i>	2,04 <i>a</i>	22,79 <i>a</i>	25,08 <i>a</i>	6,79 <i>a</i>
	2022	40,81 <i>b</i>	11,98 <i>b</i>	1,21 <i>b</i>	2,51 <i>b</i>	94,05 <i>b</i>	35,26 <i>b</i>	0,78 <i>b</i>	2,70 <i>a</i>	29,15 <i>a</i>	10,05 <i>a</i>	2,15 <i>a</i>	21,79 <i>a</i>	24,28 <i>a</i>	7,70 <i>a</i>
E x Y		***	ns	ns	***	ns	ns	**	*	ns	**	ns	ns	ns	ns

Table 1. Mean values of agronomic features and nutritional compounds of pea grain in the growing environments in two years of cultivation. Different letters within each column: significant different values ($p \leq 0.05$, Tukey's least significant difference test). The number of stars represent significant differences at the 0.05 (*), 0.01 (**), and 0.001 (***) probability level, respectively. Ns = not significant. E x Y = interaction environment x year of cultivation.

The growth parameters of pea crop (Table 1) displayed a significant higher result in the mountainous environment for both cultivation years, demonstrating that winter sowing allows to a longer period of accumulating biomass, and a more effective utilization of post-winter water (Prusiński J. et al., 2016). Among nutritional analysis, 2021 grain displayed significant higher levels of polyphenols and antioxidant activity than 2022. This trend may reflect plant response to specific abiotic stresses on both growing environments (Klepacka et al., 2011). No significant difference of IDF, LIP, TDS and RS content was recorded between the environments in the two years of cultivation. The highest values of PRO were observed in plain samples, demonstrating that spring environment conditions support the accumulation of proteins during the vegetative growth of the plant (Tao et al., 2017).

Figure 1 shows a scatter plot of pea samples grown at two different environments defined by the first two canonical functions. The distribution of cases (agronomic and nutritional features) along Root 1 was strongly influenced by all the agronomic parameters (heigh, branches, flowers, pods), as well as nutritional compounds (IDF, TDS and RS); while along Root 2 it was mainly determined by polyphenol content and antioxidant activity (TP, TF and FRAP). The multivariate technique showed high discrimination power as indicated by the Wilks' lambda value of each variable (< 0.000001), significant at $p < 0.005$.

Conclusions

The present data showed that environment is a driving factor in pea agronomic performance and nutritional composition. Nevertheless, these results are representative of only two year of crop cycle (2021 and 2022). Hence, future studies are required to further investigate this correlation.

Literature

Hu F.B. et al. 2019. Can plant-based meat alternatives be part of a healthy and sustainable diet? JAMA, 322: 1547–1548.

Heller M.C. et al. 2019. Center for Sustainable Systems, University of Michigan. Beyond Meat's Beyond Burger Life Cycle Assessment: a detailed comparison between a plant-based and an animal-based protein source.

Di Silvestro R. et al. 2012. Health-promoting phytochemicals of Italian common wheat varieties grown under low-input agricultural management, J. Sci. Food Agr., 92: 2800 – 2810.

Benzie I.F.F. and Strain J.J.1996. The ferric reducing ability of plasma (FRAP) as a measure of “antioxidant power”: The FRAP assay. Anal. Biochem., 239: 70-76.

Floegel A. et al. 2011. Comparison of ABTS and DPPH assays to measure antioxidant capacity in popular antioxidant-rich US foods. J. Food Compos. Anal, 24: 1043-1048.

Folch J. et al. 1957. A simple method for the isolation and purification of total lipids from animal tissues. J. Biol. Chem., 226(1): 4.

VELP. Elemental Analysis and the Dumas Method. VELP Scientifica. 2020. Available online: <https://www.velp.com/en-ww/du-mas-method-1.aspx> .

Prusiński, J. et al. 2016. Overwintering and yield of winter cultivars of field pea assas and white lupin orus. Electr. J. of Polish Agricultural Universities, 19: 4.

Klepacka J. et al. 2011. Phenolic compounds as cultivar-and variety-distinguishing factors in some plant products. Plant Foods Hum. Nutr., 66(1): 64-69.

Tao A. et al. 2017. Variation in yield, starch, and protein of dry pea grown across Montana. Agron. J., 109(4): 1491-1501.

Figure 1. Scatter plot of pea grain in different environments and years of cultivation according to agronomic and health-promoting compounds composition defined by the first two canonical functions.

Yield, Pests and Weeds in Lentil–Cereal Intercropping

Giacomo Tosti, Beatrice Falcinelli, Marcello Guiducci

DSA3, Univ. Perugia, IT, giacomo.tosti@unipg.it

Introduction

The contribution of grain legumes to ecosystem services in European agriculture has been thoroughly revised (Watson et al., 2017). Moreover, there is an increasing interest in cereal–legume intercropping (IC) due to the higher and more stable gross margin of IC than sole crops. Among the minor grain legume species, lentil (*Lens culinaris* Medik.) is gaining more attention, thanks to its high nutritional value and ease of cooking. Unfortunately, low and unstable lentil yields are common in Mediterranean organic production systems, and are generally linked to drought, pests (i.e., bruchid), weeds and inefficient mechanical harvest. Among the viable management solutions, IC represents a promising agroecological-based technique to overcome the drawbacks affecting lentil yield loss and instability. The aims of our research were to assess the effects of lentil-cereal IC on (i) crop productivity, (ii) weeds and (iii) bruchid pest dynamics.

Materials and Methods

A two-year field experiment was conducted in 2020 and 2021 at the experimental station of the DSA3 (FieldLab, University of Perugia, Italy; all details are described in Tosti et al., 2019). Two lentil-spring cereal intercropping mixtures (semi-additive scheme) were compared in a randomized complete block design with three replicates: (i) LT, Lentil + Triticale (\times *Triticosecale* Wittm., 'Forricale') and (ii) LB, Lentil + Barley (*Hordeum vulgare* L., 'Cometa'). The three crop species were also grown in pure stands as controls (i.e., pure stand lentil, LL; pure stand triticale, TT and pure stand barley, BB). Following Viguier et al. (2018), grain loss due to bruchids was estimated by measuring the percentage of damaged grains in each plot and the mean one-grain mass of bruchid-damaged grains. At harvest, lentil plants were collected from a 0.9 m² area in each plot. Intact sound grains (SG) and bruchid-damaged grains (DG) were separated and oven-dried for 48 hours at 80 °C, and average grain masses were determined. The total grain mass lost due to bruchids (GYL, g m⁻²) was considered the sum of the mass of DG residues (measured) plus the mass of grain consumed by bruchids (CG, g m⁻², see Eq.3).

$$\text{GYL} = \text{Mass of DG residues} + \text{Mass of CG} \quad [1]$$

GYL could also be estimated as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{GYL} &= \text{Number of DG} \times \text{Mass of one SG} = \\ &= (\text{Mass of DG residues} / \text{Mass of one DG}) \times \text{Mass of one SG} \quad [2] \end{aligned}$$

The mass of CG (g m⁻²) for each plot was calculated by substituting GYL in Eq. 1 with the terms of Eq. 2, as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Mass of CG} &= \text{GYL} - \text{Mass of DG residues} = \\ &= \text{Mass of DG residues} \times (\text{Mass of one SG} / \text{Mass of one DG} - 1) \quad [3] \end{aligned}$$

The attainable yield (g m⁻²) for each plot was calculated as the sum of the actual marketable yield and the mass of CG (Eq. 3). Finally, the yield loss due to bruchids (YLB, %) was calculated as the ratio between attainable yield and GYL (calculated as the sum of CG and DG residues).

Weed biomass was determined at harvest from the same sampling area used to determine yield and lentil grain loss due to bruchids. Weed biomass reduction (WBR, %) was then calculated according to Carton et al. (2020) as follows:

$$\text{WR} = 100 \times (\text{WB}_{\text{LL}} - \text{WB}_{\text{IC}}) / \text{WB}_{\text{LL}} \quad [4]$$

where WB_{LL} is the weed biomass at harvest in LL, and WB_{IC} is the weed biomass in the IC systems.

Results

The lentil yield was higher in 2021 than in 2020, and LL showed an approximately twofold yield compared to that achieved in both the ICs (Tab.1). Concerning cereals, TT showed the highest yield in 2020, while in 2021, the yield of TT was similar to that of BB. The grain production of triticale in LT in both years was

similar to that observed in BB in 2020 (188 g m⁻², on average), and it was significantly higher than that in LB. Bruchid damage was particularly severe in LL in 2020 (Tab.1), as losses were over 50% of the attainable yield and were significantly higher than those in the other treatments (27.4%, on average). Compared to LL, the height of the first pod insertion was increased by IC with cereals; triticale, in particular, was found to increase the first pod by 20 mm compared to barley (Tab.1). White goosefoot (CHEAL, *Chenopodium album* L.) represented 100% and 50% of the weed biomass in 2020 and 2021, respectively. In 2021, the second most represented weed species was common knotgrass (POLAV, *Polygonum aviculare* L.). In both years, weed biomass was strongly reduced by IC, which allowed almost complete weed suppression (WBR=97%±1.4 on average); in 2021, in particular, no weed biomass was even present in LB.

Tab.1 - Yield (g m⁻²), HI (%) and yield loss due to bruchids (YLB, %), First Pod Height (FPH, m) observed in pure stands of lentil (LL), barley (BB) and triticale (TT) and in lentil-barley (LB) and lentil-triticale (LT) mixtures during the 2-year experiment. P-levels for the F tests in ANOVA (** p < 0.01; * p < 0.05; ns p > 0.05) and Standard Error of the Difference (SED) are reported.

Year	Treatment	Lentil yield (g m ⁻²)	Cereal yield (g m ⁻²)	YLB (%)	FPH (m)
2020	LL	58.1	-	55.5	0.20
	LB	21.1	73.6	29.0	0.22
	LT	24.1	208	26.2	0.24
	BB	-	191	-	-
	TT	-	366	-	-
2021	LL	78.7	-	31.7	0.25
	LB	29.8	148	27.1	0.27
	LT	37.4	166	23.0	0.29
	BB	-	220	-	-
	TT	-	222	-	-
Source of variation					
T (Treatment)		**	**	**	**
Y (Year)		**	*	**	**
T x Y		ns	**	*	ns
SED		5.51	18.4	4.14	0.010

Conclusions

Lentil-spring cereal IC seems to be an interesting agroecological strategy, allowing us to contrast weed and reduce bruchid grain loss. Unfortunately, if the main goal is to obtain a sound lentil grain yield, the strong competitive effect of the cereal component must be somehow managed; otherwise, the advantages of IC are completely jeopardized. Further research is needed to find the best combination in terms of both cereal genotype choice and sowing rate. In particular, data suggest that the cereal sowing rate should be further reduced to improve the lentil yield in IC, but this choice should also be better assessed considering the consequences on pests and weeds.

Literature

- Carton et al. 2020. Intercropping winter lupin and triticale increases weed suppression and total yield. *Agriculture*, 10: 316.
- Guiducci et al. 2018. Sustainable management of nitrogen nutrition in winter wheat through temporary intercropping with legumes. *Agron. Sustain. Dev.*, 38(3): 31.
- Viguiet et al. 2018. Yield gap analysis extended to marketable grain reveals the profitability of organic lentil-spring wheat intercrops. *Agron. Sustain. Dev.*, 38: 39.
- Watson et al. 2017. Grain legume production and use in European agricultural systems. *Adv. Agron.*, 144: 235–303.

Weed Competition Ability of Perennial Forage Legumes and Grass Growth in Mixture and in Pure Stands Under Increasing Level of Simulated Shade in Rainfed Condition

Lorenzo Gabriele Tramacere¹, Alberto Mantino¹, Giorgio Ragaglini², Marcello Mele¹, Massimo Sbrana¹, Daniele Antichi¹

¹ Dipartimento di Scienze Agrarie, Alimentari ed Agro-ambientali, Univ. Pisa, IT, lorenzo.tramacere@unipi.it, alberto.mantino@unipi.it, marcello.mele@unipi.it, massimo.sbrana@unipi.it, daniele.antichi@unipi.it

² Dip. di Scienze Agrarie e Ambientali-Produzione, Territorio, Agroenergia, Univ. Milano, IT, giorgio.ragaglini@unimi.it

Introduction

In Italy, traditional olive orchards are characterised by low tree density (100-300 ha⁻¹) allowing the cultivation of forage and crops under the tree canopy (Paris et al., 2019). Eichhorn et al. (2006) reported that in Central Italy there are 20,000 ha of farmland identified as a silvoarable olive orchard. The intercropping of perennial legumes and trees is a key strategy to improve nutrient cycling in silvoarable systems (Hernandez-Esteban et al., 2019), providing also a continuous soil cover during the entire year, reducing soil erosion and enhancing weed control (Vallebona et al., 2016). However, weeds are an important component of agroecosystems; they play a fundamental role in the protection of soil and the conservation of beneficial fauna (Casanova-Lugo et al., 2023; Boinot et al., 2019), although they could determine a detrimental effect on forage yield. However, the large amount of foliage produced by trees could limit the growth of weed species due to the shade they provide (Atagnana et al., 2014). Moreover, tree species compete also with weeds for space, light, moisture, and soil nutrients. In Tuscany, sulla (*Hedysarum coronarium* L.) an autochthonous biennial legume is appreciated for its rusticity, productivity, and quality. For a better utilisation as pasture, sulla can be intercropped with Italian ryegrass (*Lolium multiflorum* Lam.). In this work, we assessed whether the forage mixture was competitive with weeds also under increasing shading conditions.

Materials and Methods

A rainfed plot field experiment was conducted at the Center for Agri-Environmental Research “Enrico Avanzi” of the University of Pisa (CiRAA), San Piero a Grado, Pisa, Italy (43°41'05.92''N, 10°20'31.34''E, 1 m above sea level and 0% slope), for two consecutive growing seasons on a clay-loam soil with pH of 8.1 and 2.5 % w/w of organic matter content in the topsoil (0-0.3 m). Before sowing, 100 kg ha⁻¹ of P₂O₅ were broadcast applied. The experiment was replicated in time on two adjacent fields, where the forage crops were grown for two consecutive years to follow their growing cycle: namely, experiment 1 referred to the biennial cycle 2019-2021, and experiment 2 to the cycle 2020-2022. The experimental layout was set up as a two-factor completely randomized design with four replicates (each plot sizing 18 m²) for both plot fields. The first factor, i.e. crop (C) included three different swards: sulla (SUL) cv. Silvan, ryegrass (RYE) cv. Teanna, intercropping (MIX) of sulla and ryegrass, 50:50 w:w. The second factor, i.e. shade (S), included three increasing simulated shade levels: (i) no shade, representing full light availability (NS), (ii) moderate shade (MS) with a reduction of potential light availability of 30% and (iii) high shade (HS) with a reduction of potential light availability of 50%. The shade was provided by woody slats built following the methodology of Varella et al. (2011). One woody structure made of parallel slats, 2 m long and 0.1 m wide, with a distance between each slat of 0.20 m for MS and 0.10 m for HS, respectively, was placed on a single plot, N-S oriented, covering a total surface of 4 m². After sowing, slats were placed at 0.8 m above ground level by means of wooden posts fixed on the borders. At each mowing time, weed biomass was collected on each plot on 2 areas of 0.25 m² each, then fresh weighted, and weighted again after oven-drying at 100°C.

Results

Cumulative weed biomass, obtained as the sum of the weed dry biomass of each mowing time, was affected only by C ($p < 0.001$) in both experiments. The mean effect of C for the experiment 1 resulted in significantly higher weed biomass in SUL plots than MIX and RYE plots, but this latter did not differ to each other (averagely + 40%). Differently, in the experiment 2 weeds on SUL and RYE plots resulted significantly greater than MIX (averagely + 80%) (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Average cumulative values of the weed biomass as affected by the crop (C), in the two years of the experiment 1 and the experiment 2. Vertical bars indicate standard error of the mean. Treatments with the same letter are not significantly different at $p \leq 0.05$ (Tukey's HSD test). MIX means mixture, RYE means ryegrass, SUL means sulla.

Conclusions

Besides the null effect of shade, our results showed that on average weeds were less abundant on MIX plots in both experiments. Averagely, the amount of weed biomass was greater in the experiment 1, and SUL plots resulted as the less competitive crop treatment in terms of weed biomass. These results showed as a legume-grass mixture could be a good strategy for agroforestry systems, from the point of view of the weed competition.

Literature

- Atangana A. et al. 2014. Ecological interactions and productivity in agroforestry systems. In: Tropical Agroforestry. Springer, Dordrecht.
- Boinot S. et al. 2019. Alley cropping agroforestry systems: reservoirs for weeds or refugia for plant diversity. *Agric. Ecosyst. Environ.*, 284: 106584.
- Casanova-Lugo F. et al. 2023. Alley cropping agroforestry systems change weed community composition and reduce dominant weed species associated with corn in southern Mexico. *Agric. Ecosyst. Environ.*, 350: 108471.
- Eichhorn M.P. et al. 2006. Silvoarablesystems in Europe –past, present and future prospects. *Agrofor. Syst.*, 67: 29–50.
- Hernández-Esteban et al. 2019. Are sown legume-rich pastures effective allies for the profitability and sustainability of Mediterranean dehesas? *Agrofor. Syst.*, 93: 2047–2065.
- Paris P. et al. 2019. What is the future for agroforestry in Italy? *Agrofor. Syst.*, 93: 2243-2256.
- Vallebona C. et al. 2016. Exploring the potential of perennial crops in reducing soil erosion: A GIS-based scenario analysis in southern Tuscany, Italy. *Appl. Geogr.*, 66: 119-131.
- Varella et al. 2011. Do light and alfalfa responses to cloth and slatted shade represent those measured under an agroforestry system? *Agroforest. Syst.*, 81: 157–173.

Oper8 Project, a New European Thematic Network on Non-chemical Methods of Weed Control

Lorenzo Gabriele Tramacere^{1,2}, Christian Frasconi^{1,2}, Lorenzo Gagliardi², Massimo Sbrana^{1,2},
Daniele Antichi^{1,2}

¹Centro di Ricerche Agro-ambientali “Enrico Avanzi”, Univ. Pisa, IT, lorenzo.tramacere@unipi.it,
christian.frasconi@unipi.it, massimo.sbrana@unipi.it, daniele.antichi@unipi.it

²Dipartimento di Scienze Agrarie, Alimentari ed Agro-ambientali, Univ. Pisa, IT
lorenzo.tramacere@unipi.it, christian.frasconi@unipi.it, lorenzo.gagliardi@phd.unipi.it, massimo.sbrana@unipi.it,
daniele.antichi@unipi.it

About the Oper8 Project

Oper8 is an European thematic network financially supported by the EU within the Horizon Europe Programme to bridge EIP-AGRI Operational Groups (OGs) working on alternative weed control methods. By joining the thematic network, the key stakeholders involved in each partner OG are enabled to share knowledge and upscale at European (EU) level the impact of weed control solutions alternative to herbicides tested at national level. Firstly, the project will define the needs for alternative weed control and barriers for its implementation across each network, that will be summarized in *ad hoc* inventory of solutions and knowledge gaps. From this starting point, National action plans will be developed in each involved country and they will be critically evaluated in a cost-benefit analysis by stakeholders, by assessing also the relevance of described solutions. Outcomes will be available as fact sheets, videos, e-learning modules and other formats. Best practices and audio-visual material will be demonstrated at regional/national agricultural fairs. Policy recommendations will be put forward from each country. Farm demonstrations will respond to specific needs and precise demand. Demo-farmers will share their experiences with other practitioners through different field events. With the ambition to achieve a high impact and improve the sustainability of the European agricultural sector, Oper8 will bring together 8 operational groups from 7 countries from the Mediterranean, Atlantic, and Nordic areas to ensure a balanced representation of different production systems in EU. Oper8 will focus on issues identified by the involved OGs with their individual approaches, identified challenges and dissemination activities.

Figure 1. Map of the Operational Group involved in the Oper8 Project (www.oper8.eu)

Operational Group from Italy: GO-IOCONCIV

The GO-IOCONCIV (<https://www.ioconciv.it/>) focused on weed control in vineyard. The OG had as challenge to reduce herbicide application and increase soil fertility by the promotion and the evaluation of alternative and sustainable ways to manage differently the inter- and intra- row space in vineyards. The use of cover crops represents an alternative soil and weed management solution which could improve conventional and organic viticulture sustainability. In fact, cover crops can deliver important agroecosystem services, e.g. improved soil fertility, reduced soil erosion and weed presence, increased carbon and nitrogen input and biodiversity. The innovation proposed aims to reduce herbicide application and tillage intensity and consists in the introduction of an annual self-reseeding cover crop under the rows, coupled with a standard cover crop mixture sown on alternated inter-rows. In particular, the innovative process implies sowing a subterranean clover in late summer/early fall under the rows (once every 3 or 4 years) that grows up until late spring-early summer, when it releases the mature seeds directly into the soil by geocarpy. In this way, the clover biomass will cover the soil in autumn, winter and spring as living mulch, and in summer as dead mulch, by avoiding so the competition for water and nutrients with the grapevines. At the end of the summer, the clover seeds will spontaneously germinate, and a new biological cycle will start under the rows, with benefits in terms of contrasting weed emergence and soil fertility improvement (i.e., by organic matter increase/conservation, reduced soil erosion and increased N availability).

Considering that the subterranean clover has already proved to be a competitive species against weeds and the permanent cover has influenced quantity and quality of grape production obtaining higher yields and higher content of nitrogen in berries, this solution could be a sustainable alternative way to manage soils and weeds in vineyards, reducing also the environmental impact and production costs.

A future challenge is the improvement of the seeding of the clover by using innovative techniques. With this purpose, the operative group developed a prototype mechanical drilling machine, able to sow the different cover crops on intra-rows and inter-row spaces. This seeder machine showed some limitations in seed distribution during the project, thus it is necessary to adapt and improve it by collaborating with farmers and investigate the better choice of clover cultivars and other crop species according to specific needs.

Figure 2. Self reseeding subterranean clover under the row, in Monterosola farm, Volterra, Pisa, Italy. Picture by Daniele Antichi.

The Oper8 Project has received funding from The European Union Horizon 2021 Food, Bioeconomy Natural Resources, Agriculture and Environment Programme under grant agreement [101060591](https://doi.org/10.1016/101060591).

A Two-Step Approach for the Calibration and Simulation of Wheat-Lentil Intercropping Systems Using MONICA

Alessandro Triacca¹, Stefano Carlesi¹, Federico Leoni¹, Gilbert Koskey¹, Anna-Camilla Moonen¹, Moritz Reckling², Claas Nendel²

¹ Group of Agroecology, Center of Plant Sciences, Scuola Superiore Sant'Anna, IT,
alessandro.triacca@santannapisa.it

² Leibniz Centre for Agricultural Landscape Research (ZALF) e.V., Institute for Landscape System Analysis, Germany

Introduction

In agriculture, crop simulation models are widely used in decision support systems (DSS) development. These models provide estimates of important agronomic parameters such as seed doses, crop yield and optimal crop harvest time based on soil and weather dynamics, crop management and environmental scenarios (Pereira et al., 2002; Confalonieri et al., 2009), which ultimately result in a reduced use of external input such as mineral fertilizer, herbicides and water (Benli et al., 2007). However, crops models need to be calibrated and validated through specific field experiments before their implementation (Van Ittersum and Donatelli, 2003).

For this purpose, the crop model MONICA is often used for running simulations of the agronomic variables on cereal crops such as wheat or barley. However, information on legume crops is still lacking, and simulations have been implemented in MONICA only for soybean and field-pea. Moreover, despite there is a growing interest in increasing the crop diversification of the European cropping systems, the development of models for simulating cereal-legume intercropping systems is still in progress. The objective of this work is two-fold. In the first step we aim to parametrise minor legume crop such as lentil into MONICA. In the second step, we aim to simulate the performance of wheat and lentil intercropping in low-input cereal-based cropping system under two contrasting climate and environmental conditions.

Materials and Methods

MONICA is an agro-ecosystem model that mathematically describes crop growth and soil processes (Nendel et al., 2011). It requires information of crop management, soil characteristics, and climate data to calculate crop-related outputs such as crop yield, N uptake and water consumption, as well as environmental outputs such as soil moisture, groundwater recharge and organic matter dynamics. In this work a two-stage method was employed to establish a modelling framework capable of simulating intercropping systems, using MONICA as a basis. In the initial stage, the legume sole crop (specifically lentil in our study) was parameterized since it was not originally included in MONICA. In the following stage, we will use this information for the implementation of MONICA for the wheat-lentil intercropping. This methodology is articulated into two stages:

- First stage: The parametrization process involved a sequential optimization method, which was partially inspired by a similar approach used for faba bean by Falconieri et al. (2019). The first step involved reviewing the literature to identify the essential parameters needed for the model. In the second step, parameter values were assigned based on the experimental data. The final step involved optimizing the parameters using the methodology described by Guillaume et al. (2011).
 - Data needed for the lentil parametrisation were collected from a set of previous experiment on lentil carried out in Pisa at the Centre for Agri-Environmental Research Enrico Avanzi (CiRAA) and in Müncheberg at the Leibniz-Centre for Agricultural Landscape Research (ZALF) from 2018 to 2023. The experiments tested different lentil cultivars and sowing densities.
- Second stage: A simple and generic formalism, inspired by the work of Confalonieri (2014), was developed to integrate single instances of MONICA to simulate intercropping systems. Using

expert-based knowledge and literature, a set of hierarchically-arranged unitless suitability functions (one for each environmental and management driver) were defined to aggregate single-species state variable to a community level.

- Specific experiment on wheat-lentil intercropping were carried out from 2022 and are ongoing at CiRAA with the scope to evaluate the agronomic performance of durum wheat-lentil intercropping in a Mediterranean cereal-based cropping systems. Throughout the growing season, we conducted repeated monitoring and sampling to assess various agronomic and environmental variables, including developmental stages, grain yield, aboveground biomass, leaf area index, plant height, N uptake, as well as soil variables such as N content, moisture, and temperature. Additionally, in 2023, a parallel experiment is currently being conducted at ZALF to evaluate the same set of agronomic and environmental variables under a contrasting environment.

Common evaluation metrics were used to assess the goodness of fit between observed and simulated values.

Results

The on-going analysis will allow the determination of a set of model parameters, useful for the simulation of lentils as a sole crop within MONICA. Subsequently, it is anticipated that the defined suitability functions will enable a consistent mathematical representation of the competition and facilitation processes occurring within a bi-specific intercropping system. Due to the extensive collection of plant and environmental variables, the simulation of lentil, as sole crop and intercropped with wheat, will be effectively assessed and evaluated.

Conclusions

This study makes a significant contribution to the parametrization of lentil, an increasingly important legume, within the crop models community. This parametrization enables the simulation of lentil in research studies, thereby facilitating the promotion and adoption of this crop. Moreover, this study makes a valuable contribution to the progress in modelling cereal-legume intercropping systems by addressing diversity at the field level. The findings of this study can significantly support farmers decision making for the use of intercropping practices, guiding them in the selection of suitable cultivar and plant density for the local environmental condition. Extend the parametrisation to other legume for intercropping systems such as chickpea and common bean is the challenge for the near future.

Literature

Benli B. et al. 2007. Assessment of winter wheat production under early sowing with supplemental irrigation in a cold highland environment using CropSyst simulation model. *Agric. Water Manage.*, 93: 45.

Confalonieri R. et al. 2009. Evaluation of parameterization strategies for rice modelling. *Spanish J. Agric. Res.*, 7: 680.

Confalonieri R. et al. 2014. CoSMo: A simple approach for reproducing plant community dynamics using a single instance of generic crop simulators. *Ecol. Model.*, 286: 1-10.

Falconnier G.N. et al. 2019. Calibration and evaluation of the STICS soil-crop model for faba bean to explain variability in yield and N₂ fixation. *Eur. J. Agron.*, 104: 63-77.

Guillaume S. et al. 2011. Methodological comparison of calibration procedures for durum wheat parameters in the STICS model. *Eur. J. Agron.*, 35: 115-126.

Nendel C. et al. 2019. The MONICA model: Testing predictability for crop growth, soil moisture and nitrogen dynamics. *Ecol. Model.*, 222: 1614-1625.

Pereira L.S. et al. 2002. Irrigation management under water scarcity. *Agric. Water Manage.*, 57: 175.

Van Ittersum M.K. and Donatelli M. 2003 Modelling cropping systems-highlights of the symposium and preface to the special issues. *Eur. J. Agron.*, 18: 187.

Improving Skills on Digital Agriculture in Europe: Lessons Learnt from the AgriSmart Project

Valentina Vaglia¹, Francesco Fava², Eugenio Carlon², George Dimitriadis³, Martyna Kurek⁴, Erika Nika⁵, Heide Reimer⁶, Peter Vnucko⁷, Ambrogio Zanzi², Stefano Bocchi²

¹ Dep. Earth and Environmental Sciences, Univ. Pavia, IT

² Dip. Scienze e Politiche Ambientali, Univ. Milano, IT

³ INNOVELA Sprl, Brussel, Belgium

⁴ ARID Association, Krakov, Poland

⁵ EXELIA, Athens Greece

⁶ DEULA-Nienburg, Nienburg, Germany

⁷ IZPI Agricultural Knowledge and Innovation Institute, Nitra, Slovakia

Introduction

The agricultural sector is one of the European Union's (EU) big employers, directly employing nearly 8.7 million people in 2020 (EUROSTAT, 2022). This sector is inherently interlinked with climate change, since agriculture is simultaneously both affected by it and contributes to it. Recognising this link, the EU has prioritised the promotion of "digital agriculture" and has signed up to relevant international commitments, especially those concerning climate change and sustainable development.

These commitments are reflected in the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP), with "smart farming" being a central component of transitioning toward more sustainable agricultural practices (EC, 2020). In terms of initial and continuing education and training, the vast majority of farmers (70%) in the EU rely solely on practical experience (Augère-Granier, 2017), and projections about the adoption of digital farming practices remain uncertain (Ehlers et al., 2022). Thus, the efforts to develop farmers' digital skills and increase the agri-food sector's sustainability must consider that agriculture has a particularly strong practical experience component; Vocational Education Training (VET) and Work-Based Learning (WBL) are important instruments for supporting these efforts.

These premises have motivated AgriSmart, an Erasmus+ KA202 project conducted by a partnership of six EU countries (Belgium, Germany, Greece, Italy, Slovakia, and Poland). AgriSmart aims at adapting VET and WBL provisions to existing and emerging occupational needs in the agricultural sector, with the overarching goal of strengthening the digital skills of farmers, as well as supporting growing awareness and stronger competencies on sustainable agricultural management practices that can and need to be adopted in line with the EU CAP. The specific objectives of AgriSmart are to:

- Design a course curriculum on climate-smart and digital practices, addressing current and future occupational needs.
- Introduce various training delivery methods and innovative open-access pedagogical resources tailored to sectoral characteristics to support VET and WBL provision.
- Increase the capacities and enhance cooperation between public and sectoral stakeholders to promote the integration of climate-smart and digital skills development in training offerings and regional policies, thus reaching out to agricultural communities.

Materials and Methods

As a first step, we conducted a desk review on VET and WBL offerings in the target countries and a questionnaire with over 80 stakeholders (farmers, sectorial experts and trainers) to investigate the most valued and needed digital skills required in agriculture and to highlight existing skills imbalances and experiences from farmers for sustainable digital farming. The following step was to develop a curriculum on digital agriculture suitable for VET and WBL provisions, along with a range of resources to support trainers and mentors in designing targeted training by using and customizing the material. These resources included a Vocational Open Online Course (VOOC) and a learner's E-book.

Another set of key informants interviews was conducted with teachers and trainers involved in VET and WBL provision in the agricultural sector, to get feedback on the generated resources and to explore their needs for the specific national context and education system. Based on these interviews, a Mentors Toolkit was produced. The open educational material has been disseminated and discussed during six national InfoDays (multipliers events) with a wide range of stakeholders (~300), including representatives of regional authorities, agricultural associations, private agri-food sector actors, organizations involved in training provision, and farm managers, to facilitate the adoption of the material and of creating the basis for post-project initiatives.

Results

The Agrismart project has generated many open educational resources (available at www.agri-smart.eu) that stakeholders have positively evaluated. However, that should still be refined and improved for the national contexts and specific training needs. The initial desk review and stakeholders' engagements have shown a strong heterogeneity across the EU on the level of skills in digital agriculture, the approaches for VET and WBL delivering in the agricultural sector, and the demand for more or less advanced digital skills. This suggests the difficulty of developing uniform training resources across multiple countries and calls for creating modular and customizable material that can (and needs to) be adapted to the local context. Regarding priority topics, we observed a general recognition of the importance of linking digital skills with the practical experience of farmers and, more specifically, to sustainable practices supported by the new CAP. Therefore the AgriSmart curriculum combined a set of Learning Units (LUs) dedicated to more general topics in agronomy (CAP, Sustainable agriculture, Water use management, Weeds and pest management) with LUs specifically focused on basic and more advanced digital agriculture skills (Agriculture 4.0, Data for sustainable production). The curriculum aims not to be comprehensive but to provide a methodological and practical reference for further integration and customization.

From the engagement with stakeholders in the policy domain, some critical considerations have emerged for future policy planning:

- The heterogeneity of the demand for digital skilled labour may be caused by a lack of educators able to create a solid EU-uniform vision about the role of digital agriculture. Filling this gap should be recognized as a priority for future initiatives at the national and EU-level.
- To reconnect agricultural management practices, scientific innovation and sustainability targets, it is important to demonstrate the cost/benefit for companies and farmers of introducing digital innovation and more sustainable agricultural practices. This could be achieved also by better-connecting theory and practice through WBL.
- In the future, it would be fundamental to support digital agriculture skills and competencies in a lifelong learning approach to increase basic digital skills and link them to evolving sustainable agriculture practices and policies. This fundamental gap must be integrated into future curricula and training material design efforts.
- Changes are needed in the legislation to retrain agricultural workers and promote marketable skills. Whilst companies operating in rural development try to push more sustainable management solutions, a legislative effort is required to produce incentive mechanisms for the farmer.

Literature

Augère-Granier M. 2017. Agricultural education and lifelong training in the EU. European Parliamentary Research Service. [www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/BRIE/2017/608788/EPRS_BRI\(2017\)608788_EN.pdf](http://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/BRIE/2017/608788/EPRS_BRI(2017)608788_EN.pdf)

European Commission (EC) 2020. Farm to Fork Strategy – For a Fair, Healthy and Environmentally-Friendly Food System European Commission, Brussels.

Ehlers, M.H. et al. 2022. Scenarios for European agricultural policymaking in the era of digitalisation. *Agric. Syst.*, 196: 103318.

Eurostat 2022. Farmers and the agricultural labour force – statistics <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained>

Agronomic and Environmental Effects of Alternate Wetting and Drying in Italian Rice Cultivation

Andrea Vitali^{1,2}, Barbara Moretti¹, Chiara Bertora¹, Eleonora Miniotti², Silvia Fogliatto¹, Marco Romani², Luisella Celi¹, Daniel Said-Pullicino¹, Francesco Vidotto¹

¹ Dept. Agricultural, Forest and Food Sciences, Univ. Turin, IT

² Rice Research Centre, Ente Nazionale Risi, Castello d'Agogna, IT

Introduction

Alternate wetting and drying (AWD) irrigation, as opposed to continuous flooding (CF) in conventionally managed rice production systems, is an irrigation practice that may allow to reduce water use and methane emissions (Linquist et al., 2015), but can be limited by yield losses (Carrijo et al., 2018). AWD, that involves the introduction of regular drainage periods during the growing season, has already been studied in Italy but only in combination with dry seeding (Lagomarsino et al., 2016, Monaco et al., 2021). This study aims at evaluating the adoption of water seeding followed by AWD from tillering stage on grain yield, yield components and greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions compared to conventional CF.

Materials and Methods

A field experiment was conducted in 2021 at the Rice Research Centre of Ente Nazionale Risi in Castello d'Agogna (PV province), North-West Italy. The experiment was performed in a split-plot design with three water management techniques, each implemented in two paddy chambers of about 1500 m² each: (i) CF - water seeding and continuous flooding; (ii) AWD safe - water seeding and moderate AWD (soil matrix potential -30 hPa at 5 cm above ground level); and (iii) AWD strong - water seeding and severe AWD (water potential -200 hPa at 5 cm above ground level). The second factor considered two rice varieties (Selenio and CL26), chosen for different morphological characteristics and root structure. A supply of 100 kg N ha⁻¹ and 120 kg N ha⁻¹ was provided to all plots across water managements for Selenio and CL26, respectively. Grain yield, yield components and quality parameters were measured at harvest. Methane (CH₄) and nitrous oxide (N₂O) emissions were measured weekly during the entire growing period by adopting a non-steady-state closed chamber technique with four replicates per treatment. Cumulative annual fluxes of CH₄ and N₂O, Global Warming Potential (GWP) and GHG Eco-Efficiency were calculated.

Results

Both AWD managements showed similar yield to conventional CF for both varieties tested (*Table 1*). With the exception of sterility, yield components were also not significantly affected by water management. Only in CL26 both AWD safe and AWD strong resulted in higher final panicle density. An increase in sterility was recorded with AWD compared with CF. Head rice recovery was significantly higher in AWD both for Selenio and CL26. AWD strong was effective in reducing CH₄ emissions compared with CF in both varieties, while AWD safe was effective only for Selenio (*Figure 1*). In the case of N₂O emissions, a high spatial variability with no significant differences among the three water managements was recorded. Methane contributed much more to the GWP with respect to N₂O across all treatments. AWD reduced GWP by 22% with AWD safe and 36% with AWD strong. AWD, especially AWD strong, showed higher Eco-efficiency than CF, with higher values for Selenio than CL26.

Table 1. Effects of water management on yield, yield components and quality parameter for Selenio and CL26. Different letters show significant differences according to Bonferroni post hoc test ($P < 0.05$).

Variety	Water management	Yield (Mg ha ⁻¹)	Panicle density (n° m ⁻²)	1000 grain weight (g)	Spikelets per panicle (n°)	Sterility (%)	Head rice recovery (%)
Selenio	CF	10.2	637	25.4	96	8.1 b	53.4 c
	AWD safe	10.3	642	25.2	101	10.9 a	55.3 b
	AWD strong	10.5	650	25.1	101	10.5 ab	58.9 a
	P(f) Water	ns	ns	ns	ns	0.027	0.031
CL26	CF	9.1	664 b	21.9	109	10.2 b	67.0 b
	AWD safe	9.3	711 a	21.6	115	12.0 a	68.0 ab
	AWD strong	9.3	717 a	21.6	114	12.9 a	68.9 a
	P(f) Water	ns	0.035	ns	ns	0.008	0.045

Fig. 1. Effects of water management on CH₄ (a) and N₂O (b) cumulative emissions for Selenio and CL26. Global Warming Potential (GWP) (average of two varieties) and Eco-efficiency (c) in different water management. Different letters show significant differences according to Bonferroni post hoc test ($P < 0.05$).

Conclusions

Water seeding of rice combined with AWD from tillering, even if it resulted in increased sterility, did not reduce grain yields compared to traditional continuous flooding. These similar results between different irrigation management could be due to the lower physiological stresses typical of the reductive conditions in flooded paddy soils. AWD allowed to reduce GWP and increase Eco-efficiency, especially with its most severe application, without significant differences between varieties, but with large variability due to soil moisture and oxidation-reduction conditions in different areas of the field.

Acknowledgements

This work was financially supported by the agricultural and forestry research funding programme (2018) of Lombardy Region through the project “RISWAGEST” (d.d.s. March 5th, 2020 – n. 2955).

Literature

- Carrizo D.R. et al. 2018. Impacts of variable soil drying in alternate wetting and drying rice systems on yields, grain arsenic concentration and soil moisture dynamics. *Field Crops Res.*, 222: 101–110.
- Lagomarsino A. et al. 2016. Alternate wetting and drying of rice reduced CH₄ emissions but triggered N₂O peaks in a clayey soil of central Italy. *Pedosphere*, 26: 533–548.
- Linquist B.A. et al. 2015. Reducing greenhouse gas emissions, water use, and grain arsenic levels in rice systems. *Glob. Chang. Biol.*, 21: 407–417.
- Monaco S. et al. 2021. Effects of the application of a moderate alternate wetting and drying technique on the performance of different European varieties in Northern Italy rice system. *Field Crops Res.*, 270: 108–220.

Environmental Sustainability of Durum Wheat Cropping Systems: a Life Cycle Assessment Perspective

Silvia Zingale¹, Carlo Ingraio², Giuseppe Indovino¹, Umberto Anastasi¹, Antonio Carlo Barbera¹, Paolo Guarnaccia¹, Thomas Nemecek³

¹ Di3A, Univ. Catania, IT, silvia.zingale@phd.unict.it; giuseppe.indovino@studium.unict.it; umberto.anastasi@unict.it; antonio.barbera@unict.it; paolo.guarnaccia@unict.it

² DEMDI, Univ. Bari, IT, carlo.ingrao@uniba.it

³ Agroscope, LCA research group, Zurich, CH, thomas.nemecek@agroscope.admin.ch

Introduction

Farming systems are currently contributing to the degradation of both terrestrial and aquatic ecosystems, by depleting water resources and driving climate change (Poore and Nemecek 2018). Several researchers have evaluated the agricultural and food production processes from an environmental perspective, and more recently, increasing attention has been paid to assessing the benefits arising from the implementation of mitigation strategies (Ingraio et al., 2018). Among others, Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) is recognised to be a systemic, standardised (ISO 2006a, b) and science-based methodology for assessing the impacts associated with the life cycle of a product or service. The application of LCA to cropping systems is particularly challenging due to the intrinsic high variability, complexity and multifunctionality of agriculture (Goglio et al., 2018). Cereal crops are posing increasing threats to environmental, and human health by being grown under intensive cropping systems which usually use huge amounts of fertilisers, agrochemicals and fuel (Zingale et al., 2022). In this context, the present study aimed at performing a *comparative* and *multifunctional* LCA on two highly different durum wheat-based (DW) cropping systems, namely 1) a low-input organic system based on growing a landrace, and 2) a conventional high-input system based on growing an improved variety.

Materials and Methods

The research was carried out in Sicily on two farms (sited in Ragusa, and Ramacca), where in the previous year the soil was cultivated with a grain legume crop and bare-fallow in the organic and conventional cropping system, respectively. From a methodological perspective, this study presents a number of elements of novelty, mainly dealing with the approach adopted to model the investigated cropping systems (*combined*), and the use of multiple functional units (FUs), including mass, land, price and quality-based ones. Primary data for the Life Cycle Inventory (LCI) step were obtained through interviews and questionnaires with the farmers over a period of four years (2018/19 – 2021/22 growing seasons). Direct field emissions of ammonia (NH₃), nitrous oxide (N₂O), nitrate (NO₃⁻), and phosphate (PO₄³⁻) were calculated following the World Food LCA Database Guidelines (Nemecek et al., 2019). Agrochemicals emissions were calculated by using the default fractions provided by the OLCA-Pest Project (Nemecek et al., 2022). The assessment of the environmental impacts was carried out by accounting for the following impact categories: Global Warming Potential (IPCC 2013 GWP100years v. 1.03), Land Use (ReCipe 2016 Endpoint H), Cumulative Energy Demand (CED v. 1.11) and Toxicity (USETox 2), as available in Simapro 9.1.0.11.

Results

The organic low-input DW cropping system was found to have lower impacts per kg grain for all the impact categories analysed (Figure 1). The better profile of this system was confirmed regardless of the FU (data not shown). In terms of CED, the conventional and high input system performed worst, as a consequence of the high amounts of diesel used for the soil tillage management, and the energetic costs associated with the production of the inputs (seeds, fertilisers, pesticides). Also as GWP impacts, differences among the two systems were appreciable, with the conventional system emitting more than five times the organic one (1.46 CO₂eq vs. 0.263). This was primarily due to the higher emissions generated within the bare-fallow

year, as well as to the intensive cultivation. Also, despite the lower grain yield of the landrace (1.9 t ha⁻¹ vs. 3.75 t ha⁻¹), the organic and low-input system had a lower land use (LU) impact than the other system, since the seeds used for sowing were self-produced, and the faba bean rotation *effect* was responsible for a lower LU compared to that of bare fallow in the conventional system. This finding shows that considering the whole cropping system with a *combined* modelling approach is needed to adequately include interactions between crops in a cropping system. Moreover, the higher toxicity impacts assessed for the conventional system were mainly caused by the emissions generated during the inputs production processes (human health) and by the contamination of soil and water with the release of agrochemicals (ecosystems).

Figure 14. Results from the Life Cycle Impact Assessment (LCIA) expressed with FU=kg of grain

Conclusions

Results highlighted the potential of low-input DW-based cropping systems based on organic farming practices and the valorisation of local genotypes for saving renewable resources and minimizing emissions of GHGs and other environmental pollutants. The findings stressed the urge for enhancing DW productivity whilst minimising environmental impacts, by adopting well-designed crop rotations, organic and conservation farming practices, less intensive tillage, and reduced use of fertilisers and agrochemicals.

Literature

Ingrao C. et al. 2018 Energy and environmental assessment of a traditional durum-wheat bread. *J. Clean. Prod.*, 171: 1494-1509.

ISO 2006a. 14040: Environmental Management-Life Cycle Assessment-Principles and Framework (ISO 14040: 2006), German and English version EN ISO 14040: 2006. International Organization for Standardization: Geneva, Switzerland

ISO 2006b. 14044-Environmental Management - Life Cycle Assessment - Requirements and Guidelines

Nemecek T. et al. 2022. Operationalising emission and toxicity modelling of pesticides in LCA: the OLCA-Pest project contribution. *Int. J. Life Cycle Assess.*, 27(4): 527-542.

Nemecek T. et al. 2019. World Food LCA Database.

Poore J. and Nemecek T. 2018. Reducing food’s environmental impacts through producers and consumers. *Science*, 360(6392): 987-992

Rockström J. et al. 2009. Planetary boundaries: exploring the safe operating space for humanity. *Ecol. Soc.*, 14 (2): 32.

Zingale S. et al. 2022. A systematic literature review of life cycle assessments in the durum wheat sector. *Sci. Total Environ.*, 844: 157230.

Sessione 4

**RESILIENZA - Adattamento delle
produzioni ai criteri di sostenibilità e ai
cambiamenti climatici**

ORAL PRESENTATIONS

Adapting Crops for the Green Transition: Smart Protein Project Experiences for Plant Protein Production Across Europe

Gabriela Alandia^{1,2*}, Nisha Sharma², Signe Marie Jensen¹, Fulai Liu¹, Harm Brinks³, Johan Wander³, Dragica Grozdanic⁴, Lucía Sanchez⁵, Avichai Amrad⁶, Daniel Marusig^{2,7}, and Gemini Delle Vedove²

¹ Dep. Plant and Environmental Sciences, Univ. Copenhagen, Denmark, gar@plen.ku.dk; gabriela.alandia@uniud.it

² Dep. Agricultural, Food, Environmental and Animal Sciences, Univ. Udine, IT, gemini.dellevedove@uniud.it; nisha.sharma@uniud.it

³ Delphy, Wageningen, The Netherlands, H.Brinks@delphy.nl; J.Wander@delphy.nl

⁴ INTIA Avda. Serapio Huici, Villava / Atarrabia (Navarra / Nafarroa), lsanchez@intiasa.es

⁵ Beotronics Ltd, Oldtown, Stoneyford, Ireland, Dragica@beotronics.com

⁶ Equinom Ltd., Givat Brenner, Israel

⁷ Dip. Scienze della Vita, Univ. Trieste, IT, daniel.marusig@phd.units.it

Introduction

Through the Green Deal strategy, European countries have committed to reduce greenhouse gas emissions and become a neutral continent by 2050 (European Commission, 2019). One of the main challenges is food production for the growing population. The transition to plant-protein diets represents an alternative solution to reduce the high environmental footprint of meat production (Detzel *et al.*, 2022). To contribute to the Green Deal, the Smart Protein EU project is aiming to develop alternative protein ingredients and products with positive impact on bioeconomy, environment, biodiversity, nutrition, food security and consumers (CORDIS, 2020). Crop production is the first step to ensure this objective and the plant-based food supply chain. For this, partners are working to understand the suitability, profitability, and potential yields of four crops grown across different regions of Europe (quinoa, fava beans, lentils, and chickpeas).

Materials and Methods

The presentation summarizes results of cultivar screening experiments in seven pilot farms established in the North (Ireland, Denmark, The Netherlands, and Poland) and in the South of Europe (Spain, Italy and Portugal) during 2020 and 2021. Based on the hypothesis that cultivars have different responses in different pedoclimatic regions of Europe we tested pre-lines and cultivars in the pilot farms and evaluated yield components: grain yield (kg ha⁻¹), thousand seed weight (g), seed protein contents (%) and protein yield (kg ha⁻¹). Data was compiled and analyzed using R statistical software (R Core Team, 2015) and the effect of genotype on each studied variable was estimated with linear mixed models and multiple comparisons. Comparisons were made within country and year and discussed by region (north and south of Europe).

Results

Results showed that fava bean has high potential for plant protein production with up to 630 kg protein ha⁻¹ especially in the North of Europe. A fava bean cultivar from UK tested both in the North and South of Europe showed good adaptation through stable grain yield production across Europe. In addition, this genotype has low levels of antinutrients. In the South of Europe, chickpea showed interesting potential with up to 661 kg protein ha⁻¹ (Table 1). The amount of plant protein produced by lentils and quinoa was lower but not negligible in terms of protein quality for specific food products.

Table 1. Seed yield, thousand seed weight (TSW) and protein content from best screening years of fava bean and chickpea cultivars validated in the North and South of Europe (2020/2021)

Year/ spp	Cultivar	Yield (kg ha ⁻¹)			TSW (g)			Protein (%)			Protein Yield (kg ha ⁻¹)			
		Est	s.e.	sign.	Est	s.e.	sign.	Est	s.e.	sign.	Est	s.e.	sign.	
2021/ Fava beans	Tiffany	2679	178	a	439	10.4	bcd	23.6	1.143	a	630	71	a	
	Bolivia	2612	178	a	429	10.4	ab	23.5	1.143	a	616	71	a	
	Lynxs	2397	205	ab	440	11.8	bce	25.8	1.320	a	462	71	a	
	Victus	2279	178	abc	497	10.4	e	26.0	1.143	a	593	71	a	
	Sunrise	2248	178	abc	426	10.4	ac	26.0	1.143	a	579	71	a	
	Fanfare	2240	178	abc	470	10.4	ce	22.9	1.143	a	514	71	a	
	Fuego	2237	178	abc	487	10.4	de	22.3	1.143	a	497	71	a	
	Taifun	2211	178	abc	425	10.4	ac	23.9	1.143	a	529	71	a	
	Alexia	1854	178	bc	378	10.4	a	21.9	1.143	a	407	71	a	
	Emilia	1707	178	c	395	10.4	ab	25.5	1.143	a	436	71	a	
2020/ Chick pea	Duratón	3245	372	b	395	35.4	a	19.1	0.355	ab	627	72.7	b	
	Amelia	3032	372	b	367	43.3	a	18.6	0.410	ab	568	89.0	b	
	Eulalia	3243	372	b	266	35.4	a	19.7	0.355	ab	635	72.7	b	
	Carmen	3303	372	b	408	35.4	a	20.2	0.355	b	661	72.7	b	
	Lola	2546	372	ab	371	35.4	a	18.8	0.355	ab	475	72.7	ab	
	B Sinaloa	802	372	a	365	35.4	a	18.5	0.355	a	149	72.7	a	
	Garabito	3123	372	b	286	35.4	a	19.5	0.355	ab	609	72.7	b	
	Cuaiz	2853	372	b	388	35.4	a	19.1	0.355	ab	552	72.7	b	
	Cultivar*Year		***			***			***			***		

Conclusions

Plant protein production in Europe can be achieved with the production of plant species such as fava beans, chickpeas, lentils and quinoa. There are cultivars that show adaptation to different latitudes of Europe and that can produce stable and high volumes of protein. Challenges to achieve stable supply under organic production systems relate to plant abiotic and biotic stress. Therefore, innovative alternatives for pest and disease control as well as breeding activities are fundamental to continue efforts towards the neutral continent expected by 2050.

Acknowledgements

This research has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 862957.

Literature

- Detzel A. et al. 2022. Life cycle assessment of animal-based foods and plant-based protein-rich alternatives: an environmental perspective. *J. Sci. Food Agric.*, 102(12): 5098-5110.
- CORDIS, 2020. Smart Protein for a Changing World. Project Description. doi:10.3030/862957.
- European Commission, 2019. Factsheet: What is the European Green Deal?. [What is the European Green Deal? \(europa.eu\)](https://ec.europa.eu/euro-observatory/en/what-is-the-european-green-deal)
- R Core Team (2015). *R: A Language and Environment for Statistical Computing*. Vienna: R Foundation for Statistical Computing.

Application of Multi-Height Beerkan Method and BEST-Procedure to Study the Water Impact Effects on Soil Hydraulic Properties Under Alternative Soil Management

Mirko Castellini¹, Antonio Preite¹, Luisa Giglio¹, Michele Rinaldi²

¹ CREA-AA, Bari, IT, mirko.castellini@crea.gov.it

² CREA-CI, Foggia, IT

Introduction

Soil management is becoming increasingly important in relation to the ongoing climate changes. In particular, it is known that a given soil can show a different resilience to rainfalls events depending on the management, structural and water content condition at the time of the events. Therefore, a dry freshly bared soil could be more prone to slaking and soil sealing and, when sloping, the soil can be more prone to surface water erosion. The multi-height beerkan method may be applied to induce a soil disturbance similar to that occurring when rainfall produces surface runoff. Since it was proposed (Bagarello et al., 2014), such method has received targeted attention both to the improvement of the methodology setup or to the application possibilities explored (Bagarello et al., 2023). In this investigation, the response of a loam soil managed in an alternative way (recently tilled or undisturbed from a long time) and subjected to infiltration experiments aimed at determining the surface soil alteration, was evaluated. The specific objective was to evaluate the different resilience degree associated to soil management in terms of water infiltration, saturated hydraulic conductivity, soil sorptivity and modeled soil water retention curve.

Materials and Methods

The investigation was carried out on a fallow loam soil at the experimental field of the Council for Agricultural Research and Economics, Research Center for Agriculture and Environment (CREA-AA) of Bari. Two plots of about 100 m² each were selected to establish alternative soil structure conditions, namely a conventionally tilled, CT (unstructured) and a no-tilled, NT (structured) plots. Single-ring infiltration experiments of the beerkan type were carried out in the spring-summer season; therefore, the measurements were obtained in dry soil conditions. For a given plot (CT and NT), 12 sampling points randomly were selected to apply the beerkan multi-height method, and 3 heights of water pouring (low, L, from approximately 3 cm; intermediate, M, height of 100 cm; high, H, height of 200 cm) were considered. To ensure flow verticality and prevent wind effects, the device by Castellini et al. (2021) was used. Infiltration runs were carried out applying a “two-stage without break” methodology where the first half of experiment differed in the ability to alter (H, M) or not (L) the soil surface, while the second one was always non-perturbative (L). Therefore, the applied sequences were of HL, ML or LL type. Surface soil hydraulic properties (saturated hydraulic conductivity, soil sorptivity and the retention curve scale parameter) were modeled by the BEST-steady algorithm using cumulative infiltration, soil texture, bulk density and volumetric water content as input (Castellini et al., 2021).

Results

Figure 1. Mean infiltration time of the applied water volume against the water pouring number (WPN).

Figure 2. Ratio between infiltration times of the applied water volume against the water pouring number (WPN).

Regardless of the soil alteration induced, in fact, at the end of the experiment (i.e., for $WPN > 21$) such ratio was always higher under CT than NT (Figure 2). The results also showed that, at the end of the run, the geometric mean of the saturated hydraulic conductivity, K_s modeled by BEST-steady was always significantly higher under NT when the H or M heights were applied, while it was not significant when a negligible mechanical soil disturbance was induced (L height). Finally, in accordance with the theory and regardless of soil management, a strong negative correlation was found between K_s and the gravitational potential energy, E_p of the water used for the infiltration runs (i.e., E_p equal to 3380, 1715 and 100 $J m^{-2}$, respectively for HL, ML and LL), as K_s decreased as E_p increased.

Conclusions

The method applied confirmed to be able to provide useful information to study the soil hydraulic properties relevant for surface runoff and to simulate that process more realistically. The better understanding of the impact of soil management on hydraulic properties will be useful to improve the sustainable management of hilly cropping systems.

References

- Bagarello et al. 2014. Soil hydraulic properties determined by infiltration experiments and different heights of water pouring. *Geoderma*, 213: 492–501.
- Bagarello et al. 2023. Comparing two methods to perform a beerkan infiltration run in a loam soil at different dates, *J. Hydrol.*, 617: 129095.
- Castellini et al. 2021. Improved Beerkan run methodology to assess water impact effects on infiltration and hydraulic properties of a loam soil under conventional- and no-tillage. *Soil Sci. Soc. Am. J.*, 85: 235–248.

Acknowledgments

This contribution is an activity of the CAMA project: PRIMA Foundation, call 2019-Section 1–GA n.1912 “Research-based participatory approaches for adopting Conservation Agriculture in the Mediterranean Area – CAMA”.

A New Approach for Developing Sustainable and Health-Promoting Durum Wheat *Composite Cross Populations*

Paolo Guarnaccia¹, Silvia Zingale¹, Umberto Anastasi¹, Giuseppe Indovino¹, Alfio Spina², Giovanni Dinelli³, Sara Bosi³, Francesca Truzzi³, Brunella Trucchi⁴, Stefano Benedettelli⁴

¹ Di3A, Univ. Catania, IT, paolo.guarnaccia@unict.it; silvia.zingale@unict.it; umberto.anastasi@unict.it; giuseppe.indovino@studium.unict.it

² CREA-CI, Acireale, IT, alfio.spina@crea.gov.it

³ DISTAL, Univ. Bologna, IT, giovanni.dinelli@unibo.it; sara.bosi@unibo.it; francesca.truzzi3@unibo.it

⁴ DAGRI, Univ. Firenze, IT, stefano.benedettelli@unifi.it; brunella.trucchi@unifi.it

Introduction

A transition from intensive to low-input farming, including organic one, is recognized to improve the sustainability of food systems. Especially, cereals play a key role in human nutrition but seriously threaten biodiversity and ecosystem functions, by being grown under intensive cropping systems, which usually need huge amounts of fertilisers, agrochemicals, and fuel (Zingale et al., 2022). The organic cereal sector is experiencing several challenges, such as the lack of varieties specifically adapted to low-input and organic farming, and the maintenance of premium prices compared with the conventional market (Migliorini et al., 2016). In this framework, combining sustainable agronomic management with the breeding of specific cultivars for organic farming is expected to provide multiple advantages, such as to cope abiotic (drought and high temperature) and biotic (weeds, pests, and diseases) threats, efficient use of native resources, especially nitrogen, environmental adaptability, yield stability and nutritional and health quality of the grain (Costanzo and Bärberi 2014). In this regard, wheat landraces and old varieties represent a source of novel alleles useful in a new approach to breeding activity to define innovative plant ideotypes (Dinelli et al., 2013). Evolutionary Plant Breeding (EPB) programs can exploit this genetic material to create new diversified populations, obtained by mixing or inter-crossing several lines, previously selected by one or more traits of interest. This research, funded by EcorNaturaSi S.p.a., presents the methodology aspects and the first results of an EPB research project, coordinated by the Universities of Catania, Firenze, and Bologna, aimed at developing different durum wheat regional *Composite Cross Populations* (CCPs) for pasta production.

Materials and Methods

Twenty-two different Parental Populations (PPs) of durum wheat were selected out of a large number of Italian landraces and old varieties provided by the Universities of Firenze within the ‘Semente Partecipata’ EU Life project. Key criteria for the selection included adaptability to local conditions and organic agronomic management, and high levels of health-promoting compounds, including polyphenols and flavonoids, with consequent increased antioxidant activity. The selected PPs were then inter-crossed according to a factorial crossing scheme to obtain 431 cross combinations, reproduced during the 2015-16 years up to the F3 generation. In 2018-19, 288 of these accessions were grown in four different Italian regions (Sicily, Apulia, Tuscany, and Veneto) following an incomplete block experimental design (augmented design) under organic farming. For all the accessions, the following morpho-agronomic traits were assessed: plant height and spike weight and length, grain yield, and yield components (number of spikes per plant, number of spikelets per spike, number and weight of kernels per spike) and grain quality (specific weight, starchy, black point and shrunken of kernels). Data were processed along with the results on the health-promoting properties of the PPs. In addition to the analysis of variance, which was performed considering the sources of variation, such as environment (E), genotypes (G), and ExG interaction, the Principal Component Analysis (PCA) was applied to represent all the analyzed variables. This allowed us to have a spatial representation of all genotypes for each environment. Based on the results, it was possible to identify for each location groups of accessions corresponding to the desired plant ideotype. Thus, the seeds of the accessions belonging to the same “cluster” were reunited, and 14 CCPs were developed. The latter were grown in the same four locations over the 2019-20, 2020-21, and 2021-22 growing seasons to

evaluate the effects of both G, E, and GxE interaction on their agronomic performances, and quality features (both technological and health-related ones). Three-way ANOVA and SDS tests for $p \leq 0,05$ were performed for such purpose.

Results

This comprehensive approach allowed the integration of both agronomical, technological, nutritional, and health-promoting characteristics in the breeding program of CCPs suitable for organic farming. Figure 1 shows the spatial distribution defined by the first two principal components (the first one defined by yield components, and the second by the morphological traits), which allowed the authors to develop the CCPs under study.

Figure 1. The 2D plot defined by the first two Principal Components (about 67% of the total variance) for the Tuscany environment is reported as an example.

Results from the multi-environmental trials confirmed the validity of the overall approach. Specifically, for agronomic traits, although yields were not fully expressed and stabilised yet, most of the CCPs evidenced optimal productive features, especially in terms of grain specific weight, number of spikelets per spike, number of kernels per spike, and thousand kernel weight. Moreover, a significant GxE interaction effect was found for most of the studied agronomic and quality characteristics. Interesting results were also found concerning the health-promoting properties of some of the CCPs, both in terms of reduced inflammatory effects of gluten and high content of bioactive compounds.

Conclusion

CCPs developed within this study offer greater potential for cultivating diversity and producing high-quality and sustainable durum wheat end products, although the complexity of the initial crossing phase. Analysis of pasta's technological and nutritional quality aspects from the investigated CCPs is ongoing.

Literature

- Costanzo A. and Bärberi P. 2014. Functional agrobiodiversity and agroecosystem services in sustainable wheat production. A review. *Agron. Sust. Dev.*, 34: 327-348.
- Dinelli G. et al. 2013. Agronomic, nutritional, and nutraceutical aspects of durum wheat (*Triticum durum* Desf.) cultivars under low input agricultural management. *Ital. J. Agron.*, 8: 85-93.
- Migliorini P. et al. 2016. Agronomic and quality characteristics of old, modern, and mixture wheat varieties and landraces for organic bread chain in diverse environments of northern Italy. *Eur. J. Agron.*, 79: 131-141.
- Zingale S. et al. 2022. A systematic literature review of Life Cycle Assessments in the durum wheat sector. *Sci. Total Environ.*, 844: 157230.

A Two-Step Evaluation of Permanent Legume Living Mulches for Organic and Conservative Vegetable Systems

Federico Leoni¹, Stefano Carlesi¹, Daniele Antichi², Christian Frascioni², Anna-Camilla Moonen¹

¹ Scuola Superiore Sant'Anna, Center of Plant Sciences, Group of Agroecology, Piazza Martiri della Libertà, 33, 56127, Pisa, Italy (Camilla.moonen@santannapisa.it)

² Center for Agro-Environmental Research "Enrico Avanzi", University of Pisa, via vecchia di Marina 6, 56122 San Piero a Grado, Pisa, Italy

Introduction

The adoption of a permanent living mulch of legumes (pLMs) can facilitate the application of conservation agriculture in organic vegetable systems (Antichi et al., 2019). The use of pLMs involves the establishment of a dense and stable sward of legumes alongside the main crop that can be transplanted with no or minimum (strip) tillage. LMs have shown an acceptable weed control effect in vegetable crops, an increase in nutrient availability and the preservation of soil structure, reducing the need for tillage and external inputs such as herbicides and fertilizers (Hartwig N. and Ammon H., 2002). One of the key factors determining the limited use pLMs at farm level is the selection of legume species or mixtures that can ensure a stable and effective living ground cover over the time, upon which a vegetable crop rotation can be established. Based on the results of a preliminary study aimed at the evaluation of the most important morphological traits of single perennial and self-seeding legume to be used as pLMs (Step 1; Leoni et al., 2020), the most promising legume species and ecotypes were implemented as pure crop and mixtures with a 3-year vegetable crop sequence (Step 2). The objective of the mixtures is to combine their unique traits in a complementary manner, ultimately enhancing the ecosystem services provided by pLMs throughout the entire crop rotation. The aim of this paper is to present the performance of the selected pLMs on the weed control and yield of the co-cultivated vegetable crops.

Materials and Methods

The preliminary screening of legumes for pLMs (Step 1) has been conducted in Leoni et al., 2020. Results from this 2-years experiment revealed that perennial and self-seeding legumes have specific and complementary morphological and phenological characteristics. Perennial legumes such as *Trifolium repens* (TR) and *Lotus corniculatus* (LC) have shown good weed control over the years but they have slow growth. On the other hand, self-seeding legumes such as *Trifolium subterraneum* (TS) and *Medicago polymorpha* (MP) have shown lower weed control capacity over the long term due to their growth cycle, but they ensure very rapid development during the early stages. Moreover, some ecotypes of MP have proven to be more suitable than commercial cultivar (e.g. cv Scimitar) due to their good self-seeding ability over the years, such as those from Talamone (MPt), Villa Salto (MPv) and Pitigliano (MPp). Based on the results obtained in the step 1, a second experiment was set-up from February 2022 and it is ongoing in a certified organic fields at Centre for Agri-Environmental Research Enrico Avanzi (CiRAA, Pisa). The trial involved the use of the most promising legumes from step1 including two perennial legumes (TR and LC) as permanent pLMs (Figure 1). Since the complementarity of the growth traits determined during the previous experiment, perennial legumes were tested as pure crop and in mixture with two annual self-seeding legumes, MP and TS, in order to have a dense and weed suppressive pLMs from early growing stages. The experimental design consisted in a randomized complete block design with three replications. A 3-year vegetable crop sequence has been established on the pLMs including broccoli (*Brassica oleracea* var. Italica) – eggplant (*Solanum melongena*) – fennel (*Foeniculum vulgare*). Plots with the vegetable crops cultivated according to the standard organic crop management, including tillage and organic fertilization (CNT1), and plots with only spontaneous vegetation (CNT2), were used as controls. PLMs were established

in plots in late winter, prior to the broccoli transplanting and maintained throughout the crop rotation. Before the transplanting, pLMs were mown at 10 cm height and strip tillage was performed.

Figure 15 Organic broccoli (cv Belstar) with pLMs of LC-TS (A) and standard organic broccoli CNT1 (B).

Results

As example of results on the effects of pLMs on the vegetable crops we report data on the marketable yield of broccoli (Figure 2). Without the use of external source of fertilisers and tillage the mixture composed LC-TS guaranteed the same marketable yield as in CNT1 (5.31 vs 4.78 fw t/ha). For the other pLMs under evaluation, the marketable yield was lower than in CNT1 and LC-TS and it was on average 2.91 t/ha. In the CNT2, where no fertilisers, tillage and pLMs were used, the marketable yield of broccoli was only 0.98 t/ha. In the control CNT1 weeds were mechanically controlled between rows and the dry biomass was indeed lower compared with the pLMs (0.56 dw g/m²). On the contrary CNT2 had the highest weed biomass (191,7 dw g/m²). In between, LC, TR, LC-TS and TR-MPv guaranteed an acceptable weed control (on average 18,34 dw g/m²). Within vegetable rows, LC-TS had the lower weed dry biomass (37,54 g/m²) but it was not different compared with CNT1 (105,8 g/m²). Instead, TR-MP and CNT2 had the highest weed dry biomass (respectively 167,04 and 177,29 g/m²). Results on an economic assessment will be provided.

Conclusions

Results from this study suggest that combine the advantages of conservation agriculture with organic agriculture can be achieved by the application of agroecological principles such as the use of pLMs. The selection of suitable pLMs for these systems is crucial, and the use of legume mixtures based on a functional approach that seeks to combine complementary traits of legume species, seems to be a promising innovation. The selection of vegetable species well-adapted to these systems and precision mechanization for pLMs' management are challenges for the near future.

Literature

- Antichi D. et al. 2019. Agronomic Performances of Organic Field Vegetables Managed with Conservation Agriculture Techniques: A Study from Central Italy. *Agronomy*, 9(12): 810.
- Hartwig N. and Ammon H. 2002. Cover crops and living mulches. *Weed Sci.*, 50(6): 688-699.
- Leoni F. et al. 2020. Legume Ecotypes and Commercial Cultivars Differ in Performance and Potential Suitability for Use as Permanent Living Mulch in Mediterranean Vegetable Systems. *Agronomy*, 10(11): 183.

Figure 16 - Marketable yield of broccoli grown with pLMs of *T. repens* as pure corp (TR) and in mix with *M. polymorpha* ecot. Talamone (TR-MPv), ecot. Villa Salto (TR-MPp), ecot. Pitigliano (TR-MPp), commercial cv Scimitar (TR-MP), *T. subterraneum* (TR-TS) and *L. corniculatus* as pure corp (LC) and in mix with *T. subterraneum* (LC-TS). CNT1 (standard crop management without pLMs) and CNT2 (spontaneous vegetation). Different letters (a-d) indicate significant differences at p<0.05 following Sidak post-hoc test

POSTERS

Optimizing Camelina Sowing Date and Cultivar Choice to Maximize Vitamin E Content

Barbara Alberghini, Federica Zanetti, Angela Vecchi, Federico Ferioli, Andrea Monti

DISTAL, Alma Mater Studiorum, Univ. Bologna, barbara.alberghini3@unibo.it, federica.zanetti5@unibo.it, angela.vecchi@unibo.it, federico.ferioli@unibo.it, a.monti@unibo.it

Introduction

Camelina (*Camelina sativa* (L.) Crantz) is an oilseed crop which has proved to be adaptable to less profitable lands and dry areas (Murphy, 2016). Moreover, camelina oil has a unique fatty acid composition, which is known to be influenced by both genetic and environmental factors (Zanetti et al., 2017, Righini et al., 2019). Furthermore, camelina possesses a tocopherol content in the range of 675-1565 mg kg⁻¹ oil, which confers its oil a high oxidative stability (Hrastar et al., 2012, Günç Ergönül and Aksoylyu Özbek 2018). Despite this, the influence of cultivar and growing conditions on tocopherols in camelina has not been deeply investigated yet. To this end, this study considered different camelina cultivars sown both in autumn and in spring in the years 2020-2022 in Northern Italy.

Materials and Methods

Research was conducted at the experimental farm of the University of Bologna in Cadriano (44° 33' N, 11° 23'E, 32 m a.s.l.), between 2020 and 2022. The soil of the trials was a silty-clay-loam (27% sand, -27% clay, 46% silt). Eight camelina cultivars were sown in autumn (SD1) in 2020 and in 2021, while they were grown in spring (SD2) in 2020 and in 2022. Autumn sowing was performed within the last ten days of October, while harvesting took place in the first ten days of June. As regards spring cycle, trials were sown in the first week of March and harvested in the second half of June. Main dates, GDD, and meteorological data of the trials are reported in Table 1.

Year	SD	Sowing date	Harvesting day	GDD	Tmin	Tmean	Tmax	Precipitation (mm)
2019-2020	SD2	05/03/2020	19/06/2020	1137	7.86	14.73	21.3	154.2
2020-2021	SD1	22/10/2020	10/06/2021	1349	4.41	9.50	14.9	296.4
2021-2022	SD1	21/10/2021	09/06/2022	1301	4.45	9.63	15.1	352.2
2021-2022	SD2	02/03/2022	22/06/2022	1266	8.59	15.3	21.9	172

Table 10. Sowing and harvest dates, cycle length and main meteorological data of the trials. *Base temperature for calculation: 4 °C.

The cultivars considered were Midas (provided by Agriculture and Agri-food Canada, Saskatoon, Canada), Cypress and 789-02 (by Smart Earth Camelina, Saskatoon, Canada), Omega (supplied by Poznan University of Life Sciences, Poznan, Poland), NS Zlatka (supplied by Institute of Field and Vegetable Crops, Novi Sad, Serbia), and CCE43 (by Camelina Company España, Madrid, Spain). The experimental design was a completely randomized block with four replicates. Seeding rate was 500 seeds m⁻², plot size was 10.5 m², and all the trials were rainfed. Camelina was harvested at full maturity. Seed samples were collected from each plot to determine seed dry matter, thousand kernel weight (TKW), and tocopherol content and composition (i.e., total tocopherols, α -tocopherol, and γ -tocopherol).

Results

Two-way ANOVA was run, considering “sowing date” and “cultivar” as factors. All variables were found significant ($P \leq 0.05$) for factor cultivar, while sowing date influenced all parameters except α -tocopherol. Moreover, interaction “sowing date x cultivar” was significant for α -tocopherol. Regarding tocopherols, γ -tocopherol accounted for 96.5% of total content on average. Thus, variations in γ -tocopherol were in line with those observed for total tocopherols.

Seed yield and TKW were higher in SD1 (2.10 Mg ha⁻¹ and 1.20 g, respectively) than in SD2 (1.63 Mg ha⁻¹ and 1.13 g, respectively), as expected from previous research (Zubr, 1997; Righini et al., 2019). On the contrary, total tocopherols and γ -tocopherol were increased in SD2 (729.3 mg kg⁻¹ oil and 704.5 mg kg⁻¹ oil, respectively) than in SD1 (682.8 mg kg⁻¹ oil and 658.1 mg kg⁻¹ oil, respectively).

The cultivars producing the highest seed yield were Cypress (2.14 Mg ha⁻¹) Omega (1.99 Mg ha⁻¹), NS Zlatka (1.95 Mg ha⁻¹), and Midas (1.85 Mg ha⁻¹) while the less productive one were 789-02 (1.67 Mg ha⁻¹) and CCE43 (1.53 Mg ha⁻¹). Cypress was also the cultivar with the highest seed weight (1.54 g),

while NS Zlatka, CCE43 and Midas had the lowest TKW (1.08 g, 1.05 g, and 1.04 g, respectively). The cultivar with the highest content of both total tocopherols and γ -tocopherol was NS Zlatka (762.9 mg kg⁻¹ oil and 739.1 mg kg⁻¹ oil, respectively), while cultivar 789-02 showed the lowest values (641.1 mg kg⁻¹ oil and 625.3 mg kg⁻¹ oil) (Figure 1). α -tocopherol was higher in SD2 than in SD1 in all cultivars, with the exception of CCE43, that had an α -tocopherol decrease up to 34.7% from SD1 to SD2.

The above-described contrasting trend observed by agronomic results compared with tocopherols content was confirmed via a correlation study. The Pearson parametric correlation test showed significant ($P \leq 0.05$) negative correlations between total tocopherols and seed yield ($r = -0.26$), and between total tocopherols and TKW ($r = -0.49$). Likewise, significant ($P \leq 0.05$) negative correlations were also observed between γ -tocopherol and seed yield ($r = -0.23$), and between γ -tocopherol and TKW ($r = -0.50$) (Table 2).

Conclusions

Camelina agronomic traits confirmed to be boosted by autumn sowing. On the other hand, spring sowing granted the highest tocopherol content. Cypress proved to be the best cultivar when considering the main agronomic traits. NS Zlatka had the highest tocopherol content, together with a high seed yield, thus this cultivar should be targeted as a spring crop to produce camelina with and improved vitamin E content for food, feed, and industrial uses.

Aknowledgements

The present research was funded by the 4CE-MED project that has received funding from the PRIMA Foundation supported by European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement GA 1911.

Literature

- Hrastar R. et al. 2012. In situ quality evaluation of *Camelina sativa* landrace. Eur. J. Lipid Sci. Technol., 114: 343–351.
- Günç Ergönül P. and Aksoylu Özbek Z. 2018. Identification of bioactive compounds and total phenol contents of cold pressed oils from safflower and camelina seeds. J. Food Meas. Charact., 12: 2313–2323.
- Murphy E.J. 2016. Camelina (*Camelina sativa*), in: Industrial Oil Crops. Elsevier, pp. 207–230.
- Righini D. et al. 2019. Shifting sowing of camelina from spring to autumn enhances the oil quality for bio-based applications in response to temperature and seed carbon stock. Ind. Crops Prod., 137: 66–73.
- Zanetti F. et al. 2017. Agronomic performance and seed quality attributes of Camelina (*Camelina sativa* L. crantz) in multi-environment trials across Europe and Canada. Ind. Crops Prod., 107: 602–608.
- Zubr J. 1997. Oil-seed crop: *Camelina sativa*. Ind. Crops Prod., 6: 113–119.

Figure 17. Effect of cultivar on tocopherol content. Different letters: significant different values ($P \leq 0.05$). Vertical bars: standard error.

	Total tocopherols	α -tocopherol	γ -tocopherol
Seed yield	-0.26 *	-0.19 ns	-0.23 *
TKW	-0.49 **	-0.02 ns	-0.50 **

Table 11. Pearson correlation coefficient and significance level among agronomic traits and tocopherol content and composition of the 8 tested cultivars. *, ** Significant at the 0.05, 0.01 probability levels, respectively; ns = not significant.

Coupling IoT Technologies, Blockchain and Modelling to Enhance Crop Production and Farmers' Financial Resilience Under Extreme Climatic Events: the RESTORATION Project

Anna Rita Balingit¹, Giovanni Argenti¹, Marco Moriondo², Giacomo Trombi¹, Roberto Ferrise¹, Sergi Costafreda-Aumedes², Riccardo Rossi¹, Gloria Padovan¹, Niccolò Bartoloni¹, Sara Landini³, Gianluca De Donno³, Virginia Fani⁴, Bianca Bindi⁵, Romeo Bandinelli⁴, Camilla Dibari¹

¹ DAGRI, Univ. Firenze, IT, @unifi.it,

² CNR, Firenze, IT, @cnr.it,

³ DSG, Univ. Firenze, IT, @unifi.it,

⁴ DIEF, Univ. Firenze, IT, @unifi.it,

⁵ DSI, Unimarconi, IT, @unimarconi.com

Introduction

The agricultural sector, being highly vulnerable to climatic events and market fluctuations, is particularly susceptible to damage due to extreme weather events (e.g. hailstorms, droughts, strong winds, floods, late frosts, etc.). Moreover, the present modification, in terms of intensity and frequency, of catastrophic climatic risks makes public intervention excessively burdensome for the state and the intervention of insurers, which in turn may destabilise the balance sheets of insurance companies (Landini, 2021). In response to these needs, the creation of an insurance system is an important financial tool for farmers.

In this context, innovative and integrated technologies can provide farmers with accurate, real-time information on crop growth and environmental conditions and an estimate of the current trends in crop development during the season. The RESTORATION project aims to develop an innovative insurance toolbox for farmers, by integrating technologies of precision agriculture, namely blockchain and the Internet of Things (IoT) so as to provide farmers with the best adaptation practices, as well as to enable insurance companies to verify their implementation, and establish economic incentives for adopting risk mitigation measures.

Materials and Methods

The crops of this study are vines, olives, wheat and forage grasslands cultivated in Tuscany Region. For these, climatic threshold values hampering their cultivation, and beyond which crop damage may occur, have been analysed from a literature review. To investigate the expected changes in the behaviour of crops development with respect to the present, the following crop simulation models (already calibrated in Tuscany region) are employed, namely UNIFI. GrapeML (Leolini et al., 2018), OliveModel (Moriondo et al., 2019), SSM-wheat (Soltani et al., 2013) and VISTOCK Model (Bellini et al., 2023) for vineyard, olive tree, wheat and grasslands, respectively. These will allow to determine the quantity of yield variation and the probability of occurrence under different projected climatic scenarios of the near-future. To this, high-resolution Regional Climate Models (RCMs) have been downloaded and will be used for crop simulation under two future scenarios (2031-2050 and 2051-2070). These RCMs entail daily maximum and minimum temperature and precipitation at a spatial resolution of 0.11° (about 12.5 km) with respect to the present (baseline from 1971 to 2005). For future projections two Representative Concentration Pathway (RCP) scenarios are considered for impact analysis, namely, RCP 2.6 and RCP 4.5.

The integration of crop models with IoT (e.g. Radio-Frequency Identification, Near-Field Communication) and blockchain technologies to automatically acquire data from the field, minimising human errors in data entry, will be tested in a pilot vineyard farm based in the Chianti Region (6.8 ha; 43°22'59.3"N 11°29'14.9"E, WGS84). To this, 10 probes for monitoring the soil moisture at 3 different depths, 4 rain

gauges and 2 air-temperature and humidity sensors were in-site installed. Recurrent measures on ~ 130 selected plants will be performed throughout the 2023 (e.g. trunk, canopy size LAI, fPAR and NDVI). For understanding the strategies to preserve profits through insurance contracts and which adaptation strategies are implemented by stakeholders, a semi-structured questionnaire was developed and shared among a regional network of farmers. Additionally, general conditions of insurance contracts, both at national and at international level, will be collected thanks to the cooperation with AIDA (Association Internationale de Droit des Assurances). The legal investigation will also consider: the PAC, the new Green Deal instances, the new regulation of AgriCat fund in Italy, the importance of insurance policy in creditworthiness assessment by Banks according to Basilea agreements.

Results

The literature review indicated water availability, in terms of Fraction of Transpirable Soil Water (FTSW) in relation with rainy days, a fundamental player in estimating yield reduction for olive tree (Moriondo et al., 2019). For cereals, like bread wheat, the grain filling stage is sensitive to high temperatures, e.g. by setting a threshold based on the number of days when maximum temperatures exceed 25 °C (HSD, Heat Stress Days), by determining variations in crop production (Gouache et al., 2012). As expected results, probability of occurrence of extreme climatic events during specific phenological phases of the crops in the future as well the impacts on yield and production will be provided by modelling. Moreover, a list of best adaptation measures will be provided to be promoted by insurance companies. Furthermore, the effectiveness and applicability of innovative means (e.g. IoT and blockchain technologies) to monitor their actual implementation will be tested and evaluated. Finally, new insurance contracts and business models will be developed for innovative smart contracts aimed at simplifying bureaucracy under a changing climate scenario and extreme and uneven events risks.

Conclusions

The RESTORATION project applies interdisciplinary and innovative approaches to reshape relationships between risks and agricultural activities with the aim of reducing the impact of potential risks due to climatic extreme events. These will be translated into new insurance contracts and insurance policies becoming a reference for prevention in the agricultural sector.

Acknowledgements

The authors would like to gratefully the RESTORATION “InsuRancEs SoluTiOns to enhance crop production Resilience to extreme climATic events by means of bLOckchaiN and IoT technologies” DM 737, CUP B55F21007810001, project funded by the European Europe - NextGenerationEU programme.

Literature

- Bellini E. et al. 2023. VISTOCK: A simplified model for simulating grassland systems. *Eur. J. Agron.*, 142: 126647.
- Gouache D. et al. 2012. Evaluating agronomic adaptation options to increasing heat stress under climate change during wheat grain filling in France. *Eur. J. Agron.*, 39: 62–70.
- Landini S. 2021. Credit in Agriculture: In the Perspective of Banking Law, Financial Market Law and Insurance Law. *European Business Law Review*, 4: 801-816.
- Leolini L. et al. 2018. A model library to simulate grapevine growth and development: software implementation, sensitivity analysis and field level application. *Eur. J. Agron.*, 99: 92–105.
- Moriondo M. et al. 2015. Modelling olive trees and grapevines in a changing climate. *Environ. Model. Soft.*, 72: 387–401.
- Moriondo M. et al., 2019. A simple model simulating development and growth of an olive grove. *Eur. J. Agron.*, 105: 129-145.
- Soltani A. et al., 2013. SSM-wheat: A simulation model for wheat development, growth and yield. *Int. J. Plant Prod.*, 7: 711–740.

Abiotic Stress and Durum Wheat: Morpho-Physiological Aspects in the Mediterranean Environment

Silvia Cantalamessa¹, Afsaneh Nematpour², Giancarlo Pagnani^{2*}, Fabio Stagnari², Michele Pisante²

¹ Dep. Agronomy, Food, Natural Resources, Animals and Environment, Univ. Padova, IT

² Dep. Bioscience and Technologies for Food, Agriculture and Environment, Univ. Teramo, IT, *corresponding author, gpagnani@unite.it

Introduction

As a result of increases in aerosols, air pollutants, and population density, obscuration or shading (decrease in global radiation, i.e., the sum of direct solar radiation and diffuse radiation scattered from the atmosphere) has become a major challenge for crop production in many areas of the world (Mu et al., 2010). Light intensity is one of the environmental factors that most affect crop growth and yield. However, there is growing concern about the current increase in cloud cover, rain, and fog; in addition, the net radiation reaching the earth's surface is decreasing (Díaz-Torres et al., 2017). Rapid economic growth and accelerated urbanization have led to significant increases in emissions of air pollutants, including automobile and industrial exhaust. Incident solar radiation was reduced by 10 to 90% (Dong B. et al., 2019). A 10% reduction in radiation can cause a yield reduction of more than 10% (Dong B. et al., 2019). Therefore, there is an increasing need for studies on changes in morphological traits and grain yields, as well as response strategies of winter wheat under shade stress, which could provide important insights for breeding wheat with high shade tolerance. The objective of this study was to evaluate the influence of variation in light intensity and nitrogen availability on the morpho-physiological response of durum wheat in a Mediterranean environment.

Materials and Methods

The experimental activity was carried out in 2016-2017 in the experimental field of the Department of Bioscience and Technologies for Food, Agriculture, and Environment, Research and Training Centre for Agronomy and Crop Production in Mosciano Sant'Angelo (42°42' N, 13°52'E, 101 m a.s.l.). The experimental area, characterized by a typical Mediterranean climate, has a loamy-clay soil texture (23% sand, 45% silt, 32% clay) with a very low natural content of nitrogen and organic matter. Following a randomized block experimental design with three replicates, two levels of light availability (100% and 20% - referred below L or S, respectively) and 3 levels of nitrogen availability (0 kg ha⁻¹ N, 100 kg ha⁻¹ N, 250 kg ha⁻¹ N) were compared. Elemental units were 1.5 x 3 m in size. Nitrogen was applied as urea in a single application at the phenological stage of stem elongation, and the shading was applied in the flowering stage. Average plant height (cm) and ear length (cm) were measured on 40 plants in each treatment at harvest. Some physiological traits were estimated using SPAD (502 plus portable chlorophyll meter; Konica Minolta, Inc, Tokyo, Japan) and Field Spec (Hand Held 2 Pro Portable Field Spec Spectroradiometer; ADS Inc, Boulder, CO, USA). Multiple measurements of SPAD to estimate chlorophyll concentration were made on 7 sampling dates between stages (DC53) and (DC75). Leaf reflectance was measured on the same sampling dates. Normalized difference vegetation index (NDVI) was calculated as follows: $NDVI = \frac{\rho_{NIR-} - \rho_{NIR+}}{\rho_{NIR-} + \rho_{NIR+}}$. Data on morpho-physiological aspects were subjected to analysis of variance (two-way analysis ANOVA). Means with statistically significant differences were compared using Fisher's LSD test (Least Significant Difference).

Results

The unfertilized control showed a significant decrease in SPAD value compared to the shaded theses. At higher doses of nitrogen (100% light / 20% light 100 kg ha⁻¹ N), a significant increase in SPAD value was observed under conditions of maximum light. In general, SPAD values are higher in the shaded theses (Fig. 1), confirming previous work (Dong B. et al., 2019). The NDVI values obtained followed the same trend

as the response of the different experimental types with respect to SPAD, both of which are determined by the chlorophyll content in the leaves, which is influenced by the nutritional status of the plant. There were no significant differences ($p \leq 0.05$) between the shaded condition, which, however, had significantly higher values than the 0 kg h⁻¹ N 100% light condition (Fig. 2).

Figure 1. SPAD average seasonal values (DC53 - DC75). Data are averages of $n=3$ independent replicates. Different letters indicate statistically different treatments for $p \leq 0.05$ (Fisher LSD).

Figure 2. NDVI average seasonal values (DC53 - DC75). Data are averages of $n=3$ independent replicates. Different letters indicate statistically different treatments for $p \leq 0.05$ (Fisher LSD).

The average length of the ears at harvest shows higher values for the plants exposed to the maximum light availability (Tab. 1). For plant height, we find significant differences for maximum light conditions and for higher nitrogen availability in shaded plants. In the absence of shading, the dose of 100 kg ha⁻¹ N resulted in the highest values (Tab. 1).

Table 1: Length values of ears (cm) and durum wheat plants (cm) in different treatments compared (average values of 1 m² plants, for 3 replicates for each treatment). Different letters indicate statistically different treatments at $p \leq 0.05$ (Fisher LSD).

Treatment	Stem length (cm)	Ear length (cm)
S - 0 kg ha ⁻¹ N	59 c	5 b
S - 100 kg ha ⁻¹ N	58 c	5.5 ab
S - 250 kg ha ⁻¹ N	63 b	5 b
L - 0 kg ha ⁻¹ N	63 b	6 a
L - 100 kg ha ⁻¹ N	67 a	6 a
L - 250 kg ha ⁻¹ N	62 bc	5.5 a

Conclusions

The results of the present study show a significant effect of light limitation on durum wheat physiological response and morphology, as well as on nitrogen availability. Increased SPAD and NDVI values were favored by light limitation due to increased chlorophyll concentrations. Nitrogen availability had incremental responses in important physiological and morphological parameters (plant height, number of spikelets, and number of grains). These results suggest that physiological and morphological traits and yield components can provide useful information for selecting shade-tolerant cultivars to maximize yield in shade-prone areas in the Mediterranean region.

Literature

- Díaz-Torres J. et al. 2017. Assessment of the modulation effect of rainfall on solar radiation availability at the Earth's surface. *Meteorol. Appl.*, 24: 180-190.
- Dong B. et al. 2019. Effects of shading stress on grain number, yield, and photosynthesis during early reproductive growth in wheat. *Crop Sci.*, 59: 363-378.
- Mu H. et al. 2010. Long-term low radiation decreases leaf photosynthesis, photochemical efficiency and grain yield in winter wheat. *J. Agron. Crop Sci.*, 196: 38-47.

The Detection of Salt-Tolerant Genotypes to Reduce Yield Losses and Pressure on Fresh-Water Reserves: A Quick, Simple, and Affordable Bioassay

Linda Carrino, Donato Visconti, Daniele Todisco, Nunzio Fiorentino, Massimo Fagnano

Dep. Agricultural Sciences, Univ. Naples “Federico II”, IT, linda.carrino@unina.it

Introduction

Global climate change has led to water scarcity in most world regions. In arid and semi-arid regions, relying on brackish water for irrigation is the only choice to ensure an appropriate level of crop yields due to a limited supply of good-quality irrigation water (Feng et al., 2019). However, seed germination, seedlings development, root elongation, and other early phases of plant establishment are the most impacted by saline stress (Wang et al., 2019; Arif et al., 2019). The impact of salt stress on crop growth is studied using a variety of approaches, including pot trials, hydroponics, and agar plates (Nakamura et al., 2021). Here, a quick, simple, and affordable method is proposed for examining plant physiological characteristics affected by salt stress by using castor bean (*Ricinus communis* L.), a crop with a salinity threshold of 7.1 dS m^{-1} (Zhou et al., 2010), well known for its capacity to grow on marginal lands (Carrino et al., 2020). Early stages of castor beans such as germination (Severino et al., 2013), seedling establishment (Pinheiro et al., 2008), and root growth (Janmohammadi et al., 2012) are inhibited by salt stress, with a large intraspecific variability. Therefore, this study aimed to identify genotypes of *Ricinus communis* L. with a high germination rate and physiological traits suitable for salt tolerance by a bioassay that can be performed on any economically important crops.

Materials and Methods

Figure 18. Experimental set-up (A) and comparison at 0, 4 and 8 dS m^{-1} of the C1012 cultivar (B).

Experimental units consisted of plastic containers originally designed as sugared almonds' boxes (30 x 40 x 240 mm). Four *Ricinus communis* L. cultivars (TUNI 1, TUNI 4, C1012, and C1028) were grown on a silica sand substrate and irrigated every two days, starting from sowing, with saline water ($0, 4, 8 \text{ dS m}^{-1}$). Ten seeds for each tested genotype were sown individually in each container and performed in triplicates for each saline level (total: 360 seeds). The standing position and water reservoir were provided by a plastic tray. The trays were placed in a growth chamber (25°C , 12/12 d/n, 40% of humidity) and moved every two days to avoid position bias. Germination and emergence were counted every day.

Plants were harvested at day 15, and the length of the main root, shoot, and fresh weight were measured (Fig.1B). Then, plants were oven-dried at 50°C until constant weight. The saline tolerance of plants was assessed by different indices associated with the number of germinated seeds and the measurements done at the end of the monitoring period on roots and stems (Table 1).

Results

Some of the main results are presented in Fig.2. C1012 and C1028 showed a decrease of SG and of the derived indices (RSG and GP) at 4 dS m^{-1} compared to the control, while TUNI 1 and TUNI 4 showed no differences. An increasing tendency of SG, RSG and GP was recorded for TUNI 1 at 4 dS m^{-1} while all cultivars showed a decrease of these germination parameters at 8 dS m^{-1} . For all

the tested cultivars, MRL (and SL) decreased as saline EC of irrigation water increased (Fig.2). A significant reduction of MRL was recorded for all the tested cultivars at 4 dS m⁻¹ compared to the control, while no significant reduction was recorded for TUNI 1. On the contrary, all cultivars showed a significant reduction of MRL (and SL) at 8 dS m⁻¹ compared to the control.

Conclusions

Limited access to freshwater resources, especially in arid and semi-arid world regions, has pushed the use of saline water for agricultural purposes. Therefore, identifying salt-tolerant crops is an essential task in the climate change era. Here, the presented low-cost methodology to identify salt tolerant genotypes, showed that, according to roots, stem, germination traits and derived indices, TUNI 1 and TUN4 had the best growth on sand irrigated with 4 dS m⁻¹ and 8 dS m⁻¹, respectively. Besides, comparing C1028 and C1012, the former showed a higher tolerance at the maximum EC tested related to the latter. The bioassay can easily be used also for other stress investigations.

Figure 2. Main root length (MRL), and number of germinations (SG) mean value \pm SE of the four cultivars according to saline water level. Mean values with the same letter do not differ according to the LSD test $P < 0.001$. S0 is the saline

Literature

Arif M. et al. 2019. Salinity Stress Alters Root Morphology and Root Hair. *Plants*, 8(7): 192.

Carrino L. et al. 2020. Phytoremediation and biofuel production with castor bean : a win-win strategy. *Agronomy*, 10: 1690.

Feng, G. et al. 2019. Evaluating the sustainable use of saline water irrigation on soil water-salt content and grain yield under subsurface drainage condition. *Sustainability*, 11: 6431.

Janmohammadi M. et al. 2012. Influence of NaCl treatments on growth and biochemical parameters of castor bean (*Ricinus communis* L.). *Acta Agr. Slov.*, 99(1): 31–40.

Nakamura C. et al. 2021. High sensitivity of roots to salt stress as revealed by novel tip bioassay in wheat seedlings. *Biotechnol. Biotechnol. Equip.*, 35(1): 246–254.

Pinheiro H.A. et al. 2008. Leaf gas exchange, chloroplastic pigments and dry matter accumulation in castor bean (*Ricinus communis* L.) seedlings subjected to salt stress conditions. *Ind. Crop. Prod.*, 27(3): 385–392.

Severino L. & Auld D. 2013. A framework for the study of the growth and development of castor plant. *Ind. Crop. Prod.*, 46: 25–38.

Wang Y. et al. 2019. Physiological adaptive strategies of oil seed crop *Ricinus communis* early seedlings (Cotyledon vs. True leaf) under salt and alkali stresses: From the growth, photosynthesis and chlorophyll fluorescence. *Front. Plant Sci.*, 9(1): 1–13.

Zhou G. et al. 2010. Determining salinity threshold level for Castor bean emergence and stand establishment. *Crop Sci.*, 50(5): 2030–2036.

Abbreviation	Index	Formula
SG	Seed germination	N° of germinated seeds
RSG	Relative Seed Germination	(SGs/SGc) x 100
GP	Germination Percentage	(SG/ tot. n° of seeds) x 100
GI	Germination index	(Gs*RLs/Gc*RLc) x 100
E	Emergence	N° of seedlings
EP	Emergence Percentage	(E/ tot. n° of seeds) x 100
RE	Relative EP	(EPs / EPc) x 100
MRL	Main Root Length	Main root length (cm)
RMF	Root Mass Fraction	(Root d.w./ plant d.w) x 100
SL	Stem Length	Stem length (cm)
SMF	Stem mass fraction	(Stem d.w. / plant d.w) x 100
SSI	Salt Susceptibility Index	(1-ys/yp)/(1-Ys-Yp)
STI	Salt Tolerance Index	(yp x ys)/(Yp) ²

Temporal Changes in Saturated Hydraulic Conductivity under Minimum- and No-tillage Soil Management

Mirko Castellini¹, Simone Di Prima²

¹ CREA-AA, Bari, IT, mirko.castellini@crea.gov.it

² SAFE, Univ. Basilicata, IT, simone.diprima@unibas.it

Introduction

The knowledge of the main physical and hydraulic properties of the soil is important for modelling the hydrological processes of agricultural systems. Among the soil properties of particular interest, the saturated hydraulic conductivity of the soil, K_s represents a key parameter, because it accounts for the soil ability to transmit water when it is full saturated. Also, since K_s is an indicator of the structural characteristics of the porous medium, thus accounts for the effects of the spatial arrangement of soil particles and soil porosity, it can potentially be used to evaluate optimal or non-optimal soil conditions for crop growth (Keller et al., 2012). However, modeling of agricultural systems may require several physical and hydraulic measurements of the soil, spread out over the entire crop cycle. Stewart and Abou Najm (2018) proposed a new model for K_s determination. It consists of thirteen different calculation approaches that differ by the way they constrained some soil parameters (i.e., macroscopic capillary length and water contents), on the use of transient or steady-state (SS) infiltration data and the fitting methods (CI, Cl, DL) applied to transient data. The objectives of the work were to test the new model under agronomic field conditions and compare the K_s estimates obtained with the different calculation approaches with a steady-state method (SSBI method) used as a reference, to study the impact of soil management (i.e., minimum tillage and no-tillage of the soil, MT and NT respectively) on K_s and evaluate the seasonal variability of K_s under MT and NT.

Materials and Methods

The study was carried out in the 2015-2016 crop season at the CREA-AA experimental farm in Foggia in a long-term experiment, started in 2002, on a durum wheat monoculture, aimed at comparing the long-term impact of MT and NT on a clay soil. The agronomic trial was sampled in five dates between November (post tillage) and June (harvest) to study the temporal variability of K_s during the entire crop cycle. For each date and soil management, 5-8 Beerkan infiltrations were carried out to obtain the cumulative infiltration curve. Beerkan tests were performed using a steel ring with a sharp edge and diameter of 8.5 cm, inserted superficially into the soil (1 cm), using 15 volumes of water of 60 ml for each experiment. Volumetric water content at the time of measurements (θ_i), bulk density (BD) and water retention of the soil were also determined, as they are needed as input for the model. The different calculation approaches were compared applying the distribution-free overlapping method, DFOM (Pastore and Calcagni, 2019), and a threshold of 75% of the overlapping areas for pairs of probability density functions of K_s , was considered to properly discriminate among calculation approaches. The temporal variability of K_s under MT and NT was investigated by using the Tukey's Honestly Significant Difference test whereas, for a given sampling date, the statistical significance between MT and NT was evaluated according to a two-tailed t-test. A significance level of $\alpha = 0.05$ was always assumed.

Results

Regardless of the calculation approach used, the K_s values changed up to two orders of magnitude over the cropping season, with the highest values observed after tillage (Fig. 1). A2 failed to provide valid estimates and was discarded. With reference to the SSBI (A5) method, used as reference for comparison purposes, the results showed a general overestimation of K_s when the simplified/transient approaches were used (differences within a factor of 4-11), while showed negligible differences (about a factor of 1) when steady-state approaches were considered. DFOM applied for pairs revealed a satisfactory agreement based on the adopted criterion (overlapping areas $\geq 75\%$), because six calculation approaches showed a relatively higher percentage similarity in frequency distributions as follows: A4SS-A5 (96), A3CI-A3CL (81), A4CI-A4CL

(81), A3DL-A3SS (78), A4DL-A4SS or A4SS-A5 (>76) (Fig. 1). This suggests that the most data demanding criterion for K_s estimation, i.e., A1 (it also required soil water retention as input), was always different as compared to the other approaches and, regardless of the approach, i.e., A3 or A4, similarity in the K_s frequency distributions were detected when using CI and CL or DL and SS.

The criteria that proved to be usable for the temporal analysis (A1, A3SS, A4SS and A5 by Stewart and Abou Najm, 2018), showed an overall similar (although not identical) information on the temporal variability of K_s . Specifically, the selected approaches generally agreed on the second half of the season,

Figure 1. Empirical cumulative frequency distribution of K_s (MT+NT) obtained from different calculation criteria.

Figure 2. Box plots of K_s (mm/h) using the calculation criteria A5 (SSBI). Solid and dashed lines indicate significant and not significant differences, respectively, between two consecutive sampling dates.

showed to be a promising tool to investigate the spatio-temporal variability of K_s .

References

- Keller et al. 2012. Using field measurement of saturated soil hydraulic conductivity to detect low-yielding zones in three Swedish fields. *Soil Till. Res.* 2012, 124: 68–77.
- Pastore and Calcagni 2019. Measuring distribution similarities between samples: a distribution-free overlapping index. *Front. Psychol.*, 10: 1089.
- Stewart and Abou Najm 2018. A Comprehensive model for single ring infiltration I: initial water content and soil hydraulic properties. *Soil Sci. Soc. Am. J.*, 82: 548-557.

Acknowledgments

This contribution is an activity of the CAMA project: PRIMA Foundation, call 2019-Section 1–GA n.1912 “Research-based participatory approaches for adopting Conservation Agriculture in the Mediterranean Area – CAMA”.

because they showed a lack of K_s seasonal changes at least from early April to June under NT; conversely, MT system was, overall, more affected by temporal changes, and findings showed more evident temporal stability at the beginning of the season.

Soil management have affected soil physical and hydraulics properties of investigated soil, because θ_i was significantly higher under NT than MT in 4 out of 5 sampling dates; similarly, BD was significantly higher under NT in the same dates. With reference to SSBI, significant differences in K_s values were detected under MT and NT only in the November (i.e., $MT \gg NT$), while were not significant ($MT \approx NT$) in the other dates.

Conclusions

In June, NT was significantly wetter and more compact but no less conductive than MT. Also, only NT showed an increasing and significant correlation between K_s and modal pore diameter, suggesting a better-connected pores network (relatively smaller and better interconnected pores) of NT soil. The model multi-approach

Evaluating a world mini-collection of domesticated cowpea (*Vigna unguiculata* [L.] Walp.) for intercropping with cereals

Daniele Cavalli¹, Luciano Pecetti², Nicolò Franguelli², Tommaso Notario², Timothy J. Close², Paolo Annicchiarico²

¹ Council for Agricultural Research and Economics (CREA), Centre for Animal Production and Aquaculture, Lodi, Italy, daniele.cavalli@crea.gov.it, luciano.pecetti@crea.gov.it, nicolo.franguelli@crea.gov.it, tommaso.notario@crea.gov.it, paolo.annicchiarico@crea.gov.it

² Department of Botany and Plant Sciences, University of California, Riverside, Riverside, California, USA, timothy.close@ucr.edu

Introduction

Cowpea is a summer legume cultivated worldwide for grain and fodder production because it has high yield potential under drought conditions. Collections of germplasm variable in phenology and morpho-physiological traits are fundamental resources to identify genotypes adapted to new cultivation environments or management practices and to develop new breeding materials. Indeed, breeding programs had been done to improve cowpea yield ability, increase tolerance to diseases and adaptation to specific photoperiodic conditions (Singh, 2014).

In Northern Italy, cowpea could be cultivated as a forage crop associated to summer cereals, with the aim of increasing the protein content of the forage. Grain hybrids of sorghum (*Sorghum bicolor* [L.] Moench) are of particular interest because of drought tolerance, and a plant type that likely do not exhibit an excessive competition with the legume. Therefore, sorghum-cowpea intercropping for silage production could be a valuable source of forage under drought conditions occurring even in Northern Italy when the crop is sown late, after Italian ryegrass or winter cereals. The interest for cowpea-sorghum associations started about 70 years ago (Haussmann, 1953), but, despite many research efforts and positive results, their cultivation did not establish. The need of diversifying cropping systems in terms of cultivated species, the occurrence of frequent summer drought conditions, and the availability of new genetic resources of cowpea and sorghum, renewed the interest on both species. The objective of the present study was to evaluate a world collection of cowpea germplasm developed at the University of California (Riverside, CA) for yield ability in Northern Italy and other plant traits. Genotypes with high yield and contrasting plant type were identified for cultivation in intercropping with sorghum.

Materials and Methods

Two hundred twenty-two accessions of cowpea were selected from the UCR Minicore collection (Muñoz-Amatriaín et al., 2021), representing landraces and breeding material from Africa, Asia, Australia, Europe, and North and South America. Two additional accessions were from Central Italy (University of Perugia; prof. V. Negri) and two from Northern Italy (University of Pavia; prof. G. Rossi).

The field experiment was established in Lodi (45°19' N, 9°30' E, 81 m a.s.l.) in summer 2022, on a sandy loam soil with sub-acid reaction. The experiment was designed as an alpha-lattice with fifteen genotypes per incomplete block and two replicates. Plots (1.5 × 1.5 m, with four rows distant 37.5 cm) were planted on the 28th of June with 18 seeds m⁻². The crop was harvested by hand for biomass yield (estimated on two representative plants per plot) and grain yield and threshed using a seed thresher. Moisture content of stems and seeds was determined after drying to constant weight. During the growing season, accessions were characterised for the following traits (IBPGR, 1983): growth habit, growth pattern (determinate, indeterminate), twining tendency, leaf size, flowering date, stem length and plant height (at harvest), harvest date, weight of 1000 seeds. Accessions were further classified according to the following classes of plant ideotype: 1) erect ideotype, with an acute-erect or erect growth habit and a large (>0.7) plant height to stem length ratio; 2) climbing ideotype, with a growth habit different from acute-erect and erect, a climbing growth pattern and twining tendency; 3) other (not well defined) ideotypes. Prior selecting interesting

genotypes for intercropping, the fifty most yielding accessions that reached maturity before the 15th of October were chosen, excluding too late genotypes. Principal component analysis (PCA) was used to investigate patterns of morpho-physiological phenotypic variation among genotypes belonging to the three classes of plant ideotype.

Results

Most of the accessions (80%) reached maturity within the 19th of September and the 7th of November (the last harvest date), while the others did not flower at all. Grain yield ranged 0.17-4.54 t DM ha⁻¹ (on average 2.49) and was greater than 2.82 t DM ha⁻¹ (on average 3.28) for the fifty most yielding genotypes. The first two principal components (PC) used to summarize the data explained 46% of the variance. The PC1 was positively correlated with flowering date, plant vigour (leaf size, plant height, stem length and crop biomass) and the weight of seeds. The second PC was positively correlated with the harvest date and plant height, while it was negatively correlated with the growth pattern, stem length and grain yield. According to methodology proposed, only 16% of the fifty accessions belonged to clearly contrasting plant ideotypes, with four accessions classified as erect ideotype and four as climbing ideotype. The two classes were well discriminated by PCA, enabling to identify two accessions for future evaluation in intercropping. The selected accessions had similar phenology, total biomass and grain yield, but a different plant type: the A49 was erect (height/stem length = 0.8) with a determinate growth, while the A50 was climbing, spreading (height/stem length = 0.4) with indeterminate growth.

Figure 1. Results of principal component analysis. Accessions are shown in the first two principal components space and marked according to their plant ideotype.

Conclusions

The cowpea collection showed high variability for all measured traits. Genotypes with contrasting plant ideotypes were identified and two with interesting yield will be evaluated in intercropping with sorghum.

Acknowledgements

This work was funded by the project DIVERSILIENCE (EU's CORE Organic Cofund Third Call 2021; grant by the Italian Ministry of Agriculture, Food Sovereignty and Forests, agreement No. 573477, 3 November 2021).

Literature

- Hausmann 1953. L'affermazione degli erbai estivi di sorgo e vigna. *Bullettino dell'agricoltura* 27: 3-18.
- IBPGR 1983. Descriptors for cowpea. IBPGR, Roma.
- Muñoz-Amatriaín et al. 2021. The UCR Minicore: a resource for cowpea research and breeding. *Legume Science* 3: 1-15.
- Singh 2014. Cowpea The food legume of the 21st century. *Crop Sci. Soc. Am., Inc. Madison (WI, USA)*.

Annual Variability of N Mineralization from Soil Organic Matter as Affected by Climate

Octavian P. Chiriac¹, Marco Pittarello¹, Barbara Moretti², Carlo Grignani², Laura Zavattaro¹

¹ DSV, Univ. Torino, IT, octavianpuiu.chiriac@unito.it, marco.pittarello@unito.it, laura.zavattaro@unito.it

² DISAFA, Univ. Torino, IT, barbara.moretti@unito.it, carlo.grignani@unito.it

Introduction

Soil organic matter (SOM) mineralization is a key process in the soil nitrogen (N) cycle, plays a crucial role in determining N availability for plant growth, and is one of the main entries in the provisional nutrient management plan calculation. Climatic variables that influence soil temperature and water content are known to affect N mineralization by modifying soil microbial activity in SOM decomposition. However, the relationships between N mineralization and climatic variables are complex and may vary depending on soil properties, soil microbiology, and crop management. Therefore, understanding the long-term drivers of SOM mineralization is essential to predict this relevant source of N for crops, in particular in a context of changing climate. Long-term observations spanning various decades of climate data coupled to N mineralization measurements are required to do this analysis.

The aim of this work, carried out under the H2020 TUDI project (GA n. 101000224), was to assess the influence of climate on SOM mineralization through the analysis of a series of climatic variables on the interannual variability of mineralized N, in long term field experiment in NW Italy.

Materials and Methods

The research was conducted at the long-term experimental platform of Tetto Frati of the Univ. of Turin, active since 1992. The climate is temperate sub-continental (avg. precipitation 760 mm, avg. T 12 °C), the soil is loamy and fertile (Grignani et al., 2007). The trial compares various maize-based cropping systems with different types and amounts of N fertilization, in a randomized block design. Three unfertilized treatments were selected, under the hypothesis that the plant N uptake is a proxy of the mineralized N along the season (De Neve, 2017), and that in the absence of fertilizer supply the only important source of N is SOM mineralization. The plant uptake in plots continuously cropped with maize for silage (MS0), maize for grain (MG0) and maize-It. ryegrass double cropping (MR0), in the time span from 1994 to 2022, was considered as the dependent variable. As independent variables, 19 agro-meteorological indices were computed from the local weather station: min, avg and max air T, daily T excursion, growing-degree days (GDD) with a 0°, 5° and 10°C basis, Rainfall+Irrigation, coefficient of variation of R+I, period of maximum drought, ET₀, soil moisture from a simple water balance (R+I-ET₀), and from a water balance following FAO-56 procedure (Allen et al., 1998) using AquaCrop stress coefficient (Trout et al., 2021) for each cropping system; De Martonne Aridity Index, UNEP Aridity Index, Lang's factor and Emberger's factor (Reig-Gracia et al., 2021). These variables were calculated for cumulated 2-, 4-, 6-, 8- 10- and 12-months periods before harvest of each year, plus a 6-months period from the previous crop harvesting to the next sowing, to assess the most relevant time when SOM mineralization can accumulate N in soil.

A simple correlation analysis allowed the selection of non-correlated independent variables (Spearman's $\rho < 0.6$) for each time period, and the remaining ones were standardized and used as explanatory variables of the plant N uptake in a stepwise linear model, using a variable selection procedure. The model with the highest adjusted R² was considered. Software R ver. 4.2.3 for Windows was used.

Results

After selection, the remaining explanatory variables considered were ET₀, MWB, R.I., cv.R+I, T_{min} and Esc. The best model for each treatment (Tab. 1) included standardized variables. The period considered was 12 months for MG0 and MS0 and 10 months before harvest for MR0.

Table 1. Result of the best-fit model using standardized variables ($p < 0.01$ for all).

System	Period	Intercept	ET0	MWB	R.I.	cv.R+I	Tmin	Esc	R ² (adj.)	RMSE
MG0	12	120***	-19**	-16*	30***	-	-	-	0.41	23
MS0	12	109***	-18*	-15.	23**	-	-12*	-	0.32	25
MR0	10	107***	-19**	-12*	-	-24***	-9*	10*	0.34	19

Signif. codes: '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1

MG0= maize for grain, MS0= maize for silage, MR0= maize-It. ryegrass double cropping, Period= months before harvest
 ET0= potential evapotranspiration, MWB= soil moisture from water balance, R.I.= Rainfall and Irrigation
 cv.R+I= coefficient of variation of R+I, Tmin= minimum temperature, Esc= daily temperature excursion

In all cropping systems, ET0 and MWB influenced N uptake. ET0 negatively affected crop uptake because of lower water availability for microorganisms and crops. MWB negatively affected crop uptake, contrary to expectation: the soil is loamy, so there are no waterlogging problems. R.I. positively affected N uptake in MG0 and MS0 cropping systems due to increased soil water availability. Cv. R+I negatively affected plant uptake in the MR0 system; this was explained by considering that when rainfall is concentrated, long dry periods hinder N mineralization and crop growth. Tmin also negatively affected N mineralization in the MR0 and MS0 systems: high temperatures and warming trends negatively affected N mineralization and plant production. Esc positively influenced N uptake by plants in the MR0 cropping system: the daily temperature excursion seemed to promote this process. Linear models explained 32% to 41% of the annual variation in mineralized N uptake. This is in line with other studies assessing climate effects on SOM mineralization variability in time and space: the model in Zhang et al. (2022) explained 29% of the variation in unfertilized wheat yield in China in a 35-year long-term experiment, while in Dessureault-Rompré et al. (2010) it explained 26% of the variation in potentially mineralizable N in 56 soil sampling sites in Canada, both using climatic variables only.

Conclusions

We found that rainfall, irrigation and daily temperature excursion positively influenced N mineralization from SOM in unfertilized soils. On the other hand, evapotranspiration, calculated soil moisture, temperature and rainfall variations negatively influenced this process. Under conditions of increasing aridity due to lower and more concentrated rainfall and higher temperatures due to climate change, both N mineralization from SOM and plant production could decrease in this site.

A limitation of our study is the assumption that unfertilized maize is a good indicator of SOM N mineralization: both are affected by the same climatic variables, therefore it is impossible to separate crop stress effect from N shortage. In addition, data were obtained from one site only, and need a validation from other environments. The model predictive capacity of N mineralization from SOM is expected to improve by including crop, soil and climate parameters from other long-term experiments in a multiple regression model.

Literature

- Allen et al. 1998. FAO Irrigation and drainage paper No. 56. Rome: FAO 56.97
- De Neve 2017. Organic matter mineralization as a source of N. In: Adv. in res. on fertil. manag. of veg. crops. Springer.
- Dessureault-Rompré et al. 2010. Relationships among mineralizable soil N, soil properties, and climatic indices. SSSAJ, 74: 1218-1227.
- Grignani et al. 2007. Production, nitrogen and carbon balance of maize-based forage systems. Eur. J. Agron., 26: 442-453.
- Reig-Gracia et al. 2021. Package ClimInd: Climate Indices. <https://gitlab.com/indecis-eu/indecis>
- Trout et al. 2021. Evapotranspiration and water stress coefficient for deficit-irrigated maize. J. Drainage Irrig. Mach. Eng. 147(10): 04021044.
- Zhang et al. 2022. Responses of wheat yield under different fertilization treatments to climate change based on a 35-year in situ experiment. Agriculture, 12: 1498.

Leaf Gas Exchange of Lignocellulosic Perennial Grasses Under Different Soil Water Availability

Sebastiano Andrea Corinzia^{1*}, Danilo Scordia², Giorgio Testa¹, Elena Crapio¹, Antonella Iurato¹, Cristina Patané³, Salvatore Luciano Cosentino¹

¹ Di3A, Univ. Catania, IT, andrea.corinzia@unict.it; cosentin@unict.it

² Dip. di Scienze Veterinarie, Univ. Messina, IT

³ CNR-IBE, Sede Secondaria di Catania, IT

Introduction

Water and energy efficiency in agriculture is a main goal of agricultural research with the aim of reducing crop water footprint and external energy requirement per unit of production, contributing to reduce the pressure on the limited global freshwater resources and non-renewable energy sources. Perennial crops are recognised to be more efficient than annual crops concerning the biomass production. Among them, giant reed (*Arundo donax* L.), miscanthus (*Miscanthus x giganteus* (Greef et Deuterand)) and African fodder cane (*Saccharum spontaneum* L. ssp. *Aegypticum* Wild (Hack.)) are selected as the most suited to Mediterranean conditions (Clifton-Brown *et al.*, 2017; Cosentino *et al.*, 2014; Cosentino *et al.*, 2015). The field trial aims to assess the physiological response of diverse lignocellulosic perennial grasses under three different irrigation regimes in the second year after plant establishment.

Materials and Methods

The field trial was carried out at the Experimental Farm of the University of Catania (10 m a.s.l., 37°24' N, 15°03' E) in a typical Xerofluvents soil (USDA, 1999). Six genotypes were evaluated in a split-plot experimental design with three replications: two *A. donax* L. ecotypes, named ARCT and ARMO (clone Fondachello and clone Morocco), the commercial *Miscanthus x giganteus* (Greef et Deuter) named MxG, two seed-based *Miscanthus* hybrids named GNT9 and GNT10, and one ecotype of *S. spontaneum*, named SAC. The main factor assigned to the plots is the irrigation factor, with 3 levels: 100%, 50% and 0% of maximum crop evapotranspiration (ET_m) restoration during the summer months (June-August). Genotype is the second factor, assigned to the sub-plots within the main irrigation plots. Each combination of irrigation and genotype is replicated 3 times within the main plots.

Net photosynthesis ($\mu\text{mol CO}_2 \text{ m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$), transpiration ($\text{mmol H}_2\text{O m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$) and stomatal conductance ($\text{mol H}_2\text{O m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$) have been measured by the LCi-SD Portable Photosynthesis system (ADC BioScientific Ltd.) on the basis of CO₂ and H₂O gas exchange. Instant water use efficiency (iWUE) has been calculated as the ratio of net photosynthesis and transpiration.

Three-factor ANOVA with date, genotype and irrigation as the sources of variance has been performed on net photosynthesis, transpiration, stomatal conductance and iWUE using R software (Team, 2013).

Results

Net photosynthesis depends on stomatal conductance, thus the irrigation input, which led to higher stomatal conductance, induced higher values of net photosynthesis (**Figure 1**). Irrigation explained most of the variance of net photosynthesis. The effect of genotype is statistically significant, and some trends can be observed among genotypes: *A. donax* genotypes, despite of the C₃ metabolism, maintained higher net photosynthesis during summer months in comparison with *S. spontaneum* and particularly with *Miscanthus* hybrids, while *Miscanthus* hybrids showed a higher decrease in net photosynthesis, particularly in the I0 input. Date, genotype, irrigation and the irrigation x genotype interaction have a statistically significant effect on IWUE. During summer months, characterized by high temperature and vapor pressure deficit, which limit the efficiency of photosystems and increase the atmospheric water uptake, the IWUE was generally lower for all the genotypes (**Figure 2**). The highest values of IWUE were recorded in September, which is characterized by lower temperature and vapor pressure deficit than summer months.

Table 1 Three-way ANOVA for main effects and interaction on LAD, AGB, iPAR and RUE. The mean of squares is reported. Year represents the within-factor, irrigation and genotypes are the between-factor effects. Degree of freedom (df) and significance: $P \leq 0.05$ (*), $P \leq 0.01$ (**), $P \leq 0.001$ (***)).

Source of variation	df	gs	A	E	iWUE
Genotype	5	0.1951***	820***	56.7***	29.31***
Irrigation	2	0.0807***	1462***	92.4***	27.07***
Date	8	0.0444***	665***	18.1***	29.9***
Genotype x Irrigation	10	0.0032	79***	4.3***	3.54*
Residuals	376	0.0022	14	0.9	1.67

Figure 1. Net photosynthesis rate ($\mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$) trends for 3 water restoration levels (I0, I50, I100) and for 6 genotypes examined in this study: ARCT: *A. donax* ecotype Catania, ARMO: *A. donax* ecotype Morocco, SAC: *S. spontaneum*, GNT10: *Miscanthus x giganteus* hybrid 10, GNT9: *Miscanthus x giganteus* hybrid 9, MxG: *Miscanthus x giganteus*.

Figure 2. Instant water use efficiency (IWUE) ($\mu\text{mol CO}_2 \text{mmol}^{-1} \text{H}_2\text{O}$) trends trends for 3 water restoration levels (I0, I50, I100) and for 6 genotypes examined in this study: ARCT: *A. donax* ecotype Catania, ARMO: *A. donax* ecotype Morocco, SAC: *S. spontaneum*, GNT10: *Miscanthus x giganteus* hybrid 10, GNT9: *Miscanthus x giganteus* hybrid 9, MxG: *Miscanthus x giganteus*.

Conclusions

Irrigation is a key factor in achieving high physiological performances in the semi-arid Mediterranean environment; however high net photosynthesis rate can be achieved even under rainfed management by selected genotypes that are adapted to low soil moisture.

Literature

- Clifton-Brown J. et al. 2017. Progress in upscaling *Miscanthus* biomass production for the European bio-economy with seed-based hybrids. *Gcb Bioenergy*, 9: 6–17.
- Cosentino S.L. et al., 2014. Response of giant reed (*Arundo donax* L.) to nitrogen fertilization and soil water availability in semi-arid Mediterranean environment. *Eur. J. Agron.*, 60: 22–32.
- Cosentino S.L. et al. 2015. *Saccharum spontaneum* L. ssp. *aegyptiacum* (Willd.) Hack. a potential perennial grass for biomass production in marginal land in semi-arid Mediterranean environment. *Ind. Crops Prod.*, 75: 93–102.

Yield of Lignocellulosic Perennial Grasses Under Different Soil Water Availability

Sebastiano Andrea Corinzia¹, Elena Crapio¹, Danilo Scordia², Antonella Iurato¹, Giorgio Testa¹, Cristina Patané³, Salvatore Luciano Cosentino¹

¹ Di3A, Univ. Catania, IT, andrea.corinzia@unict.it

² Dip. di Scienze Veterinarie, Univ. Messina, IT

³ CNR-IBE, Sede Secondaria di Catania, IT

Introduction

Water and energy efficiency in agriculture is a main goal of agricultural research with the aim of reducing crop water footprint and external energy requirement per unit of production, contributing to reduce the pressure on the limited global freshwater resources and non-renewable energy sources. Perennial crops are recognised to be more efficient than annual crops concerning the biomass production. Among them, giant reed (*Arundo donax* L.), miscanthus (*Miscanthus x giganteus* (Greef et Deuterand)) and African fodder cane (*Saccharum spontaneum* L. ssp. *Aegypticum* Wild (Hack.)) are selected as the most suited to Mediterranean conditions (Clifton-Brown *et al.*, 2017; Cosentino *et al.*, 2014; Cosentino *et al.*, 2015). The field trial aims to assess the response of diverse lignocellulosic perennial grasses under two different irrigation regimes in the second year after plant establishment.

Materials and Methods

The field trial was carried out at the Experimental Farm of the University of Catania (10 m a.s.l., 37°24' N, 15°03' E) in a typical Xerofluvents soil (USDA, 1999). Seven genotypes were evaluated in a split-plot experimental design with three replications: three *A. donax* L. ecotypes, named ARCT, ARMO and ARPI (clone Fondachello, clone Morocco and clone Piacenza), the commercial *Miscanthus x giganteus* (Greef et Deuter) named MxG, two seed-based *Miscanthus* hybrids named GNT43 and GNT3, and one ecotype of *S. spontaneum*, named SAC. The main factor assigned to the plots is the irrigation factor, with 2 levels: 100% and 0% of maximum crop evapotranspiration (ET_m) restoration during the summer months (June-August). Genotype is the second factor, assigned to the sub-plots within the main irrigation plots. Each combination of irrigation and genotype is replicated 3 times within the main plots. Irrigation was scheduled when the sum of daily ET_m corresponded to the volume, subtracting rainfall events from the calculation. The daily ET_m was calculated according to:

$$ET_m = ET_0 \times K_c \times K_p$$

where ET_m is the maximum daily evapotranspiration (mm); E₀ is the evaporation of class-A pan (mm); K_p is the pan coefficient, equal to 0.80 in semi-arid environment. Crop coefficients (K_c) were those applied for *Miscanthus x giganteus*, *Arundo donax* and *Saccharum spontaneum* grown in the same environment (Cosentino *et al.*, 2015).

The irrigation volume was calculated according to the following equation:

$$V = 0.66 \times (FC - WP) \times \phi \times D \times 10^3$$

where V = water amount (mm); 0.66 = readily available water not limiting for evapotranspiration; FC = soil water content at field capacity (27% of dry soil weight); WP = soil water content at wilting point (11% of dry soil weight); ϕ = bulk density (1.1 g cm⁻³); and D = rooting depth (0.6 m).

At the end of summer season, when rainfall increases in frequency, the irrigation was suspended.

In mid-winter the stems were collected from a 4 m² subplot, counted for stem density and weighted as fresh and dry biomass. The aboveground biomass (AGB) yield was calculated from the dry biomass production of the subplot.

Results

Miscanthus ecotypes had the highest stem density for the irrigation thesis, especially MxG, followed by *S. spontaneum*. *A. donax* genotypes had the lowest stem density with negligible differences among the irrigation theses.

GNT3 showed the highest AGB yield. The AGB yield increased with the level of water restoration for all the genotypes, with less differences between dry and irrigated in *Arundo* genotypes. The highest AGB yield in dry conditions has been observed in *A. donax* ecotypes.

Figure 1. Stem density (stems m⁻²) for 2 water restoration levels and for 7 genotypes examined in this study: ARCT: *A. donax* ecotype Catania, ARMO: *A. donax* ecotype Morocco, ARPI: *A. donax* ecotype Piacenza, SAC: *S. spontaneum*, GNT43: *Miscanthus x giganteus* hybrid 43, GNT3: *Miscanthus x giganteus* hybrid 3, MxG: *Miscanthus x giganteus*.

Figure 2. Total AGB, divided per biomass fractions (Mg ha⁻¹) for 2 water restoration levels and for 7 genotypes examined in this study: ARCT: *A. donax* ecotype Catania, ARMO: *A. donax* ecotype Morocco, ARPI: *A. donax* ecotype Piacenza, SAC: *S. spontaneum*, GNT43: *Miscanthus x giganteus* hybrid 10, GNT3: *Miscanthus x giganteus* hybrid 9, MxG: *Miscanthus x giganteus*.

Conclusions

Irrigation is a key factor in achieving high biomass yield in the semi-arid Mediterranean environment; however, selected genotypes can provide acceptable AGB yield even under rainfed management.

Literature

Clifton-Brown J. et al. 2017. Progress in upscaling *Miscanthus* biomass production for the European bio-economy with seed-based hybrids. *Gcb Bioenergy*, 9: 6–17.

Cosentino S.L. et al. 2014. Response of giant reed (*Arundo donax* L.) to nitrogen fertilization and soil water availability in semi-arid Mediterranean environment. *Eur. J. Agron.*, 60: 22–32.

Cosentino S.L. et al. 2015. *Saccharum spontaneum* L. ssp. *aegyptiacum* (Willd.) Hack. a potential perennial grass for biomass production in marginal land in semi-arid Mediterranean environment. *Ind. Crops Prod.*, 75: 93–102.

Climate-Smart Forage Systems for Climate-Smart Soils

Claudia Dămăţircă^{1,2}, Barbara Moretti², Luisella Celi², Maria Vicenza Chiriaco¹, Giampiero Lombardi², Laura Zavattaro³

¹Euro-Mediterranean Center on Climate Change, IAFES Division, Viterbo, IT, claudia.damatirca @cmcc.it

²Dip. Scienze Agrarie, Forestali e Alimentari, Univ. Torino, IT

³Dip. Scienze Veterinarie, Univ. Torino, IT

Introduction

Agriculture is an essential sector in the European Green Deal framework and plays a crucial role in achieving the *climate-neutrality by 2050* goal. Increasing soil organic matter (SOM) has been often touted as an effective climate mitigation measure, with the potential to reduce and offset part of the GHG emissions from agriculture (Kopittke et al., 2022). In addition, SOM indirectly contributes to an increased productivity, and thus to food security, while contributing to agricultural ecosystem adaptation to climate change (Chenu et al., 2019). Permanent grassland, alternation of grassland and cropland, organic fertilisation or crop residue incorporation are considered efficient management strategies in terms of increasing SOM and soil health (Chenu et al., 2019). However, hitherto insufficient research has been conducted on the long-term effects of these practices on carbon (C) turnover and partitioning into different soil pools. Accrual of C in the more stable fraction is preferable in terms of climate change mitigation, but labile fractions of SOM - with lower residence time - are essential in terms of nutrient recycling and soil fertility, as they substrate to microbes and their mineralization provides nutrients to plants. The aim of the present study was to evaluate the long-term effect of different grass- and maize-based forage systems on the organic C distribution in the various SOM fractions in both topsoil (0-30 cm) and subsoil (30-90 cm), through a combined analysis of selected data from two previous papers.

Materials and Methods

Researches were conducted at the Tetto Frati long-term experimental platform of the University of Turin (NW Italy), established in 1992 (Zavattaro et al., 2012). The experimental design (randomized block with three replicates) compared, among others, three grass-based cropping systems: permanent grassland (PG-FYM); four-years old temporary grassland (TG-FYM) in rotation to three-four years of maize for silage; Italian ryegrass and maize for silage annual rotation (DC-FYM), all fertilised with farmyard manure at 170 kg N ha⁻¹ (Dămăţircă et al., 2023b); and eight maize-based cropping systems derived from the factorial combination of maize for silage (RR: residue removed) or maize for grain (RI: residue incorporation), with three fertilisation strategies: bovine slurry (SLU); farmyard manure (FYM); and mineral N as urea (MIN), all corresponding to 250 kg N ha⁻¹, and their respective 0N controls (CTR) (Dămăţircă et al., 2023a). Soils were sampled at 0-30 cm and 30-90 cm depths to analyse SOC content and type. SOM density fractionation was performed according to Cerli et al. (2012), in order to separate i) free particulate organic matter - *f*POM; ii) occluded POM - *o*POM; and iii) mineral associated OM - MAOM. Data were analysed using a linear mixed-effects model

Results

After 29 years, PG-FYM and RI-FYM had the highest SOC content in the topsoil, while RR-CTR and RR-MIN had the lowest ($P < 0.001$). In subsoil, the higher rate of organic amendments led to an increased SOC content, while RG-FYM, DC-FYM and PG-FYM systems showed the lowest SOC content. Also, PG-FYM and RI-FYM were able to foster the *f*POM C content in topsoil, while in the subsoil the highest *f*POM C was found under PG-FYM (Figure 1). FYM + RI caused a higher occlusion of OC in the aggregates in topsoil, followed by RR-FYM and PG-FYM. RR-CTR led to the lowest *o*POM C. In subsoil, only RR-FYM and RI-FYM were able to increase *o*POM C, while no differences were found between the other cropping systems. PG-FYM resulted more efficient in increasing MAOM C content in topsoil, while RI-FYM significantly increased MAOM C in the subsoil. On the contrary, RR-MIN was the least efficient in

fostering MAOM C in topsoil, and RG-FYM, DC-FYM and PG-FYM in subsoil. When the whole 0-90 cm profile was considered, RI-FYM highlighted the greater MAOM C content, compared to DC-FYM that showed the lowest MAOM C content.

Figure 19. SOC content in the different organic matter fractions in topsoil and subsoil. Lower case letters indicate significant differences in the *f*POM fraction. Lower case letters in italic indicate significant differences in the *o*POM fraction. Capital letters indicate significant differences in the MAOM fraction.

Conclusions

This study highlighted that in our specific pedo-climatic condition, permanent grassland, farmyard manure and residue incorporation had a significant positive effect on SOM, fostering both labile and more stabilised fractions. However, PG positive effects were visible mainly in the topsoil, while organic fertilisation in synergy with residue incorporation positively affected both topsoil and subsoil. FYM and RI can be validated as strategic practices in the transition toward a circular economy, as they decrease the over-exploitation of non-renewable natural resources (such as fossil fuels), increase soil health and contribute to GHG emission reduction, while supporting food security.

Literature

- Cerli, C. et al. 2012. Separation of light and heavy organic matter fractions in soil - Testing for proper density cut-off and dispersion level. *Geoderma*, 170: 403-416.
- Chenu C. et al. 2019. Increasing organic stocks in agricultural soils: Knowledge gaps and potential innovations. *Soil Tillage Res.*, 188: 41-52.
- Dămățircă et al. 2023a. Residue incorporation and organic fertilisation improve carbon and nitrogen turnover and stabilisation in maize monocropping. *AGEE*, 342: 108255
- Dămățircă et al. 2023b. Grassland's dirty little secret: enhanced carbon dynamics in permanent vs temporary grasslands is limited to the topsoil. Under submission
- Kopittke P.M. et al. 2022. Ensuring planetary survival: the centrality of organic carbon in balancing the multifunctional nature of soils. *Critical Reviews in Environ. Sci. Technol.*, 52: 4308–4324.
- Zavattaro L. et al. 2012. Options to reduce N loss from maize in intensive cropping systems in Northern Italy. *AGEE*, 147: 24–35.

Assessment of Grazing Intensity Integrating Google Earth Engine (Sentinel-2) and Livestock GPS locations

Luca de Guttery¹, Laura Stendardi², Sergi Costafreda-Aumedes³, Edoardo Bellini¹, Andrea Confessore¹, Chiara Aquilani¹, Marco Moriondo³, Nicolina Stagliano¹, Carolina Pugliese¹, Giovanni Argenti¹, Camilla Dibari¹

¹ DAGRI, Univ. Firenze, IT, luca.deguttery@unifi.it, giovanni.argenti@unifi.it

² EURAC Research, Bolzano, IT, laura.stendardi@eurac.edu

³ CNR IBE, Firenze, IT, sergi.costafreda@ibe.cnr.it

Introduction

The evaluation of grazing intensity is one of the key parameters to develop an efficient and sustainable management of pastures (Bernués *et al.*, 2011). The use of remote sensing techniques, namely by exploiting vegetation indices (VI), has been tested as a new methodology to aid pasture management by monitoring grazing intensity (GI) (Jansen *et al.*, 2021, Li *et al.*, 2016). Moreover, recently developed platforms, such as Google Earth Engine (GEE), give the possibility to exploit very large catalogs of readily processable satellite data and to drastically reduce the amount of time needed to process images. In our study, we were able to integrate innovative pasture management technologies such as GPS locations of grazing animals (from virtual fencing collars) and remote-sensed derived VIs from Sentinel-2 (processed in GEE), with the aim to establish a methodology for monitoring grazing intensity in a Mediterranean silvopastoral system using pixel-level validation.

Materials and Methods

The study area is located in Maremma (South Tuscany) and is characterized by pastures in open woodlands grazed by *Maremmana* beef cattle. For the present study, we considered only the portions of pastures not covered by trees. A total of 22 animals were equipped with GPS collars, registering their position every 15 minutes. We gathered GPS animal positions from March 2021 until September 2021 and aggregated them to obtain daily percentages of animal presence within cells of 10x10m (corresponding to the pixel grid of Sentinel-2) over an area of approximately 7.5 ha. For the same period, the time-series of level 2A Sentinel-2 images of the study area was retrieved and analysed in GEE. After applying a cloud filter, a set of VIs was calculated for each image, including NDVI, GEMI, GNDVI, GLI, SIPI, SAVI, EVI and GCI. Afterward, difference images were computed by subtracting each pair of consecutive images. GPS data were temporally aggregated to match the dates of the difference images, for a total of 40 dates between March and September 2021. Thus, for each 10x10m cell of the pasture, the newly create dataset contained information on the grazing intensity (*i.e.*, % of animal presence, averaged over the period between two consecutive S2 images) and the concurrent difference of each VI. Subsequently, a re-elaboration was done by recalculating the value of each cell as the mean of the 5x5 neighbouring cells, to level off the inevitable noise present in the data. The last step consisted in applying linear regression models between animal presence and the differences in VIs, to explore whether the latter could be a good predictor of grazing intensity.

Results

Preliminary results show a good potential in using remote-sensed derived vegetation indexes as a tool to monitor grazing intensity. Since all analyzed indexes behaved rather similarly, in this section we report the results of the regressions referring to NDVI only, as it is the most commonly used index and the simplest to interpret. Strong positive linear relationships were found in many cases between VI differences and animal presence on the same pixel, indicating that the animal presence strongly influenced the spectral response captured by the satellite. However, unclear patterns (*i.e.*, negative relationships) are present for some of the considered dates (Table 1). The time of the year seems to play a role too, since the better fits were found in the first part of the season (approximately until June) (Figure 1), indicating a sensibility of

this technique to the environmental conditions (*i.e.* the presence of a healthy/green grass paddock), especially in a Mediterranean climate where seasonality has a strong influence on vegetation dynamics.

Table 12. Dates, slopes and R^2 values of regression models for NDVI

Date	Slope	R^2
21/03/2021	-0.01	0.001
24/03/2021	0.11	0.301
29/03/2021	-0.12	0.789
31/03/2021	0.19	0.792
08/04/2021	-0.10	0.836
23/04/2021	0.12	0.301
25/04/2021	-0.47	0.747
03/05/2021	-0.15	0.744
13/05/2021	0.37	0.690
25/05/2021	4.94	0.784
28/05/2021	2.20	0.372
30/05/2021	4.56	0.236
04/06/2021	1.29	0.462
09/06/2021	0.96	0.137
12/06/2021	3.43	0.131
14/06/2021	8.19	0.235
22/06/2021	1.29	0.288

Figure 20. R^2 trend over the whole season (March - September 2021) for NDVI

Conclusions

The use of remote sensing, and more specifically vegetation indexes, to monitor grazing intensity is a promising field of research. Our data do not yet fully confirm the potential of using VIs as proxies for monitoring grazing intensity. However, our preliminary results show that a relation is often found. The influence of seasonality should be addressed more deeply, since it could explain the decreasing trend that was found for the goodness of fit (R^2) of the models through the whole season as well as the contrasting slopes found in the first part of the season, when the re-growth of the grass might be a confounding factor in analyzing the spectral signal. Furthermore, our most-likely limitation was to consider animal presence as a proxy for grazing intensity. Animals are grazing only for a part of their time, hence not affecting the available forage just by being in a certain location. On the other hand, GPS locations of animals are rather commonly registered as part of other innovative management practices (e.g., virtual fencing). Hence, given the potential of coupling innovative practices, we think that our results should encourage more in-depth research in this field. As part of future analysis, we will have access to GPS devices that record the positions together with the feeding, ruminating, walking and resting phases of animals. We strongly believe that with this type of information we could draw more accurate conclusions on the relation between VIs and grazing intensity, possibly integrating what can be inferred from location-only GPS data.

Literature

- Bernués A. et al. 2011. Sustainability of pasture-based livestock farming systems in the European Mediterranean context: Synergies and trade-offs. *Livest. Sci.*, 139: 44–57.
- Li Fei et al. 2016. Mapping grazing intensity using remote sensing in the Xilingol steppe region, Inner Mongolia, China. *Remote Sens. Lett.*, 7(4): 328-337.
- Jansen V.S. et al. 2021. Using satellite-based vegetation data for short-term grazing monitoring to inform adaptive management. *Rangel. Ecol. Manag.*, 76: 30-42.

Modelling Context-Specific Mitigation Potential of Greenhouse Gas Emissions and Nitrogen Losses in Key European Farming Systems for Dairy Production

Xabier Díaz de Otálora^{1,2}, Agustin del Prado^{2,3}, Federico Dragoni¹, Fernando Estelles⁴, Barbara Amon^{1,5}

¹ Leibniz-Institute for Agricultural Engineering and Bioeconomy, DE, fdragoni@atb-potsdam.de

² Basque Centre for Climate Change, ES

³ Basque Foundation for Science, ES

⁴ ICTA-Universitat Politècnica de València, ES

⁵ University of Zielona Góra, PL

Introduction

Dairy production is one of the primary agricultural sources of greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions and nitrogen (N) losses. As a consequence, European dairy production systems (DPS) are facing increasingly binding emission reduction requirements. In this context, about 10% of total GHG and almost all NH₃ emissions from DPS are related to manure management (Sefeedpari et al., 2019). Nonetheless, unlike other animal categories, ruminants are able to transform feedstock that is inedible for monogastric animals into high-quality nutritionally concentrated products (i.e., milk and dairy products) significantly contributing to global food security (Feil et al., 2020). Furthermore, the maintenance of grasslands provides many ecosystem services and is key to increase carbon stocks, contributing to the mitigation of agricultural GHG (Bossio et al., 2020).

European DPS are highly diverse (Díaz de Otálora et al., 2022). Different structural characteristics and contexts largely determine performances and mitigation potentials (Gonzalez-Mejia et al., 2018). In this context, there is a lack of knowledge on the effects of different mitigation measures applied to different DPS. The “MilKey” and “DairyMix” projects (www.milkey-project.eu; www.dairymix.eu) contribute to fill this gap. In particular, this study identifies and assesses the single and combined effect of selected mitigation measures on GHG emissions and N losses from manure management and fertilization in four key DPS in Europe by means of a whole-farm modelling approach.

Materials and Methods

An updated version of the SIMS_{DAIRY} model (Del Prado et al., 2011) was applied to evaluate the effect of selected emission mitigation measures on different DPS. This whole-farm system model simulates the interrelated processes, loops and fluxes of a DPS, allowing for the evaluation of the effect of different mitigation strategies on GHG emissions and N losses across different farm subsystems. The study was based on four case study farms across Europe (Germany, Ireland, and Italy). The selected case studies represented different typologies of DPS based on their production systems, intensity, productivity, management practices, socioeconomic attributes, namely: i) a Western Europe conventional intensive system (WC_i), ii) a Western Europe organic semi-extensive system (WO_s), iii) an Atlantic conventional semi-extensive system (AC_s), and iv) a Mediterranean conventional intensive system (MC_i). The effect of i) rigid slurry covers (compared to open or crusted), ii) slurry injection (compared to broadcast application), iii) anaerobic digestion (AD) and iv) urea replacement with ammonium nitrate were modelled. Variations with respect to the baseline modelling for each individual compound (e.g., CH₄, N₂O, NH₃, NO₃ and NO_x) were calculated.

Results

Anaerobic digestion resulted in a lower GHG emissions in all considered DPS. In this sense, while this option was shown to be effective in the reduction of N losses from manure storage, contrasting effects were observed in the N losses from the fields, showing an increase in the MC_i. As for the use of rigid slurry covers, a general reduction was observed both in N losses from manure storage in all DPS as well as the

direct GHG N₂O emissions from manure management. Slurry injection was shown as an effective mitigation measure to reduce the N losses from the fields, with a particular positive impact on the NH₃ emission from this source in all DPS. Lastly, the substitution of urea with ammonium nitrate reduced N losses in all DPS modelled while increasing the GHG emissions due to higher direct N₂O emission from the fields, specially in the MC_i. In addition, our results demonstrated the advantages of cumulative implementation of adapted mitigation options to offset the observed negative effects of single-option application. In this sense, the combined application of slurry injection together with anaerobic digestion was presented as a positive measure to reduce the negative trade-offs (i.e., pollution swapping) observed from the single modelling of anaerobic digestion.

Conclusions

Against the “*one-fits-all*” emission reduction strategies, the application of context-specific measures in different DPS typologies lead to a substantial reduction of farm GHG emissions and N losses in the case studies evaluated. Furthermore, the combined application of different mitigation strategies favours positive synergistic effects at the same time that negative trade-offs are minimized. In this context, the implementation and promotion of circular mixed crop-livestock systems is evident. Identifying options for the integration of dairy and crop production systems at farm and regional level can further contribute to mitigate GHG and reduce nutrient losses.

Literature

- Bossio D.A. et al. 2020. The role of soil carbon in natural climate solutions. *Nat. Sustain.*, 3: 391–398.
- Del Prado A. et al. 2011. SIMS_{DAIRY}: A modelling framework to identify sustainable dairy farms in the UK. Framework description and test for organic systems and N fertiliser optimisation. *Sci. Total Environ.*, 409: 3993–4009.
- Díaz de Otálora X. et al. 2022. Identification of representative dairy cattle and fodder crop production typologies at regional scale in Europe. *Agron. Sustain. Dev.*, 42: 92.
- Feil A.A. et al. 2020. Sustainability in the dairy industry: a systematic literature review. *Environ. Sci. Pollut. Res.*, 27: 33527–33542.
- Gonzalez-Mejia A. et al. 2018. Metrics and methods for characterizing dairy farm intensification using farm survey data. *PLoS One*, 13: 1–18.
- Sefeedpari P. et al. 2019. Technical, environmental and cost-benefit assessment of manure management chain: A case study of large scale dairy farming. *J. Clean Prod.*, 233: 857–868.

Acknowledgements

This study was supported by the German Federal Ministry of Food and Agriculture (BMEL) through the Federal Office for Agriculture and Food (BLE) under the “MilKey” project (grant number 2819ERA08A), funded under the Joint Call 2018 ERA-GAS, SusAn and ICT-AGRI 2, and the “DairyMix” project (grant number 2821ERA15A), funded under the Joint Call 2021 ERA-GAS, SusCrop, SusAn and ICT-AGRI-FOOD. BC3-Research is supported by the Spanish Government through María de Maeztu excellence accreditation 2018–2022 (Ref. MDM-2017-0714) and by the Basque Government through the BERC 2018–2021 program. Agustín del Prado is financed through the Ramon y Cajal program by the Spanish Ministry of Economy, Industry, and Competitiveness (RYC-2017-22143).

Crop Performance of Peanut in a South Italy Environment: Effect of Irrigation and Plant Growth-Promoting Microorganisms on Water Productivity

Michele Andrea De Santis, Daniela Campaniello, Damiana Tozzi, Luigia Giuzio, Maria Rosaria Corbo, Antonio Bevilacqua, Milena Grazia Rita Sinigaglia, Zina Flagella

DAFNE, Univ. Foggia, IT, michele.desantis@unifg.it, zina.flagella@unifg.it

Introduction

Peanut is a staple crop widely cultivated in America, Asia and Africa as a source of unsaturated fatty acids and plant proteins. Despite the potential favourable climate conditions, peanut is not widespread in the Mediterranean basin. Also, according to the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), the optimization of management to improve food water footprint and use efficiency is mandatory for modern agriculture. In order to evaluate the adaptability of peanut in the Mediterranean environment, a two-years field trial was conducted in South Italy, under different levels of irrigation. The application of plant growth-promoting microorganisms was also tested to verify the impact on crop water productivity.

Materials and Methods

The field trials were conducted at farm level at Foggia (Italy, 41° 30' 40.109" N, 15° 40' 28.101" E, at 37 m a.s.l.) in two consecutive crop years (2021 and 2022). Two different botanical types of peanut genotypes (large seed Virginia and medium seed Spanish) were cultivated in a factorial combination of two irrigation levels (full and half irrigation) and 2 fertilization treatments (with and without plant growth-promoting microorganisms, PGPM), with three replications. Nitrogen (40 kg/ha-N) and phosphorous (100 kg/ha P₂O₅) were, respectively applied at sowing as urea and triple superphosphate. Inoculation was carried out with a commercial microbial consortium (Bottos Mykopower) that included: *Glomus intraradices*, *Glomus mosseae*, *Glomus deserticola*, 10%; *Trichoderma asperellum*, *Bacillus pumilus*, *Bacillus coagulans* (10⁶ CFU/g). Sowing was carried out on 21/05/2021 and 16/05/2022. Manual and mechanical weed control was adopted and no fungicides or insecticides were needed. Starting irrigation (100 mm) was provided for all experimental combinations in the first 40 days, then two water regimes were adopted with a weekly replenish of crop evapotranspiration (ET) minus effective rainfall. ET was calculated according to the formula: $ET = PET \times Kc$, with PET as potential evapotranspiration (Penman-Montheith) and Kc as crop coefficients for peanut according to the FAO56 handbook for the Mediterranean environment (0.40, 1.15, and 0.6 at the initial, mid-season and late stage). A total irrigation of 203 (2021) and 240 (2022) mm (half irrigation) and 348 (2021) and 365 (2022) mm (full irrigation) in the two years was applied. The impact of agronomic management was also assessed by spectral vegetation indices (NDVI, OSAVI) during seed maturation, by a field spectroradiometer (Apogee SS-110). At maturity pod and seed yield and their components were assessed. Water use efficiency was expressed in terms of agricultural water productivity (AWP) calculated as the ratio between pod yield and the sum of rainfall and irrigation amount. Protein content was also determined (De Santis et al., 2023). Means were separated by least significant difference (LSD).

Results

OSAVI during seed maturation showed a positive relationship with AWP (Figure 1). The two crop years showed no significant differences in terms of pod yield (3.9 t/ha). The interaction genotype x irrigation x inoculation for pod yield, OSAVI, AWP and protein content (PC) is reported in Table 1. The Virginia-type genotype was significantly more productive and showed a positive response to irrigation. On the other hand, the Spanish-type genotype resulted less adaptable. The inoculation with the PGPMs led to a significant increase in AWP with 50% irrigation in the Virginia-type genotype (Table 1); this was associated to a significant increase of the aerobic spore forming bacteria (bacilli) in soil, as reported in De Santis et al.

(2023). Few changes occurred in protein content (PC) that resulted negatively influenced by irrigation amount in Virginia-type genotype.

Figure 13. Relationship between AWP and OSAVI of the two investigated peanut genotypes.

Table 14. Agronomic response to irrigation and biofertilizer of one Virginia-type and one Spanish-type peanut genotype.

Irrigation	Genotype	PGPM	OSAVI	pod yield (t/ha)	AWP (kg/mm)	PC (%)	
50%	Virginia	control	0.347	3.5	7.3	26.4	
		inoculated	0.363	5.2	10.5	26.4	
	Spanish	control	0.244	1.7	3.1	24.9	
		inoculated	0.262	2.6	5.0	25.0	
100%	Virginia	control	0.348	6.1	9.6	25.8	
		inoculated	0.376	6.6	10.0	25.3	
	Spanish	control	0.271	2.3	3.1	25.0	
		inoculated	0.273	2.7	4.0	25.1	
			LSD	0.041	1.1	2.1	0.3

Conclusions

The adaptability of peanut under Mediterranean conditions (South Italy) was investigated. The outcomes indicate a differential response of the two genotypes investigated, with a better response of the Virginia-type one, which showed higher crop productivity. The inoculation of PGPM may represent a smart solution to optimize peanut production, especially for the most responsive genotype under water-saving irrigation strategies.

Literature

De Santis et al. 2023. Agronomic Response to Irrigation and Biofertilizer of Peanut (*Arachis hypogaea* L.) Grown under Mediterranean Environment. *Agronomy*, 13: 1566.

Acknowledgements: This research was funded by Apulian Region through the grant “Produzione e valorizzazione dell’arachide da frutto in Puglia—PEANUTPUGLIA” (P.S.R. Puglia 2014/2020-Misura 162)—C.U.P.: B77H20001660009, DDS: 94250038034. We thank farm Pedone for the field trials, together with Luca Ardito and “La Cenerentola” company for the supply of genetic material.

Simulating Soil Heterotrophic Respiration with ARMOSA Model: Calibration with Continuous Field Measures of CO₂ Soil Fluxes from the AGRESTIC Project

Mara Gabbrielli¹, Marco Botta¹, Marco Perfetto¹, Iride Volpi², Diego Guidotti², Cristiano Tozzini³, Pierluigi Meriggi⁴, Alessia Perego¹, Marco Acutis¹, Giorgio Ragolini¹

¹ Dip. Scienze Agrari ed Ambientali, Univ. Milano, IT, mara.gabbrielli@unimi.it

² AEDIT srl, Pisa, IT, volpi@aedit.it

³ Centro di Ricerca di Scienze delle Piante, Scuola Superiore Sant'Anna di Pisa, IT, cristiano.tozzini@santannapisa.it

⁴ Horta srl, Piacenza, IT, p.meriggi@horta-srl.com

Introduction

Crop management effects on soil respiration (Rs) and organic carbon pools in agricultural soils can be evaluated using process-based dynamic simulation models. Measured data are required to perform model calibration: within the LIFE project AGRESTIC - Reduction of Agricultural Greenhouse gases Emissions Through Innovative Cropping systems (LIFE17 CCM/IT/000062), coordinated by Horta srl, CO₂ soil fluxes were measured in continuous for three years in two pilot farms located in northern and southern Italy (Ravenna and Foggia) for two cropping systems, conventional (CCS) and efficient (ECS).

Materials and Methods

Soil fluxes of CO₂ were measured through greenhouse gases (GHG) monitoring stations, one installed in Ravenna (RAV) and the other one in Foggia (FOG). In each site, eight flow-through non-steady-state automatic chambers were each set to record 9 measurements per day up to 10 cm depth. An IT infrastructure developed within the project allowed to flag the data quality and calculate daily Rs, including both autotrophic (Ra) and heterotrophic (Rh) respiration. Additional technical information on the prototype is reported in Volpi et al. (2020). Data elaboration to calculate cumulative fluxes of CO₂ was performed, using a script written in R language, by aggregating the data by month considering the soil use (crop type or bare soil). ARMOSA model (Perego et al., 2013), which simulates crop growth, water, carbon and nitrogen dynamics under different pedoclimatic conditions, was employed to simulate soil Rh in the conventional cropping systems. The model was calibrated on CO₂ measures from bare soil periods, because during crop growth periods Rh cannot be discriminated from Rs in CO₂ fluxes (Tab. 1). Soil parameters employed in the CN dynamics module were calibrated separately for the superficial soil layer (10 cm depth) and for the deeper soil layers of the profile. Surface crops residue mineralisation rates, and their limiting factors, were simulated with ARMOSA dedicated mulch module (Tadiello et al., 2023). Measured CO₂ fluxes were scaled, by applying Rh/Rs ratios (Rana et al., 2018), to assess ARMOSA Rh prediction even during crop growth periods.

Results

At monthly aggregation level, bare soil cumulative CO₂ emissions EF (modelling efficiency) and CRM (coefficient of residual mass) values were optimal, even if a high RRMSE was reported for 2021 (Tab. 1). Cumulative CO₂ emissions simulated during crop cultivation reported a slight deviation from the values (*, Tab. 1) estimated by applying Rh/Rs ratios. The cumulated Rh of the bare soil periods were satisfactorily simulated (average RRMSE 16%) for the calibration dataset. Validation results for FOG CCS were satisfactory for bare soil periods cumulative emissions (average RRMSE 13.5%). Overall, ARMOSA model satisfactorily represented emissions trends over time (Fig. 1), as influenced by weather conditions, tillage events type and depth, crop residue type and location (buried or superficial).

Table 1. Calibration dataset (RAV CCS): crop sequence, measured (scaled estimated values are flagged with *) and simulated cumulative CO₂ emissions (g CO₂ m⁻²), number of measure (n), RRMSE (%), EF (unitless) and CRM (unitless) for monthly cumulative CO₂ emissions during bare soil periods.

Soil use	Date start	Date end	Measured CO ₂	Simulated CO ₂	n	RRMSE	EF	CRM
Bare soil	2019-12-12	2020-04-01	166	139	110	31.2	0.5	0.2
Maize	2020-04-03	2020-09-10	280*	341	152			
Bare soil	2020-09-16	2020-10-23	501	466	33	7.0	0.9	0.1
Durum wheat	2020-10-24	2021-06-23	305*	365	220			
Bare soil	2021-06-28	2022-05-16	766	710	202	44.2	0.8	0.1
Tomato	2022-05-21	2022-08-25	295*	173	97			
Bare soil	2022-09-10	2022-09-26	159	106	9	33.2	-	0.3

Figure 1. Daily CO₂ emissions for the calibration dataset: simulated (blue) and measured (black) values. Error bars represent the standard deviations. Measured emissions during crop cultivation (light blue boxes) are reported as non-scaled values. Tillage events are reported as dashed (harrowing) and solid (plowing) lines.

Conclusions

ARMOSA model calibration for CO₂ soil fluxes will allow to evaluate management practices aimed at soil GHG emissions mitigation, through model application in a wide range of pedoclimatic conditions and cropping systems.

Literature

- Perego A. et al. 2013. The ARMOSA simulation crop model: overall features, calibration and validation results. *Ital. J. Agrometeorol.*, 3: 23–38.
- Rana G. et al. 2018. CO₂ and H₂O flux partitioning in a Mediterranean cropping system. *Agric. Forest Meteorol.*, 260, 118–130.
- Tadiello T. et al., 2023. A new module to simulate surface crop residue decomposition: Description and sensitivity analysis. *Ecol. Model.*, 480: 110327.
- Volpi I. et al. 2020. Improving GHG flux monitoring in agricultural soil through the AGRESTIC prototype: a focus on the assessment of data quality. *IEEE International Workshop on Metrology for Agriculture and Forestry (MetroAgriFor)*, 139–143.

Working on Ancient Wheats and Old Durum Wheat Cultivars at the Dept. Of Agricultural Sciences Of Sassari

Francesco Giunta¹, Rosella Motzo¹, Marina Mefleh², Martina Careddu¹

¹ Dip. di Scienze agrarie, Univ. Sassari, giunta@uniss.it, motzo@uniss.it, m.careddu2@phd.uniss.it

² Dep. of Soil, Plant and Food Science, Univ. Bari "Aldo Moro", marina.mefleh@uniba.it

Introduction

The interest of the Dept. of Agricultural Sciences of the University of Sassari on ancient wheats and old durum wheat cultivars initiated in 2007 with a series of papers on the effects of breeding on phenology, grain yield and physiological traits of durum wheat and has led, more recently, to another series of papers on cropping systems suitable for old cultivars and ancient wheats and on their quality, that will be synthesized here.

Grain yield and grain protein of old and modern durum wheat cultivars grown under different cropping systems (Giunta et al., 2019)

A five-year field trial was performed in a typical Mediterranean environment to compare grain yield (GY) and GY stability, grain protein percentage (GP) and GP stability resulting from different cropping systems: two based on 14 old durum wheat landraces/cultivars grown in low-fertility soils; and one based on 14 modern cultivars grown in high-fertility soils. Cropping systems were also differentiated in terms of sowing date, sowing rate (250 vs. 350 viable seeds m⁻² for the modern cultivars only) and nitrogen rate (36, 76 and 112 kg N ha⁻¹ on average for the 'OLDlow', 'OLDmedium' and 'MODERN' cropping systems, respectively). The interest towards old cultivars and their role in modern agriculture is mainly associated with the recovery of abandoned low-fertile areas and their high protein percentage. Although their lateness would theoretically imply a potentially high impact of the terminal drought characteristic of Mediterranean environments, the old cultivars in this study exhibited comparable stability in grain yield to that associated with modern cultivars, which flower within the optimal window for this kind of environment. The low GP stability in the pool of old cultivars analyzed in this experiment should be interpreted positively, as it mostly arose from the more favourable environmental conditions in spring. Moreover, the old cultivars guaranteed a high protein percentage, even with low fertilization rates and in low-fertility soils, and an almost complete recovery of the fertilizers applied.

Old tall durum wheat cultivars and ancient wheats are suited for dual-purpose utilization (Giunta et al., 2017; Cadeddu et al., 2021 a and b)

The lateness, tallness and high vigour of old tall durum wheat cultivars could be advantageous for dual-purpose use and their high propensity for lodging should be reduced by grazing. A 3-year field trial was performed in Sardinia, Italy, in a typical Mediterranean environment. Crops of the durum wheat cultivar Senatore Cappelli were sown in October, and grazing was simulated by clipping half of the plots at the terminal spikelet stage of development. In the Mediterranean environment studied, old tall durum wheat cultivars as represented by cultivar Senatore Cappelli showed good suitability for dual-purpose use. The low grain yield potential of these types of cultivars contributed to reducing the negative effects of clipping on GY. In addition, their competitiveness with semi-dwarf ones in environments with low attainable yields benefited from the high straw yield due to their low HI. Moreover, they were able to preserve their characteristically high protein percentage in grains when properly managed in terms of nitrogen fertilization. Their good recovery after clipping, despite the decrease in spike population density, was attributable to the high number of leaves that emerged after clipping, which guaranteed that the inevitable reduction in radiation interception following clipping did not impact spike fertility.

Khorasan, einkorn, and emmer wheats, clipped at the terminal spikelet stage or left unclipped, were compared in a two-year field trial. Grain yield was not penalized by clipping: the increase in the harvest index compensated for the decrease in biomass. Here we show for the first time that ancient wheat species

are suitable for dual-purpose utilization (herbage plus grain in the same season) rendering them valuable for marginal areas; this was because the early sowing adopted for dual-purpose utilization allowed them to take full advantage of their lateness in terms of herbage yield, and to bring flowering forward (i.e. make it earlier) so that a satisfactory grain yield was obtained, even under severe water stress. Dual-purpose utilization of ancient wheats increases the sustainability of mixed cropping systems, by making herbage available to animals in a critical period, without decreasing the grain yield attainable after grazing in the same season.

On average, clipped crops showed a lower (by about 46 kg ha⁻¹) total N uptake at maturity compared with unclipped crops, but dual-purpose utilization did not negatively affect the N uptake if the N removed by clipping was taken into account. Clipping did not negatively affect N partitioning to the grain as the N harvest index increased after clipping as a consequence of the increased harvest index.

Grain quality (Mefleh et al., 2020)

By considering the entire productive chain of a durum wheat product, from seed (cultivar choice) to bread, it is possible to link genotypic-related variations in bread quality to specific grain quality traits (N content per grain). Old cultivars are able to produce grains with high N content even in low fertile soils and with low N inputs.

The agronomic and bread-making performances of 14 old Italian durum wheat varieties grown under two low nitrogen (N) inputs (46 and 86 kg ha⁻¹) were determined and the relationships among grain, semolina, dough and bread quality parameters were established. The old varieties yielded similarly to the check modern variety Svevo under both N levels. Increasing N fertilization from 46 to 86 kg ha⁻¹ caused an increase in grain protein percentage as a result of a decrease in grain weight and an increase in gliadin content. Despite the resulting decrease in the gluten index, dough and bread quality improved at the highest N rate, highlighting the influential role of protein percentage and gliadin in bread quality. The genotypic variation in grain protein percentage among old varieties was more strongly associated with glutenin than with gliadin content. Variation in the gluten index was high (4–54); indeed, it was the most variable semolina parameter, and proved to contribute the most to variation in bread quality. This variation was independent of the glutenin alleles (HMW 20, 20*, 7, 13+16, 6+8) and was linked to the quality of the grain in terms of grain weight and the associated mg of N per grain. Remarkably, two old varieties, namely Calabria and Cappelli, were able to produce both a good yield and high-quality bread.

Experiments in progress

Pheno-morphological characterization of old wheat cultivars and landraces and development of growth and development models via two field trials, one with old cultivars of durum wheat, both tall and short, early and late, in intercropping and in pure stands; the other with various accessions of Tricu Cossu, a local bread wheat landrace obtained from different farmers in Gallura. In another trial, cultivar Senatore Cappelli sown in October has been grazed by sheep at the 5-6 leaf stage.

Literature

- Giunta et al. 2017. Old tall durum wheat cultivars are suited for dual-purpose utilization. *Eur. J. Agron.*, 90: 67-77.
- Giunta et al. 2019. Grain yield and grain protein of old and modern durum wheat cultivars grown under different cropping systems. *Field Crops Res.*, 230: 107-120.
- Mefleh et al. 2020. From seed to bread: variation in quality in a set of old durum wheat cultivars. *J. Sci. Food Agric.*, 100 (11): 4066-4074.
- Cadeddu et al. 2021a. Ancient wheat species are suitable to dual-purpose utilization in marginal Mediterranean environments. *Agron. Sustain. Dev.* 41: 15.
- Cadeddu et al. 2021b. Effects of clipping on the nitrogen economy of four Triticum species grown in a Mediterranean environment. *Field Crops Res.*, 267: 108162.

A Network of Farms to Develop and Test Innovations for Climate-Smart Cropping Systems

Elisa Marraccini¹, Vittoria Giannini², Gabriela Alandia¹, Giorgio Borreani³, Mirco Corazzin¹, Gemini Delle Vedove¹, Francesco Ferrero³, Stefano Grigolato⁴, Carmelo Maucieri², Tanja Mimmo⁵, Carlo Nicoletto², Silvia Panozzo⁶, Gaetano R. Pesce², Gabriele Rolando³, Luigi Sartori, Paolo Sivilotti¹, Enrico Sturaro², Ernesto Tabacco³, Massimo Tagliavini⁵, Eren Taskin⁵, Damiano Zanotelli⁵, Maurizio Borin²

¹ DI4A, Univ. Udine, IT, elisa.marraccini@uniud.it

² DAFNAE, Univ. Padova, IT, vittoria.giannini@unipd.it

³ DISAFA, Univ. Torino, IT, giorgio.borreani@unito.it

⁴ TESAF, Univ. Padova, IT, stefano.grigolato@unipd.it

⁵ Faculty of Agricultural, Environmental and Food Sciences, Univ. Bolzano, IT, tanja.mimmo@unibz.it

⁶ IPSP-CNR, IT, silvia.panozzo@cnr.it

Introduction

Digital technologies are essential to achieve a carbon-neutral Europe by 2050. In the farming sector, technologies such as precision farming, artificial intelligence, prediction systems, or green data spaces will help analysis and decision-making, and are expected to reduce global emissions by 15% (European Commission, 2020). Moreover, for a green, digital and resilient economy the direct involvement and engagement of stakeholders is fundamental to empower them and let them lead the digital green transition (Muench et al., 2022). Nowadays, several approaches are applied according to stakeholders' interests and needs to conduct participatory planning and on-farm experimentation; co-develop and explore solutions; monitor and assess systems and processes; and/or disseminate and promote production practices (Bouma, 2021; Lacoste et al., 2021; Toffolini and Jeuffroy, 2022). In this context, the main goal of Task 4.2.1 of the Italian Agritech National Center is to set up a network of farms composed of several units in forms of living labs in order to test in real conditions innovative approaches and climate-smart agricultural practices.

Material and Methods

The methodology used to set-up a farm network can be summarized in three steps. The first regards an overall discussion among research groups involved on the: a) definition of the main issues of investigation/demonstration according to the general objectives of the Spoke 4 within the Agritech National Center, b) identification of potential farms that could contribute to co-develop innovation according to the defined objectives. The second step will be operative, based on the interaction and collaboration among researchers, farmers and stakeholders to build the farm network. This activity is based on: a) field visits and involvement of the farms; b) initial on-farm assessments; c) identification of individual farmer preferences for the issues of investigation and the type of involvement in the network.

Once the network will be established, the third step will start. In that last phase, individual farmer-researcher-farmer and farmers-researchers-farmers/stakeholders contacts will take place to test and demonstrate in real conditions innovative climate-smart agricultural practices.

Preliminary results and discussion

The preliminary results include the farm network design. The network will involve farms mainly located in Northern Italy and particularly the Po valley, which is one of the most productive Italian agricultural areas, which is particularly affected by climate change (flooding, salinity, drought).

Considering the framework in which the research activity is set, a series of indicators dealing with water, carbon and energy management will be co-constructed and analysed. Moreover, we will build water and carbon-related scenarios starting from the farm business as usual and then taking into account the effectiveness of innovation on both carbon and water footprints for a subset of farms aiming at co-

developing and testing innovation. Examples of innovations include the implementation of drought resistant summer crop genotypes, cover crops, innovative irrigation systems or weed management.

The design of the network considered the expected activities in the farms belonging to the network, the type of farms involved and the structure of the network. The network is composed of some farms collaborating in the project with different research units. These farms could be differently involved according to their features: 1) *commercial farms* providing data and feedbacks to the network, participating to the demonstration activities taking place in other farms of the network; 2) *demonstration farms* providing data and feedback to the network and wishing to host demonstration or on-farm experiments in their farm; 3) *lighthouse farms* already having an outstanding performance in terms of resilience to climate change on their farm and wishing to participate to demonstration actions. These lighthouse farms can be part of the network either from the beginning or can be recognized as such according to the performance results measured during the project.

A group of farms within the network having the same farming system and collaborating with a research group involved in the project will create a living lab. Therefore, there will be 14 living labs in the farm network as summarised in Table 1. Within the network, four living labs of arable farms are expected, followed by three living labs of orchard and vineyard farms.

Table 1. Farming systems involved in the farm network

Research group involved	Arable farms	Mixed farms	Orchard farms	Vineyard farms	Vegetable farms	Forestry systems
CNR	X		X	X		
University of Bolzano			X			
University of Padova	X			X	X	X
University of Torino	X	X	X			
University of Udine	X	X		X		

Conclusions

The set-up of a farm network within the Spoke 4 of the Italian Agritech National Center is expected to generate several types of outcomes: 1) establishing a medium-term agricultural monitoring network able to provide multiannual data about cropping system resilience to climate change; 2) enabling peer-to-peer and researcher-farmers learning to generate innovative knowledge on climate-smart cropping systems; 3) testing different cropping systems and technological solutions.

Acknowledgement

This study was carried out within the Agritech National Research Center and received funding from the European Union Next-GenerationEU (PIANO NAZIONALE DI RIPRESA E RESILIENZA (PNRR) – MISSIONE 4 COMPONENTE 2, INVESTIMENTO 1.4 – D.D. 1032 17/06/2022, CN00000022). This manuscript reflects only the authors' views and opinions, neither the European Union nor the European Commission can be considered responsible for them.

Literature

Bouma J., 2022. Transforming living labs into lighthouses: a promising policy to achieve land-related sustainable development. *Soil*, 8: 751-759.

European Commission, 2020. Factsheet: Supporting the Green Transition. [Supporting the green transition \(europa.eu\)](https://ec.europa.eu/eip/agriculture/en/supporting-the-green-transition)

Lacoste M., et al., 2022. n-Farm Experimentation to transform global agriculture. *Nature Food*, 3: 11-18.

Muench, S., Stoermer, E., Jensen, K., Asikainen, T., Salvi, M. and Scapolo, F., 2022. Towards a green and digital future, EUR 31075 EN, Publications Office of the European Union, Luxembourg.

Toffolini Q. & Jeuffroy M.-H., 2022. On-farm experimentation practices and associated farmer-researcher relationships: a systematic literature review. *Agron. Sustain. Dev.*, 42.6: 114.

Greenhouse Gas Emissions and Yield of Durum Wheat Under Organic and Conventional Fertilization in Three Type Soil

Lucia Ottaiano¹, Eugenio Cozzolino², Ida Di Mola¹, Maria Eleonora Pelosi¹, Luca Vitale³
Giuseppe Maglione³, Bruno di Matteo³ Daniele Todisco¹, Nunzio Fiorentino¹, Mauro Mori¹

¹ DiA, Univ. Napoli, IT, lucia.ottaiano@unina.it, ida.dimola@unina.it, mariaeleonora.pelosi@unina.it,
daniele.todisco@unina.it, nunzio.fiorentino@unina.it, mori@unina.it

² CREA-CI, Caserta, IT, eugenio.cozzolino@crea.gov.it

³ CNR-ISAFOM, Portici, IT, luca.vitale@cnr.it, giuseppe.maglione@cnr.it, bruno.dimatteo@isafom.cnr.it

Introduction

Agriculture contributes to global climate change with the emission in atmosphere of greenhouse gases. Agricultural soil management practices can contribute for about 60% of the total nitrous oxide emissions from the agricultural sector (Smith et al., 2007). The soil texture is a driver of N₂O emissions as it regulates the oxygen and humidity availability for soil microorganisms. In this scenario, it is essential to define sustainable management practices to minimise the impact of cropping systems on the global environment while maintaining the yield and quality. The aim of this study was to evaluate the N₂O emissions and the quality-quantitative production of durum wheat on three different types of soil under different fertilization.

Materials and Methods

The study was carried out from autumn 2020 to spring 2021 at the experimental site of the Department of Agricultural Science, in Portici. The experimental design was a factorial combination between three different types of soil (clay, sand and loam) and four different fertilization strategies (not fertilized -Cont; treated with compost -Com; treated with digestate -Dig; treated with mineral -Min). The dose of nitrogen was calculated according to balance method and, it was 120 kg ha⁻¹. The compost and digestate were entirely distributed at the sowing; the nitrogen organic content was 2% and 0.6%, for compost and digestate, respectively. Instead the mineral fertilizer was distributed as ammonium nitrate (26% N) in two times (30% at the sowing and 70% at the tillering-stem elongation). During the crop cycle N₂O emissions were measured by the static chamber technique. The gas samples were then analysed by gas chromatography. At the harvest, made on June 23 2021, a 2 m² sampling area was cut and weighed, in order to determine the grain yield, plant height and harvest index (HI). In addition, on three samples of 100 seeds per each treatment and replicate, the percentage of vitreous and shrinking kernels was evaluated by visual inspection. Protein content, expressed in percentage, was determined in laboratory.

Results

Wheat yield was affected by the interaction between types of soil and fertilization strategies (ST x F). The best performance was recorded in sandy soil with digestate fertilization (0.27 kg m⁻²) that was significantly different from all other treatments (Fig.1), contrarily in the other two soils no significant differences were found between the organic fertilizations. Interestingly, only in the clay soil the Min showed higher values than organic fertilizations (Fig.1).

The interaction ST x F affected only shrinking and protein percentage. The HI was higher in sandy soil (36.9% vs. 33.1% of the mean value of clay and loam soils), as well as the vitreousness percentage that was 33.1% vs. 16.0% (mean value of clay and loam soils) (Tab.1). The mean value of the plants height was 65.3 cm. The shrinking percentage was low in all treatments, only

Figure 1: Yield of wheat as affected by types of soil and nitrogen fertilization strategies.

the clay-control treatment reached 4% (Tab.1). Finally, the higher protein content was found in clay soil with mineral fertilization (16.8%) while, as expected, the lowest one in no fertilized sandy soil (9.1%) (Tab.1). On average, the protein content was 14.4%, 13.5%, and 11.2% for loam, clay and sandy soil, respectively, while it was 16.5%, 12.7%, 11.6%, and 11.2% for Min, Com, Cont, and Dig, respectively.

Table 1. Harvest index, height, vitreousness, shrinking and protein content of wheat as affected by the interaction between soil type and fertilization strategies.

Treatments		HI %	Height cm	Vitreousness %	Shrinking %	Protein %
Soil Type	Fertilization					
Loam	Cont	30.7 ± 0.60	66.5 ± 3.00	10.0 ± 2.89	1.3 ± 0.67 bc	14.7 ± 0.28 c
	Dig	33.7 ± 2.92	62.1 ± 1.10	16.7 ± 8.29	1.3 ± 0.67 bc	12.5 ± 0.32 e
	Com	33.7 ± 2.52	69.2 ± 2.20	8.3 ± 2.40	1.0 ± 0.58 bd	15.0 ± 0.39 bc
	Min	30.5 ± 1.04	65.7 ± 0.95	18.3 ± 4.41	0.7 ± 0.67 cd	15.5 ± 0.63 b
Sandy	Cont	38.7 ± 2.13	65.7 ± 1.84	24.0 ± 2.08	0.0 ± 0.00 d	9.1 ± 0.39 h
	Dig	38.7 ± 0.67	61.1 ± 2.48	36.7 ± 1.76	0.0 ± 0.00 d	11.1 ± 0.50 f
	Com	37.8 ± 0.73	70.2 ± 2.17	32.3 ± 1.20	0.0 ± 0.00 d	10.7 ± 0.91 fg
	Min	38.8 ± 0.17	67.0 ± 1.09	39.3 ± 2.85	0.0 ± 0.00 d	13.8 ± 0.13 d
Clay	Cont	22.8 ± 0.33	65.7 ± 3.18	2.3 ± 1.20	4.0 ± 0.58 a	11.2 ± 0.30 f
	Dig	29.7 ± 2.40	63.4 ± 3.41	19.3 ± 4.91	1.7 ± 0.88 b	10.1 ± 0.65 g
	Com	34.2 ± 1.01	62.1 ± 0.34	27.7 ± 9.13	0.3 ± 0.33 d	12.5 ± 0.53 e
	Min	36.7 ± 4.17	65.4 ± 4.23	25.7 ± 2.85	0.3 ± 0.33 d	16.8 ± 0.26 a
Significance						
Soil Type (ST)		**	NS	**	**	**
Fertilization (F)		**	NS	**	**	**
ST x F		NS	NS	NS	*	**

In each column, different letters indicate significant differences; NS, *, and ** refer to not significant or significant at $p < 0.05$, and $p < 0.01$.

Cumulative N₂O emission was significantly affected by the main factors. The highest values were recorded in clay and loam soils (30.75 mg m⁻², on mean) but only the one was different from sandy soil (25.75 mg m⁻²). As expected, the highest value of N₂O emission was found under Min fertilization, while the lowest one in the control; the two organic strategies were not statistically different between them (Fig.2).

Conclusions

Our results highlight that in the sandy soil the wheat yield reached the highest values, particularly under digestate fertilization and, interestingly, the lower cumulative N₂O emission. However, in sandy soil, the protein content of kernels was lower, similar to what that recorded for the fertilization with digestate. Obviously, further research is needed for confirming these results.

Literature

Smith P. et al. 2007. Agriculture. In: B. Metz, O.R. Davidson, P.R. Bosch, R. Dave, L.A. Meyer (Eds.), Climate Change 2007: Mitigation. Contribution of Working Group III to the 4th Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change, Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, pp. 497-540.

Figure 2. Cumulative N₂O emission in to types of soil and nitrogen fertilization strategies.

Yield and Quality Comparison of Hard Common Wheat Varieties in NE Italy in the Dry Year 2022

Anna Panozzo¹, Simone Piotto¹, Riccardo Boscaro¹, Giuseppe Barion¹, Mirko Volpato², Teofilo Vamerali¹

¹ DAFNAE, Univ. Padova, IT, anna.panozzo@unipd.it; simone.piotto.1@phd.unipd.it; riccardo.boscaro@unipd.it; giuseppe.barion@unipd.it; teofilo.vamerali@unipd.it

² Grandi Molini Italiani S.p.a., Marghera, Venezia, IT, MVolpato@grandimolini.it

Introduction

Common wheat is the most cultivated staple crop worldwide, and the Italian production covers only 43% of national needs (ISTAT, 2021). Besides, the stability of wheat production has been reduced in the last decades due to the negative effects of climate change, with increasing incidence of extreme weather events (i.e., high temperatures, drought, floods) which lead to yield and quality impairments Huzsvai et al., 2022; Mirón et al., 2023). In this framework, there is urgent need to preserve wheat productivity, in order to feed a growing world population, but also to ensure high-protein contents in the grains, that are requested by baking industries. The screening of current wheat varieties, including the most recently released, is a relevant tool to identify the most tolerant to abiotic stresses and climate change constraints, able to ensure farmers with high yield and quality levels.

This study was carried out within the Agritech National Research Center financed by the European Union – NextGenerationEU (PIANO NAZIONALE DI RIPRESA E RESILIENZA, PNRR – MISSIONE 4 COMPONENTE 2, INVESTIMENTO 1.4 - D.D. 1032 17/06/2022, CN00000022) and aimed at comparing the yield and quality of four hard common wheat varieties, among the most cultivated in NE Italy, in order to identify the most tolerant to the current context of climate change.

Materials and Methods

The experiment was conducted at the experimental farm “Lucio Toniolo” of the University of Padova, at Legnaro, during the 2021-2022 growing season involving four hard wheat varieties (*Triticum aestivum* L.): ACA 360 (Consorzio Agrario del Nordest, Verona, Italy), Criterium (ISTA, Potenza, Italy), Aurelius (Saatbau, Leonding, Austria) and Rebelde (ApsovSementi, Voghera, Italy). Sowing took place on 28 October 2021, with a density of 500 seeds m⁻², and 12.5 cm apart rows; harvest occurred on 20 June 2022 for ACA360, and a few days later on 28 June for the others. Pre-sowing fertilization consisted in 32 kg ha⁻¹ of N, 96 kg ha⁻¹ of both P₂O₅ and kg ha⁻¹ of K₂O (as ternary fertilizer) incorporated into the soil through harrowing. During the crop cycle, dress application of N occurred twice for a total amount of 176 kg N ha⁻¹. Monthly air temperature was higher than the 10-year historical mean in May and June (+2.4 and +1.8°C respectively). The crop received only 289 mm of precipitation, compared to 595 mm of the historical mean, with spring and early summer months being the driest. Wheat grain yield was revealed at maturity over a 2-m² sampling area for each replicate and variety, with 3 replicates for each variety (n = 3). The testing weight of grains was determined with the equipment GAC 500XT (Dickey-John, Auburn, IL-USA). The quality parameters were measured by Near-Infrared Spectroscopy (NIRS) technology with Infratec-1241 instrumentation (Foss Analytical, Hillerød, Denmark) and rheological properties by the Brabender farinograph and the Chopin alveograph.

Results

Grain yield reached values ranging between 6.5 and 8.8 t ha⁻¹, with var. Criterium and Rebelde revealing the highest potential (> 8.5 t ha⁻¹), as supported by the highest harvest index (HI) > 0.35 (Figure 1). ACA 360 showed the highest TGW, i.e., 48 g, largely above the other varieties (average 33 g). Both ACA 360 and Rebelde also had the highest testing weight (86.9 kg hl⁻¹).

Figure 1. Grain quantitative parameters (means \pm S.E.; n=3) in the four investigated wheat varieties. TKW: thousand kernel weight; HI: harvest index. DW: dry weight. Differences for Tukey's HSD test at $p \leq 0.05$.

The highest grain protein content was found in ACA 360, with 18.4% DW, followed by Aurelius and Rebelde (15.5%), and lastly Criterium (14.2%). Only ACA 360 achieved values of rheological parameters in line with the standards for hard type wheat, while the other varieties showed very low values (Table 1), likely due to marmorated stink bug attacks, that affected grain maturation despite the targeted insecticide treatment at flowering time.

Table 1. Grain protein content (GP) and dough rheological properties in the four tested wheat varieties.

Variety	GP (% DW)	W	P/L	Stability (min)	Water absorption 500 UB (%)
ACA 360	18.4	532	0.69	30.6	63.4
Aurelius	15.5	176	0.18	11.3	52.4
Criterium	14.2	109	0.16	9.0	53.6
Rebelde	15.5	206	0.23	11.9	54.1

Conclusions

There is an increasing interest for hard type varieties of common wheat, as requested by the baking industries. The screening of the best available genetic materials is crucial to identify the most suitable varieties to each environment. Here we demonstrate that in a very dry season var. Rebelde, already known in the most productive areas of north Italy, as well as the recently released var. Criterium, are promising varieties in order to combine high yield and quality under drought and heat stress during spring and summer. Attention should be paid to crop protection against the marmorated stink bug for preserving adequate rheological properties of the dough. ACA 360 revealed to be a short-season variety of superior quality (W being higher than Manitoba), although somewhat at the expense of productivity.

Literature

- Huzsvai L. et al. 2022. Response of winter wheat (*Triticum aestivum* L.) yield to the increasing weather fluctuations in a continental region of four-season climate. *Agronomy*, 12: 314.
- Mirón I. et al. 2023. The influence of climate change on food production and food safety. *Environ. Res.*, 216: 114674.

What Happens to Soil Organic Carbon in Venetian Low-lying Plain? Insight from a Long-term Experiment

Ilaria Piccoli, Riccardo Polese, Nicola Dal Ferro, Francesco Morari, Antonio Berti

DAFNAE, Univ. Padova, IT, ilaria.piccoli@unipd.it

Introduction

Nowadays the importance of increasing SOC in the soil gains growing attention due to its double function of restoring soil fertility (Tiessen et al., 1994) and mitigating climate change (Chabbi et al., 2017). As also demonstrated by the attention drawn by the COP21 initiative of “4 per 1000” (Minasny et al., 2017) increasing and/or maintaining the SOC stock in word soils is now more than ever a central issue (Poulton et al., 2018; Rumpel et al., 2018; Soussana et al., 2019). Consequently, understanding the factors affecting and/or limiting the C sequestration into soil might play a key role in sustaining crop production, on the one side, and, protecting environmental health, on the other. Nevertheless, it is now accepted by the whole scientific community that soil has a finite capacity to store SOC and that its reaction to C input is not linear, nor infinite but tends toward a saturation level. The carbon saturation threshold is considered soil- and land use-dependent, being greater in natural environments than in cultivated soil or increasing with the fraction of swelling clay minerals (Six et al., 2002; Stewart et al., 2007). Within this context, the aim of this study was to investigate the potentialities to maintain/improve the SOC stock of the two C input that are mostly available in the Veneto region i.e., crop residue and dry poultry manure using a long-term experiment started in 1966.

Materials and Methods

The LTE used for this study is located at the experimental farm of Padova University (Veneto Region, NE Italy 45° 21 N; 11° 58 E; 6 m a.s.l.) on a Fluvi-Calcaric Cambisol (FAO-UNESCO 2008) with a silt loam texture. The trial, which began in 1966, has been conducted on 60 plots of 35 m² each. The experimental treatments were derived from the factorial combination of three crop residue managements (previous crop residue incorporation “RI”, previous crop residue incorporation added with 1 t ha⁻¹ of dried poultry manure “RI + PM”, and residues removal “RR”) with five levels of nitrogen fertilisation (0, 60, 120, 180, and 240 kg ha⁻¹ y⁻¹) in a randomized block design with 4 replications. The PM was applied by burying it during shallow disk harrowing immediately after harvest providing about 60 kg N ha⁻¹. Before 1984, the trial was conducted with maize (*Zea mays* L.) in monoculture. Thereafter, a variable rotation scheme was used. Soil sampling was performed in 2020 at the end of the winter wheat growing season. 60 undisturbed soil cores were collected in the middle of each plot among the 0-60 cm soil profile through a hydraulic sampler, subsequently cut into two layers (0-30 cm and 30-60 cm) and measured for bulk density according to the core method. At the same positions, also 0-30 and 30-60 cm disturbed soil samples (120 in total) were collected, air-dried, and analysed for SOC through an elemental analyser. The 0-30 cm SOC stock obtained in 2020 was then compared with the pre-existent soil data series (1966, 1982, 1986, 1993, 2006) to evaluate its evolution.

The same data series was used to estimate the degree of soil C saturation according to the model proposed by Hassink (1997), Dexter et al. (2008) and a few selected from Six et al. (2002). In brief, the hereafter called “Hassink” and “Dexter” models estimates the maximums storable SOC as 1/20 of the fines₂₀ (i.e., particle < 20 µm) and 1/10 of the clay (i.e., particle < 2 µm), respectively. Among the 11 regression models proposed by Six et al. (2002) we tested the ones more suitable for the studied experimental design, i.e., the models involving a cultivated ecosystem with prevalence of 1:1 clay mineral considering the protection capacity of both particles < 20 and < 50 µm.

Data belonging to the 2020 sampling campaign were analysed with a linear mixed-effect model based on a restricted maximum likelihood estimation method treating crop residue management, N level, and their interaction as fixed while the block as a random effect. Post-hoc pairwise comparisons of least-squares

mean were performed, using the Tukey method to adjust for multiple comparisons. Statistical analyses were performed with SAS software (SAS Institute Inc. Cary, NC, USA), 5.1 version.

Results

Preliminary results showed that higher 0-60 cm SOC stock was found after 54 years of the experiment when residues were incorporated into the soil compared to residue removal (75.0 vs 69.0 t ha⁻¹) while poultry manure had a negligible effect. Comparing the 0-30 cm SOC stock with pre-existent data series, a general decreasing trend was observed from the start of the experiment in 1966 up to 1986, being greater in residual removal (-8.6 t ha⁻¹) than residual incorporation (-4.8 t ha⁻¹, irrespective of poultry manure addition). In 2020, the difference between the above-mentioned systems was 4.1 t ha⁻¹ corresponding to a 2.2 ‰ which is lower than what was suggested by the 4 per 1000 initiative. This SOC stock attributed to residue retention arose in response to 141 t C ha⁻¹ residue, resulting in a 0.1% yearly conversion rate that is sensibly lower than what is generally reported in the literature.

The soil C saturation exhibited a declining trend from the starting of the experiment until now in all tested models. Higher saturation level was estimated by Six (1:1 0-20 µm) model (average: 47%) followed progressively by Six (cultivated 0-20 µm) (average: 45%), Dexter (average: 41%), Six (cultivated 0-50 µm) (average: 39%), Six (1:1 0-50 µm) (average: 34%) and Hassink model (average: 30%). Despite some differences in the absolute C saturation degree, the variation between the start of the experiment and 2020 always amounted to about 19%.

Conclusions

Crop residue retention demonstrated to scarcely increase the SOC stock, being far from the 4 per 1000 target, therefore, an alternative use (e.g., bioenergy production) of at least part of crop residues is conceivable in temperate climate for a more efficient C cycle.

The studied soil was demonstrated also to be far from C saturation, being in the 30-47% degree of saturation range. Therefore, specific studies on how both organic and inorganic (i.e., carbonates) C fractions related to different soil aggregates and aggregate mineralization are namely requested.

Literature

- Hassink J. 1997. The capacity of soils to preserve organic C and N by their association with clay and silt particles, *Plant Soil*, 191(1), 77–87.
- Minasny B. et al. 2017. Soil carbon 4 per mille. *Geoderma*, 292: 59–86.
- Poulton P. et al. 2018. Major limitations to achieving “4 per 1000” increases in soil organic carbon stock in temperate regions: Evidence from long-term experiments at Rothamsted Research, United Kingdom. *Glob. Chang. Biol.*, 24: 2563–2584.
- Rumpel C. et al. 2018. “4 per 1,000” initiative will boost soil carbon for climate and food security. *Nature*, 553: 27.
- Six, J. et al. 2002. Stabilization mechanisms of soil organic matter: implications for C-saturation of soils, *Plant Soil*, 241(2): 155–176.
- Soussana J.F. et al. 2019. Matching policy and science: Rationale for the ‘4 per 1000 - soils for food security and climate’ initiative. *Soil Tillage Res.*, 188: 3–15.
- Stewart C.E. et al. 2007. Soil carbon saturation: concept, evidence and evaluation. *Biogeochemistry*, 86: 19–31.
- Tiessen H. et al. 1994. The role of soil organic matter in sustaining soil fertility. *Nature*, 371: 783–785.

Impact of Alley Poplar Silvoarable Systems with Soybean on Microclimatic Variables

Simone Piotto¹, Anna Panozzo¹, Gaia Pasqualotto², Vinicio Carraro², Giuseppe Barion¹, Stefano Nale³, Lorenzo Furlan³, Tommaso Anfodillo², Teofilo Vamerali¹

¹ DAFNAE, Univ. Padova, IT, simone.piotto.1@phd.unipd.it; anna.panozzo@unipd.it; giuseppe.barion@unipd.it; teofilo.vamerali@unipd.it

² TESAF, Univ. Padova, IT, gaia.pasqualotto@unipd.it; vinicio.carraro@unipd.it; tommaso.anfodillo@unipd.it

³ Agenzia Veneta per l'Innovazione nel Settore Primario – Veneto Agricoltura, Legnaro, IT, stefano.nale@venetoagricoltura.org; lorenzo.furlan@venetoagricoltura.org

Introduction

Given the increasing concern on food supply for the next years due to the growing population and the negative impact of climate change, agricultural systems are required to adopt adequate mitigation strategies for preserving and/or improving productivity (Matocha et al., 2012). Among different solutions, agroforestry systems are capable to improve crop resilience using more efficiently the environmental resources and establishing a better microclimate for intercrops (Lasco et al., 2014). These benefits could be of interest in the Po valley in northern Italy, which is one of the most threatened area by climate shifts. In 2022, this area faced one of the worst droughts, and the frequency of prolonged drought periods is further increasing (Straffelini & Tarolli, 2023). The introduction of trees in arable land is expected to mitigate heat waves, provide a windbreak effect and reduce evapotranspiration for the intercrops, although the agroforestry design should be carefully defined. This study was carried out within the Agritech National Research Center financed by the European Union – NextGenerationEU (PIANO NAZIONALE DI RIPRESA E RESILIENZA, PNRR – MISSIONE 4 COMPONENTE 2, INVESTIMENTO 1.4 - D.D. 1032 17/06/2022, CN00000022) and aimed at monitoring environmental parameters, such as PAR, air temperature, VPD and soil water potential, at different distances from a poplar row, and the effects on soybean yield.

Materials and Methods

The microclimatic variables were recorded from end May to end August 2022 in a silvoarable alley-cropping system with different poplar clones (*Populus × euroamericana*) type HES (Higher Environmental Sustainability) at their fifth year of cultivation at the “Sasse Rami” pilot farm of Veneto Agricoltura, in Ceregno (Rovigo, NE Italy, 45° 05' 06" N, 11° 87' 66" W; 0.5-1 m a.s.l.). The poplars were arranged in N-S oriented rows 40 m apart, placed along the drainage ditches (~150 m long), with 6 m among trees along the row, allowing for a density of ~40 trees ha⁻¹. Environmental parameters and soybean yield have been assessed at different distances along transects orthogonal to the tree rows both at east (E) and west (W) sides, named ¼H, ½H, H and FS, where H=tree height (12 m) and FS=middle of the inter-row (i.e., 20 m; as a proxy of full sun controls). PAR was determined in both sides at ½H, H and FS by SQ-202X-SS (Apogee Instruments, Inc., Logan, UT, USA), air temperature and VPD in both sides at ½H and FS by ATMOS14 (METER Group, Inc., Pullman, WA, USA), soil water potential in the west side at ½H, H and FS at 0,3 m and 0,6 m depth by TEROS21 (METER Group, Inc., Pullman, WA, USA). Soybean yield (var. Nirvana; ERSA – Gorizia, Italy) was determined in both sides and all the above-mentioned distances. Statistical analyses were carried out with R studio v. 1.4, using the Tukey's HSD test for means separation ($P \leq 0.05$). Hourly microclimatic data were averaged over the June-August period.

Results

When compared to FS, PAR was lower at west from 9:00 to 11:00 in H (-45%; $p \leq 0.05$) and from 10:00 to 13:00 in ½H (-51%; $p \leq 0.05$), while at east from 15:00 to 16:00 in H (-63%; $p \leq 0.05$) and from 11:00 to 16:00 in ½H, with the highest differences from 13:00 to 14:00 (-27%; $p \leq 0.05$) (Fig. 2). Late in the afternoon and only at west in early morning, values were higher in ½H and in H vs. FS.

Soil water potential at 30 cm of depth from June 1 to August 15, was significantly lower by 34% at H and by 10% at 1/2H vs. FS (-698 Pa in H, -959 Pa in 1/2H vs. -1062 Pa in FS; $p \leq 0.01$) (Fig. 2). The moderate differences in 1/2H are due to shading and also to lower crop development and water demand.

VPD and air temperature differences between 1/2H and FS were lower during the central hours of the day, in the morning at west, and in the afternoon at east of the poplar rows, especially in the hottest days. From 19:00 to 8:00 and mainly in early morning, air temperature was slightly higher at 1/2H, with the highest differences in the hottest days (Fig. 2).

Soybean yield was comparable to C in H (-1%), slightly lower in 1/2H (-11%) and lower in 1/4H at east (-24%) and significantly lower at west (-64%; $p \leq 0.001$).

Figure 2: June to August hourly average PAR (above left), soil water potential at 0,3 m and 0,6 m (above right) at 1/2H, H and FS, hourly VPD difference 1/2H vs. FS (below left), and hourly air temperature difference 1/2H vs. FS.

Conclusions

Due to shading, regularly repeated N-S poplar rows positively affect microclimatic variables by lowering air temperature and VPD during the day and by increasing soil moisture, although penalising PAR availability in the morning at west and in the afternoon at the east. However, soybean yield was only slightly impaired compared to other studies, significantly only in the strict neighbouring at west of trees. These results demonstrate that a summer crop like soybean is only partially negatively affected by limited solar radiation in a very dry year like 2022.

Literature

Matocha J. et al. 2012. Integrating Climate Change Adaptation and Mitigation Through Agroforestry and Ecosystem Conservation. *Agroforestry - The Future of Global Land Use*. 105-126.

Lasco R.D. et al. 2014. Climate risk adaptation by smallholder farmers: the roles of trees and agroforestry. *Curr. Opin. Environ. Sust.*, 6: 83-88.

Straffelini E. and Tarolli P. 2023. Climate change-induced aridity is affecting agriculture in Northeast Italy. *Agric. Syst.*, 208: 103647.

Yield and Yield Components of Alternative Crops in a Climate-Changing Mediterranean Environment

Cataldo Pulvento, Luigi Tedone, Claudia Ruta, Giuseppe De Mastro

DISSPA, Univ. Bari, IT, cataldo.pulvento@uniba.it

Introduction

Climate change is expected to have increasing significant effects on Mediterranean agriculture, impacting crop production, water availability, and overall agricultural sustainability. Precipitation patterns and air temperatures are being affected, leading to increased frequency and intensity of droughts and extreme rainfall events. These changes can negatively impact crop yields and increase the risk of soil erosion and desertification (Giannakopoulos et al., 2009). Heat stress can reduce crop yields, affect fruit quality, and disrupt pollination processes. Moreover, increased temperatures can contribute to the spread of pests and diseases, further impacting agricultural productivity (IPCC 2014). In general climate change is expected to exacerbate water scarcity issues in the Mediterranean region and it may result in shifts in the suitability of certain crops and agricultural practices. Areas that were traditionally suitable for certain crops may become less favorable, while new regions may become suitable for cultivation. This necessitates adaptive measures, such as crop diversification and changes in farming systems, to maintain agricultural productivity (Quiroga et al., 2016).

Resilient crops possess traits that enable them to thrive in challenging environments, such as drought tolerance, heat resistance, and disease resilience. These traits can help Mediterranean farmers adapt to the changing climate conditions and maintain agricultural productivity. Some species, such as Quinoa (*Chenopodium quinoa* Willd.) and Sorghum (*Sorghum bicolor* (L.) Moench), have characteristics of resilience to climate change. Their ability to adapt to diverse environmental conditions, including drought, heat, and poor soil quality, contributes to their resilience and makes them valuable for agricultural systems striving for climate change adaptation. In 2022 a field was carried out in Policoro (MT) in order to evaluate the yield performance of some varieties of quinoa and sorghum, under rainfed conditions.

Materials and Methods

The field trial was carried out at UNIBA didactic-experimental station "E. Pantanelli" in Policoro (MT) (40.13 N, 16.40 E, 31 m asl). This site is characterized by a Mediterranean climate according to the De Martonne classification with an average annual rainfall of 560 mm, distributed mainly in autumn and winter and mild temperatures in autumn with a maximum temperature reaching 40-42 °C in summer. The soil has a clayey texture. Four varieties of quinoa and nine varieties of sorghum were tested under rainfed conditions using a randomized block experimental design with three replicates.

Results

Tables 1 and 2 show the main production data of the crops. For sorghum, the highest weight in grains was recorded by the Aralba variety, while for quinoa, Puno and Keykorn varieties showed the best performances in terms of grains produced. The

Figure 1 - Field trials in Policoro

production data will be statistically analyzed together with the data from the second year of the trial.

Table 1. Grain yield, dry biomass, height and diameter of sorghum varieties in Policoro.

Variety	Plant height (cm)	Stem diameter (cm)	Seed yield (g plant ⁻¹)	Dry biomass (g plant ⁻¹)
ARSENIO	135.7a	2.3a	132.8c	332.1c
ICEBERG	129.1b	2.1b	122.5c	252.5c
GGOLD	111.2c	2.0b	200.8a	327.2c
ARALBA	140.3a	2.5a	218.9a	560.9a
HERALD	120.8b	2.1b	126.9c	197.5d
ARABESK	139.2a	2.1b	127.6c	323.8c
ARTIST	124.1b	2.3a	152.8b	390.0b
<i>p-value</i>	<0.05	<0.05	<0.05	<0.05

Values followed by different letters are significantly different among treatments according to LSD test at $p < 0.05$

Table 2: Grain yield, dry biomass, height and diameter of quinoa in Policoro.

Variety	Plant height (cm)	Stem diameter (cm)	Seed yield (g plant ⁻¹)	Dry biomass (g plant ⁻¹)
TITICACA	133.0a	1.6a	18.9b	53.0a
VIKING	98.7b	1.5a	10.4b	31.5b
KEYKORN	139.0a	1.8a	24.7a	54.2a
PUNO	142.8a	1.6a	30.8a	47.8a
<i>p-value</i>	<0.05	<0.05	<0.05	<0.05

Values followed by different letters are significantly different among treatments according to LSD test at $p < 0.05$

Conclusions

The production results of first experimental year showed good adaptability to the trial area of all tested sorghum and quinoa varieties. Although promising, the data will be statistically analyzed together with those deriving from the second year of experimentation in order to confirm if grain sorghum and quinoa can effectively represent a crop alternative for Mediterranean cropping systems affected by problems related to climate change.

Literature

Giannakopoulos C. et al. 2009. Climatic changes and associated impacts in the Mediterranean resulting from a 2 °C global warming. *Glob. Planet. Change*, 68(3): 209-224.

IPCC 2014. *Climate Change 2014: Impacts, Adaptation, and Vulnerability. Part B: Regional Aspects. Contribution of Working Group II to the Fifth Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change.*

Quiroga S. et al. 2016. Impacts of climate change on European agriculture: results of a case study with potato. *Agron. Sustain. Dev.*, 36(1): 7.

Adoption of Conservation Agriculture in Winter Wheat (*Triticum Aestivum* L.) with the Aim of Saving Water, Protecting the Environment, Improving Soil Health and Reducing CO₂ Emissions

Maria Florencia Ribero¹, Antonio Berti¹, Michele Pisante²

¹ Dep. Agronomy, Food, Natural Resources, Animals and Environment, Univ. Padova, IT, mariaflorescia.ribero@studenti.unpd.it; antonio.berti@unipd.it

² Dep. Bioscience and Technology for Food, Agriculture and Environment, Univ. Teramo, IT, mpisante@unite.it

Introduction

Today's world requires us to move our thinking towards a more holistic mentality, towards the total and global integration of food, economy, culture, planet, etc., no longer seeing agriculture as a loose link. In this way we are obliged to recognise the strengths and weaknesses of current food production systems that require urgent modifications to achieve efficiency and address the crises we face (Kassam et al., 2022)

The importance of CA lies in the fact that in the face of soil degradation it is presented as a sustainable alternative. The agronomic practices applied in conservation agriculture are based on 3 interrelated principles such as minimal or no soil tillage in all farming operations involved, implementation of permanent vegetation cover, and finally diversification of the cropping system (Kassam et al., 2019). There is a wide variety of studies regarding conservative agriculture, but the issue of the transition period, the initial period when crop yields are below those of conventional agriculture, is not very clear. This period is a cause of low adoption of the practice by farmers.

To explore this issue in this project, studies were conducted to determine the effects of no-tillage on soil quality and quantitative and qualitative yields of winter wheat (*Triticum aestivum* L.).

Materials and Methods

The experiment took place at the Experimental Farm "Lucio Toniolo", in Legnaro, PD (NE Italy, 45° 21 N; 11° 58 E; 6 m a.s.l.). The soil is a fluvio-limestone cambisol with a silt loam texture (FAO-UNESCO, 2008). An experiment comparing three types of tillage (minimum tillage (MT), direct seeding (DS) and conventional tillage (CT)) was set up in 2018. The experimental design is a randomised block design, with a total area of 2 hectares (1 hectare per block). In 2021/2022 the wheat crop was sown on 27 October. The accumulated rainfall during the crop cycle was 331.4 mm, and the average of the last 60 years for the crop cycle period is 605.55 mm and as for the average of the maximum and minimum temperature were 19.4 °C and 9.2 °C respectively during the crop year 2021/2022, and the average of the last 60 years of the maximum and minimum temperature is 17.5 °C and 8.3 °C respectively.

During the crop cycle, a series of measures were taken to monitor the development of the wheat crop. Three indices were measured:

Normalised Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI), Leaf Area Index (LAI) and SPAD, as an indicator of chlorophyll content. NDVI was measured with the Crop Circle (Holland Scientific, Nebraska, USA), LAI with the SunScan (Delta-T Devices, UK) and chlorophyll with the SPAD 502 Plus. All three measurements were carried out from the flowering phase until harvest (5 times). After harvest, for the analysis of total nitrogen and organic carbon, samples were taken in 18 points of the experimental field, at a depth of 0-20 cm corresponding to the arable layer. These results were used for comparison with those obtained in 2008 on the same field, where no-tillage management had not yet been implemented. The fields were sampled in the 0-30 cm layer taking 40 samples per field (block) on a regular grid. Up to 2017 the fields were conducted with CT, with the same crops and agricultural practices. This allows us to understand the transition process from one management practice to another.

Results

Considering measurements taken during the crop cycle, no significant differences ($p>0.05$) were observed between managements types for NDVI, LAI and Chlorophyll test. Also, wheat yield not showed significant differences ($p>0.05$) between treatments, with an average of 6.39 t ha^{-1} for MT, 6.39 t ha^{-1} for CT and 5.83 t ha^{-1} for NT.

The results obtained in the sampling carried out in 2022 after harvest of the wheat crop, showed significant differences ($p<0.05$) for total Kjeldahl nitrogen (NKT) for NT compared to CT, with a mean of 0.104% for CT and 0.120% for NT, MT had a mean of 0.114% NKT (table 1). For organic carbon, a significant difference was also obtained for NT compared to TC. The mean for NT was 0.897%, and a mean of 0.705% for TC and 0.828% for MT in the organic carbon analysis (table 2).

Table 1. Fisher (LSD). Analysis of differences between categories with 95% confidence interval for the percentage of total nitrogen (TKN %), 2022.

Treatments	Means	Groups	
NT	0.104	A	
MT	0.096	A	B
CT	0.084	B	

Table 2. Fisher (LSD). Analysis of differences between categories with 95% confidence interval for organic carbon (%), 2022.

Treatments	Means	Groups	
NT	0.897	A	
MT	0.828	A	B
CT	0.705	B	

Considering the soil analyses conducted in 2008 as a baseline prior to the introduction of the different tillage treatments, the field mean for organic carbon was 0.728 %, which compared to 2022 shows an increase of 23% for NT, 13% for MT and a decrease of 3% for TC.

Conclusions

In a year with extreme climatic conditions such as extreme temperatures and low and poorly distributed rainfall, the type of management showed no differences in terms of vegetation indices and yield.

On the other hand, after only 6 years from the introduction of CA, the soil begin to show an increase in organic carbon and nitrogen TKN with the reduction of tillage intensity, with no-tillage having the greatest impact.

Literature

FAO-UNESCO, 2008. Soil map of the world. Revised Legend. ROMA.

Kassam A. et al. 2022. Successful Experiences and Lessons from Conservation Agriculture Worldwide. *Agronomy*, 12: 769.

Kassam A. et al. 2019. Global spread of Conservation Agriculture. *Int. J. Environ. Stud.*, 76: 29–51.

Leaf Gas Exchange of Sicilian Wheat Landraces Under Contrasting Soil Water Content

Giorgio Testa¹, Alessio Scandurra¹, Paolo Caruso¹, Valeria Cafaro¹, Cristina Patanè², Salvatore Luciano Cosentino¹, Sebastiano Andrea Corinzia¹

¹ Di3A, Univ. Catania, IT, andrea.corinzia@unict.it

² CNR-IBE, Sede Secondaria di Catania, IT

Introduction

In Sicily, more than fifty local populations of durum (*Triticum durum*) and bread wheat (*T. aestivum*) and bread wheat have been preserved by scientific institutions and by local farmers, despite their low productivity, because of their favourable agronomic characteristics which give tolerance or resistance to biotic stress (pathogens and weeds) and abiotic stress, leading to the adaptability to the local environment where these populations have been selected.

Water availability is the main limiting factor for wheat production. Net photosynthesis is the main driver of dry matter accumulation and consequently of grain yield, and it is highly sensitive to water limitation and temperature stresses. The object of the present work is to evaluate the gas exchanges of several Sicilian ancient landraces of durum and bread wheat in comparison with commercial varieties in organic and conventional management and under irrigated and dry conditions.

Materials and Methods

The field trial was carried out at the experimental farm of the University of Catania (37° 24' N., 15° 03' E., 10 m a.s.l.), in a representative area of Sicilian cereal farming, in a typical Xerofluvents soil with a preponderantly clayey texture. The experimental design was a factorial split-plot design with three experimental factors and three replicates. The irrigation was the experimental factor assigned to the main plots and had two levels: 100% of maximum crop evapotranspiration (ET_m) restoration and rainfed. The second factor was the agronomic management, with two categories, organic and conventional. The third experimental factor was the genotype with eighteen categories: twelve local Sicilian populations of durum wheat (“Bidi”, “Castiglione Glabro”, “Giustalisa”, “Margherito”, “Perciasacchi”, “Realforte”, “Ruscia”, “Russello – Priziusa”, “Russello Ibleo”, “Timilia”, “Tripolino” e “Urria”), one local Sicilian populations of bread wheat (“Maiorca”), one old variety of durum wheat (“Senatore Cappelli”), three commercial variety of durum wheat (“Core”, “Mongibello” e “Amedeo”) and one commercial variety of bread wheat (“Bologna”).

Sowing was carried out on January 13, 2021 with a target sowing density of 400 plants m⁻².

The fertilisation was performed before sowing applying 54 kg ha⁻¹ of N as ammonium sulphate and 138 kg/ha-1 P₂O₅, and just before stem elongation phase applying 26 kg ha⁻¹ of N as ammonium nitrate in the plots managed according to the conventional management. The organic plots were fertilised applying the same amount of nitrogen as organic fertiliser in pellet with 7% of N and 13% of P₂O₅ before sowing. Weeding has been performed only in the conventional management plots. Physiological measurements have been carried out weekly from flowering until full ripening using the LCi-SD Portable Photosynthesis system (ADC BioScientific Ltd.), which measures net photosynthesis rate (μmol CO₂ m⁻² s⁻¹), transpiration rate (mmol H₂O m⁻² s⁻¹) and stomatal conductance (mol H₂O m⁻² s⁻¹) on the basis of CO₂ and H₂O gas exchange. Instant water use efficiency (iWUE) has been calculated as the ratio of net photosynthesis and transpiration.

Results

Wheat responded to the different levels of water availability in the soil, showing lower net photosynthesis rates and lower iWUE in rainfed conditions, as a consequence of the reduced water availability (Figures 1 and 2). Conventional management generally improved net photosynthesis rates, with some exceptions (Figure 1). The commercial bread wheat variety “Bologna” showed the highest net photosynthesis rate,

followed by the ancient landraces “Realforte” and “Margherito”. Many ancient wheat landraces showed higher iWUE than commercial varieties, especially in rainfed conditions. Higher iWUE were achieved in irrigated conditions and in organic management (Figure 2).

Figure 1. Net photosynthesis rate ($\mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$) trends for 2 water restoration levels (Rainfed and Irrigated),

2 agronomic management (Conventional and Organic) and for 18 wheat varieties. Red segments represent the variety mean.

Figure 2. Instant water use efficiency (IWUE) ($\mu\text{mol CO}_2 \text{ mmol}^{-1} \text{ H}_2\text{O}$) trends for 2 water restoration levels (Rainfed and Irrigated), 2 agronomic management (Conventional and Organic) and for 18 wheat varieties. Red segments represent the variety mean.

Conclusions

The ancient Sicilian wheat landraces showed similar net photosynthesis rate and higher iWUE in comparison with the commercial varieties, especially in rainfed conditions, suggesting their higher suitability for low soil moisture availability that is common in the Mediterranean drought-prone areas.

Can the Adoption of Conservation Agriculture Actually Increase the Soil Carbon Content?

Antonio Troccoli¹, Salvatore Baiano², Michele Rinaldi¹, Luigi Morra²

¹ CREA-CI, Foggia, IT, antonio.troccoli@crea.gov.it

² CREA-CI, Caserta, IT, luigi.morra@crea.gov.it

Introduction

None or Minimum soil disturbance, crop diversification, and permanent soil cover represent the three main principles of conservation agriculture (CA). The CA adoption can have several positive effects: protect the environment, reduce the impacts of climate change on agricultural systems (adaptation) as well as contribute to the reduction greenhouse gases (GHG) emissions through a more sustainable approach to agricultural practices (mitigation). A prolonged study on the sole practice of no-tillage (NT) in conditions of continuous cultivation of durum wheat led to slight losses in yield, but not in the quality of the wheat or semolina, and to a positive judgment on the sustainability of the agronomic system (Troccoli et al., 2015), especially in the upper soil layer, in term of soil organic carbon (SOC) increase (+13.2% compared to the tillage system) (Troccoli et al., 2022). No-till or minimal tillage, in combination with other regenerative practices, improve soil aggregation, water infiltration and retention, and carbon sequestration (Hobbs et al., 2008). Furthermore, permanent soil cover combined with no-tillage promoted an accumulation of organic carbon in surface layers and reduced soil organic matter losses, resulting in a promising strategy for maintaining or even increasing soil carbon and nitrogen stocks (Lal, 2005). No-tillage and residues management are widely considered the most important conservation agriculture practices as alternatives to conventional ploughing and tillage disturbance (Gristina et al., 2018). We report an assessment of the change in SOC content and soil aggregate stability when switching from a simple NT system (without cover crop rotation and residue management) to a full CA system.

Materials and Methods

The trial has been started in 1994/1995 growing season and it is still in progress at the experimental farm (41°27'57" N; 15°30'20" E; 80 m a.s.l.) of CREA-CI of Foggia (Apulia, Southern Italy), a typically Mediterranean environment. The soil has a clay-loam texture and is classified as Typic Calcixerpt. Main profile soil traits were 27.8% clay, 28.7% sand, 43.5% silt; pH 8.7; 11.8 g kg⁻¹ total C. Mean long-term rainfall of the site is 479 mm. Mean air temperatures are 12.2 °C in fall, 8.2 °C in winter, and 17.6 °C in spring. In 1994 an experimental area of 12,000 m² was divided into two contiguous areas of 6,000 m², one devoted to no-tillage management (NT) and direct soil seeding using suitable seeding machinery (Gaspardo Directa), while the other area was kept on conventional tillage (CT), carrying out moldboard ploughing to 30 cm depth followed by a disc-harrow and flexible harrow for the seedbed preparation. Until to 2008/2009 growing season, in both agronomic systems, durum wheat was continuously grown, and wheat straws were removed from field. In NT system, the weed control was performed using glyphosate at a rate of 720 g of active ingredient ha⁻¹ one week before sowing. For seedbed preparation, 36 kg N ha⁻¹ plus 42 kg P ha⁻¹, as diammonium phosphate (18-46-00), were spread on the CT field and incorporated into the soil with secondary tillage, while in NT area the same fertilizer was spread and left on the surface. Top dressing (64 kg N ha⁻¹ as ammonium nitrate) was applied in both plots at 21-29 tillering stage, according to BBCH scale (Meier et al., 2009). Starting from the 2009/2010 growing season, the two areas destined to NT and CT systems were divided in two sub-areas, each hosting or not a biennial rotation with cover crop *Vicia faba* L. var. *minor*. The cover crop was terminated at the full flowering stage and the biomass left on surface or incorporated into the soil in the NT or CT system, respectively. After harvest, wheat straw residue in the four areas was managed similarly. For the soil analysis, on November 2022, each of the four areas was partitioned in three sub-areas where soil was sampled by collecting five soil cores. Two soil layers were considered: 0-10 cm and 10-30 cm. SOC was determined by the Walkley-Black colorimetric method (FAO,

2020). Soil aggregates stability in the 0-10 layer was estimated by measuring the mean weight diameter (MWD) of aggregates by the Wet Sieving Apparatus model 08.13 (Royal Eijkelkamp, Giesbeek, NL).

Results

After the first fifteen years from the beginning of the trial, the NT and CT systems showed a significant increase in SOC value in both soil layers, but more consistent in the NT system (Tab. 1). The introduction of green manure in crop rotation and residue retention on field enhanced the increase of SOC, but only in combination with No Tillage. The management of wheat straw residues in the NT or CT monoculture system, as well as in the CT rotation, did not result in any change in the SOC value. The MWD instead was higher in the NT system than in CT irrespective from cover crop rotation.

Table 1 Effect of the combinations of tillage managements, cover crop rotation and crop residues retention in a durum wheat system on SOC content and MWD from 2009.

Period	Soil Layer (cm)	No Tillage (NT)		Conventional Tillage (CT)	
		Rotation	Monoculture	Monoculture	Rotation
Start of trial 1996	0-40	SOC (g kg ⁻¹)			
		No		No	
		-----Wheat straw removal-----			
2009	0-10		17.9±0.2	15.2±0.1	
	10-30		15.1±0.4	14.8±0.1	
	0-30		16.1±2.0	14.9±0.1	
		Yes		Yes	
		-----Residue retention -----			
2022	0-10	20.5±0.6	17.9±0.9	15.8±2.0	14.7±0.2
	10-30	15.7±0.8	14.2±1.4	14.1±0.1	15.0±0.4
	0-30	17.3±3.4	15.4±2.7	14.7±1.2	14.9±0.2
	0-10	1.43±0.29	1.30±0.47	0.45±0.09	0.66±0.13

Conclusions

The adoption of CA in a cereal system, especially in Mediterranean conditions, can represent a good opportunity to increase organic soil carbon, sequester it in the soil and improve soil structure.

Literature

- FAO. 2020. A protocol for measurement, monitoring, reporting and verification of soil organic carbon in agricultural landscapes – GSOC-MRV Protocol. Rome. <https://doi.org/10.4060/cb0509en>.
- Gristina L. et al. 2018. No-till durum wheat yield success probability in semi arid climate: A methodological framework. *Soil Tillage Res.*, 181: 29-36.
- Hobbs R.P. et al. 2008. The role of conservation agriculture in sustainable agriculture. *Philos. Trans. R. Soc. Lond., B, Biol. Sci.*, 363: 543-555.
- Lal R. 2005. Enhancing crop yields in the developing countries through restoration of the soil organic carbon pool in agricultural lands. *Land Degrad. Dev.*, 17: 197–209.
- Meier U. et al. 2009. The BBCH system to coding the phenological growth stages of plants-history and publications. *J. Cultiv. Plant.*, 2: 41-52.
- Troccoli A. et al. 2015. Is it appropriate to support the farmers for adopting conservation agriculture? Economic and environmental impact assessment. *Ital. J. Agron.*, 10: 661.
- Troccoli A. et al. 2022. Is it Sustainable to Cultivate a Monoculture of Durum Wheat with Prolonged No-Tillage Management? *Ann. Agric. Crop Sci.*, 7(1): 1105.

Sessione 5

**TRACCIABILITÀ - Promozione della
sicurezza, tracciabilità e tipicità delle
filieri**

ORAL PRESENTATIONS

Evaluation of Different Growing Systems on the Productive and Quality Features of Saffron (*Crocus sativus* L.)

Giovanni Dinelli, Mattia Alpi, Elettra Frassinetti, Ilaria Marotti

DISTAL, Univ. Bologna, IT, giovanni.dinelli@unibo.it, mattia.alpi3@unibo.it, elettra.frassinetti2@unibo.it, ilaria.marotti@unibo.it

Introduction

Saffron (*Crocus sativus* L.) is considered the most expensive spice on earth, reaching 10-30 euro per gram, due to its high labor cost (almost 400 hours for a kg). The spice is cultivated worldwide, mainly in middle east and for a small part also in the Mediterranean region. Despite its value, saffron cultivation has not significantly changed since thousands of years ago. The leader country on the production is Iran with a production that varies from 80 to 160 tons of product and constitute more than 90% of the total worldwide production (Husaini et al., 2010). Today, saffron cultivation is facing challenges such as climate change, soil diseases, and labor shortages which reduce saffron production in the world (Morodi, 2022). In the saffron production the qualitative aspects play a relevant role in determining the economic value of the spice. The quality of saffron stigma depends on a plethora of environmental factors, nutrition, and post-harvest processes such as drying and storage conditions (Gresta et al., 2009). In this work different alternative approaches for the cultivation of saffron (from stigma to bulb production), namely full controlled conditions (soiless) and hybrid conditions (stigma production under controlled conditions and bulb production under field conditions) were compared with traditional field cropping. In addition, the effect of different cultivation techniques on quality parameters of the spice was investigated.

Materials and Methods

For the soilless trials two aquaponic systems equipped with neon or led lamps, located at the Department of Agricultural and Food Science (DISTAL-University of Bologna) were employed. Each aquaponic system consisted of two implants: one devoted to the rearing of European eel (*Anguilla anguilla* L.) and the other one devoted to saffron production. The two coupled implants are potentially independent one another and are recirculating water through height differences and a submerged pump. The aquaponic systems are placed within climatic chambers (180x210x235 cm): the same temperature and photoperiodism conditions were set. For blooming phase, a 11/13 photoperiod and a temperature of 15 °C/10 °C (day/night) were set up. The plant density was 110 bulbs m⁻². The experimental scheme was a randomized-block design with three replicates. The factorial arrangement included two factors: the growing season (with three levels: 2019, 2020, 2021) and the light type (with two levels: led and neon). In the 2022-2023 growing season trial, different production systems were compared: soilless system, hybrid system (blooming in soilless system and vegetative phase in open field) and open field cycle. The field trials were carried out in an organic farming located near Bologna (latitude 44°29' 09" N, longitude 11°18'59"E, 72 m a.s.l.). For the field trials the plant density was 75 corms m⁻², while for the soilless trials with led lamps the plant density was 600 corms m⁻². Agronomic data as flowers number, flowering period duration, flowers and stigmas fresh and dry weight, for both implants were collected. Flowers and stigma were analyzed for bioactive compounds: polyphenols, flavonoids and antioxidant activity with FRAP assay (Dinelli et al., 2009). In addition, drug has been qualified for crocin, picocrocin and safranal total content (Cardone et al., 2019). As concerns the vegetative phase, leaves length and numbers was measured. At the end of the saffron cycle the number of daughter corm, and daughter corm per corm were counted; corms weight and diameter have been measured. Experimental data were elaborated according to analysis of variance (ANOVA). Significance between means was determined by least significant difference values for $p < 0.05$.

Table I. Production and quality parameters of saffron grown under controlled conditions (aquaponic systems equipped with led or neon lamps). Data refers to mean value of the three –year trials (plant density 110 bulbs m⁻²). Different letters represents significant different values (p<0.05).

	Led	Neon
Flowering duration (d)	13.7 (b)	14.4 (a)
N° of flowers per bulb	1.95 (a)	1.53 (b)
Flower fresh wieght (g)	0.293 (a)	0.238 (b)
Flower FW (g/m ²)	0.116 (a)	0.099 (b)
Stigma fresh weight (g)	0.232 (a)	0.123 (b)
Stigma FW (g/m ²)	0.131 (a)	0.101 (b)
Picrocrocin (mg/kg)	105.9 (a)	98.1 (a)
Safranal (mg/kg)	37.9 (a)	44.5 (b)
Crocic (mg/kg)	188.4 (a)	181.8 (a)

standards). During the vegetative phase, the LED system showed a better performance than the neon system. In particular, LED lighting ensured the production of bulbs with a greater diameter and weight than the neon system (data not shown). The main limitation of the production of saffron under controlled conditions is the operational cost for the vegetative phase, which can account for up to over 70% of the total costs. In order to overcome these limitations, in the 2022/2023 growing season, a comparative trial was set up between soilless, hybrid and open field cultivation of saffron. The hybrid system (blooming in soilless system and vegetative phase in open field) assured productive and quality performance comparable to soilless system (Table II). A relevant reduction of the productive cost was observed for the hybrid system compared to soilless system (data not shown), with a positive effect on the profitability (41 vs 72 € m⁻² for soilless and hybrid system, respectively).

Conclusions

LED lighting has shown great benefits in the qualitative and quantitative production of saffron as well as a great reduction in energy consumption compared to neon lamps. Furthermore, the LED lighting system can be more modulated on the specific requests of the system, allowing greater management of the light intensity and the spectral emission actually absorbed by the plant. The transplantation of bulbs in the open field at the end of flowering allows a greater reduction of the initial investment cost in the development of the soilless system allowing a greater production of larger bulbs. Further investigations are underway in order to better modulate the hybrid saffron cultivation system

Literature

- Cardone L. et al. 2019. Evaluation of corm origin and climatic conditions on saffron (*Crocus sativus* L.) yield and quality. J. Sci. Food. Agric., 99: 5858-5869.
- Dinelli G. et al. 2009. Determination of phenolic compounds in modern and old varieties of durum wheat using liquid chromatography coupled with time-of-flight mass spectrometry. J. Chrom. A, 1216: 7229–7240.
- Douglas M.H. 2014. Saffron (*Crocus sativus* L.): The effect of mother corm size on progeny multiplication, flower and stigma production. Sci. Hortic., 166: 50–58.
- Gresta F. et al. 2009. Analysis of flowering, stigmas yield and qualitative traits of saffron (*Crocus sativus* L.) as affected by environmental conditions. Sci.Horticul., 119: 3-15.
- Husaini A., et al. 2010. Sustainable Saffron (*Crocus sativus* Kashmirianus) Production: Technological and Policy Interventions for Kashmir. Report
- Moradi S. 2022. Saffron production Under Controlled Conditions. In: Vakhlu, J., Ambardar, S., Salami, S.A., Kole, C. (eds) The Saffron Genome. Compendium of Plant Genomes. Springer, Cham.

Results

In the three-year trial under controlled condition, the two main factors (growing season and light type) resulted statistically significant at p<0.05, while the interaction was not significant. The led light assured better productivity and quality of the spice than neon light (Table I), probably due to the different light spectra and intensity (PPFD) (data not shown). In particular, the LED lighting ensured flowering comparable to that observed in the open field. Douglas et al. (2014) reported an average production of 1.1-1.5 flowers/bulb under field conditions. Both types of lighting made it possible to produce stigmas of good quality (I class according to ISO3623:2003

Table II. Production and quality parameters of saffron grown under soilless (aquaponic system equipped with led lamps), hybrid and field conditions. Data refers to mean value of the growing season 2022/2023). Different letters represents significant different values (p<0.05).

	Soilless	Hybrid condition	Field
Plant density (bulb/m ²)	600	600	75
Flowering duration (d)	10.5 (a)	10.6 (a)	11.1 (a)
N° of flowers per bulb	2.5 (a)	2.4 (a)	1.7 (b)
Flower FW (g/m ²)	0.749 (a)	0.677 (a)	0.321 (b)
Stigma FW (g/m ²)	0.461 (a)	0.581 (a)	0.259 (b)
Picrocrocin (mg/kg)	106.1 (a)	103.2 (a)	106.2 (a)
Safranal (mg/kg)	47.6 (a)	48.4 (a)	45.3 (a)
Crocic (mg/kg)	165.4 (a)	151.6 (a)	155.1 (a)

Multi-Mycotoxin Long-Term Monitoring Survey on North-Italian Maize over an 11-Year Period (2011–2021): The Co-Occurrence of Regulated, Masked and Emerging Mycotoxins and Fungal Metabolites

Sabrina Locatelli¹, Valentina Scarpino², Chiara Lanzanova¹, Elio Romano³, Amedeo Reyneri²

¹ CREA-CI, Bergamo, IT, sabrina.locatelli@crea.gov.it; chiara.lanzanova@crea.gov.it

² DISAFA, Univ. Torino, IT, valentina.scarpino@unito.it; amedeo.reyneri@unito.it

³ CREA-IT, Treviglio, IT, elio.romano@crea.gov.it

Introduction

Maize (*Zea mays*) is considered one of the most susceptible crops to mycotoxin-producing fungi throughout the world, mainly belonging to the *Fusarium* spp. and *Aspergillus* spp. (Munkvold et al., 2019). Maize is mainly used as animal feeds in Italy, as well as for human consumption, being essential for all the protected designation of origin (DOP) products (Rai S. et al., 2018). Our study investigated the occurrence of regulated mycotoxins in 3769 maize grain samples collected from 88 storage centers by the National Monitoring Network over an 11-year period (2011–2021). Moreover, an in-depth survey over a 4-year period, characterized by extremely different meteorological conditions, was conducted to investigate the co-occurrence of regulated, masked, and emerging mycotoxins. The aims of this survey were twofold: first aim was to draw up mycotoxin profiles of the maize grain grown in Northern Italy to highlight the different occurrences between years and production areas in order to point out the environmental conditions that aggravate the contaminations of regulated mycotoxins. The second aim was to investigate the role of emerging mycotoxins and their co-occurrence with the regulated ones.

Materials and Methods

Meteorological Data. Data were taken from different Regional Environmental Protection Agencies (ARPA) meteorological stations located in the main Italian maize growing regions.

Samples. A total of 3769 representative maize grain samples were collected, after dry processing, over an 11-year period (2011–2021) from 88 storage centers. These storage centers are distributed in five geographical areas (West, Center, South Po, Adriatic, and East), which represent the regions in Northern Italy with the greatest cultivation of maize.

Regulated Mycotoxins Analyses. The regulated mycotoxin concentration levels in the maize samples collected during the 2011–2021 period were determined by means of an Enzyme-Linked Immunoassorbent Assay (ELISA).

Multi-Mycotoxin LC-MS/MS Analysis. The maize lot samples from the drying and storage centers, collected during the 2012–2015 period, were analyzed by means of a multi-mycotoxin LC-MS/MS analysis. The extraction phase was described in detail by Sulyok et al. in 2006. The chromatographic and mass spectrometric parameters of the investigated analytes were described by Malachova et al. 2014.

Statistical Analysis and Data Elaboration were described by Locatelli et al. (2022).

Results

This study evaluated, for the first time, mycotoxin profiles obtained from the contamination of regulated, masked, and emerging mycotoxins and fungal metabolites in maize grown in Northern Italy through an extensive survey conducted on maize grain lots from 88 storage centers over the 2011–2021 period, year by year.

Meteorological Trends. Different meteorological trends were observed over the 2011–2021 period by measuring the daily mean precipitation and temperature during the ripening period of maize kernels. The rainfall range observed over the years, where the average of 10 meteorological stations was considered, was

between 152.08 mm in 2011 and 350.33 mm in 2014. Differences were also observed regarding temperatures. The mean meteorological trend was also observed considering the five geographical areas. The precipitation and temperature data from the two meteorological stations chosen to represent each geographical area were averaged over the 2011–2021 years. A different distribution of rainfall was observed within the different areas.

Regulated Mycotoxins. Fumonisin B (FBs) were the most common mycotoxins, being present in at least 97% of the samples analyzed from 2011 to 2021. The statistical analysis showed that the years with the highest and lowest contaminations were 2019 and 2011. During these years, the contamination level ranged between 25 and 47,300 µg/kg. Throughout the years in which this study was carried out, the presence of aflatoxin B1 (AF B1) was lower than that of FBs, with an average level of between 0.6 in 2014 and 12.5 µg/kg in 2012. The effects of the year and area on the occurrence of deoxynivalenol (DON) and zearalenone (ZEA) in the maize lots were also detected. The years with the higher levels of contamination were 2013 and 2014 while the year 2021 was found to be the least contaminated. In 2014, the maximum concentration reached 36,583 µg/kg, and 100% of the analyzed samples were positive.

Masked Mycotoxins, Emerging Mycotoxins and Other Fungal Metabolites. An in-depth study was carried out during the 2012–2015 period to evaluate the contamination levels of masked and modified mycotoxins, and emerging fungal metabolites in the same maize lots. As far as the masked mycotoxins are concerned, the mainly detected forms were those associated with DON, such as deoxynivalenol-3-glucoside (DON-3-G), and the acetylated forms, 3-acetyldeoxynivalenol (3-ADON) and 15-acetyldeoxynivalenol (15-ADON). The emerging mycotoxins and fungal metabolites mainly produced by *Fusarium* spp. of the *Liseola* section, such as beauvericin (BEA), bikaverin (BIK), fusaric acid (FA), fusaproliferin (FUS), and moniliformin (MON), were detected for all the years and in all the areas.

Conclusions

The survey confirmed that *Fusarium* spp. were the most frequent fungi and fumonisins were the main mycotoxins that were constantly detected in the different years and areas. Moreover, the areas characterized by high fumonisin levels were also the most prone to contamination by emerging mycotoxins produced by the same *Fusarium* species of the *Liseola* section. On the other hand, as a result of climatic changes, maize grains have also been affected by the increased frequency of aflatoxin accumulation. DON, ZEA, and other emerging mycotoxins produced by the same *Fusarium* species as the *Discolor* section occurred more abundantly in some areas in Northern Italy and in years characterized by predisposing meteorological conditions. The mycotoxin contaminations of both regulated and emerging mycotoxins showed a pronounced year-by-year variation due to both the geographical characteristics of the maize growing area and the meteorological conditions during sensitive periods of maize grain development, especially during the ripening period. The definition of risk areas/zones is essential to understand the impact of mycotoxin contaminations on the food and feed chains, in consideration of a changing climate change scenario.

Literature

- Rai S. et al. 2018. Gluten-free products for celiac susceptible people. *Front. Nutr.*, 5: 116.
- Locatelli S. et al. 2022. Multi-Mycotoxin Long-Term Monitoring Survey on North-Italian Maize over an 11-Year Period (2011–2021): The Co-Occurrence of Regulated, Masked and Emerging Mycotoxins and Fungal Metabolites. *Toxins*, 14: 520.
- Munkvold G.P. et al. 2019. Mycotoxins in corn: Occurrence, impacts, and management. In *Corn: Chemistry and Technology*, 3rd ed.; Serna-Saldivar, S.O., Ed.; AACC International Press: Washington, DC, USA, 2019; pp. 235–287.
- Malachova et al. 2014. Optimization and validation of a quantitative liquid chromatography—Tandem mass spectrometric method covering 295 bacterial and fungal metabolites including all relevant mycotoxins in four model food matrices. *J. Chromatogr. A*, 1362: 145–156.

Funding: This research was undertaken with the financial assistance of the Italian Ministry of Agricultural Food and Forestry Policies-MiPAAF as part of the following research programs: MICOPRINCEM, RQC MAIS (D.D. N. 88666, 3 December 2014) and RETI2020 (prot. 198541, 30 April 2021). Moreover, in 2018, CREA carried out this work in collaboration with ISMEA as part of the “Cereal Quality Territorial Observatory” project of the National Cereal Plan, funded by the Italian Ministry of Agricultural, Food and Forestry Policies (MiPAAF).

Multielement profile and chemometrics for traceability of Pomodorino del Piennolo del Vesuvio PDO

Luigi Ruggiero¹, Raffaella Ofano¹, Diana Agrelli¹, Carmine Amalfitano¹, Paola Adamo^{1,2}

¹ Dep. of Agricultural Sciences, Univ. Naples "Federico II", IT, luigi.ruggiero@unina.it

² Urban and Territorial Planning Laboratory "Francesco d'Ambrosio", Univ. Naples "Federico II", IT

Introduction

The Pomodorino del Piennolo del Vesuvio (PPV) is a traditional variety of tomato, grown in Campania (Italy) on the slopes of Somma-Vesuvius volcano complex, sold assembled in bunches and characterized by long shelf-life. PPV was awarded by Protect Designation Origin (PDO) in 2009. Local "custodian farmers" play an important role in conserving traditional cultivation management and biodiversity, as well as organoleptic properties deriving from Vesuvian environment. Due to the high typicity and higher selling value, PPV is susceptible to origin fraud.

Multielement fingerprinting is one of the most widely used technique to discriminate the geographical origin of food (Luykx and van Ruth, 2008). It takes advantage of the fact that mineral elements can be transferred from soil to agricultural products and thus any difference in element distribution between different geographic regions are reflected in agriproducts (Ruggiero et al., 2021).

Thus, the main aim of our study (carried out in framework of TOMATO TRACE 4.0 project, PSR 2014-2020, Campania Region) is to valorise PPV strengthening the traceability system. A way to achieve this is to link the tomato to the soil characteristics by multielement fingerprinting. In this work, the multielement profiles of PPV (three local varieties) from five PDO and two not PDO farms were investigated in 2021 production year. In addition, the multielement profile of cultivation soils (total and bioavailable elements) was investigated to evidence the variability of the PDO or not PDO soils and relationships with related tomatoes.

Materials and Methods

A total of 131 samples of full ripe tomatoes (500 g each) of three PPV local varieties ("Acampora"AC, "Cozzolino" CZ and "Patanara"PT) and 42 cultivation soils (depth of 35 cm), were collected at the end of July and beginning of August 2021 in five PDO farms (Farm 1-5) around the Somma-Vesuvius volcano complex (different slope exposition and altitude) and from two farms outside the PDO area in the municipalities of Sessa Aurunca (CE) (Farm 6) and Massa Lubrense (NA) (Farm 7), both in the Campania region. Briefly, a total of 19 elements (Ca, Cu, Fe, Mg, Mn, Mo, Na, Ni, P, K, Zn, Ba, Cd, Co, Cr, Cs, Li, Rb, and Sr) were determined in squeezed and freeze dried tomato subsamples (200 mg) by acid mineralization in a N₂ pressurized microwave (1:3 HCl:HNO₃ at 240°C) and ICP-MS (ICAP-Q, Thermo Fisher Scientific). The same 19 elements were determined in the potentially bioavailable soil fraction (0.05 M EDTA, pH 7 soil extraction; PBE) and readily bioavailable soil fraction (1 M NH₄NO₃ soil extraction; RBE) from 2 mm sieved soil (Agrelli et al., 2017). The soil and tomato data underwent to explorative analysis by Principal Component Analysis (PCA) with previous Bartlett sphericity and KMO tests. Also, the relationship between elements in soils and tomatoes was investigated by Spearman Correlation Analysis supported by Shapiro-Wilk test normal distribution tests. Stepwise Linear Discriminant Analysis (S-LDA), dividing the data of samples into calibration and validation sets (70% and 30% of samples, respectively), was performed to discriminate tomatoes by farms.

Results

Explorative analysis on multielement profiles

The PCA analysis on multielement profile of PPV evidenced a tendency to a natural grouping of tomatoes according to provenance farms to the detriment of different local varieties that did not evidence any tendency to a natural grouping. This suggests that these profiles did not strongly depend on the local varieties studied, but mainly on the origin, since the cultivation environments (soil, climate, management,

etc.) could be different although the farms fell into a relatively small area. On the other hand, in particular, the Campania areas investigated were influenced by many different events of the Campania volcanisms which over time have conditioned the characteristics of the local soils. The same analysis applied on PBE and RBE evidenced groupings according to farms, therefore, the PCA of multielement profile of bioavailable fractions was in agreement with that of PPV tomatoes. In addition, the Spearman analysis showed that the 68.4% of 19 elements in bioavailable soil fractions and fruits were significantly correlated.

Step-wise Liner Discriminat Analysis

Figure 21 Score plot of S-LDA, Farm 1-5 (PDO) and Farm 6,7 (NO-PDO)

On the basis of the suggestion of PCA analyses, the S-LDA model was applied on PPV multielement profiles grouped by farms (Fig.1). The model gave 100% of correct classification and external validation, with Wilks lambda of 0.0001 ($p < 0.001$), demonstrating a great discriminating power of multielement fingerprint. Further, the stepwise procedure chose the discriminating elements (84.2% of total) in the following order of decreasing weight: Rb > Sr > Mo > Cs > Co > Cd > Fe > Cu > Zn > Na > Mn > Li > Ca > Mg > K > P). Among the previous, the elements Fe, K, Mg, Mo, Na, Zn, Cd, Co, Cs, Li, Rb, and Sr in bioavailable soil fractions showed a significant correlation with those in fruit. This suggested that they were the most reliable multielement set to discriminate the provenance. This means that the excluded Ca, Cu, Mn, Ba and P set,

lacking of a linear relationship with bioavailable soil fraction, could vary not strictly with soil characteristics.

Conclusions

The multielement fingerprinting of PPV tomatoes, collected in 2021, was able to discriminate the samples from the five PDO farms and the two NO-PDO farms in the Campania region. Further studies are ongoing to increase the robustness of the model by adding new samples from different years, to increase the seasonal variability, and farms, to increase the spatial variability.

Literature

- Agrelli D. et al. 2017. Soil versus plant as indicators of agroecosystem pollution by potentially toxic elements. *J. Plant Nutr. Soil Sci.*, 180(6): 705–719.
- Luyckx D.M.A.M. and van Ruth S.M. 2008. An overview of analytical methods for determining the geographical origin of food products. *Food Chem.*, 107(2): 897–911.
- Ruggiero L. et al. 2021. Provenance discrimination of Sorrento lemon with Protected Geographical indication (PGI) by multi-elemental fingerprinting. *Food Chem.*, 362: 130168.

Combining a crop model and remote sensing for crop trait retrieval: a methodological framework

Fosco Mattia Vesely¹, Anne Schucknecht², Mirco Boschetti³, Gabriele Candiani³, Monica Pepe³, Stefano Bocchi⁴, Francesco Fava⁴

¹ Dep. Agricultural and Environmental Sciences, Univ. Milano, IT, fosco.vesely@unimi.it

² Image Simulation and Processing Team, OHB System AG, DE

³ Institute for Electromagnetic Sensing of the Environment, Italian National Research Council, IT

⁴ Dep. Environmental Science and Policy, Univ. Milano, IT

Introduction

Monitoring the spatial and temporal dynamics of crop traits is an important step for improving the efficiency and sustainability of agronomic management practices. Satellite remote sensing techniques allow for a regular and spatially explicit assessment of crop traits (e.g., Nutini et al., 2018) like Leaf Area Index (LAI) or nitrogen content, thus providing suitable information to support crop management at farm and landscape scale. However, retrieval of crop traits from remote sensing data often relies on context-specific empirical models based on extensive field data collections. As an alternative, physically-based radiative transfer models (RTM) are used as a more generalizable option, but their parametrization is often difficult, and inversion can be problematic. Hybrid retrieval methods have been recently proposed (e.g., Tagliabue et al., 2022) to combine the strengths of RTM with flexibility of machine learning (ML) algorithms. These methods use a RTM to simulate a large dataset of spectra and corresponding biophysical/biochemical traits to train ML regression algorithms that are then used to retrieve the canopy traits from satellite-measured spectra. This study proposes a hybrid modelling approach that integrates a crop model with the RTM to forward simulate spectra from realistic traits, and then use ML regression for retrieval of crop traits from satellite remote sensing data. This has two potential advantages: on the one hand, it could further increase the overall model transferability by lowering framework dependency on field data. On the other hand, it could provide a dynamic data assimilation framework of remote sensing data into the crop model to infer variables that cannot be directly related to reflectances. This abstract describes the implementation of the proposed methodological framework for crop trait retrieval, which will be refined and validated with ongoing dedicated experimental studies.

Materials and Methods

The proposed modelling framework is illustrated in Figure 1 and briefly described in this section.

Figure 22: Schematic representation of the proposed generic workflow

The Decision Support System for Agrotechnology Transfer (DSSAT) crop model (Hoogenboom et al., 2019) simulates crop development and growth related to Genotype \times Environment \times Management interactions. DSSAT runs on *i*) time-series of climate variables including: radiation, air temperature and precipitation; *ii*) applied management interventions; *iii*) species and cultivar parametrization descriptive of the plant genetics. The coupled leaf-canopy radiative transfer model PROSAIL (Feret et al., 2008) simulates reflectance spectra from the daily DSSAT output of LAI, leaf biomass and leaf nitrogen content (Thorpe et

al., 2012). The simulated time series of reflectance generated by the coupled models are converted to NDVI and compared with NDVI measured by satellite sensors. An optimization algorithm is used to minimize the differences across simulated and measured NDVIs by varying DSSAT crop parameters, with the goal to perform a reflectance-based crop calibration (Shiklomanov et al., 2021). The calibrated coupled model is used to generate a training dataset including both traits (predicted variable) and reflectance values (predictor) to train a ML algorithm. Finally, the trained ML algorithm is used for crop traits retrieval from remotely sensed reflectance values.

Results

The proposed framework has been implemented for rice crop monitoring in the “Lombardo-Piemontese” rice district (45.1° – 45.5°N, 8.1° - 8.8° E). Rice is simulated within the DSSAT 4.8 (Hoogenboom et al., 2019) modelling framework sourcing: i) the climate data from ERA5 (Muñoz-Sabater et al., 2021) resampled to daily time resolution available at the Climate data store (<http://cds.climate.copernicus.eu/>). ERA5 cells covering the rice district which are classified as rice fields for at least 70% by the CORINE land cover map of 2018 (Forslund, 2018) are used; ii) to include uncertainties in actual management operation, two fertilization levels and three fixed sowing dates are combined to explore realistic farming activities. In addition, watering interventions are applied so to avoid any water stress, whereas pests and weeds are not simulated, soil is assumed as a generic silty loam; iii) a realistic DSSAT rice cultivar calibration is pursued as follows: the species parameters are kept at default values while 5 of 12 parameters related to cultivar phenology (i.e., P1, P20, P2R, P5, G3) are recalibrated by Gaussian process optimization algorithm. The reference dataset of observations is populated by NDVIs computed from Harmonized Landsat and Sentinel-2 archive (Claverie et al., 2018) at centroids of cadastral parcels at least 1.5ha wide. The calibrated coupled DSSAT–PROSAIL model generates a daily dataset about $1.3 \cdot 10^5$ record long (i.e.: 17 climate data cells, 9 years, 3 sowing dates and 2 fertilization levels) suitable for training a Random Forest ML algorithm over realistic rice reflectance and traits.

Conclusions and outlook

This study describes the methodological workflow to combine crop models, RTMs and ML algorithms to retrieve crop biophysical/biochemical traits from remotely sensed imagery, and illustrates its implementation on a case study on rice crops in northern Italy. The proposed approach can be adapted to different crops and satellite sensors. The next step will be to refine and validate the modelling framework on rice using existing and newly acquired field and satellite datasets. To this end, a field campaign is planned during the 2023 rice growing season to collect field data on canopy traits and spectral reflectance during multiple rice phenological stages.

Literature

- Claverie M. et al. 2018. The Harmonized Landsat and Sentinel-2 surface reflectance data set. *Remote Sens. Environ.*, 219: 145-161.
- Feret J.B. et al. 2008. PROSPECT-4 and 5: Advances in the leaf optical properties model separating photosynthetic pigments. *Remote Sens. Environ.*, 112.6: 3030-3043.
- Forslund L. 2018. CLC 2018—Copernicus Land Monitoring Service. *MDPI St. Alban-Anlage* 66: 4052.
- Hoogenboom G. et al. 2019. The DSSAT crop modeling ecosystem. *Advances in crop modelling for a sustainable agriculture*. Burleigh Dodds Science Publishing 173-216.
- Muñoz-Sabater J. et al. 2021. ERA5-Land: A state-of-the-art global reanalysis dataset for land applications. *Earth Syst. Sci. Data*, 13: 4349-4383.
- Nutini F. et al. 2018. An operational workflow to assess rice nutritional status based on satellite imagery and smartphone apps. *Comput. Electron. Agric.*, 154: 80-92.
- Shiklomanov A.N. et al. 2021. Cutting out the middleman: Calibrating and validating a dynamic vegetation model (ED2-PROSPECT5) using remotely sensed surface reflectance. *Geosci. Mod. Dev.*, 14: 2603-2633.
- Tagliabue G. et al. 2022. Hybrid retrieval of crop traits from multi-temporal PRISMA hyperspectral imagery. *ISPRS J. Photogramm. Remote Sens.*, 187: 362-377.
- Thorp K.R. et al. 2012. Estimating crop biophysical properties from remote sensing data by inverting linked radiative transfer and ecophysiological models. *Remote Sens. Environ.*, 124: 224-233.

POSTERS

Hemp Inflorescences Traceability by Low Field NMR Relaxometry and Biometric Evaluation

Salvatore Baiano¹, Mariarosaria Sicignano¹, Francesco Raimo¹, Luisa del Piano¹, Tommaso Enotrio¹, Paolo Lo Meo², Delia Francesca Chillura Martino², Pellegrino Conte³

¹ CREA-CI, Caserta, IT, salvatore.baiano@crea.gov.it, mariarosaria.sicignano@crea.gov.it, francesco.raimo@crea.gov.it

² Dip. Scienze e Tecnologie Biologiche Chimiche e Farmaceutiche, Univ. Palermo, IT, paolo.lomeo@unipa.it, delia.chilluramartino@unipa.it

³ Dip. Scienze Agrarie, Alimentari e Forestali, Univ. Palermo, IT, pellegrino.conte@unipa.it

Introduction

Hemp (*Cannabis sativa* L.) is a multipurpose crop with many environmental benefits such as carbon storage, breaking the cycle of diseases, soil erosion prevention, biodiversity, low or no use of pesticides, contributing to the European Green Deal objectives (https://agriculture.ec.europa.eu/farming/crop-productions-and-plant-based-products/hemp_en). Industrial varieties, complying with 0.2% Δ^9 -tetrahydrocannabinol (THC) threshold set by the EU legislation, can be cultivated without restrictions. Other than its traditional use as a source of bast fibres from the stems, hemp is cultivated also for non-textile applications. Inflorescences can be used to extract essential oils (EO), that are high-value products. Different cultivars, however, produce EOs with very diverse molecular compositions and aroma profiles (Bertoli et al., 2010), thereby implying the need of an authentication process of the raw materials. To this purpose, we decided to apply different NMR techniques together with biometric data to reveal differences among seven different hemp cultivars. High resolution NMR spectroscopy and fast field cycling NMR relaxometry have already shown their ability in differentiating among plant tissues having different origin (Berns et al., 2011). The use of NMR techniques is advantageous because these are quick and non-destructive as compared to other experimental analytical methods (Preto et al., 2013). Moreover, the possibility to combine NMR results to biometric investigations via statistical analyses make the aforementioned techniques very powerful (Piacenza et al., 2022).

Materials and Methods

Two monoecious (Codimono and Carmaleonte) and five dioecious hemp cultivars (Carmagnola, Carmagnola Selected (CS), Eletta Campana, Fibrante and Fibranova) were grown in open field in Battipaglia (Italy) during 2021. Biometric measurements and inflorescences sampling were done at the end of the crop cycle. Inflorescences were treated at 65 °C and then ground for analysis. FFC NMR experiments were performed using a Stelar Spinmaster FFC 2000 relaxometer (Stelar s.r.l., Mede, PV - Italy) at the constant temperature of 25 °C. The experimental setup was already used elsewhere (Conte et al., 2021). The experimental data were processed with ModelFreeFFC developed at University of Bologna (Bologna, Italy) to obtain the distributions of the correlation times (τ_C). A Bruker Avance 400 spectrometer operating at 100 MHz on the ¹³C and a rotor spin rate of 13 kHz were used for CPMAS ¹³C NMR experiments. The crystalline-to-amorphous ratio in cellulose was determined by the deconvolution of the signals in the 95-80 ppm interval according to Park et al. (2010). A Perkin Elmer AAnalyst 400 with flame atomization (Waltham, MA – USA) was used for quantification of total-recoverable levels of Cu, Fe, Mn and Zn in inflorescences after nitric-perchloric acid digestion. Principal Component Analysis (PCA) was done using the R software (v4.1.2) using the FactoMineR package.

Results

The τ_C distributions obtained by the FFC NMR study (not shown), evidenced a presence of either two or three bands in three distinct relaxation domains for all the samples. By considering that inflorescences are complex systems made by different molecules, it is possible to attribute the higher values of τ_C to low molecular mobility components, like polysaccharides, proteins, fibres and adsorbed water, while the

intermediate and lower ones to more mobile components, such as polyphenols, cannabinoids, terpenes and others. The peaks of τ_C in each domain ($\tau_{C1} < \tau_{C2} < \tau_{C3}$) differed with the cultivar, thus indicating differences

in the molecular composition of the inflorescences. The CPMAS ^{13}C NMR spectra, instead, did not evidence differences among the cultivars with the exception of the 95-80 ppm interval, where the changes in the peaks were attributed to the amorphous and crystalline forms of the cellulose. Finally, biometric measures and metal concentrations also evidenced some significant differences among the cultivars (data not shown). Thus, a principal component analysis was performed on the parameters obtained by the different NMR techniques, metal levels and biometric measures. Three different groups of cultivars were clearly separated with PCA analysis (Figure 1). Along the PC1, explaining 40.6 % of variability, Codimono and Carmaleonte were clearly separated from Eletta Campana, Carmagnola and CS, for higher values of τ_{C2} , indicating a different composition of the intermediate molecules, as well as for lower values of stem dimensions. Along the PC2, explaining 24.8 % of variability, instead, Fibranova and Fibrante were separated from the other cultivars by the higher crystalline-to-amorphous ratio, and in part by higher τ_{C3} . Also lower growth of inflorescences and female plants contributed to these differences.

Conclusions

This work proves the applicability of FFC NMR relaxometry, together with CPMAS ^{13}C NMR, to distinguish among inflorescences from different hemp cultivars and to correlate with biometric parameters. Future research is needed to extend the investigation in order to correlate relaxometric characteristics also to biochemical composition of hemp inflorescences.

Acknowledgements

This work was supported by UNIHEMP research project “Use of iNdustrIal Hemp biomass for Energy and new biocheMicals Production” (ARS01_00668) funded by Fondo Europeo di Sviluppo Regionale (FESR) (within the PON R&I 2014-2020—Axis 2—Action II—OS 1.b), CUP: B76C18000520005.

Literature

Berns A.E. et al. 2011. Applicability of solid state fast field cycling NMR relaxometry in understanding relaxation properties of leaves and leaf-litters. *Org. Geochem.*, 42: 978-984.
 Bertoli A. et al. 2010. Fibre hemp inflorescences: from crop-residues to essential oil production. *Ind. Crops Prod.*, 32: 329–337.
 Conte P. et al. 2021. Fast field cycling NMR relaxometry as a tool to monitor Parmigiano Reggiano cheese ripening. *Food Res. Int.*, 139, 109845.
 Park et al. 2010. Cellulose crystallinity index: measurement techniques and their impact on interpreting cellulase performance. *Biotechnol. Biofuels* 3:10 <http://biotechnologyforbiofuels.com/content/3/1/10>
 Piacenza D.F. et al. 2022. Differentiation among dairy products by combination of fast field cycling NMR relaxometry data and chemometrics. *Magn. Reson. Chem.*, 60: 369–385
 Preto M.S.M et al. 2013. Determination of herb authenticity by low-field NMR. *Food. Chem.*, 136: 1272-1276.

Plants Toxic to Farm Animals: Assessment of their Chemical Compounds and Distribution in Central Italy

Elisabetta Bianchi^{1,2}, Giovanni Argenti¹, Nicolina Staglianò¹, Federico Selvi^{1,2}, Silvia Lamanna³, Claudia Focardi³

¹ DAGRI, Univ. Firenze, IT, giovanni.argenti@unifi.it, e.bianchi@unifi.it, nicolina.stagliano@unifi.it, federico.selvi@unifi.it

² Italian National Biodiversity Future Center (NBFC), PNRR - CN 5 - SPOKE 7

³ Istituto Zooprofilattico Sperimentale del Lazio e della Toscana "M. Aleandri", silvia.lamanna-esterno@izslt.it, claudia.focardi@izslt.it

Introduction

The feeding of herbivorous animals is mainly based on the consumption of plants as fresh forage, hay, or silage. Consequently, it is possible that these animals eat toxic or potentially toxic plants. The damages are rather varied and include chronic and debilitating damages and, in the worst case, mortality (Bernhoft, 2010). Animals tend to change their eating habits when forced to overgraze in areas where they wouldn't naturally, following transport or stress, making themselves more vulnerable to possible poisoning. Furthermore, we cannot exclude the possibility that intoxications may also occur from forage contaminated by toxic plants, which therefore disregard the selective nature of the animal. Most toxic plants are spontaneous and found in permanent meadows, pastures and woods; they can be native plants of a particular area, or they can be of allochthonous origin. In some cases, toxic species are also used as ornamental plants or for other purposes. During their evolution, since plants are sessile organisms, they have had to adapt to many types of abiotic (light, wind, rain, temperature, etc.) and biotic (pollinators, competitors, herbivores, pathogens, etc.) stresses, therefore defence mechanisms such as allelopathy is quite common. The nature of toxic secondary metabolites changes with varying place of origin and environmental conditions. The main toxic components of plants include tannins, phenolics, alkaloids, phytohemagglutinins, terpenes, cyanogenic glycosides, and oxalates, etc (Mircea and Draghia, 2014).

In collaboration with Istituto Zooprofilattico Sperimentale of Tuscany and Lazio, this work aims to present an ongoing project concerning the distribution of toxic plants and their analytical determination in different seasons for the regions of Tuscany and Lazio to increase the knowledge of these species and to limit and avoid losses of farm and grazing animals.

Materials and Methods

Starting from the updated checklist of the vascular flora present in Italy (Bartolucci et al., 2018), the toxic entities present in studied areas were selected and the appropriate bibliographic searches were carried out in order to be able to create a database that included the following information for each entity: scientific name, common name, regional distribution, types of toxin, class of toxins, toxic part of the plant, sensitive animal species, target organs, symptoms, toxic doses. Based on the data collected, some taxa were selected for field collection in two different seasons of the year. The following data were noted for each sample: collection location, collection point coordinates and collection date. Once collected, samples were stored in transparent plastic bags in a freezer at -4 °C until the laboratory analysis of the toxic compounds carried out by the chemical lab of Istituto Zooprofilattico Sperimentale of Tuscany and Lazio in Scandicci (Firenze). All sample, after being extracted and purified by using QuEChERS, were analysed by LC-MS/MS for toxin determination.

Results

The work is still in progress and 146 potentially toxic taxa for livestock and grazing animals have currently been identified, we report some examples in table 1. Among them, 23 have currently been selected for field collection to evaluate how chemical components vary in two different seasons (Figure 1).

Table 1. Example of toxic taxa and related characteristics reported on the database

Taxon	Toxins	Toxic part of the plant	Animals	Target organs	Symptomatology	Toxic doses
<i>Aconitum lycoctonum</i> L. emend. Koelle	aconitine	leaf, stem, roots, seeds	equine	digestive, respiratory, circulatory, nervous	sialorrhoea, colic sometimes diarrhoea; tremors, spasm, muscle twitching, ataxia, paralysis; dyspnoea, bradycardia, etc.	300-400 g of fresh roots
<i>Colchicum autumnale</i> L.	colchicine	juvenile leaves, fruits, seeds, bulbs	equine, cattle	digestive, respiratory, circulatory, nervous	anorexia, sialorrhoea, colic, diarrhoea, gastroenteritis, apathy, restlessness, ataxia, cardiac disturbances, tachycardia, etc.	1 mg kg ⁻¹ of colchicine
<i>Datura stramonium</i> L.	atropine, scopolamine	whole plant	equine, cattle, pigs	digestive, nervous, urinary, reproductive	excitation convulsions and tremors, loss of appetite, colic and dry mucous membranes, miscarriage, etc.	0.5% of the ration

The database will be made available on a website accessible to different staff and stakeholders, such as veterinary services to facilitate the identification of the plant possibly responsible for a given poisoning event and to identify the toxin compounds for a rapid adoption of specific health measures.

Figure 1. Example of data collection of toxic taxa selected for chemical analysis

Moreover, on the website specific data sheets for each toxic plant identified during this project will be arranged, reporting botanical description, photographs and other information to help also not experts in plant identification.

Conclusions

Our results will be made accessible to public, thus contributing to the reduction of poisoning risks from toxic plants and to the solution of toxicity problems found in animals, facilitating the identification of the responsible species and possible veterinary solutions for the treatment of occurring health diseases.

Literature

- Bartolucci F. et al. 2018. An updated checklist of the vascular flora native to Italy. *Plant Biosyst.*, 152: 179-303.
- Bernhoft A.J.A.B. 2010. A brief review on bioactive compounds in plants. In: *Bioactive compounds in plants-benefits and risks for man and animals*, 50: 11-17.
- Mircea C. and Draghia L. 2014. Allergenic and Toxic Compounds in Ornamental Plants - A review. *Bulletin UASVM Horticulture*, 71:180-194.

Digital Tools for Field Phenotyping of Processing Tomato Genotypes

Andrea Burato¹, Federico Landi², Alfonso Pentangelo¹, Raffaele Cavaliere², Francesco Vitale¹,
Domenico Ronga², Mario Parisi¹

¹ CREA-OF, Pontecagnano Faiano, IT, andrea.burato@crea.gov.it; alfonso.pentangelo@crea.gov.it;
francesco.vitale@crea.gov.it; mario.parisi@crea.gov.it

² Dep. Pharmacy, Univ. Salerno, IT dronga@unisa.it; f.landi26@studenti.unisa.it; r.cavaliere11@studenti.unisa.it

Introduction

Italy is the first producer of processing tomatoes (*Solanum lycopersicum* L.) in the Mediterranean area and lies in the global top-three countries, ensuring 15% of the total yield (5.5 million tons in 2022) (WPTC). Since genotype × environment interaction greatly affects plant behavior, the comparison of new genotypes in open field conditions represents an essential tool for local growers. In the present work, an open-field trial aimed at comparing the agronomic performances of new promising genotypes was monitored with digital tools throughout all the cycle to evaluate additional physiological parameters.

Materials and Methods

In the present study, carried out on a sandy loam soil at Marigliano (Naples, Italy) in 2022 growing season, 9 new determinate tomato genotypes (3 elongated – G1-3; 6 blocky – G4-9) were assessed. The total amount of rainfall was 68.6 mm throughout all crop cycle and maximum temperature frequently exceeded 30 °C after 24th May. Seedlings were transplanted in twin rows on 12th April with a density of 3.51 plants m⁻² and each genotype had three contiguous replicates. The total N, P and K supplies were calculated on the base of soil analysis, and a total of 675 mm of water was supplied during the crop cycle through a drip irrigation system. Weed management and plant protection were performed according to the Campania Region cultivation protocols. A single harvest was conducted on 27th July, when ripe fruits accounted for approximately 85% of the total.

Vegetative physiological parameters were assessed every two weeks, starting from blooming. An MPM-100 (ADC BioScientific Ltd.) was used to estimate chlorophyll (ChlM), flavonols (FlvM) and anthocyanins (AnthM) contents, and Nitrogen-Flavonol Index (NFI). A FLIR Ex-series thermal imaging camera was used to measure superficial temperature of tomato leaves (Temp). Leaf area (Area) was assessed with a LI-3050C leaf area meter (Ecosearch, Montone (PG), Italy). Total yield (TY), its components of marketable (MY) and unmarketable (UY) fruits, and Brix Yield (BY, as brix t ha⁻¹) were assessed for each replicate, as described by Ronga et al., 2019. Mean fruit weight (FRW), average number of marketable fruits per plant (FN), and technological traits of fruits (soluble solids content – SSC; fruit dry matter – FDM; pH; titratable acidity – TTA) were evaluated as described by Parisi and Burato et al. 2022. Analysis of variance (one-way ANOVA) was applied on all recorded data and a Tukey HSD test was adopted to separate means. A correlation among evaluated parameters was calculated through the Pearson coefficient *r*.

Results

At blooming phase, G4 recorded the largest leaf area (1732.7 cm²). At fruit setting, G8 had the greatest chlorophyll content (0.85), while G5 had the largest leaf area (5057.5 cm²).

At harvest (Table 1), G2 and G5 recorded the highest TY (146.6 and 160.0 t ha⁻¹, respectively), MY (123.6 and 134.6 t ha⁻¹, respectively) and Brix Yield (6.63 and 6.68 brix t ha⁻¹, respectively), due to the highest number of fruits per plant (> 74; data not shown) in the relative fruit-shape groups (elongated for G2 and blocky for G5). Only G4 recorded 66.3 g of FW, however not resulting in a higher yield.

Regarding the fruit technological quality, significant differences among the tested genotypes were found for SSC and TTA traits. Indeed, G6, G7, G8 and G9 showed the best value of TTA (> 0.45 g%), while G2 and G4 recorded the highest SSC (5.37 and 5.20 °Brix, respectively; data not shown).

Some agronomic and technological parameters had significant correlations with non-destructive measurements which were carried out 10 days before harvest. ChlM was positively correlated with TY ($r = 0.71, p < 0.05$), while PRI had a strong correlation with FW ($r = 0.89, p < 0.01$).

Table 15. Yield traits (FW, TY, MY, UY and BY), and physiological parameters measured at 10 days pre-harvest (ChlM, FlvM, NFI, Temp, Area and PRI)

Var	Harvest (27 th July)					Pre-harvest (17 th July)					
	FW	TY	MY	UY	BY	ChlM	FlvM	NFI	Temp	Area	PRI
G1	59.0 ab	122.8 ab	104.8 ab	11.9 b	5.4 abc	0.6 a	0.4 a	1.8 a	27.9 a	4143.8 a	0.05 a
G2	54.7 ab	146.6 ab	123.6 ab	7.4 b	6.6 ab	0.8 a	0.5 a	1.5 a	24.9 a	4001.5 a	0.04 a
G3	63.8 a	135.7 ab	106.9 ab	17.7 b	5.1 abc	0.7 a	0.6 a	1.2 a	26.2 a	3787.1 a	0.06 a
G4	66.3 a	128.3 ab	116.0 ab	8.9 b	6.0 abc	0.7 a	0.4 a	1.7 a	26.4 a	4390.0 a	0.06 a
G5	61.7 ab	160.0 a	134.6 a	15.7 b	6.7 a	0.7 a	0.4 a	1.7 a	27.6 a	4686.7 a	0.06 a
G6	56.7 ab	121.3 b	99.7 b	15.6 b	4.8 c	0.7 a	0.4 a	1.8 a	26.5 a	4459.6 a	0.04 a
G7	60.1 ab	126.0 ab	108.6 ab	11.2 b	5.2 abc	0.6 a	0.5 a	1.2 a	25.9 a	3687.8 a	0.06 a
G8	58.9 ab	138.6 ab	92.3 b	44.0 a	4.4 c	0.7 a	0.6 a	1.2 a	26.9 a	5955.2 a	0.06 a
G9	50.5 b	116.1 b	100.8 b	9.3 b	4.9 bc	0.6 a	0.5 a	1.4 a	27.4 a	4809.9 a	0.03 a
p	0.015	0.016	0.007	5.82E-05	0.001	0.695	0.184	0.080	0.137	0.067	0.972

G1: Passenger – ISI Sementi; G2: HMC 627147 – HM Clause; G3: Fantix – Syngenta; G4: Aprix – HM Clause; G5: Vulspot – Nunhems Basf; G6: Dobler – ISI Sementi; G7: Blend – Esasem; G8: UG 16112 – United Genetics; G9: Waller – Syngenta.

Conclusions

The present work gave preliminary insights about the implementation of digital measurements as early predictors of the agronomic performance of processing tomato genotypes, in the context of a traditional in-field-comparison. However, further studies are required to better understand how to valorize these hypotheses in terms of measurement timing and frequency, and which physiological parameters to consider.

Literature

Parisi M. et al. 2022. Towards the Optimal Mineral N Fertilization for Improving Peeled Tomato Quality Grown in Southern Italy. Horticulturae, 8: 697.
 Ronga D. et al. 2019. Effects of Nitrogen Management on Biomass Production and Dry Matter Distribution of Processing Tomato Cropped in Southern Italy. Agronomy, 9: 855.
 World Processing Tomato Council WPTC Crop Update <https://www.wptc.to/production/> (accessed on 10 May 2023)

FoodOnLine Project: Identification of Metabolomic Profiles for the Certification of Agri-food Products and their Traceability Through Block Chain Technology

Silvana Cangemi¹, Attilio Mondelli², Georgia Mouzakioti¹, Antonio De Martino³, Giovanni Vinci¹, Pierluigi Mazzei⁴, Giorgio Ciardella², Riccardo Spaccini^{1*}

¹CERMANU NMR, Univ. di Napoli Federico II, IT silvana.cangemi@unina.it, mouzakiotigeorgia@gmail.com, giovanni.vinci@unina.it, riccardo.spaccini@unina.it

²Farzati Tech, Farzati Consulting srl, IT, attilio.mondelli@farzatictech.it, giorgio.ciardella@farzatictech.it

³Dept. of Agricultural Sciences, Univ. di Napoli Federico II, IT, ademarti@unina.it

⁴Dep. of Pharmacy, Univ. di Salerno, IT, pmazzei@unisa.it

The identification of metabolic markers related to origin and quality of agri-food products and the implementation of analytical information in an objective bio-fingerprint represents a current challenge in the food sector. The present research project aims to combine integrated analytical techniques, based on the evaluation of metabolic components, with AI protocols in order to define a smart procedure for assessing the origin and the quality of agri-food products. Such a system may serve as a reliable tool to perform a product traceability during its critical production and transformation phases. The Nuclear Magnetic Resonance (NMR) spectroscopy include different methods to determine metabolic biomarkers attributable to specific agri-food products. In particular, High Resolution Magic Angle Spinning (HRMAS) represents an advanced NMR methodology which integrates the advantages of the liquid-state high resolution NMR with those of the direct analysis of dried sample through solid-state NMR [1]. Moreover, it allows to examine agri-food products without any preliminary and time-consuming extraction, thus reducing the risks associated with the alteration of the bulk matrices. In this project HRMAS it is hence used to achieve meaningful NMR spectra of unaltered food matrices, such as dairy products, seeds and tomato. The NIR spectroscopy is the reference approaches for holistic, rapid, and valuable chemical characterization of agri-food products [2]. On this basis, the attempt is to correlate the NMR-based qualitative and quantitative metabolomic profile of specific food products with the chemical patterns detected by NIR. The large range of analytical data derived from applied spectroscopic methodologies will undergo a statistical screening and validated through multivariate statistical analyses. The initial analysis performed on different samples of wheat-seeds, pulped tomatoes, cow-milk and wood biomasses confirmed the potential of NMR characterization to effectively discriminate the molecular components and the metabolomic profiles of the analysed samples (Figure 1). The NMR and NIR spectral information will be processed into a digital fingerprint related to molecular information to support a product traceability. For this purpose, the BluDev® technology developed by Farzati-Tech, will define a bio-digital fingerprint (BFP - BioFingerPrint) to store the information in a composite database using the paradigms of the Blockchain. Blockchain is a type of data structure that allows transactions to be identified and tracked digitally and to share this information across a distributed network of computers, creating the basis of a distributed network of trust. The aim is to trace all subsequent events in the life of the product / lot as a digital object, with unique information linked to the entire supply chain and throughout its life cycle.

Figure 1 a) ¹H HR-MAS NMR spectra of a durum wheat flour (TELEMACO)

b) PCA score plot of the ¹H HR MAS NMR of four wheat cultivars

b

Achille
Creso
Telemaco
Minosse

Bibliography

- [1] Mazzei et al. 2018 *Journal of Agricultural and Food Chemistry* 66(11), 2580-2588
- [2] Ruggiero et al. 2022 *Food Chemistry* 375, 131822

Evaluation of the effects of plant growth promoting microorganisms on wheat growth by spectral phenotyping: preliminary results from Agritech Project

Michele Andrea De Santis¹, Antonio Bevilacqua¹, Annalisa d'Amelio¹, Damiana Tozzi¹, Luigia Giuzio¹, Michele Rinaldi², Nicola Pecchioni², Zina Flagella¹

¹ DAFNE, Univ. Foggia, IT, michele.desantis@unifg.it, zina.flagella@unifg.it

² CREA-CI, Foggia, IT

Introduction

The Green Deal goals of sustainability are demanding to face the increase in world population and the climate change scenario. The optimization of wheat crop is strategic to achieve these targets. The adoption of DSS, precision farming and smart solutions such as plant growth-promoting microorganisms (PGPMs) are within the key strategies for modern agriculture. PGPMs are often referred as “biofertilizers” that can increase the availability of nutrients and plant growth (Di Benedetto et al., 2019). Most of the literature deals with the effects of these biofertilizers on horticulture crops, while few investigations are available on wheat, especially under open field trials. The aim of the current study was to investigate the effectiveness of PGPMs in improving wheat growth and crop performance. To this aim, in this preliminary investigation within task 6.1.1 of Agritech Project, the effect of different microorganisms on different wheat genotypes was assessed by spectral phenotyping.

Table 1. List of biofertilizer treatments.

Treatment	N rate (kg/ha)	PGPM	Concentration	Rate
T1	0	-	-	-
T2	75	-	-	-
T3	150	-	-	-
T4	75	¹ <i>Azospirillum brasilense</i> <i>Pantoea dispersa</i>	10 ⁸ CFU/kg	75 kg/ha
T5	75	² <i>Pseudomonas fluorescens</i> + AMF	10 ⁸ CFU/g	200 g/ha
T6	75	³ <i>Bacillus subtilis</i>	10 ¹² CFU/kg	5 l/ha
T7	75	⁴ <i>Pseudomonas migulae</i>	10 ⁷ CFU/ml	10 ml/m ²
T8	75	⁵ <i>Azotobacter salinestrus</i> + AMF	10 ⁷ CFU/g	50 g/ha

1 = Agrowin (Probelte) Winrpon; 2 = Agrowin (Probelte) Biocult P; 3 = Bayer Serenade ASO; 4 = wild isolate Unifg (Di Benedetto et al., 2019); 5 = Syngenta Nutribion N; AMF = arbuscular mycorrhizal fungi.

Materials and Methods

The field experiment was conducted during the 2022-2023 crop seasons in South Italy at Foggia (CREA CI, 41°27'03" N, 15°30'06" E; 70 m s.l.m.). Three wheat genotypes, including two durum (Antalis, Fuego) and one bread (Solehio) wheat varieties were adopted for the study. Sowing was carried out on 22/12/2022 with a density of 400 seeds/m². A split plot design with three replicates was carried out with three genotypes and treatments, including different N rates and biofertilizers as described in Table 1. Split nitrogen (N) fertilization was applied for 1/3 at tillering and 2/3 at stem elongation, as ammonium nitrate (AN). Phosphorous was applied before sowing at a rate of 30 kg/ha of P₂O₅, as triple phosphate. Crop physiological traits, grain yield and quality performance are to be investigated at the end of the crop cycle. Instead spectral reflectance was already assessed by a field spectroradiometer (Apogee SS-110) during tillering (Z2), stem elongation (Z3), booting (Z4), flowering (Z6) and grain filling (Z8). Green chlorophyll index (GCI) was calculated according to the formula: [(R_{nir} / R_{green}) - 1] (De Santis et al., 2022). Soil samples were analyzed immediately before inoculation (sowing) and at booting development stages; total

bacterial count, aerobic and anaerobic spore forming bacteria, nitrogen fixing bacteria, pseudomonads, actinobacteria and soil bacteria growing at 22 °C were analyzed as reported by De Santis et al. (2023). Microbiological results were standardized as increase/decrease of counts referred to the data before inoculation. Means were separated by least significant difference ($p < 0.05$).

Results

The response of crop vigor, in terms of GCI (Figure 1), an estimator of N uptake during crop development, showed an increasing trend up to anthesis (Z6) with a later reduction due to N remobilization and crop senescence. In the late stage Z7 the durum wheat genotypes showed lower values than the bread one (Solehio), due to their earliness. In addition, within biofertilizer treatments, the inoculation with *Bacillus subtilis* (commercial) and *Pseudomonas migulae* (Unifg wild isolate) showed the highest values with respect to the not inoculated control (T2) at anthesis stage, when the highest values were achieved. Microbiological analysis of soil confirmed the increase in PGPMs due to inoculation; mainly, pseudomonads counts increased in T7 treatment by 1-2 log CFU/g, thus suggesting the robustness of the wild *Ps. migulae* strain to persist into the soil. Higher counts in bacilli (spore forming bacteria) were also found in T6 sample, also highlighting the ability of *B. subtilis* to survive.

Figure 24. Variations of GCI during crop development for Antalis (orange), Fuego (yellow) and Solehio (green) wheat genotypes (a) and response of GCI measured at flowering stage (b) in relation to the different biofertilizer treatments with respect to the uninoculated control (T2).

Conclusions

Spectral phenotyping showed differences in the response to the application of the different PGPMs, with a positive association between GCI values and soil microbiota. The evaluation of nutrient use efficiency and of grain yield and quality performance is in progress and might support these preliminary results in order to detect and to validate smart farming practices to improve wheat sustainability and quality .

Literature

- Di Benedetto et al. 2019. Isolation, Screening, and Characterization of Plant-Growth-Promoting Bacteria from Durum Wheat Rhizosphere to Improve N and P Nutrient Use Efficiency. *Microorganisms*, 7: 541.
- De Santis et al. 2022. Water Use Efficiency, Spectral Phenotyping and Protein Composition of Two Chickpea Genotypes Grown in Mediterranean Environments under Different Water and Nitrogen Supply. *Agriculture*, 12: 2026.
- De Santis et al. 2023. Agronomic response to irrigation and biofertilizer of peanut (*Arachis hypogea* L.) grown under Mediterranean environment. *Agronomy*, 13: 1566.

Acknowledgments

This study was carried out within the Agritech National Research Center and received funding from the European Union Next-GenerationEU (PIANO NAZIONALE DI RIPRESA E RESILIENZA (PNRR) – MISSIONE 4 COMPONENTE 2, INVESTIMENTO 1.4 – D.D. 1032 17/06/2022, CN00000022). This manuscript reflects only the authors' views and opinions, neither the European Union nor the European Commission can be considered responsible for them.

Greenhouse Covered by Photoluminescent Polyethylene Improves the Agronomical Response of Eggplant (*Solanum melongena* L.)

Ida Di Mola¹, Eugenio Cozzolino², Lucia Ottaiano¹, Maria Eleonora Pelosi¹, Sabrina Nocerino¹, Massimo Rippa³, Pasquale Mormile³, Luca Beltrame⁴, Mauro Mori¹

¹ DiA, Univ. Napoli, IT, ida.dimola@unina.it, lucia.ottaiano@unina.it, mariaeleonora.pelosi@unina.it, sabrina.nocerino@unina.it, mori@unina.it

² CREA-CI, Caserta, IT, eugenio.cozzolino@crea.gov.it

³ Institute of Applied Science and Intelligent Systems of National Research Council (ISASI-CNR), Pozzuoli, IT, m.rippa@isasi.cnr.it, p.mormile@isasi.cnr.it

⁴ Lucedentro SRL, Sassuolo, IT, beltramefrancoluca@gmail.com

Introduction

The cultivation under greenhouse, thanks to the use of different covering materials, allows to modify the light environment (i.e., light intensity and spectral composition), affecting crop physiology, yield and nutritional quality of the products (Di Mola et al., 2021). In the past, various light sources have been used in greenhouses, and among these ones, light-emitting diodes (LEDs) have gained popularity in the last decade; however, the widespread use of LEDs is mainly limited by the high upfront costs. Currently, agricultural films for greenhouses are increasingly used to control the light environment; these films are obtained by adding light conversion agents, such as fluorescent materials able to convert UV light into blue-violet or red-orange light. In our previous research, we tested the agronomical and physiological response of lettuce grown under a greenhouse covered with poly-methyl-methacrylate (PPMA) panels doped with a blend of the rare-earth inorganic material with a photo-luminescent effect (Di Mola et al., 2022). Our results showed that the red-supplemented light spectrum under the doped greenhouse cover contributed to increased plant growth and yield, but the PMMA is not particularly suitable for covering greenhouse. Therefore, starting from these results, in the current experiment we wanted to evaluate the productive response of an eggplant hybrid cultivated under a greenhouse covered by a polyethylene film doped with a blend of rare-earth inorganic complexes, with a photo-luminescent effect in the red region of the PAR spectrum.

Materials and Methods

The test was carried out at the private farm “I Saporì della Terra” located in Parete (CE- Italy). An innovative greenhouse covering material (a polyethylene film doped with a blend of rare-earth inorganic complexes, **Doped**) was compared to a common covering material “Suntherm” (**Control**) produced by Ginegar and supplied by Polyeur. The tested crop was the eggplant (*Solanum melongena* L.) hybrid “Senegal” (Semillas Fitó Italia, Padova, Italy) with cylindrical fruits, of medium length, dark color and good firmness. Within each greenhouse, we individuated three sampling areas corresponding to three replicates. The transplant was made on March 8, 2022 with a plant density of 10.200 plants per hectare (1.40 x 0.70 m) and the harvest was made in 8 times starting from June, 16 until July, 21. At each harvest, marketable yield was determined; in addition, on the fruits of the fourth harvest, also the following qualitative parameters were assessed: firmness, dry matter (DM) percentage, hydrophilic and lipophilic antioxidant activity (HAA and LAA, respectively), phenols, ascorbic acid (AA), and carotenoids. All data were subjected to analysis of variance (two-way for yield data and one-way for the all other parameters) with the SPSS software (SPSS version 22, Chicago, IL, USA) and means were separated with the Tukey’s test ($p < 0.05$).

Results

The eggplant yield was significantly affected by the interaction between the greenhouse covering material and the harvest dates (Fig.1). Notably, for the first four harvests, the yield under the Doped film was always significantly higher than the control (+21.8%, on mean), while from the fifth harvest until in the last one, there were not significant differences between each harvest (Fig. 1). Overall, the total yield was slightly higher under the Doped film (10.8 vs. 8.9 t ha⁻¹). As regards the qualitative parameters of eggplant fruits, only the firmness and carotenoids were significantly affected by the greenhouse covering material (Tab. 1). Particularly for both parameters, the cultivation under greenhouse film doped with rare-earth inorganic complex elicited higher values: +14.2% and +10.8%, for firmness and carotenoids, respectively; the trend was similar also for dry matter percentage and ascorbic acid, even if the variations were not significant (Tab. 1).

Figure 1. Marketable yield of eggplant was affected by greenhouse covering film.

Table 1. Qualitative parameters (firmness, DM, HAA, LAA, AA, phenols, and carotenoids) of eggplant fruits as affected by greenhouse cover films (Control: common film; Doped: film doped with rare-earth)

Treatments	Firmness kg cm ⁻²	DM %	HAA mM AA 100g ⁻¹ dw	LAA mM Trolox 100g ⁻¹ dw	AA mg g ⁻¹ fw	Phenols mg Gallic Acid g ⁻¹ dw	Carotenoids mg g ⁻¹ fw
Control	1.69±0.01 b	7.6±0.1	3.86±0.29	24.9±1.1	59.4±1.46	3.12±0.08	0.037±0.002 b
Doped	1.93±0.01 a	8.0±0.2	3.06±0.04	26.4±0.5	61.2±4.48	3.18±0.08	0.041±0.002 a
Significance	**	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns	*

In each column, different letters indicate significant differences; ns, *, and ** refer to not significant or significant at p < 0.05, and p < 0.01.

Conclusions

Our results highlight that the cultivation of eggplant under a greenhouse covered with a polyethylene film doped with a blend of rare-earth inorganic complexes, with a photo-luminescent effect in the red region of the PAR spectrum, elicited an increase in marketable yield in the first harvests (in our case the first four ones) and it did not affect or it positively affected the qualitative parameters. Obviously, further research is needed to confirm this behaviour and also evaluate the response of other vegetable crops.

Literature

Di Mola I. et al. 2021 Optical characteristics of greenhouse plastic films affect yield and some quality traits of spinach (*Spinacia oleracea* L.) subjected to different nitrogen doses. *Horticulturae*, 7: 200.

Di Mola I. et al. 2022 Greenhouse photoluminescent PMMA panels improve the agronomical and physiological performances of lettuce (*Lactuca sativa* L.). *Horticulturae*, 8: 913.

Acknowledgements

The Work is co-funded by LUCEDENTRO SRL

Mineral Elements Content In Globe Artichoke As Affected By Mulching Treatment

Gaetano Pandino, Salvatore Susino, Giuseppe Zito, Claudia Formenti, Salvatore Alfio Salicola, Aurelio Scavo, Gaetano Roberto Pesce, Sara Lombardo, Giovanni Mauromicale

Di3A, Univ. Catania, IT, sara.lombardo@unict.it

Introduction

In the Mediterranean Basin, the use of mulching practices is commonly adopted to compensate for the scarcity of water resources, by reducing crop-field evaporation (Zhang et al., 2017). The most used mulching material is low-density polyethylene (LDPE), since it exhibits good thermal and chemical resistance, as well as a good processability. Unfortunately, these characteristics make LDPE a slowly degrading product for possibly hundreds of years. As a consequence, the intensive use of non-degradable plastic mulching in agriculture is provoking significant environmental and human health problems through the generation of enormous amounts of non-degradable and difficult-to-recycle microplastic wastes (Rodrigues et al., 2019). Therefore, research needs to focus on sustainable and environmentally friendly alternatives to plastic films that guarantee both crop production and quality. Organic and biodegradable mulch films could represent an excellent solution to the adverse environmental impact derived from plastic film (Abbate et al., 2023). Based on the aforementioned considerations, the aim of our work was to compare the effect (if any) of two different environmental-friendly mulching treatments (organic and biodegradable mulch film) on the accumulation of some mineral elements in the edible fraction (receptacle) of globe artichoke.

Materials and Methods

Experimental field was conducted on Gela Plain (46 m a.s.l, 37°11' N, 14° 11' E), a typical area for globe artichoke cultivation in the Mediterranean Basin. A split-plot experimental design with three replications was adopted to evaluate the effects of the different mulching treatments [organic (crop residues of durum wheat crop); biodegradable mulch film; control (without mulch)] and two genotypes of globe artichoke (*Cynara cardunculus* var. *scolymus*) ('Tema 2000' and 'Opera') as sub-plot. Each one was planted manually by using semi-dormant offshoots ('ovoli') and plantlets with 3-4 leaves, respectively, in August 2021. Crop management practices were consistent with the usual local practices. At least 5 capitula per replicate, disease-free and at the usual marketing stage were harvested (between January and March), then the receptacles were manually separated from the other fractions of the capitula. The content of mineral elements (Ca, Mg, K, Fe, Mn and Zn) was performed according to AOAC (1995), and expressed as g or mg kg⁻¹ of dry matter (DM). The data were subjected to two-way ('mulching treatment x genotype') analysis of variance and means were separated by LSD test, when the *F*-test was significant.

Results

The mineral elements content of the receptacle was significantly influenced by the mulching treatment and the genotype under study. As regards the mulching treatment, significant differences were found for the Ca, K, Fe and Zn content (Figure 1). For example, organic mulching with durum wheat crop residues particularly favored the accumulation of Ca and Fe by increasing their content of about 14 and 38%, respectively. As compared to the control, both mulching treatments reported a decrease of 10 and 15%, respectively, for K and Zn (Figure 1). In relation to the genotype, significant differences were found for all the mineral elements under study, except for K, Zn and Fe (Figure 1). The levels of Ca, Mg and Mn were higher by about 23% in 'Tema 2000' than in 'Opera'.

Figure 1. Effect of mulching treatment and genotype on mineral elements content (\pm standard deviation) of globe artichoke receptacle. Different letters within each factor under study indicate significant differences for $P \leq 0.05$.

Conclusions

The acquired results highlighted how the content of mineral elements of the globe artichoke receptacle varied in relation to the mulching treatment. However, given the nutritional importance of the mineral elements in the human diet, further studies on the effect of mulching treatment in other genotypes, as well as extending the evaluation on other qualitative parameters, would be necessary.

Literature

- Abbate C. et al. 2023. Soil bioplastic mulches for agroecosystem sustainability: a comprehensive review. *Agriculture*, 13: 197.
- AOAC 1995. Official Method 975.03: Metals in Plants. 16th edn, Arlington, VA.
- Rodrigues M.O. et al. 2019. Impacts of plastic products used in daily life on the environment and human health: What is known? *Environ. Toxicol. Pharmacol.* 72: 103239.
- Zhang H. et al. 2017. Effects of water stress on processing tomatoes yield, quality and water use efficiency with plastic mulched drip irrigation in sandy soil of the hetao irrigation district. *Agric. Water Manag.*, 179: 205–214.

A Multidisciplinary Approach to Detect Stress Symptoms in Vegetable Crops

Massimo Pugliese^{1,2}, Luca Alfarano^{1,2}, Roberta Bulgari¹, Gica Stefanescu Miralles^{1,3}, Lorenzo Comba^{1,4}, Riccardo Cecire¹, Mery Malandrino⁵, Luisella Celi¹

¹ DISAFA, Univ. Torino, IT, roberta.bulgari@unito.it

² Centro Agroinnova, Univ. Torino, IT

³ Computer Science Department, Univ. Torino, IT

⁴ Institute of Electronics, Computer and Telecommunication Engineering, CNR, IT

⁵ Department of Chemistry, Univ. Torino, IT

Introduction

Stress factors are among the primary causes of crop losses worldwide, and abiotic stresses reduce the average yields for most major crops by more than 50% (La Pena and Hughes, 2007). The reduction of yield under abiotic stress is mainly due to the energy that crops have to use for adaptation; these yield losses are usually known as “fitness cost” of the crops. Fusarium wilt, caused by *Fusarium oxysporum* f. sp. *lactucae*, is an example of biotic stress recently introduced in Europe that can influence lettuce growth and cause severe losses (Gilardi et al., 2016). It is therefore of considerable interest the identification of strategies to avoid the onset of stresses or mitigate their negative effects on plants.

This work is thus aimed to evaluate the effects of biotic and abiotic stresses on vegetables, through a multidisciplinary approach. Premise of the present research is to define a methodological approach to detect, even proactively, stress symptoms in crops and manage them to preserve the quantity and quality of production. Lettuce was chosen as model species, since it is representative of green leafy vegetables widely consumed worldwide (Kim et al., 2016) and can be easily cultivated in hydroponic systems. Soilless culture can increase crops yield but also quality and safety of fresh produce (Gonnella and Renna, 2021).

Materials and Methods

Two-week-old lettuce (*Lactuca sativa* L. var. *gentilina*) plantlets were transplanted in plastic pots (2 L), on a peaty substrate mixed with perlite, in a glasshouse at the Centre Agroinnova of the University of Turin (Grugliasco) and cultivated in a closed soilless cultivation system, under monitored conditions. The concentrations of nutrients in the nutrient solution, expressed as mM, were: 11.24 mM NO₃⁻, 4.8 mM NH₄⁺, 0.75 mM KH₂PO₄, 0.75 mM K₂SO₄, 0.012 mM Iron chelate EDTA, 2 mM MgO, 2 mM SO₃²⁻, 0.2 mM B, 0.001 mM Mo, 0.15 mM Zn, 3.1 mM CaO, 0.05 mM Cu²⁺, 0.25 mM Mn²⁺, and 12.2 mM K⁺. The plants have been subjected to combined abiotic and biotic stresses as follows: a) Water stress (W) (- 20/40% in terms of irrigation duration) alone and with biotic stress (B); b) Nutritional stress (N) (- 20/40% N and P) alone and with biotic stress (B); c) Water stress + nutritional stress (W+N) alone and with biotic stress (B); d) Control (C) alone and with biotic stress (B). The biotic stress was determined through an artificial inoculation with the pathogen *Fusarium oxysporum* f. sp. *lactucae*. One plant was present in each pot and 15 pots were considered for each treatment.

Biotic stress evaluation

The plants were checked weekly to establish the disease development and to count any wilted plants. The final disease rating was performed 30-40 days after planting by dissecting the plants longitudinally at the collar to assess the presence of vascular browning. To quantify the severity of the disease, the disease severity rating (DS 0–100) was based on a scale, as described in Gilardi et al., 2018.

Quality evaluation and nutrient status

During the growing cycle, every 7 days, *in vivo* measurements were performed to estimate the leaf chlorophyll content with a Chlorophyll Meter SPAD-502 (Konica Minolta Sensing Inc., Osaka, Japan).

At harvest, 30-40 days after planting, the fresh weight of plants was determined and the concentration of chlorophylls, carotenoids, phenols, anthocyanins, nitrate, and sugars were studied through spectrophotometric methods. Macro and micronutrients (N, P, K, Ca, Mg, Cu, Zn, and Fe) were determined in the dry matter by a CN elemental analyser, ICP-OES, and ICP-MS (Malandrino et al., 2011). Nutrient balance was also carried out quantifying all elements in the nutrient solution, in the substrates after harvesting, and in the discharge waters.

Proximal sensing

In order to investigate the capability to detect stress symptoms and predict the quality parameters of lettuce plantlets by proximal sensing technology, the experimental campaign also involved the multitemporal acquisition of leaves spectral signatures on four different epochs (time points). In particular, the measurements were performed every 7 days, in accordance with quality evaluation, using the RS-5400 UV-visible-shortwave near infrared spectroradiometer equipped with the leaf clip tool. A set of 18 lettuce leaves were randomly selected within each group of considered treatments, and their spectral signatures were monitored, leading to an overall set of 576 acquisitions. The obtained spectral data were processed on Matlab software, firstly to correct for light scattering variations by the multiplicative scatter correction (MSC). Then data were analyzed using the principal component analysis (PCA) method to decrease the noise and reduce the number of latent variables. Finally, a supervised machine learning clustering method was adopted to investigate the capability to classify data in the appropriate classes.

Results and Conclusions

The trials, still in progress, will allow to obtain data deriving from both *in vivo* and destructive analysis, which can be correlated, to optimize the study and the management of different individual and combined stresses in leafy vegetables. The response to single or combined stresses in plants involves various changes in their morphology and physiology. The proposed methodology seems suitable to be included in a larger, integrated framework in which different techniques/analyses are combined to study the stresses at different levels and better identify them.

Acknowledgements

This study was carried out within the Agritech National Research Center, Spoke 6, Task 6.1.1 and received funding from the European Union Next-GenerationEU (PIANO NAZIONALE DI RIPRESA E RESILIENZA (PNRR) – MISSIONE 4 COMPONENTE 2, INVESTIMENTO 1.4 – D.D. 1032 17/06/2022, CN00000022). This manuscript reflects only the authors' views and opinions, neither the European Union nor the European Commission can be considered responsible for them.

Literature

- Gilardi G. et al. 2016. A new race of *Fusarium oxysporum* f. sp. *lactucae* of lettuce. *Plant Pathol.*, 66: 677–688.
- Gilardi G. et al. 2019. Nursery treatments with resistant inducers, soil amendments and biocontrol agents for the management of the Fusarium wilt of lettuce under glasshouse and field conditions. *J. Phytopathol.*, 167: 98–110.
- Gonnella M. and Renna M. 2021. The Evolution of soilless systems towards ecological sustainability in the perspective of a circular economy. Is it really the opposite of organic agriculture? *Agronomy*, 11(5): 950.
- Kim M.J. et al. 2016. Nutritional value, bioactive compounds and health benefits of lettuce (*Lactuca sativa* L.). *J. Food Compos. Anal.*, 49: 19-34.
- La Pena R.D. and Hughes J. 2007. Improving vegetable productivity in a variable and changing climate. *J. SAT Agric. Res.*, 4: 1–22.
- Malandrino M. et al. 2011. Accumulation of heavy metals from contaminated soil to plants and evaluation of soil remediation by vermiculite. *Chemosphere*, 82: 169-178.

Towards the Production of Durum and Common Wheat for a 0-residues Food Supply-Chain

Amedeo Reyneri¹, Luca Capo¹, Aldo Ferrero¹, Marta Guarise², Giacomo Pedretti², Massimo Blandino¹

¹ DISAFA, Univ. Torino, IT, amedeo.reyneri@unito.it, luca.capo@unito.it, aldo.ferrero@unito.it, massimo.blandino@unito.it,

² Agricola2000, IT, m.guarise@agricola2000.com, g.pedretti00@agricola2000.com

Introduction

The agricultural sector is increasingly the subject of new challenges: agriculture is required to satisfy the food security needs of a growing world population, and, at the same time, to comply with qualitative, health and environmental, all traits related to food safety issue. The food supply chain has shown growing interest in products with a high technological quality and safety profile and, in particular, without pesticide residues. In this context, this study was aimed to develop a cultivation protocol for the sustainable production of common and durum wheat with "zero" residues, i.e. with the same active ingredient (a.i.) residues level of plant protection products allowed in organic farm productions (< 0.01 mg/kg), according to conventional production methods (High input Agriculture) (Tei et al., 2022).

Materials and Methods

With the previously reported aim, field experiments were set up at plot and farm scale in the 2019-20 and 2020-21 growing seasons in Lombardia and Piedmont regions.

Several post-emergence herbicides and fungicides, referred to triazole, carboxamide, strobilurines or SDHI chemical groups, were applied at different timing (growth stage following BBCH Scale) following the schedule summarized respectively in table 1 and table 2.

A factorial experimental design, with 4 replicates were applied for durum wheat in Vignate (MI) and Liscate (MI), and for common wheat in Carmagnola (TO).

Wheat was harvested in July through a plot combine and a representative grain sample for each plot was collected at harvest and whole milled (1 mm) in order to analyze the occurrence of pesticides. The common wheat samples were also subjected to pearling, in order to remove the first cortical layers (5% by weight), to evaluate the effect of the milling pre-processing on the residue content.

Pesticide determination was performed according to the European Standard UNI EN 15662:2018 and applying a multi-residuals liquid chromatographic method.

Table 1: Herbicides and application timing compared

Timing and growth stage		Active ingredient		
		Pinoxaden Clopyralid Fluroxypir	Florasulam Haluxifen methyl	Diflufenican
T1	Beginning of tillering (GS 21)	X	X	X
T2	Full tillering (GS 25)	X	X	X
T3	Beginning of stem elongation (GS 30)	X	X	X

Results

Among the herbicides applied, only a.i. Clopyralid was detected in all samples treated with this molecule, with a content which was comprise between XX-XX for durum wheat and XX-XX for common wheat (Table 2). The concentration of Clopyralid increase with the delay of application (Table 3). All the others herbicide a.i. did not present residues greater than the analytical Limit of Quantification (LOQ).

Table 2: Fungicide and application timing compared

Timing and growth stage		Benzovindiflupyr Pydiflumetofen	Azoxystrobin Fluxapyroxad	Prothioconazole Tebuconazole
T1	End of stem elongation (GS 35)	X	X	X
T2	Mid boot stage (GS 43)	X	X	X
T3	Middle of heading (GS 55)	X	X	X
T4	Early flowering (GS 63)	X	X	X
T5	Early milk (GS 73)	X		X

Among fungicide, the presence of Pydiflumetofen was detected in both years, while Benzovindiflupyr was found only in 2020 trials, both only in the case of later applications at early milky stage (Table 4). The other fungicide a.i. were never detected. For the a.i. above LOQ limits, pearling further reduced concentrations; among the fungicides only Pydiflumetofen remains beyond the target limits.

Table 3: Herbicides: number of analyzed sample and percentage of sample with concentration >LOQ (0.01 mg/kg) at different growth stage (BBCH)

Active ingredient	Samples (n.)	LOQ (% of samples)					
		2020			2021		
		GS 21	GS 25	GS 30	GS 21	GS 25	GS 30
Clopyralid	13	87	93	100	-	-	-
Florasulam	24	0	0	0	0	0	0
Fluroxypir	26	0	0	0	0	0	0
Haluxifen methyl	24	0	0	0	0	0	0
MCPA	26	0	0	0	0	0	0
Pinoxaden	26	0	0	0	0	0	0

Table 4: Fungicides: Number of analyzed sample and percentage of sample with concentration >LOQ (0.01 mg/kg) at different growth stage (BBCH)

Active ingredient	Samples (n.)	LOQ (% of samples)									
		2020					2021				
		GS 35	GS 43	GS 55	GS 63	GS 73	GS 35	GS 43	GS 55	GS 63	GS 73
Azoxystrobin	8	-	-	-	-	-	0	0	0	0	0
Benzovindiflupyr	24	0	0	0	0	100	0	0	0	0	0
Fluxapyroxad	12	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Prothioconazole	40	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Pydiflumetofen	8	0	0	0	0	100	0	0	0	100	100
Tebuconazole	24	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Conclusions

The production of "zero" residue grain with the same level of residues allowed in organic productions (< 0.01 mg/kg) is possible by following a careful selection of a.i. and timing of application. If Clopyralid was the only herbicide always present in all the analysis, among the fungicides analysed, only late applications after flowering can show positive values for certain SDHI molecules. In 2022 growing season, first important supply chain operators in the pasta sector, have already applied the disciplinary which guarantee "zero" residues, reporting this claim in the label.

Literature

Tei F. et al. 2022. Sistemi colturali e sostenibilità in un contesto di transizione ecologica. Società Italiana di Agronomia. Coop. Libreria Editrice, Padova, 58 pp.